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**Policy Advice and Expertise in Higher Education Policymaking in Algeria
and Scotland: A Comparative Case Study (1999-2020)**

This thesis is submitted in partial fulfilment of the requirements
of the University of the West of Scotland
for the award of Doctor of Philosophy

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1st August 2024

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Abstract

This comparative case study analysed how Algeria and Scotland harnessed the expertise offered by their respective policy communities (e.g. think tanks, industry umbrella organisations, academic researchers, student representatives, societal interest groups, political parties, lobby groups, government, and the higher education sector itself) to inform the policy making process in three higher education policy areas for each country developed between 1999 and 2020. In Algeria, the designated higher education policies were the Bachelor, Masters and Doctorate (BMD) Programme (2003-2020), Quality Assurance in Higher Education (2008-2020) and International Mobility (2014-2019). In Scotland, the policy areas were the funding developments in Higher Education mainly the tuition fees policy (1999-2016), Widening Access (2014-2019), and Higher Education Governance Reform (2011-2016). Drawn from relevant literature, several key concepts from the literature on policy making, policy expertise, policy advice, research utilization and policy networks were utilised as the lens through which to theorise the findings emerging from this study. The study adopted a comparative historical case study method as the relevant research method. Data were collected through semi-structured interviews with key informants (n41) in both Algeria and Scotland. In addition, in both countries relevant data was obtained from a discourse analysis of relevant written materials such as newspaper articles, consultation papers, government documents, party manifestos, parliamentary reports, press releases, and briefings. Through thematic analysis, including the constant comparison strategy, key issues were identified from the study's findings, which include similarities as well as differences regarding policy advice and expertise informing higher education policymaking between Algeria and Scotland between 1999 and 2020. The findings demonstrated how policy advice and expertise shaped key policy developments in higher education in the two countries, namely, in Algeria, BMD, Quality Assurance, and International Mobility while in Scotland, Funding, Widening Access and Governance policy areas. Secondly, it showed the ways in which policy community members engaged in policymaking processes through similar strategies. Further, it revealed the relationship existing between the government and the policy community and how this influences policymaking dynamics. Finally, it explained how despite the historical, political, and cultural differences between the two countries, several similarities exist in terms of the way policies in higher education are perceived by the policy actors involved in policymaking

processes. The study concludes that while governments in both countries must be more open to the advice and expertise of policy communities, Algeria has a learning opportunity from Scotland which has had a deeper and advanced experience with policy development in higher education.

Keywords: Higher education, policymaking, policy advice, expertise, case study research, Algeria, Scotland.

Dedication

I dedicate this thesis to the one I lost too soon. To you Nawel.

To my mom and dad for their endless support.

To Gourine Mohamed Reda, whatever lies ahead, this work bears the imprint of your support.

To the one who taught and keep teaching me how to love unconditionally, to you Taline, my sweet little bundle of joy. I hope you grow up to be proud of your Mommy.

Acknowledgements

Firstly, I thank Allah for blessing me with the courage and support and surrounding me with good people to undertake this journey.

I am grateful to my lead supervisor Dr Yonah Matemba for his valuable guidance, consistent support, and scholarly comments throughout my studentship. I am also indebted to my second supervisor Dr Hartwig Pautz for the feedback and the faultless supervision he has provided. Both of supervisors offered an exquisite blend of encouragement, critical friendship, and intellectual rigour that was pivotal to complete this study.

I would like to extend my appreciation to the Algerian Government and the Ministry of Higher Education and Scientific Research for offering this scholarship and for providing funding for me to pursue my research on a full-time basis.

I am profoundly thankful to all my participants, who consented to be interviewed for this study and gave up their valuable time to talk to me in spite of heavy workloads. It was a highlight of this research process to have met and discussed this subject with those involved in shaping higher education policy in the two countries. Their perspectives have been essential in figuring out the complex background to this study. Without their voluntary contribution this study would not have been accomplished.

I wish to put on record the help and support from the University of the West of Scotland's School of Education and Social Sciences for granting me such opportunity and for making resource available to make this work possible. Special thanks go to the library staff who helped me with many book requests and interlibrary loans.

Authors' Declaration

I hereby declare that the doctoral thesis entitled, *Policy Advice and Expertise in Higher Education Policymaking in Algeria and Scotland: A Comparative Case Study (1999-2020)*, except where explicit reference is made to the contribution of others, is the result of my own work and has not been submitted for any other degree at the University of the West of Scotland or any other institution.

Signature

Zenati Nor Elhouda

Abbreviations and Acronyms

ACF: Advocacy Coalition Framework

AHDR: Arab Human Development Report

BAME: Black, Asian and minority ethnic (BAME) communities

BERA: British Educational Research Association

BMD: Bachelor, Masters and Doctorate

CBI: Scotland Confederation of British Industry

CIAQES: National Commission for the Implementation of Quality Assurance in Higher Education

CNAS: The National Council of Professors of Higher Education and Scientific Research

CNE: The National Evaluation Committee

CNES: The National Council of Higher Education Professors

CNRSE: Commission Nationale de Réforme du Système Educatif (National Commission for Reform of the Educational System)

CNU: Conférence Nationale des Universités or The National Conference of Universities

CoWA: Commission on Widening Access

CREID: Centre for Research in Education Inclusion and Diversity

CRU: Conférences Régionales des Universités or The Regional Conferences of Universities

CSC: Committee of Scottish Chairs

EBPM: evidence-based policy making.

EHEA: The European Higher Education Area

EIS: Educational Institute of Scotland

ENQA: European Association for Quality Assurance in Higher Education

EUA: European University Association

FNTES: The National Federation of Workers in Higher Education and Scientific Research

GDSRTD: The General Directorate for Scientific Research and Technological Development

GUSRC: Glasgow University Students' Representative Council

HE: Higher Education

HEIs: Higher Education Institutions

HEPI: Higher Education Policy Institute

HEREs: Higher Education Reform Experts

HESA: the Higher Education Statistics Agency
HNC: Higher National Certificate
HND: Higher National Diploma
IPPR: Institute for Public Policy Research
LLD: The Scottish Government's Lifelong Learning Directorate
MENA: Middle East and North Africa
MESRS: Ministry of Higher Education and Scientific research
NGOs: Non-Governmental Organizations
NPM: New Public Management
NUS: National Union of Students
OA: Outcome Agreement
OBI: Open Budget Index
OBI: Open Budget survey
OECD: Organisation for Economic Co-operation and Development
QAA: the Quality Assurance Agency
QAR: Quality Assurance Managers
QEF: Quality Enhancement Framework
R&D research and experimental development
RNAQES: National Reference Framework for Quality Assurance in Higher Education
S&T: Science and Technology
SCVO: Scottish Council for Voluntary Organisations
SE: Scottish Executive
SFC: Scottish Funding Council
SG: Scottish Government
SG: Scottish Government
SHEFC: Scottish Higher Education Funding Council
SNAPAP: The National Federation of Public Administration Employees in the Sector
SNAPES: The Independent National Union of Higher Education Employees
SNECHU: The National Union of University Hospital-Based Research Professors
SNEU: The National Union of University Professors

SNP: Scottish Nationalist Party

SPARQS: Student Participation in Quality Scotland

SPIC: Scottish Parliament Information Centre

SSE: Socio-Economic Sector

STUC: Scottish Trades Union Congress

TUC: Trades Union Congress

UCU: University and Colleges Union

UK: United Kingdom

UKVI: UK Visas and Immigration

Chapter 1

Introduction

1.1 Statement of the Problem

This study critically examines the role and impact of policy advice and expertise on policy making in higher education in Algeria and Scotland. It scrutinises how in the two countries various policy actors such as think tanks, industry umbrella organisations, academic researchers, student representatives, societal interest groups, political parties, lobby groups, government, and the higher education sector itself have engaged with, and shaped the development of key policies policy in the governance and practice of higher education. Policy advice in higher education policy making in Scotland has not received enough attention. However, there are some academic publications addressing the issue in the wider context of the United Kingdom for example (Connaughton, 2005, 2006; Fleischer, 2009). The same is noted in Algeria where such analysis remains patchy or non-existent. As far as it can be ascertained, to date no empirical study has examined the role of policy advice and expertise in policymaking in higher education between the two countries. Underlying the comparative case study approach utilised in this study is the assumption that the differing socio-political and cultural contexts of Algeria and Scotland create different ways of producing and employing policy advice and expertise which, although different, have recognisable similarities.

The study contributes to the growing body of literature on policy advice and policy advisory systems (e.g., Boston, 1994; Halligan, 1995; Craft and Howlett, 2013; Veselý, 2013; Weaver and Stares, 2001; Howlett and Migone, 2013; Connaughton and Devane, 2023; Craft, Head and Howlett, 2024); knowledge, policymaking and power (e.g., Sabatier and Jenkins-Smith, 1993; Weiss, 1999; Webber, 1991; Reimers and McGinn, 1997; Sutton, 1999); policy transfer typologies (e.g. Dolowitz and Marsh, 1996; Keating and Cairney, 2012; Dolowitz, 2017); policy networks (e.g. Peterson, 2003; Stone, 2010; Hecló, 1978; Haas, 1992); and agenda-setting theory (e.g. Kingdon, 2010). In both non-governmental sectors, such as academia, business associations and community organisations, and in governmental departments, professional experts develop policy-relevant information and arguments to inform policy makers and the decision-making process. These experts are actively involved in policy debates and political communication with policy makers, but with variable success in influencing policy outcomes. The comparative approach serves to highlight how institutions, dissimilar in both countries, shape this relationship.

As a researcher from Algeria (Global South) but with exposure to the Global North where I have lived for five years undertaking this doctoral degree, my positionality had a critical role in shaping this study. This duality of perspectives allowed me to critically engage with the variations of knowledge production and policy development between the two contexts. While Algeria and Scotland are two countries with contrasting historical and cultural contexts, I chose to compare them to understand how one country from the Global south and another from the Global North function within the institutional frameworks guiding policymaking in higher education but also how each country respond to international and global policy trends in higher education. Algeria represents a postcolonial Global South country with a complex legacy of French colonization, top-down reforms, and an engagement with external influences. On the other hand, Scotland offers a Global North context with a strong and distinctive policy identity shaped by devolution yet still embedded within a broader UK and European landscape. This comparative lens enables a deeper understanding of how policy advice is shaped, received, and translated in two different geopolitical and historical settings, offering insights into how power is distributed within the actors' constellations in the field, how policy advice is produced, negotiated and ultimately implemented, to varying degrees, in higher education policymaking. The remainder of this introduction develops as follows. It sets the research aim, research questions and objectives guiding the study, then outlines the focus and scope underpinning the research, explains the researcher's motivation behind conducting this study and closes by discussing the overall structure designed for this thesis.

1.2 Research Aim

The aim of this historical-comparative study was to examine the ways in which policy advice and expertise shaped the development of key policies in Higher Education Policymaking in Algeria and Scotland between 1999-2020.

1.3 Research Objectives

To support the aim, the following were the objectives of the study:

1. To analyse the role of the different policy actors in the development of key higher education policies in Scotland and Algeria between 1999 and 2020.
2. To examine how policy advice from different policy actors shaped higher education policy in Algeria and Scotland.

3. To compare major policy areas in higher education policymaking between Algeria and Scotland.
4. To draw lessons for both countries in terms of utilizing expertise to inform policy choices.

1.4 Research Questions

Consistent with the aim and objectives of the study, the following research questions provided a useful guide in the presentation and analysis of the findings reported in this study:

1. To what extent did the different policy actors' advice contribute to the making of higher education policy in Algeria and Scotland? In what ways was this knowledge used? What strategies did the different policy actors use to influence the course of higher education policymaking?
2. What common/differing aspects do the two countries have in terms of involving a variety of policy actors to inform the higher education policy choices?
3. What lessons can be learnt from two decades of using expertise in higher education policymaking for both countries?

1.5 Scope of the Study

The definition of the scope of study was grounded in a set of well-considered factors. First the careful selection of the research time frame spanning from 1999 to 2020. The year 1999 represents a drastic shift in the history of both Algeria and Scotland. In 1999, a Scottish Parliament and Scottish Executive were established by the UK Government. This instance is known as the devolution and refers to the transfer of authority and responsibility to local communities with the aim of better representation in the decision-making process (UK Government, 2013). This shift of power meant that the Scottish government would have authority and oversight over the vast majority of public services including those over education policy (Scottish Parliament, 2022). In Algeria, the turn of the millennium is seen as the beginning of a new political era for Algeria with the official end of the long civil war with the coming of Abdelaziz Bouteflika as President in April 1999 (Schulhofer-Wohl, 2007).

The historic events taking place in 1999 present a new era for both Algeria and Scotland and had a direct impact on their respective higher education systems. The researcher selected the start date for the study because it would have been challenging to examine the policy advice and expertise phenomena in higher education policy making prior to 1999 with Algeria's

political turmoil and instability and with Scotland still, to a certain degree, an integral part of the United Kingdom. As for the end date (2020) is related to the most recent developments taking place with some of the policy areas selected for the analysis. The period is also long enough to explore how policy advice as a phenomenon evolved and how it shaped HE policies. Another crucial factor was the thorough literature review, which allowed for a rigorous understanding of the key themes, identification of prominent scholars and their respective viewpoints, and the examination of recurrent debates. This investigation led to well defined boundaries for this research and the exclusion of aspects that were already dealt with, avoidance of redundancy, and at the same time allowed the research to focus on filling a research gap instead of getting carried out to unnecessary data. Previous studies helped anchor the research in the proper theoretical and conceptual frameworks.

The research questions, research objectives, and the research aim were also pivotal in determining the scope of the study as they define the type of data needed to provide meaningful answers, and the proper tools for the data collection. Both data collection tools (interviews and document analysis) were chosen because of their ability to address the research objectives, the same logic goes for the sampling of the research participants, and the drafting of the interview schedules. Following these parameters meant that there is no abundant data gathered that goes beyond the scope of this research and that research questions and the data are aligned.

Other considerations include practical issues such as the amount of time allocated from the Algerian ministry of higher education to complete the PhD and financial resources which influenced heavily the selection of participants, the sample size and the data collection tools, and the time dedicated to data collection. These practical limitations meant that the research had to focus on depth instead of breadth while making sure that the interviewees were carefully selected to be representative of their communities, organizations, and groups to ensure the viability of the data.

1.6 Motivation

It is such a daunting task to answer the question of why doing a PhD, because one's mind suddenly goes blank, not because you don't have something to say but rather having too much to say. I have always been passionate about conducting research since the first homework I got at elementary school where I was asked to interview family members about what they liked most about me. There I was with my little notebook and tiny pencil eager to hear what everyone had to say. I could not wait for tomorrow to come, so I can share with my classmates and teacher what I got. As I grew older, I started developing a strong sense of curiosity about the

world of politics but never had the courage to investigate a topic related to this field. In Algeria, talking about political matters was a short cut to getting in trouble. Fortunately, the country has undergone a massive shift from that mindset, and I am now able to talk freely without fearing the consequences. Curiosity and passion for making a contribution to the world were not the only reasons for embarking on such journey. In the past ten years or so, I had the opportunity to be taught by brilliant university professors and I could not but to admire the way they think, behave, and teach. Do not get me wrong, I also had amazing schoolteachers who left the strongest impressions, yet there was something different with university professors. It was their effortless way to make an impact with a simple question. They made me rethink every aspect of my life and made sure I never accept a fact without questioning it. At that very moment, I got instantly inspired and I knew exactly what to do with my life. I wanted to become a university professor and a PhD was the key. I want to inspire future generations, to share knowledge, and to change the growing perception of how useless it has become to even consider finishing your studies in a country like Algeria. In giving, I also aspire to grow on a personal level, as a human being, and be more compassionate and self-confident to empower other girls and women to follow their dreams despite what the society dictates. I received so much criticism for “throwing away” five years of my life for a project that, for some, was not guaranteed instead of fitting into traditional roles. Yet, here I am, feeling more fulfilled than ever.

1.7. Contribution of the Study

The choice of the topic stems from a personal passion for policymaking in Higher education and a practical gap in the scholarship around policy advice in higher education policymaking in both Algeria and Scotland. Therefore, the study aspires to make both theoretical and empirical contributions to the world of academia.

The findings from the study will provide empirical evidence on how policy advice influenced higher education policy in two variant contexts and discuss to what extent policy actors took part in shaping the discourse around higher education in Algeria and Scotland. This evidence will help fill a conceptual gap found in the scholarship around this topic. As it has been noted by several researchers such as (Hustedt and Veit, 2017; Hustedt, 2019), the literature around policy advice and policy advisory systems is deeply rooted in studies conducted in Westminster-styled administrations, specifically in Australia, Canada, New Zealand, and the

UK (Craft and Halligan, 2017; Craft and Halligan, 2020). This means that there is a dearth in studies covering other systems, especially in developing countries with the exception of a few.

In addition to addressing the gap, the study will also make a contribution through the use of the comparative case study approach, which will put a developed country with a devolved system of governance with international ties against a developing country with a centralised system and a postcolonial heritage. This strikingly different political, economic, and cultural contexts will also prove that they have an impact of how policy advice is used to inform the debate. This means that the study will have implications for both policy studies and higher education research.

The significance of the study also lies in its real world application of the findings generated from the study. As policy makers and the constellation of policy actors are usually regarded as two distinct groups with their own minds and views, this research aspires to move these two communities closer by providing a blueprint of how each of them thinks about policymaking, what their priorities are and how they want to be treated. As each policy actor (academics, think tank members, lobbyists, internal advisors, NGOs, trade unions, Student unions...) has an agenda of his own which at times does not go along with that of the policymaker. This research explicitly discusses these views and propose remedies.

This research will also add to the persisting debates on how evidence influences policymaking and to what extent can a policy be evidence based or evidence informed, drawing from the academic work on research use, policy advisory systems, policy making models, and policy networks to build a well-balanced narrative. This narrative will also supplement original empirical data for a global South country that has been for so long absent from similar debates and expand on the available insights from the Scottish case.

Finally, the comparative case study approach will allow the demonstration of the similarities and differences of policy advisers' and experts' involvements in the making of higher education policy in Algeria and Scotland.

1.8 Structure of the Thesis

The dissertation has adopted the following structure. Chapter 1 is an introduction that includes the statement of the problem, research aims, research questions, scope of the study and the

scholarly contribution of the thesis. The chapter also puts Algeria and Scotland in comparative perspectives politically, economically.

Chapter 2 puts Algeria and Scotland in a comparative position to critically explore the Global South vs The Global North power dynamics. Algeria, a country still struggling with its postcolonial heritage against the unique devolved governance system under which Scotland operates. The chapter also addresses the political and economic landscapes in the two countries, scrutinizes the impact of the UK context and its implications for multilevel governance in the Scottish case, and the international drivers for reform in Algerian Higher education. The chapter closes by exploring how the two countries represent two distinct cases for path dependency.

Chapter 3 describes the background and context and analyses the Algerian and Scottish higher education and role of policy, key policies guiding/governing higher education in the two countries. This chapter presents a critical analysis of how in both countries higher education developed over the past 20 years. In Algeria, the policies underpinning the introduction of the BMD system, quality assurance, the link between HE and the Algerian economy, and the internalisation of higher education are discussed. In Scotland, the chapter addresses the tuition fees policy, quality assurance, widening access and the HE governance reform.

Chapter 4 presents the conceptual frameworks for the study drawn from key literature review of the literatures on policymaking and policy process models along with expert knowledge, which entails policy networks such as issue networks, epistemic communities, policy communities, and advocacy coalitions. Moreover, a section is devoted to policy advice and advisory systems.

Chapter 5 describes the research methodology for the study and comprise the following subsection: research paradigm, research method adopted, data collection tools, samples and sampling procedures, analysis of data, criteria of data quality (credibility, transferability, dependability, and confirmability), along the ethical considerations (Privacy, anonymity, and confidentiality).

Chapter 6 represents the first main thematic chapter in the thesis. It explores how policy advice has shaped higher education policy in Algeria and Scotland based on the findings from the interviews and the document analysis. In the focus are commissions and committees in both countries, the work of panels, the influence of think tanks, and conferences and symposiums in the six selected policy areas. In Algeria, the designated higher education policies were the

Bachelor, Masters and Doctorate (BMD) Programme (2003-2020), Quality Assurance in Higher Education (2008-2020) and International Mobility (2014-2019). In Scotland, the policy areas were the funding developments in Higher Education mainly the tuition fees policy (1999-2016), Widening Access (2014-2019), and Higher Education Governance Reform (2011-2016).

Chapter 7 is the second thematic chapter in the thesis. It identifies the strategies used by policy actors and experts in influencing higher education policymaking in Algeria and Scotland. These include the use of evidence, networking, expertise, and epistemic authority, taking part in governmental calls for evidence and consultations, lobbying, proper communication skills set, horizon scanning and policy learning. The chapter also critically discusses why certain strategies work better.

Chapter 8 is the third thematic chapter, which further discusses the commonalities and differences in the way Algeria and Scotland employed policy advice to inform higher education policy choices. The chapter presents the researcher's reflections on the use of policy advice and its influence on higher education in Algeria and Scotland.

Chapter 9 is the conclusion of the study. It also offers some proposals on how policy advice should best be understood and used. The chapter addresses several issues. First, it summarises the key findings of the study in response to the three research questions. Second, it details the potential importance of this thesis and its contribution to the world of academia while also raising some limitations of the study. Third, it discusses implications and recommendations for future research.

Chapter 2

Algeria and Scotland in Comparatives Perspectives

2.1 Introduction

The chapter sets Algeria and Scotland in a comparative perspective to offer a critical investigation of how the Global North vs Global South discourse has shaped the perceptions around these two countries and to provide a context and rationale behind the particular choice of these two politically, economically, and culturally distinct entities. The examination also extends to include other significant factors influencing the two countries' trajectories in terms of how they chose to run their higher education sectors. In Scotland, the devolved nature of the Scottish system provided a ground for the examination of multilevel governance, a defining feature of the country's governance mechanisms, whereas in Algeria, the impact of globalisation and international pressures had driven the country's higher education system towards a specific direction. Collectively, this analysis reveals that both Algeria and Scotland demonstrate strong patterns of path dependency, each in their own unique way.

2.2 Implications of Global South-North Power Dynamics

Therien (1999) argues that the concepts of the Global North and South were a widely popular lens to view poverty and disparity in the world for over a generation. This led to the shaping of scholarly discourse in a way that sees the world divided into two distinct spheres. A Northern part characterized by a rich thriving industry and a Southern part scarred by poverty and deprivation. The generalization that aims at painting the global south as a specimen of countries marked by turbulent political events, fragile economies, and a home for corruption and criminality can be deceptive (Grimm, 2019). On the other hand, the North was portrayed as the nexus of sustainable growth and wealth. This terminology is still commonly used to depict the historical distinctions in living conditions, prosperity, and global influence despite the worldwide reconfiguration (Kowalski, 2020). In this regard, it is highly important to highlight that the global South is often regarded as a construct forged by Western countries and applied to define specific populations and geographical areas, which opens up reflection on the degree of its authenticity (Kloß, 2017).

There is a widespread belief that the knowledge produced from the Global North is superior in certain ways as it lays the foundation for how power is distributed between the centre and periphery. This view insinuates that academic research produced by and about the North is more relevant than the one carried out by and about the Global South since peripheral countries are seen as the ones who passively receive the core countries' breakthroughs both in historical and scientific chronicles and narratives that themselves remain predominantly western (Castro Torres and Alburez-Gutierrez, 2022; Chakrabarty, 2000).

Building on this view, Lumb (2023) argues that Global North organizations often look at the Global South in general, and Africa in particular as incompetent and that they are supposed to provide leadership and guidance to these countries while using terms like poverty reduction and mentoring to justify their superior status. While African establishments strive to be involved in global knowledge production, their institutional collaborations with the Global North have a peculiar focus on recruiting students obstructing equal cooperation that can be mutually beneficial (Lumb, 2023). A common view is that knowledge production is almost exclusive to the Global North, nevertheless, ongoing conversations are addressing the issue of knowledge production, dissemination and realignment within universal settings (Collyer, 2016).

The 1960s witnessed a prevalent wave of exploitation, hence the terms Global South and Global North were coined to depict the resistance against the ongoing colonization and neocolonial coercion. One might think that securing independence would eradicate the inequalities inherited from the colonial era, yet despite national endeavours, these leftovers remain ingrained in postcolonial communities (Gonzalez-Vicente, 2019). Political standpoints in these countries (Post colonial) as well as societal organizations and governance structures are heavily shaped by the colonial heritage (Parashar and Schulz, 2021). In their pursuit of independence, these countries were forced to maintain internal plurality while reinforcing national identities, which would often lead to demands of self-governance and autonomy in the form of nationalist mobilisation and campaigns (Chandrashekara, 2018).

It's interesting to note that Scotland's experience with devolution has also been strongly linked to a strong sense of national identity, which manifested in social movements as a political expression. The current devolved political structure was shaped and legitimized in large part by this strong sense of national identity (Ichijo, 2012). Additionally, Scottish nationalism is not only characterized by geographical borders or the desire for independence; rather, it is

entrenched in the population's culture and psychology and continues to play a vital role in Scottish politics and society, influencing the country long after the modern Scottish Parliament was established (Soule, Leith, and Steven, 2012). Algeria, on the other hand, had its own unique colonial experience because it was regarded as an essential constituency that belongs to France, which made the decolonization process particularly challenging. Both sides in the Algerian War of Independence engaged in extreme violence, and the FLN used Cold War politics to undermine French colonial defences. Following the independence in 1962, approximately 1.5 million pied noirs were forced to relocate to France and the situationally dual identity of European Algerians was no longer viable (Davis, 2011).

Even after their independence, postcolonial countries keep grappling with persistent inequalities related to gender, economy, and geography. These inequities are even present in collaborative projects within Southern countries (South-South) and often take the shape of the power vested primarily in the central government and occasional bottom-up policies (Gonzalez-Vicente, 2019). Furthermore, it has been noted by Eleazer and Kingdom (2021) that policies coming from the Global North often aim at reinforcing the principles of subordination and dependency and linking southern economies, politics, and cultures to the agenda set by the North thus hindering attempts at achieving true independence and progress. To protect their economies, South-South partnerships were born to guard against the exposure of Northern exploitation and mitigate the negative effects of globalization (Asante, 2018).

2.2.1 Political landscape

The Algerian political context, of course, differs markedly from the UK and Scottish context. In 1991, the Islamic Salvation Front (FIS) unexpectedly won the first round of parliamentary elections in December 1991. This prompted the Algerian military to step in and postpone the second round of elections to avoid the establishment of what the secular elite feared as an extremist-led government. Following the military's suspension of the election process, there was a violent outburst and widespread violations of human rights throughout the nation. A wide range of atrocities, including sexual assault, forced disappearances, mass murders, massacres, and political assassinations, could happen to civilians (Zeraoulia, 2022). When the army started to crack down on the FIS, supporters of the group started attacking government targets. Fighting turned into an insurgency that saw severe violence from 1992 to 1998, killing over 150,000 people, many of whom were believed to have been killed by extremists during their indiscriminate massacres of villagers (Schulhofer-Wohl, 2007).

By the late 1990s, the government took control, giving orders to dissolve the Islamic Salvation Army, the armed wing of FIS in January 2000. With the military's support, former president Abdelaziz Bouteflika emerged victorious in the 1999 presidential election. President Bouteflika proposed his amnesty project, known as the Civil Concord, in 1999, replacing President Liamine Zaroual's failed Rahma initiative. The Civil Concord was later replaced by the Charter for Peace and National Reconciliation in 2006 (Daoudi, 2020). Although it is widely acknowledged that the 2006 Reconciliation Charter and the 1999 Civil Concord brought peace to Algeria, the amnesties granted to terrorists and state security forces, as well as the enforced silence, are seen as deeply unjust, especially by the families of the 8,000 "disappeared" and the 200,000 victims of the conflict. Compensation has not allowed for true reconciliation, especially for the families of the disappeared, who demand to know the truth (Bertelsmann Stiftung, 2022).

Although there has been a multiparty system in Algeria since 1989, religiously guided parties are illegal in the country. The 2012 laws pertaining to political parties and elections have made it easier for new parties to form. In 2019, there were 64 official registrations. Parties are not thought to represent the populace, though, and their social foundations are still weak. Currently, 36 parties are represented in the APN, or National Popular Assembly. The Democratic National Rally (Rassemblement National Démocratique, RND) and the National Liberation Front (Front de Libération Nationale, FLN) have dominated electoral politics over the past ten years (Bertelsmann Stiftung, 2022).

The possibility of a fifth term for Bouteflika, a president who suffered a stroke in 2013 and was unable to perform his duties properly, sparked the Hirak. The demonstrations began on February 16, 2019, and continued through March 2020. The COVID-19 pandemic caused them to end, but they resumed in February 2021, a year later. The marches continued to be national, popular, and pacifist. The movement's demands did not change. They called for the actual destruction of the "system" and its delegates, press freedom, judicial independence, political supremacy over the military, and democracy (Ourahmoune, 2021; Spitz, 2023). Following Bouteflika's resignation in April 2019, Algerians elected Abdelmadjid Tebboune, a former prime minister, as the nation's new president in December 2019. Algeria conducted a referendum on its constitution in 2020, and President Tebboune implemented the results in January 2021 (Szmolka, 2022). The state's authoritarian tendencies, the trauma of the 1990s, and the top-down reconciliation process had seriously damaged citizen trust, but the Hirak

started a process of gradual convergence and fostering confidence (Bertelsmann Stiftung, 2022).

In the United Kingdom, the devolution (the transfer of power by a central government to local or regional administrations (Torrance, 2024) was an important aspect of a post-1997 agenda-setting pathway of constitutional policy programs that significantly defined the Blair Government's strategy, especially in its early years (McGarvey and McConnell, 2012). The Blair Government's electoral prospects and reputation were bolstered by the programmatic aspect of Scottish devolution, which also addressed the issue of Scotland's perceived democratic deficit and served as a precursor to the Blair Government's non-conservative stance on the UK constitution. McGarvey and McConnell (2012) further maintain that the devolution in Scotland was prompted by both positive and negative factors. Firstly, the rejection of Thatcherism which gave rise to a "negative consensus." Secondly, a devolution would stop UK government policies from being imposed on Scotland when there is no popular support for them. Thirdly, it would restructure Scotland's executive government since the Scottish Office at the time was generally seen as being insensitive to a Scottish agenda. On the positive side, it was projected that devolution would provide a more favourable opportunity to customize Scottish public policy processes and outcomes to better represent Scottish conditions and preferences (McGarvey and McConnell, 2012).

In the Scottish referendum held on September 11, 1997, a resounding majority approved the creation of a Scottish Parliament with tax-varying powers. The Scotland Bill was introduced by the Government later on in the first parliamentary session. In 1998, the Scotland Act was passed by the UK Parliament, establishing Scotland's first Parliament since 1707 (UK Government, 1998) although Scotland witnessed an "administrative devolution" back in 1885 (Torrance, 2024). Under the terms of this Act, the Scottish Parliament may pass legislation affecting Scotland on a range of internal matters. In areas not reserved to Westminster, the Scotland Act 1998 gives the Scottish Parliament the power to pass primary and secondary legislation (UK Government, 1998; Holden, 2010). Since 1999, there have been several adjustments and expansions to the powers granted to the Scottish Parliament as part of devolution. These include the Scotland Acts of 2012 (UK Government, 2012) and 2016 (UK Government, 2016), which each granted significant additional powers with bipartisan support (UK Government, 2019).

Reserved matters include the constitution, foreign affairs, defence, international development, the Civil Service, financial and economic matters, immigration and nationality, misuse of drugs, trade and industry, aspects of energy regulation (e.g. electricity, coal, oil and gas and nuclear energy), aspects of transport (e.g. regulation of air services, rail and international shipping), employment, social security, abortion, genetics, surrogacy, medicines, broadcasting, equal opportunities. Consequently, devolved matters include health and social work, education and training, local government and housing, justice and policing, agriculture, forestry and fisheries, the environment, tourism, sport and heritage, economic development and internal transport (UK Government, 2019).

In 2003 and 2007, there were elections to the Scottish Parliament. After negotiations with the other parties, the Scottish National Party (SNP), which had defeated Labour by one seat in the May 3, 2007, elections, established Scotland's first minority government, with Alex Salmond serving as Prime Minister (Holden, 2010). Following the Scottish National Party's 2007 win, the Scottish Executive became the Scottish Government (Unger, 2013). The win also launched the spark for a counter-devolution movement under the Scottish Government's 2009 White Paper, "Your Scotland, Your Voice" which served as the foundation for a draft bill that aimed to call for a referendum. One of the options in the referendum regarding Scotland's future government was Scottish independence (McGarvey and McConnell, 2012). The SNP roots can be traced back to 1934 when John MacCormick established the Scottish National Party (SNP) in 1934 to secure Scotland's Home Rule through a Scottish Parliament inside the United Kingdom, not to establish an independent Scotland. But his party's members completely rejected this plan, ousted MacCormick from the SNP leadership, and chose to become a separatist movement instead (Raina, 2023).

The Scottish National Party (SNP), which received 47% of the vote and a majority in government, proposed the referendum in May 2011. Nevertheless, the political discussion was only sparked by the May and June 2012 campaigns of Yes Scotland and Better Together, two opposing movements. Yes Scotland, with backing from the SNP, ran an independence campaign. The three pro-Union political parties in Scotland; Scottish Labour, Scottish Conservative Party, and Scottish Liberal Democrats; supported the "No" vote campaigned by Better Together Scottish Green Party and Scottish Socialists (Antunes, 2015).

On September 18, 2014, the Scottish Independence Referendum was held, the question "Should Scotland be an independent country?" was rejected by a margin of 10.6 percentage points when

55.3% voted 'No', and 44.7% voted 'Yes'. Including the rejected ballots, the referendum had an attendance of 84.6% (84.5% based on valid votes) (UK Parliament, 2014). Then First Minister Alex Salmond resigned in the wake of the result, and Nicola Sturgeon took over. Two years later, the Brexit referendum in June 2016 gave the independence movement new life and immediacy, as Scotland voted 62% to 38% to stay in the UK while the rest of the UK voted 52% to 48% to leave. In May 2019, Ms. Sturgeon set aside the second half of 2020 for a second constitutional referendum, but in the face of Westminster's unwavering opposition, the momentum did not translate into tangible action towards an independence referendum (Cochrane, 2023).

2.2.2 Economic Performance

With a Population of 43.9 million in 2020 (World Bank, 2020), Algeria's economy has been performing poorly as a result of a public sector-led model that is outdated and hydrocarbon production that has remained stagnant (World Bank, 2020). Algeria has recovered since the early 2000s and entered a new phase of its political and economic system (growth rate increased to more than 2.0% between 2000 and 2013). This is the outcome of three things coming together: First, the dramatic decrease in the various forms of armed violence that defined the 1990s as explained in this chapter. Second, a notable rise in the state's financial reserves, or the fiscus, associated with improved hydrocarbon valorization. Up until the global economic downturn in the middle of 2014, there was a high demand for raw materials on the market where these were exported. The third factor is the election of Abdelaziz Bouteflika in April 1999 (Haouas, Ochi and Labidi, 2021). However, as Chekouri, Chibi and Benbouziane (2017) have noted, despite the fact that the dependency on oil revenues have had a positive impact on economic growth in Algeria, it remains pivotal to diversify the sources of economic revenues to navigate the up and down of the global market.

Owing to their favourable financial circumstances, the authorities started implementing a number of large-scale public investment projects in 2001 as part of an expansionist budgetary policy. The Support Program for Economic Recovery (PSRE) 2001-2004 with a budget of 525 billion dinars (USD 7 billion) and launch the Complementary Plan for Support to Growth (Economic growth support programme 2005-2009) with a budget of 4202.8 billion dinars (USD 55 billion), and the Consolidation of Economic Growth Programme (PCCE: 2010–2014) with a budget of 21,214 billion dinars (USD 286 billion). (Dahmani and Rekrak, 2015; Rey and Hazem, 2019). Due to these reforms, Algeria witnessed a remarkable an overall economic

growth (Necir and Nadhir, 2019) as its GDP grew at an average annual rate of about 4% between 2000 and 2015; however, this relatively satisfactory growth is still vulnerable because it depends heavily on the hydrocarbons sector and public demand. Algeria has advanced economically over the last 20 years thanks to the boom in hydrocarbons. In 2008, the nation invested in infrastructure projects bolstering economic growth, almost completely paid off its multilateral debt, and implemented redistributive social policies that reduced poverty and markedly enhanced Human Development Indicators (World Bank, 2023). In 2017 and 2018, Algeria implemented new tariffs on certain products and suspended imports of others in an effort to limit imports and promote Algerian producers (Bertelsmann Stiftung, 2022).

The shift to a growth model led by the private sector is proving difficult; private companies are still small, low-productivity, and primarily informal, and they face numerous obstacles such as stringent regulations, restricted access to capital and skilled labour, or the dominance of state-owned businesses (World Bank, 2020). Furthermore, little regional trade exists, and market liberalization efforts are hindered by a restrictive investment law that allows foreign ownership of businesses to account for no more than 49% of their total ownership. Algeria's difficult economic climate, erratic political situation, and reliance on hydrocarbons all continue to impede the country's chances of achieving sustainable economic growth (Bertelsmann Stiftung, 2022). The production of hydrocarbons and export earnings continue to be crucial to the nation's economy. In terms of GDP (gross domestic product), the hydrocarbon industry accounted for 19%, product exports for 93%, and budgetary revenues for 38% between 2016 and 2021 (World Bank, 2023).

On the other side, Scotland's population, according to the Office for National Statistics (ONS), was 5.47 million in mid-2020, representing 8.1% of the UK's total population. According to data from ONS, the Scottish economy contributed roughly 8% of the UK's GDP in 2019 (UK Parliament, 2021). Scotland's onshore GDP is currently valued at £162.4 billion, or £32,000 per person. The equivalent amounts in cash prices in 1999 were £15,500 per person and £78.6 billion. This indicates a 107% increase over nearly 20 years (Scottish Government, 2019). Scotland is a small open economy that makes up around one-third of the UK's landmass and is home to abundant natural resources on both land and in the sea (Scottish Government, 2022).

During the post-Devolution period, Scotland's relative economic performance has been equivalent to the UK's; however, up until 2003, Scotland's relative performance was noticeably lower due to abnormal performance in some industrial sectors, such as hotels and catering,

financial services, and construction (McLaren et al., 2011). UK government policy includes initiatives to support Scotland's and the country's economy as a whole. Devolution has, in the meantime, enabled administrations in Scotland and elsewhere to formulate policies targeted at enhancing their own economies and well-being (UK Parliament, 2021).

Since 1999, ten frameworks, plans, and strategies have been developed to advance Scotland's economy (SPICe, 2019b). The then Scottish Executive introduced *The Way Forward: Framework for Economic Development in Scotland* in 2000. *A Smart, Successful Scotland*, the first economic strategy for a devolved Scotland, came into effect in 2001 and built upon the first one. In 2004, the framework and strategy were updated. The Scottish Government released the *Government Economic Strategy* in 2007, just before the financial crisis and recession hit. Following the 2011 election, the government revised its economic strategy and released an *Economic Recovery Plan* in 2008. Scotland's *Economic Strategy* was subsequently released by the government in 2015. Scotland's primary economic policy document as of right now is this 2015 strategy, but since then, there has been constant policy turbulence to support it. The *Enterprise and Skills Board: Strategic Plan* was created in 2018 as a result of the 2016 launch of the *Enterprise and Skills Review*. Finally, the *Economic Action Plan* arrived in late 2018. However, this could be considered more of a website that lists various economic initiatives and support than it is a plan Scottish Government (2019).

Since 2007, the SNP government has made improving relative economic performance one of its top priorities and all other political parties in Scotland also fairly support this goal (McLaren et al., 2011). This did not protect Scotland's economy, like that of the rest of the UK, from having several difficulties which include the effects of the 2008–2009 financial crisis, the UK government's austerity measures, the 2014 oil price shock, and the early adjustments made in anticipation of the UK's exit from the European single market (Scottish Government, 2022). Nevertheless, since the financial crisis of 2008–2009, Scotland's labour market participation has done well, with headline labour market indicators (unemployment and employment) nearing record highs. Scotland's employment rate increased gradually before the COVID-19 pandemic (December to February 2020), rising from 69.8% in February to April 2010 to 75.4% (Scottish Government, 2022).

The UK as a whole continues to be Scotland's principal trading partner. According to data from the Scottish Government, 38% of Scotland's exports were to other countries in 2020, with the remaining 62% going to the rest of the UK. 33% of Scotland's imports came from outside the

UK, and 67% came from the rest of the UK (UK Parliament, 2021). Overall, Scotland's economic policy environment has changed over the past 20 years, moving from a more limited enterprise agency approach to a more comprehensive whole government approach Scottish SPICe (2019b). Ministerial accountability for economic policy has also taken on various forms and identities. This more comprehensive approach to economic policy has its advantages, but it has also undermined accountability and made it harder to determine what truly works (SPICe, 2019b; Scottish Government, 2019b).

2.3 The UK: Policymaking and Pressures on Higher Education

Since the 1980s higher education reforms in the UK witnessed a gradual shift towards the adoption of a neoliberal ideology (Fotiadou, 2022). Ball (2012) notes that these changes show a wider shift in policy which consider education more as a product in the market and students are seen as consumers while universities compete as service providers. This shift has changed the values in education focusing more on performance, accountability and financial returns instead of traditional principles revolving around public good and fairness. During the economic downturn and cuts in public spending in the 1980s, the Thatcher government looked into changing the student support system. They chose to pass some of the costs onto students, their families and sponsors to reduce government spending on higher education (Welch 2009; Wilson 1997; Lewis Bolton and Wilson 2024).

Since higher education was seen as a private good instead of a public one, students were expected to pay for their education through tuition and loans following the principle that the government is making an investment in their skills which will have lucrative outcomes in the long haul (Exley and Ball 2014). As a result, students were expected to be drawn toward disciplines with business orientations over those in the arts humanities and social sciences which were deemed less financially rewarding (Exley and Ball 2014). Interestingly, Ball (2009) believe that the privatisation of education is part of a bigger reform movement instead of being the end. For Welsh (2009), the Conservative government initiated the move towards the privatisation of the sector through a remarkable increase in its control by managing the funding aspect as it deliberately resorted to cuts in public spending and nurturing private sector principles such as productivity and competition. These amendments were further intensified by the labour government which took control in 1997 (Welch 2009). In Scotland, where the conservative government did not enjoy the Scottish MPs unwavering support, the shift towards

a marketized education was widely rejected (Byrne and Ozga 2008). The labour governments, on the other hand, had their agenda oriented more towards fair access to higher education (Welch 2009). The 1990s also witnessed a rise in productivity and competition because funding for academic programs became dependent on performance in the Research Assessment Exercise (RAE) (Exley and Ball 2014). By 1997, student enrolment grew significantly whereas student funding kept declining which led to the commissioning of the National Committee of Inquiry into Higher Education, also known as the Dearing Report (1997) to tackle these funding issues. The report represents a significant moment in the history of UK higher education for being the first thorough review in the span of several years. The report advised that while the UK government would remain the primary funder of higher education, graduates and the society should contribute to the costs of higher education (Bolton and Hubble 2018). The adoption of market-oriented funding mechanisms where most students must pay their tuition fees marked the UK governments' official commitment to incorporate the market principles into its higher education system (West 2001). Moreover, the combination of the demand of the international market and the new funding models transformed the students and staff interactions into economic transactions where academic knowledge is the product that must be sold (Exley and Ball 2014).

Quality assurance was another significant area that received considerable attention with the setting of the Quality Assurance Agency (QAA) in 1997 to promote quality practices and resources in the UK. Following this initiative, the government launched diverse funding programs to enhance the teaching standards in higher education institutions and to widen access for marginalised groups (Welch 2009).

The 2004 higher education act put forward varying tuition fees while offering maintenance grants and higher loan limits as a form of support for student from low-income households and universities in their turn had to make sure that students from disadvantaged backgrounds were guaranteed access to their higher education institutions (Wyness, 2010; Bolton and Hubble, 2018). This approach (the provision of financial payments and grants) was described as probably the best recommended course of action to increase enrolment rates within people from lower socioeconomic status (Pennell and West, 2005). The framework was not completely unproblematic and did face resistance at first but it led universities to financial stability and helped entrench the idea of graduates' contribution to their education in UK higher education policy (Browne, 2010).

Another milestone in the history of the UK higher education was the commissioning of an Independent Review of Higher Education Funding and Student Finance led by Lord John Browne to assess the sustainability of the UK funding system in 2009, which in 2010 recommended the removal of tuition fees limits to permit universities to set their own charges shifting the financial burden from taxpayers to students and improving the education quality via competition, principles strongly endorsed by the coalition government (Hubble, 2010; Hickey, 2022). A year later, the UK government suggested that the fee cap should be raised to £9 000 and keeping a base fee of £6 000 (Universities that charged more than £6 000 must offer scholarships and meet access requirements) (Bolton and Hubble, 2018; Carasso and Gunn, 2015). In 2016, The UK government launched the teaching excellence Framework (TEF) to recognize and reward high quality teaching and through which it conditioned universities' capacity to increase their tuition fees to £9 250 with their ability to reach certain teaching standards (Department for Education 2016; Hubble, 2017). Under the pressure from the public demanding change, Prime Minister Theresa May launched a review of the student finance system, known as the Augar Review (Lewis and Bolton, 2022). This review aimed to assess post-18 education and funding to enhance access to all academic, technical and vocational education (Lewis Bolton and Wilson, 2023). The goal of the review was to improve access to different education paths, to increase value for students and taxpayers and tackle skill shortages in the economy (Independent panel report to the Review of Post-18 Education and Funding, 2019).

At the international level, The United Kingdom is considered a leader in the internationalization of higher education mainly because it attracts many international students and has set up programs abroad (Riedl and Staubmann, 2021). The UK is important for providing higher education options to students from both the EU and other countries (Wes,t 2001). This status stems from the OECD and the European Commission engagement in the evaluation and ranking processes of education systems globally to assist countries in determining their own level compared to others in the world (Grek 2009; Grek and Ozga 2010). As the Crown jewels, Scottish universities were able to build an international reputation for excellence becoming one of Scotland's most compelling soft power assets (McClory, 2023).

The UK used to operate under a dual design to manage cross student mobility in higher education before the Brexit vote. The first model took a focus on a commercial international education system that aimed to attract foreign students to the UK which has become a vital source of income for teaching and research (Adams, 2022). The other model was the EU's

Erasmus+ program which promoted student exchanges based on mutual benefits (Highman, Marginson and Papatsiba 2023). However in December 2020, the UK decided to leave this program and introduced a new domestic option called the Turing Scheme (Paul, 2021).

The World system theory which divides the world into core countries like Canada France Germany the UK and the US, peripheral countries in Latin America and Africa, and Semi-peripheral countries such as those in Asia and Eastern Europe contends that while Core and peripheral countries retain their status, semi peripheral countries have the ability to either move closer to the center or glide away depending on global social, political, and economic conditions (Chen and Barnett, 2000). International students tend to be attracted to core countries due to their resources and knowledge, which give their overall movement a specific pattern that is closely linked to economic status of these countries (Chen and Barnett, 2000). Other factors include the cost of tuition fees, the perceived quality of education and the academic reputation of the institution including how well-known an institution is and how its degrees are viewed in job markets both locally and globally can also affect student movement (Bourke 1997; Briggs, 2006; Park, 2009; Kahanec and Kralikova, 2011).

The opportunities offered by advanced economies for a decent education and career provide a strong and luring temptation for international students to settle in these countries instead of returning to their home countries and developing their nations (Chen and Barnett, 2000). As a result, the destination countries profit from these students while their home countries lose important human capital which feels like a waste of money on their education and training that ended up as a consumption rather than an investment (Kelo and Wächter, 2004).

2.4 Exploring Multilevel Governance in the Scottish Context

A close look will prove that local governments in the UK operates within a multi layered system commonly known as Multi-Level Governance where the decision-making power is distributed among the local, regional, national, and even international levels of the government (McConnell 2006). As a concept, MLG examines how the variety of individual actors and actors' constellations (both institutional and non-institutional) interact with each other in policymaking across different levels of governments crossing traditional boundaries that are not physically real and forging networks (Piattoni 2009). The term multi-level-governance was initially coined by Marks (1993, 1996) and later improved by Hooghe and Marks (2001). The framework has been put forward as a theoretical lens to account for the growing complexity

and interdependence within EU governance and to help unravel the complicated relationships in EU governance as it shows how different groups and connections work together in contemporary political systems (Hooghe and Marks, 2001; 2003; Piattoni, 2009). The framework examines the distribution of power and explains how central governments lose some control to local, international, and supranational institutions and how power spreads between government and community actors (Piattoni, 2009; Piattoni, 2010).

Scotland is a prototype of this structure since the local government has to function and manage its responsibilities with the Scottish Parliament, the UK government, and other organizations and engage in a dialogue with multiple parties (Wilson, 2003). These mechanisms reflect the main tenets embedded in MLG, which claim that there is no one central authority controlling the governance but more of a web of overlapping roles among various government levels and policy networks (McConnell, 2006).

In Scotland, the devolution intended to set a new governance style that is influenced by Scotland's own historical traditions (McAteer and Bennett, 2005). After the devolution, local and national governments were brought closer together which led the Scottish executive to become easier to reach and more responsive to local governments than before, boosted Scotland's abilities to enact policies and laws and brought together different levels of government to address Scotland's distinctive challenges and opportunities in a display of a radical move towards a more coordinated governance model (Bennett, Fairley and McAteer, 2002). These features correspond with the principles of MLG which call for a decision making process that is more inclusive, decentralized and collaborative involving multiple government levels (Hooghe and Marks, 2001). In Scotland, McAteer and Bennett (2005) contend that the concretization of this system of governance on the ground has been shaped and in some aspects constrained by the long standing traditional patterns and past political actions (McAteer and Bennett, 2005).

For McConnell (2006), the establishment of the Scottish parliament exhibit strong signs of an oriented shift towards an era of "new politics" where local representatives no longer have to, physically, go to Westminster to take part in legislative actions resulting in a tighter relationship between the Scottish parliament and the local authorities than the one shared between these local authorities and the UK government previously. In theory, the Scottish case reflects the true principles of MLG features, yet on the ground the reality is slightly different. The policy and funding along the political norms and institutional cultures in Scotland seem to reflect the

influence exerted by Westminster years after the devolution, an influence that has not gone unnoticed and that clashes with the Scottish desire behind the devolution for more inclusive type of politics (McAteer and Bennett, 2005). A deeper look unveils that the power balance between the central and local governments has hardly changed and despite the existence of cooperation signs and more local power, the latter seem to struggle for independence which highlights the limits of power distribution under the MLG framework (McConnell, 2006). This environment added more tension to the central/local relationship and the interactions between the different levels of government became plagued with mistrust making it hard to manage (McAteer and Bennett, 2005).

The academic scholarship around the devolution has a tendency to concentrate on the transfer of power from the UK national level downwards while the research on internalisation examines the shift of power upward to international organizations such as the European Commission and those involved in the Bologna Process (Keeling, 2006). Based on Piattoni (2010) who discusses the three dimensions where MLG takes place, Fumasoli (2015) builds on his analysis to discuss MLG phenomenon in higher education policymaking. Piattoni (2010) and Fumasoli (2015) argue that MLG occurs along three spheres. The first sphere is the center–periphery where power is devolved to smaller local governments through Type I arrangements such as bestowing public universities with more independence and autonomy or Type II methods such as providing local governments with financial rewards to support higher education. The second sphere is the domestic–international where some powers are transferred by the government to international organizations. An example of this is the Bologna Process, which affects how curriculums are structured or the European Commission, which helps fund research. The third sphere is the state–society where the government transfer authority to social groups. This includes collaborations between public and private sectors in research and professional groups such as academics who help shape career paths or provide expertise for policymaking committees.

This context depicts a multilevel governance system in which policy authority is distributed between local, national, and international levels. However, it is paramount to highlight that as Gallacher and Raffe (2012) explained, the growth and complexity of international ties can have a detrimental effect on national policymaking since the decisions made in one country are increasingly affecting the ones made in others.

Scottish higher education policy takes place within a complex system of governance as it operates under a devolved nation within the central authority of the UK while being part of a bigger European and global policy landscape. Since its inception in 1999, the Scottish government has been in control of education including the provision of higher education funding, guidelines about access, and the quality of knowledge while the UK government regulates important economic factors, immigration, and research funding through UK Research and Innovation (UKRI) which curbs Scotland's independence in these areas (UK Government, 2013). Furthermore, certain areas like immigration fall under the UK Government, particularly through UK Visas and Immigration (UKVI), creating a cross-jurisdictional dependency since these aspects are not devolved to the Scottish Government. Universities themselves bear responsibility for ensuring compliance with regulations and maintaining academic quality (Cobbett, 2025). This interdependency between Scottish universities and the UK-wide regulatory demonstrates that while Scotland's universities are a devolved matter, they are not immune from British political developments as flagged by Alastair Sim, Director of the Scottish Principals' pressure group, Universities Scotland, who warned that the Augar report's proposed reduction of fees for English, Welsh, and Northern Irish students would have a negative impact on Scottish and EU students attending Scottish universities (Valentine, 2019). Furthermore, it is important to highlight that universities in Scotland have to balance being both UK and Scottish establishments, which creates a more layered power dynamic and complicates the interdependencies between Scottish universities, the Scottish Government, and the UK government (Scott, 2021).

At the global level, Scottish universities are in constant contests as they strive to meet the European and international higher education standards through agreements like the Bologna Process and involvement in EU and NON-EU programs even after Brexit (Scottish Government, 2025).

The Bologna process welcomes both individual and group actors including national higher education ministries and various international organization to actively engage in the process in a display of multi-level governance (Enders and Westerheijden, 2011; Elken and Vukasovic, 2014). An example of how invested Scotland was in the Bologna process was the pilot verification process it took part in for the BP to help align its national qualifications with the European Higher Education Area (EHEA) in 2006 where the results were discussed with other stakeholders and countries (QAA Scotland, 2007).

Although the Scottish experience after the devolution exemplifies, to a certain extent, the principles behind MLG where power is decentralized and shared across different levels of institutions, actual power remains unevenly distributed and the degree through which actors benefit from the framework is highly dependent on their previous roles and affiliations within policy networks endorsing the idea that established institutions and interests have a decisive influence on shaping policy (McAteer and Bennett, 2005).

2.5 Global Pressures and Higher Education Reform in Algeria

In Algeria, the collection of global trends and international policies framed the educational reforms in the country especially in higher education where there is an urgency in modernizing the system, promoting a culture of quality while meeting international standards. However, the internalisation endeavours would often collide with the country's desires to decolonize, advance equality and access and preserving its cultural identity (Lahmar, 2024). Ball (1998) contends that educational policy is inevitably shaped by global influences and organizations such as the world bank.

In state-run higher education systems, like the case in Algeria, the government is the principal authority overseeing how HE institutions function due to their dependency on the government's funding (Benstaali, 2013). This control is exerted either by setting the sector's strategic missions and policies directly or through appointed boards. This dominant presence often undermines the HE institutions' autonomy, constrain academic freedom and enforce restrictions on students and staff unions to keep the political control under control. These circumstances frequently lead to policies born out of loyalty and conformity among universities' staff (Kilemi, 2022).

In the 1980s, the United Kingdom was the second destination (after France) for Algerian students wishing to pursue their studies or benefit from training abroad and many successful studies abroad exchange programs have also been run by British universities with Algerian universities (UK Parliament, 2022). The Algerian government issued the the Framework Act no. 08-04, which was passed on January 23, 2008 to endorse and stressing high quality, inclusive education and promoting bilingualism in tune with UNESCO's aim for universal literacy. The same act also supports the principles of lifelong learning and teaching methods that stimulate critical thinking and problem-solving skills in line with the United Nations' Sustainable Development Goals (Lahmar, 2024).

Moreover, the Act authorized the creation of private universities marking a radical change in the government's policy which previously stood against these establishments, yet in reality, the process is deemed slow (Bedaida, Benguerna and Jean-Baptiste, 2022). The Act is an attempt to embrace global influences while preserving Algeria's national identity with a focus on market-oriented approaches and neoliberal ideas such as the focus on science and technology to ensure relevance to global education. Despite these steps, there are still challenges hindering the full adoption of these principles in the ground (Lahmar, 2024).

Algeria was not a member in the Bologna Process but since the Bologna Agreement which was previously restricted to the member countries, was expanded in 2003 when a working group recognised the strategic importance of North African countries, particularly those located in the Southern Mediterranean as potential participants (Zgaga, 2006). The focus on "the external dimension" was an attempt to encourage regional collaboration, promote cultural exchange, enhance the quality of higher education and create a united regional job market with clear qualifications (Zgaga, 2006, p 03). Following this initiative, Algeria chose to align its higher education system with the Bologna guidelines and in 2004, the countries concerned with the expansion were invited to take part in conferences and seminars (Huisman et al., 2012).

Higher education in Algeria was strongly influenced by the bologna process which was launched in 1999, a significant external scheme that aims at fostering international collaboration by allowing students to move between countries without worrying about their qualifications being unrecognized internationally, and to improve the quality and relevance of teaching and learning experiences (The European Commission, 2022). Gradually, the Bologna Process evolved from a simple government initiative to an intricate system with various levels and participants bound by the principles of mutual cooperation (Witte, 2006). The complexity in its design and interactions, made the Bologna hold strong implications of multi-level, multi actor, and multi issue governance (Vukasovic et al., 2018).

The international dimensions especially the one of Europe have had a significant impact on the higher education system in Algeria. An obvious example is the adoption of the three cycles model known as the BMD system (Bachelor-Masters-Doctorate) from European educational structures, which was highly encouraged by the Bologna Process (Huisman et al., 2012). Joint study schemes such as the Erasmus Programme launched in 1987, which Algeria became part of in 2014 and the Catania declaration enhanced students' opportunities for studying abroad (Europe) by covering the financial expenses of their studies. These programmes improved

student mobility, quality assurance and regional cooperation by bringing Algeria closer to European academic standards (Huisman et al., 2012).

Policies promoting mobility in Europe were usually driven by goals related to education and culture through the mobilisation of organizations like the British Council which worked hard to promote international cultural understanding without any political agendas through joint projects (Fisher, 2009). One of the biggest initiatives that fostered collaboration between the Algerian Government and the UK through the British council was the programme for postgraduate students to study abroad, which played an important role in (British Council, 2014). The scheme focused on providing the students with the necessary international academic expertise and quality training necessary to make a positive impact on their home country's educational system once they finished the programme and build long term capacity in the long run (Rose, 2015).

The adoption of the BMD system brought Maghreb countries (Morocco, Algeria, and Tunisia) closer despite the fact that they each implemented the BMD system on their own terms as the three joined their first official seminar concerning the theme on November 18-19-2004 in Marseille flagging the beginning of a joint effort to reflect on higher education reforms in the Maghreb inspired by the Bologna Process (Eta and Mngo, 2021). Two years later, education ministers representing 12 Mediterranean countries, including Algeria, met in Italy to support the Catania Declaration (2006) marking an important step towards the harmonization of these countries' education systems with the Bologna process, stressing the expansion of the framework beyond European borders, and highlighting the common aim of creating similar and compatible higher education systems to promote student mobility, assuring quality and recognizing qualifications throughout the region (Zgaga, 2006). The regional discussions grew to include conversations across the Mediterranean as an effort to actually expand the European Higher Education Area to incorporate Maghreb countries and create a shared higher education and research space bringing Europe and the Mediterranean together (World Education News and Reviews, 2006). The same year, the Bilateral Ministerial Committee (the UK-Algeria Joint Committee on Bilateral Relations) was established to provide an appropriate framework for discussing political, economic, educational, cultural relations and international issues of common interest (The Embassy of Algeria, 2020).

In Algeria, the adoption of the BMD structure inspired by the Bologna Process was heavily influenced by the French efforts in promoting the reforms in its former colonies where French

remain widely spoken (Eta and Mngo, 2020). This involvement created some sensitivities among certain nationalists and politicians in the country who still held a grudge against France's colonial past in Algeria and provoked apprehensions about a potential of neo-colonialism and the spread of global education since the Algerian higher education system became similar to that of Europe (Boufeldja, 2013).

The Bologna process principles were further promoted through the implementation of the Trans-European Mobility Programme for University Studies (TEMPUS) in Northern African and Maghreb countries (Benstaali, 2019). As expected, this EU funded initiative attained important achievements such as the improvement of the programmes quality and boosting international collaboration despite the challenges that included mainly the bureaucratic obstacles Benstaali (2013).

These reforms were endorsed worldwide by international organizations like the European Commission, UNESCO, the World Bank and the OECD, which made sure the Bologna process gains funding and visibility in international meetings (Eta and Mngo, 2020; Huisman et al., 2012).

Elken and Vukasovic (2014) note that the reciprocal discussions occurring at international levels often lead Transnational groups to work together more often and more deeply than national groups did with each other or with international organizations fostering an informal exchange between these global actors that extends beyond the Bologna process limits. Adopting the Bologna process standards and attending its international meetings meant that there was an exposure to international influences yet like anything new there is always a fear of postcolonial ghosts and becoming too dependent on foreign ideologies that can dilute the Algerian identity (Boufeldja, 2013; Lahmar, 2024).

2.6 Algeria and Scotland: Two Cases for Path Dependency

To gain deeper understanding to why higher education policies in Scotland and Algeria diverged significantly despite their exposure to similar global pressures to reform their higher education systems, the concept of path dependency offers a fuller grasp of this phenomenon.

Scotland before the devolution enjoyed an administrative independence and was well known of its distinctive universities (Torrance, 2024). Ever since the devolution, Scotland adopted a policymaking policy style based on mutual cooperation and constant discussions and reviews

that go back and forth with its policy community (Cairney, 2012). Scotland's consultative approach involved various groups ranging from university leaders, to professional organizations and the civil society leading to a gradual shift in policy rather than abrupt or extreme reforms (Keating, 2010).

The Scottish Executive (which became the Scottish Government in 2007) and the Scottish Parliament equally opened up for citizens and community groups to take part in the policymaking resulting in growing participation especially from certain groups as more people believed that the Scottish Executive performed a better job in listening and responding to their needs compared to the UK Government (Mahendran and Cook, 2007). While others have voiced some concerns that the establishment of a Scottish Parliament would threaten universities' reputation (Times Higher Education, 1999a)

Eventually, higher education was positively impacted by the new governance arrangement as universities gained more prominence and better hearing in national policy discussions, acquired more power to influence the policy making as the higher education leaders and representatives were had essential seats at the policy debates' table but exposed universities to more governmental scrutiny (Raffe, 2015).

In Algeria, the legacy of the colonial rule, the centralized system of governance under the authority of the ministry of higher education and Scientific research (Metatla, 2016) and a dependence on foreign technical help created a policymaking culture characterised by government-led reforms, weak institutional autonomy and limited engagement from stakeholders (Zerig 2021; Maqoura and Bouriche, 2020).

The persistence presence of these features despite the attempts to reform often indicates that new policies would add to the existing systems and laws instead of replacing them (McDermott 2018). These long-standing established frameworks that become embedded in the policy system can undermine the full adoption of new reforms and even at the micro level, individuals also tend to hold to their belief systems and mindsets despite the existence of evidence that refute these perspectives or offer better alternatives (Samadi et al. 2024).

Algeria and Scotland's histories, political culture and governance structures affect how they respond to policy advice as changes in institutions often follow a set path based on their past and each society has grown in its own way influenced by its history. This in turn affects how and if changes can happen (Samadi et al., 2024).

2.7 Conclusion

This chapter shed lights on important concepts such as the South and the North to have a fuller picture of Algeria and Scotland's divergent views and governance structures. Algeria's colonial history and postcolonial heritage is compared to Scotland's experience with the devolution. The chapter also discussed the political landscapes and economic performances of the two countries between 1999 and 2020. Scotland is then positioned within the UK wider policymaking context which prompted an examination of the issue of multilevel governance in Scotland. The analysis concludes with an exploration of how path dependency can provide deeper understanding of the effects of past cultural, and historical trajectories on the present and future of higher education policy in Algeria and Scotland.

Chapter 3

Higher Education in Algeria and Scotland: Contexts, Developments and Key Policy Areas

3.1 Introduction

This chapter analyses HE systems in terms of the key policies guiding their development in Algeria and Scotland. The first section of the chapter highlights the distinctive features of Algerian higher education before exploring the major policy developments in the country. Following this, the policy environment before 1999 is briefly discussed to set the context for the following detailed discussion of policy developments. The post 1999 policies include the shift towards the Bachelor-Masters-Doctorate (BMD) system at the start of 2004, and the government's readiness to answer the sector's calls for a better-quality assurance system. The last and probably most important policy development in HE in Algeria is the PhD Scheme initiative through which Algeria sought to demonstrate its openness to the world. The second section of the chapter discusses the Scottish higher education landscape. Here, the Scottish Government's abolition of higher education tuition fees, a marked deviation of the devolved Scotland from the rest of the UK, constitutes the first policy area that will be explored in this thesis. The chapter examines other key policy developments such as the quality assurance and widening access to higher education to more societal groups. The last area chosen for the study is the controversy around the governance arrangements in Scottish Universities and the subsequent drafting of the Higher Education Governance (Scotland) Act 2016 (Scottish Parliament, 2016).

3.2 Algerian Higher Education: An Overview

The Algerian Educational system before the French colonisation was firmly anchored in traditional Islamic principles and values communicated to the people through primitive religious schools known as zaouïas and madrasas. This configuration was drastically shattered once the French set foot on the Algerian ground following the armed confrontation which led to the annihilation of many scholars and educators, the demolition of libraries, and the shutdown or reuse of the religious and educational institutions such as mosques and Zawiyas (Djebbar, 2007).

During the colonial rule, Algeria witnessed the establishment of its first formal university with the passage of the Law of 30 December 1909 which set up the University of Algiers. The creation of this institution was part of a broader strategic plan and colonial agenda to assimilate the Algerian society into French culture instead of benefiting the Algerian society (Belhocine, 2022).

The period following Algeria's independence in 1962 until 1971 which marked the initial phase of higher education evolution and expansion, witnessed the inception of the Ministry of Higher Education and Scientific Research to supervise and regulate the sector (Meziane and Mahi, 2010). Nevertheless, the French colonial skeletons kept looming over manifesting in the selection, curricula, structure, and staff, which was heavily influenced by the French model (Chachoua and Schoelen, 2019).

According to Bouleries (2013), the 1971 higher education reform prioritized the democratization of access to provide opportunities for students from all regions and social classes to enrol at the university through the provision of free education, the nationalization (Algerianization) of the teaching staff and academic curricula content by replacing- foreign instructors by Algerian ones. Ironically, the reform's design was the outcome of European, Eastern, as well as American educational advisory services (Guerid, 2007 in Chachoua and Schoelen, 2019). These efforts fulfilled its intended objectives, and by the mid-1980s, Algerian faculty members replaced the foreigners especially in fields as medicine, in a significant move towards reclaiming national stewardship over education, reinforcing the use of Arabic in higher education (started with Islamic studies and Arabic language programs, and later extended to fields such as journalism, philosophy, and history) which served cultural and political agendas (Le Roux, 2017; Lahmar, 2024). Despite the fact that the late 1990s marked the full adoption of Arabic as the principal language of instruction, scientific disciplines continued to be taught in French creating challenges for students who completed their previous education in Arabic before colliding with an abrupt shift to French in higher education (Lahmar, 2024).

The focus of the Algerian government in the next period (1984-1999) was oriented towards the enhancement of quality and efficiency of higher education system through another substantial reform that came with the No. 84-209 in 1984, which reorganized higher education into three separate stages: a foundational cycle for general education, a second for specialised training, and a third for advanced and doctoral-level studies. The new design aimed at promoting the introduction of progressive specialization and aligning education with the employment

market's needs. Despite the achievements of the sector during this period which manifested in the expansion of institutions and the significant rise in student enrolment numbers, the progress was still hindered by poorly equipped facilities and scholarly significance (Belhocine, 2022).

The 1990s were scarred by the tragic and bloody events marking the civil conflict and so was the higher education system when academic staff became targeted by armed Islamist insurgents because they were perceived as allies of the regime and intelligence services kidnapped those who were allegedly sympathizing with the FIS party (Colonna, 2004; Ghanem, 2022). With the aggravation of violence, many academics were forced to flee the country to safer destinations like Europe and the United States, leading to a massive brain drain and leaving higher education destabilised until the turn of the millennium when President Abdelaziz Bouteflika's election broke a decade of bloodshed and set in motion a period of recovery (Bouherar and Salem, 2025). These circumstances prevented an overhaul destined towards integrating more autonomy in universities that was meant to be implemented in 1998/1999 (Chachoua and Schoelen, 2019).

Since its outset, the Algerian higher education system runs under the direct authority of a government minister appointed by the President of the Republic to formulate and implement higher education national policy whereas universities receive their funding primarily from the government through fixed government budget allocation, they have the freedom and capacity to bolster their funding resources from both public and private sources (Benchikh, 2018).

The centralised approach through which the Algerian government chose to govern the higher education system has serious implications on the management process triggering inefficiencies, delays in decision making, financial losses, a disconnect between policy and on ground realities which in their turn had a negative impact on the quality of education (Ghouati, 2014; Rose, 2015; Souleh, 2016; Bouchikhi and Barka, 2017).

It has been observed that in developing countries, like Algeria the HE sector is recognized as a key force for modernization and development (Buonti, 2011). Therefore, the expectations towards the Algerian university system have attracted considerable attention. For Bouchikhi and Barka (2017) universities are, mainly, expected to create knowledge; improve equity among the population; and respond to students' needs. Consequently, this has caused an increase in the demand for access, accompanied by pressure exercised by students who expect quality education. According to Buckner (2011), MENA (the Middle East and Northern Africa) countries can be divided into two types of higher education models: public-sponsored mobility

and private-based systems. Algeria falls under the first category meaning that the higher education sector is predominantly public, and government funded. This means that it is the central government which is accountable for reconstructing the system to meet students demands as well as those of the market. Nevertheless, the Algerian government has been struggling with fewer resources to allocate to the sector (Bouchikhi and Barka, 2017).

Furthermore, the demand for professionalization and the extension of the purposes of higher education to employability and integration of students into the business world are at the heart of a global process of transformations aimed at bringing education and economy closer together (Benziane, 2004). In the European Union, the Bologna process is one of the instruments of construction of the ‘knowledge economy’. The Bologna declaration sought to create a European Higher Education Area and set a number of interconnected goals, such as making higher education in Europe more appealing, encouraging the employability and mobility of European citizens, and improving the comparability and compatibility of higher education systems (The Bologna declaration, 1999). Six action lines were suggested: Establishing a credit system as a proper means of promoting mobility, promoting staff and student mobility, promoting European cooperation in quality assurance, promoting the necessary European dimensions in higher education, Adopting a system of easily readable and comparable degrees (including the implementation of the Diploma Supplement), Adopting a system essentially based on two main cycles: undergraduate and graduate (The Bologna declaration, 1999; Farshid et al., 2012)

Algeria struggled with the question of the employment of young graduates, because of a decoupling of higher education and employment. Thus, the objectives of professionalization of offers of training and improvement of employability and integration of graduate students have become a major challenge for the Maghreb higher education systems in general and Algeria in particular (Ghouati, 2015).

3.2.1 The BMD System

The second reform effort was that of the three-cycle degree framework for higher education which came to be known as the “LMD System” (License/Bachelor/Master- Doctorate) from September 2004 onwards (Buckner, 2011). It replaced the classical (old) system, i.e., four years bachelor, two years magister - four years doctorate (Sarnou et al., 2012) and was similar to what existed already in the US and some European countries or was in the making in the latter,

through the Bologna Process (Berrouche and Berkane, 2007). As part of both reforms “massification” was an important higher education defining feature that was in part motivated by the demographic reality of a large youth population (Noui, 2020). However, some have observed that massification policies in Algeria have led to favouring quantity over quality (Bouchikhi and Barka, 2017). In other words, the quality of higher education was said to have decreased. Concerns about quality on the one hand and the higher education sector’s weak role in Algeria’s economic development on the other hand (Talbi, 2015) have been raised since this second reform. The next section outlines the key policies the Algerian government opted for between 1999 and 2020.

The need for change emerged from several dysfunctions that were thought to keep the Algerian university from reaching its fullest potentials. Therefore, and for the Algerian government to accomplish its agenda, the Bachelor-Masters-Doctorate system was introduced. The introduction of such reform led to considerable interest within scholarly circles and the Bachelor-Masters-Doctorate system became the focus of most if not all recent (at the time) publication on Algerian higher education (Meziane and Mahi, 2010; Benouar, 2013; Bouzid, Berrouche and Berkane, 2013; Ghouati, 2015; Sarnou et al, 2012; Ghouati, 2015; Badran, Baydoun and Hillman, 2019).

The BMD reform, which was inspired by the principles of the Bologna process, has come to modernise universities to equip them with the ability to deal with the challenges of globalization and internationalisation of higher education (Noui, 2020). Also, the modernisation efforts sought to offer better training in order to satisfy the labour market requirements. The recurrent problem has always been that of the lack of employability of graduates. Another aim was to ensure the best governance possible to relieve universities from overwhelming bureaucracies (European Commission Education, Audiovisual and Culture Executive Agency, 2012; The Government of Algeria, 2019; Noui, 2020). In order to achieve the latter objective, the BMD reform, enshrined in Law no. 99-05 from April 4, 1999 (Government of Algeria, 1999a), relaxed the status of the university by conferring on it the status of public institution of scientific, cultural and professional character.

The BMD was launched in 2004 through an executive decree that regulates the organization and the functioning of the higher education institutions (Berrouche and Berkane, 2007). The reform meant that the degree system was changed from a ‘licence’, modelled on the French system, into a ‘Bachelor’ system, modelled on the Bologna Process and thereby on the system

prevalent in anglophone countries. This meant that the new Algerian equivalent of a Bachelor programme was reduced, in 2004, in length from 4 to 3 years. The 'Magistre' degree was replaced, in 2007, by the postgraduate Masters degree. The doctorate system remained the same. Changes at the curricula level also took place to adapt to the demands of the globalization wave (Rabah and Raouti, 2023). The overall objective was to synchronize Algerian higher education with European practice to enhance student and faculty exchanges and, to some extent, share research (Buckner, 2011; Rezig, 2011; Waterbury, 2019).

The implementation of the reform has evolved through a process of four phases. Between 2000 and 2004, the reform was prepared; between 2004 and 2008 the reform started; between 2008 and 2013 reform efforts were consolidated, and from 2013 onwards the reform was deepened and improved (MESRS, 2018). There were also a series of evaluative events (these will be discussed in the thematic chapters), during which four main axes were examined. First, the sector's strategic plan and reform design as determined by the ministerial departments. Second, the state of reform implementation in higher education institutions and its evaluation, as determined by the institutions' reports, which were developed with the support of their scientific bodies, consolidated in regional conferences, and enhanced by teacher interviews. Third, the status of the partnership with the environment issue, as determined by the socioeconomic sector representatives. Fourth, the contribution of social partners, teachers, and students to the HE sectors (The Algerian Ministry of Higher Education and Scientific Research, 2018).

The BMD system was implemented in response to the ever-increasing pressures of globalisation, which compelled Algeria to reform its higher educational system to improve the quality of university education. The adoption of a system of clearly readable and comparable degrees, as well as that of a credit system to promote mobility for students, academics, and administrative staff, are the key objectives behind the implementation of the BMD system (Mellouk, 2013). Further, The BMD'S structure was supposed to feature strict standards and frequent student evaluations and institutions would have some flexibility in determining the form and the content of their curriculum (Badran, Baydoun and Hillman, 2019).

The reliability, efficiency, and relevance of the procedures envisioned by the reform in order to see how far the BMD has contributed to ending the contradictions between what the reform set as goals in theory and what it has actually achieved in practice (Berrouche and Berkane, 2007; Zorgan, 2012). Thus, following the debates over whether the BMD was effective, a

considerable amount of research called for a quality assurance scheme. According to Bouchikhi and Barka (2017), while imitating European policies for higher education, policy makers in Algeria have focused on form and ignored substance. This resulted in a set of deficits, one of which was around reconciling demands to democratise access to higher education with demands for high-quality education (European Commission. Education, Audiovisual and Culture Executive Agency, 2012)

3.2.2 Quality Assurance

In an investigation of the duality of the massification policy and higher education quality in order to determine the type of correlative relation the two have, Noui (2020) asserts that university massification policies both before and after 1999 have led to favouring quantity over quality resulting in graduates with low employability. The quality of higher education has become a growing concern for a variety of stakeholders interested in the outcomes of higher education programmes, including public officials, political leaders, students, and business leaders (Guessoum, 2019). In this context, these various stakeholders are calling on Algerian higher education to respond to these quality and relevance requirements, to adapt and fulfil the country's new socioeconomic needs as well as international norms and standards of higher education quality (Bouzid, Berrouche and Berkane, 2013; the Government of Algeria, 2022). The Ministry of Higher Education and Scientific Research (MESRS) has already concluded that the adoption of Quality Assurance in the Algerian Higher Education sector is highly required and to some extent overdue. A national committee was formed to design a national quality assurance framework that could be adapted by the country's universities and "Grandes Ecoles" (Guessoum, 2019). While the framework was developed, less work was conducted around the establishment of actual quality assurance agencies. Algeria has taken a more of a gradual approach. Put differently, Algeria's strategy appeared to be relatively small scaled as internal reviews, conducted by the universities themselves, were favoured over opting for one central agency that monitors quality (Badran, Baydoun and Hillman, 2019).

Recognizing the need to reform their higher education system to align it with international standards, many Arab countries including Algeria have taken important initiatives supported by the European Union's Erasmus+ programme, to install Bologna-inspired structures and quality-assurance mechanisms (Zabalawi and Floden, 2019). To support and spread the culture of quality in the university environment and among all parties benefiting from higher education, in 2008 the Ministry of Higher Education organized an international conference on quality assurance. The conference came to clarify the new project and its objectives as well as

a study of the extent to which it can be embodied in the field. The law no 99-05 from April 4, 1999 (Government of Algeria, 1999) also established the national conference of universities and regional bodies for consultation, coordination and evaluation (Art 43 amended by Article 4 of Law 2000- 04 from 6 December 2000). As it has created a national committee for the evaluation of public institutions of a scientific, cultural and professional nature and other institutions of higher education (Article 43 b). In 2008, The National Evaluation Council (CNE) was created and a working group responsible for reflecting on the implementation of the project (quality assurance) was created, supported by certain international experts (Guessoum, 2019).

Further, the Ministry of Higher Education and Scientific Research under the executive decree of 21 January 2010 established a national council for the evaluation of scientific research and technological development (Guessoum, 2019). The board is responsible for the strategic evaluation and monitoring of assessment mechanisms for the national policy of scientific research and technological development (Guessoum, 2019). In addition to a National Commission for the Implementation of Quality Assurance in Higher Education (CIAQES), whose approach was deemed decentralized and more oriented towards internal evaluation within each university education (Benjelloun, 2019). The mission is to regularly assess, in accordance with the principles of objectivity, independence and transparency, all activities and actions of the higher education institutions, in terms of governance and research in relation to the objectives assigned to the higher education and training institution as part of public policy of higher education (Benjelloun, 2019). Its guidelines included a set of actions that should provide the sector with a quality assurance system. These consisted of the establishment of quality assurance units within each higher education institution, the training of quality assurance managers-QAR of the units, the setting of a national standard, and the creation of a quality assurance agency (Benjelloun, 2019).

The National Commission for the Implementation of Quality Assurance in Higher Education CIAQES began its work of structuring quality assurance units in each university and research organisation (CIAQES, 2017). These quality assurance units bring together the main actors of the university community and the parties involved and are headed by quality assurance managers whose role is to raise awareness and steer self-evaluations (The Government of Algeria, 2019). Training in quality management and university evaluation has been scheduled for quality assurance managers (The Government of Algeria, 2019). Seminars and conferences on quality assurance in higher education are periodically organised by quality assurance managers in many academic institutions. Technical workshops focus on the development of

the national guidelines by adopting a participatory approach with all the actors of the university community (The Government of Algeria, 2019). Previously, and after the organisation of an international QA symposium in Algiers in June 2008, work on raising awareness was carried out through the organisation of seminars and regional workshops to prepare the advent of QA units at all academic institutions. Preparation of curricula for the training of QA managers, as well as training experts (The Government of Algeria, 2019).

The National Committee for the implementation of quality assurance in higher education, with the help of heads of quality assurance units, has created the national directory, which includes the norms and standards related to quality assurance. It established the National Quality Assurance Authority, which was presented for the first time in 2014, then introduced a set of modifications to be submitted for the second time in 2016 (Badran, Baydoun and Hillman, 2019).

3.2.3 Higher Education and Economy

Universities have frequently been regarded as key institutions in the process of social change and development through the production of highly skilled labour and research output to meet perceived economic needs (Brennan, King and Lebeau, 2004). Therefore, it is necessary to establish a form of connection between the two worlds in order to better adapt the qualifications provided by education to the needs of the developing economy (The Government of Algeria, 2019).

Higher education and the economy are closely interrelated (Benziane, 2004; Ghouati, 2015; Bouchikhi and Barka, 2017). Despite the many reforms the sector had witnessed, the current system is still based on the 1971 model, which has not kept its pace with new developments in communication and information technologies. As a result, the skills of many who are products of this system are now obsolete, contributing to Algeria's crisis (Benziane, 2004). Mediterranean Arab countries have a higher average expenditure on education than their Gulf counterparts. Yet, both Gulf and Mediterranean Arab countries fall behind many emerging Asian countries (Nour, 2011). In Algeria, public spending on education has positively affects economic growth (Mekdad, Dahmani and Louaj, 2014; Sawli, Abderahmani and Elharouchi, 2019)

The General Directorate for Scientific Research and Technological Development, founded in September 2009, and created by the law 08-05 of February 23, 2008 (Government of Algeria, 2008), enshrines scientific research and technological development as national priorities. The

legislation which also defines the five-year scientific national research plan (2008-2012), was expected to move the national research system to more excellence for a sustainable development (Benouar, 2013). Reforms for the period stretching from 2014 to 2018 aimed at building linkages between university and industry, to motivate the innovation thinking, and encourage researchers to develop their results in research units within enterprises, (Souleh, 2016). In practice, most of the Algerian higher education institutions work separately from their surroundings and are unable to interact with society and industry (Saad, Guermat and Boutifour, 2020).

3.2.4 Internalisation of Higher Education (The PhD Scheme)

Algeria's international development strategy aims at increasing the number of national students and academic staff studying abroad, increasing the quota of foreign students and academic staff (Executive Decree No. 18-95 of 19 March 2018). To this end, the institution's lecturers will be obliged to improve the quality of teaching (The Government of Algeria, 2019). Other possible measures to encourage internationalisation are related to better international recognition of university programmes, close cooperation with other recognised institutions, and knowledge and research challenges. Algeria participates in international projects in the field of higher education, such as the international mobility of Erasmus+ Credits; Erasmus+ Capacity building in higher education; PRIMA Initiative; and the H2020 research project (The Government of Algeria, 2019). Nonetheless, one of the main problems that the sector seems unable to handle is brain drain. Although researchers have debated whether people who have never changed their citizenship are not a "loss" for their native nations (Ozden, 2006), the result of this movement is certainly damaging to the Arab region as a whole. Ozden (2006) maintains that the Arab region is gradually losing highly valuable human capital; potential graduates who are highly educated and who can lead and encourage creativity, innovation, inventions and knowledge creation in the region. Alkubaisi and Rasool (2020) deduced that Algeria is among the main Arab countries exporting a high percentage of emigrants to other countries. Badran, Baydoun and Hillman (2019) claim that it was estimated that Algeria had 22,000 researchers working in-house while 40,000 were abroad. The Arab Human Development Report (AHDR) of 2016 attributed brain drain to the exclusion of youth in Arab society because of the barriers of patronage, nepotism, and autocratic controls (De Bel-Air, 2016). In 2009, and as a counter reaction, the then minister of higher education announced that Algeria would limit the number of study abroad scholarships to exceptional baccalaureate exam

performers in an attempt to stop the brain drain. He further asserted that beginning in September of the following year, the government would double grant funds for Algerian university students and further improve the working conditions of researchers (Sawahel, 2009).

Algeria displays a strong commitment to student support (indirect, financial support in the form of accommodation, food, medical services and socio-educational services and facilities) (The Government of Algeria, 2019), making Algeria one of the last few standing countries in the world which offer such support for both local and foreign students (Chachoua and Shoelen, 2019)

the UK government represented by Hugh Robertson MP, British Foreign and Commonwealth Office Minister for North Africa and the Middle East and the Ministry of Higher Education and Scientific Research decided in January 2014 sign a five-year agreement to fund 500 PhD studentship for Algerian students at UK universities (UK Government, 2014b). This is a part of Algeria's plan to strengthen its universities' English language degree programmes and expand its international alliances into the Anglophone world. In 2014–15, the first cohort of 69 Algerian doctoral students were placed at UK universities with the assistance of the British Council (British Council, 2018).

3.3 Scottish Higher Education: An Overview

By the opening decades of the 17th century, Scotland had a well-founded university system leaving behind England and Ireland in respect of the number of institutions and their accessibility, as the country did not operate under formal any entry requirements until the late 19th century and villages and schools often delivered high quality education that made university entry quite possible (Bell, 2000). The Scottish education system, often compared to that of England, was heavily influenced by the effects of both anglicisation and globalisation (Bell, 2000).

The Scottish society and culture have been for so long distinctly defined by their education systems which represent one of three core institutions marking Scottish character in contrast to England (Humes and Bryce, 2018). This distinctiveness stemmed from the 1707 Union binding England and Scotland, a union built upon an agreement that safeguards Scotland's national identity embedded in its established church and legal system, which differ substantially from those in England, and its sophisticated education system which has been moulded by both religious and governmental efforts in the 16th and 17th centuries (Bell, 2000).

Another defining feature of the Scottish education system lies in its unwavering commitment to a system supported by public funds, with less support for private education compared to England. Historically, Scottish universities have been run under public control, with the principle of universal public elementary education reinforced since the 1870s (McPherson and Raab, 1988).

Over the course of history, Scottish universities received more governmental sponsorship than their counterparts in England, partially because of smaller endowments and a greater emphasis on teacher education, which may provide an explanation of the Scottish universities' tendency to identify more as public institutions (Bell, 2000). These funding arrangements exposed Scottish universities to a progressively greater central government control, especially in the aftermath of World War II (Simpson, 1983).

In terms of reforms, Scottish higher education underwent two radical reforms. By the halfway mark of the 20th century, Scotland had four historic universities (St Andrews, Glasgow, Aberdeen, and Edinburgh) founded in the 15th and 16th centuries, and about a dozen colleges responsible for the provision of advanced technical education, teacher and nurse training, and special programs in music and arts. In the wake of the UK-wide Robbins Report in 1963, which advocated the expansion of higher education, several of these colleges were upgraded or restructured: Strathclyde University was founded in Glasgow, Heriot-Watt University in Edinburgh, one of St Andrews' colleges became the University of Dundee, and a completely new university was founded in Stirling, while other colleges continued on delivering higher education programs (Paterson, 2021a). The 1980s marked the end of this foundational stage of institutional reforms, yet the ever increasing demand for higher education brought about further expansion to the non-university sector (Burnhill, Garner and McPherson, 1988). Although the public sector education in colleges witnessed to a certain degree positive development, the Scottish higher education system still struggled with keeping up with the improved outcome at school levels and expanding access (McPherson, 1990).

The second reform phase began in the early 1990s through the process of merging the remaining colleges with existing universities or granting them (colleges) university status. The period was also marked by a significant surge in sub-degree level courses, supplied by local technical colleges that had been created from the 1950s onward. The mid-1990s saw Scottish higher education blossom into four different categories: The ancient universities, the institutions founded in the 1960s, the former colleges turned universities in the 1990s, and the

technical colleges offering qualifications below degree level (Paterson, 2021b). Despite these structural reforms, a considerable fraction of non-degree higher education continued to be delivered by local technical colleges, most of which were established between the 1950s and 1970s (Paterson, 2003).

From the outset of the 20th century, a tension between local collaboration and centralised control shaped modern Scottish education (Grek and Ozga, 2010). When contrasted to the English model, Scottish local authorities play a defining role when acting in harmony as part of a shared mission (McPherson and Raab, 1988). Other academics stressed that the central government has always been the dominant force running education policy in Scotland due to the country's small size, pronounced cultural emphasis on education, and the smoothness with which key stakeholders can be brought together to reach consensus (Grek and Ozga, 2010).

Many scholars claim that education is a social policy area that represents a manifestation of Scottish 'distinctiveness' due to its long-standing Scottish autonomy in this matter (Mooney and Poole, 2004; Viebrock, 2009). Cairney et al. (2016) explain that the 'Scottish approach' refers to Scotland's unique style of making and implementing policy. This uniqueness sparked an interest in Scottish policy making style in general and higher education policy making in particular (Cairney, 2013a; Cairney, 2013b). A large and growing body of literature has investigated higher education policy in post-devolution UK. The policy making process in Scotland since devolution has been described as consensual as it has been developed through a series of reviews within the policy community (Cairney, 2020). The procedure is more consultative and seeks to involve more strongly all relevant stakeholders, if compared to policy making in England. This has also led to more gradual policy evolution rather than radical change (Keating, 2010).

The policy agenda has often been set by England, given its strongly politicised approach and the implications for Scotland of initiatives such as top-up fees. The Scottish policy community has been strong enough to come up with a series of distinct solutions to similar problems as well as taking account of different circumstances (Keating, 2010). There is a large volume of published studies dedicated to the careful examination of whether the devolved countries are converging or diverging from the Westminster model of governance (Gallacher and Raffae, 2012; Mooney and Poole, 2004; Viebrock, 2009; Arnott and Menter, 2007; Keating, 2010; Keating, 2005). These studies concluded that there are areas of convergence between Scotland and England as well as those of divergence.

Riddell, Blackburn and Minty (2016) claim that Scottish higher education has become increasingly divergent, particularly in relation to tuition fees and student support. A view endorsed by Gallacher and Raffe (2012) who attribute this to five factors: the redistribution of formal powers associated with devolution; differences in values, ideologies and policy discourses across the four territories; the different composition, interests and policy styles of their policy communities; the different ‘situational logics’ of policy making and the mutual independence of policy decisions in the different territories. The authors further argue that each of the five factors claimed to promote divergence can be associated with corresponding pressures for convergence. In Scotland policy and delivery systems are small enough to allow short lines of communication and a dialogue among policy makers, administrators and service providers (Keating, 2010). This style of policy making is illustrated by reforms in higher education, which have taken strikingly divergent paths in England and Scotland. Scottish policy has been less market-oriented than England’s and concerned with incremental rather than radical change in the higher education sector (Universities UK, 2017).

3.3.1 Tuition Fees

Between 1998 and 2007, Scotland's tuition fee policy underwent significant change, much of it influenced by UK policy developments that had previously resulted from the National Committee of Inquiry into Higher Education's work. The UK Government commissioned this work in 1996, under the direction of Sir Ron Dearing, and the findings were published in July 1997. According to the Dearing Report, in order to meet future demands related to increases in student enrolment and the need for infrastructure investment, the sector would require a substantial increase in funding over the next 20 years. The Dearing Committee's recommendation that students contribute financially to the expense of their higher education sparked intense public debate at the time. Several strategies were taken into consideration, such as paying yearly tuition or, in an alternative, making a one-time graduate payment (SPICe, 2019a).

Following the devolution, funding and support arrangements in higher education across the UK were substantially reformed. From 2000-01, and following the report of Andrew Cubie, a more generous approach to student support, was adopted: tuition fees for eligible full-time Scottish and EU students were abolished in Scotland. Students from the rest of the UK students had to

pay tuition fees for the first three years of their degree, with the final year paid by the Scottish Executive (SPICe, 2019a; Universities UK, 2017).

With the introduction of variable tuition fees in England from 2006-07, the previous Scottish Executive took the decision to increase fees in Scotland to guard against “fee refugees” from England and other parts of the UK potentially displacing Scotland domiciled students (SPICe, 2011). The Student Fees (Specification) (Scotland) Order 2006/401 (the 2006 Order), which was made under the Further and Higher Education (Scotland) Act 2005, sets out fee level and allows Ministers to increase fees specified in the Order without the need for further legislation, as long as fee levels rises are not greater than inflation (Scottish Government, 2006). The fee levels specified in the Order have been updated since 2006, although fee levels have not changed in the last two years (SPICe, 2011).

As an alternative to tuition fees, a system of graduate endowments was introduced by the Scottish Government (Graduate Endowment and Student Support) (Scotland Act 2001) (Scottish Government, 2001). The level was initially set at £2,000 and was to be repaid in the same way as income-contingent student loans. However, various groups including lone parents, mature/independent students, disabled students, and students studying for HNC and HNDs in further education institutions were exempt from the Graduate Endowment.

In June 2007, plans to abolish the endowment were announced (BBC News, 2007). The new Scottish Government, under the Scottish National Party, stated that the endowment had failed to deliver the aims of removing barriers and widening access and that the income raised from it had been lower than anticipated. It found that the endowment had burdened many graduates and families with additional debt and had acted as a disincentive to accessing higher education (Denholm, 2013). The Graduate Endowment Abolition (Scotland) Act 2008 (UK Government, 2008) meant that no current or future students would pay the endowment, and neither would those who graduated on, or after, 1 April 2007 (SPICe, 2011). In 2014, this statement was carved at Edinburgh's Heriot-Watt University as a perpetual promise made by the ten first Minister Alex Salmond (The Herald, 2014).

One of the most frequently discussed topics with regards to the supposed Scottish distinctiveness is the example of university tuition fees (Viebrock, 2009; De Wit, Deca and Hunter, 2015; Masetti, 2019). This is one of the areas where Scotland decided to set its own rules when the Scottish Executive used the freedom created by devolution to clearly diverge

from Westminster policy and abolish the tuition fees. This was then followed by the abolition of the graduate endowment fee in 2008 (SPICe, 2011).

During the referendum campaign, the Scottish government argued that free tuition for Scottish and EU students symbolised Scotland's preference for universal services and was intrinsically fairer than the 'marketized' systems operating in the rest of the UK invoking principles of both social justice and pragmatism (Riddell, Blackburn and Minty, 2016).

3.3.2 Quality Assurance

Scottish and English universities face many of the same challenges as they have had to absorb a huge increase in student numbers while meeting their governments' expectations to play a significant role in driving economic development and to serve the needs of business at the sub-state or regional level (Paterson, 2001). Moreover, universities are also required to provide mass education, conduct world-class research in the face of global competition, and retain their academic autonomy under pressure from both government and commercial sponsors (Salmi and Altbach, 2020).

Higher education policies related to quality assurance are instigated to ensure the provision of high-quality education and reinforce university accountability and transparency in using public funding and meeting the needs of the diverse stakeholders. Every higher education institution is dedicated to a policy of self-evaluation of all its programs, procedures, services and administrative mechanisms on a regular basis, which encompasses a quality self-assessment (Gamage et al., 2020). In the UK, the QAA has developed a quality code for higher education as a reference point to enable universities and colleges to understand what is expected from them, protect public and student interests, and championing UK higher education's world-leading reputation for quality (Gamage et al., 2020). In Scotland, HEIs are autonomous and self-governing institutions. Each is responsible for the quality of its own programmes and the institutions with degree awarding powers are also held accountable for the academic standards of the awards they offer. Whereas evaluation at national level in HEIs is the responsibility of the Scottish Funding Council (SFC) (The Further and Higher Education (Scotland) Act 2005).

The QAA explains that the threshold academic standards represent the minimum level of achievement attained by students to be qualified for the award or qualification. Academic standards on the other hand are set by the degree-awarding bodies and may surpass threshold academic standards and are based on the student's performance to earn a specific classification of a qualification. Academic quality revolves around the teaching services provided by HEIs

to allow students to reach their fullest capacities and obtain their rewards and stretches over learning, teaching and assessment. Quality assurance is the broad field that keeps the academic standards and quality of higher education provision under scrutiny to make sure they deliver properly (QAA, 2017).

In 2003, a major review of arrangements for quality assurance in learning and teaching in Scotland was undertaken. The SFC, along with other stakeholders such as QAA Scotland (which manages key elements of the framework), Universities Scotland, NUS and SPARQS developed Scotland's distinct enhancement-led approach to quality assurance known as "Enhancement Framework" (QEF). This framework has five parts aimed at making continuous improvements to the quality of learning and teaching (SPICe, 2010a). The national programme of Enhancement Themes provided by the Quality Enhancement Framework is also central. This aims at developing and sharing good practice in learning and teaching in higher education. The themes provide a rich set of reference points for institutions to draw on in developing their own policies and practice (Knox and Wyper, 2008).

3.3.3 Widening Access

Widening access is one of the major policy objectives in Scottish higher education policy Gallacher (2006) and investigating the efficiency of the government's widening access initiatives is a continuing concern within many academic circles (Murphy and Morgan-Klein, 2001; Gallacher, 2006; Riddell, 2016; Riddell, Blackburn and Minty, 2016; Blackburn et al, 2016). Gallacher (2006) contends that while there is evidence that high levels of participation have been achieved in Scotland, and some evidence of reduction in inequalities in participation rates among young people entering higher education, there is also evidence of persisting inequalities, and of patterns of differentiation and stratification despite the policies designed to widen access. Mooney and Poole (2004) have similar criticism as they maintain that educational inequalities still exist in Scotland. For instance, they find that only 17 per cent of young people taking full-time first-degree courses at Scottish HEIs are from 'low participation neighbourhoods' while the proportion of accepted applicants from socio-economic groups 3, 4, and 5 to UK HEIs has remained constant (at around 36 per cent) since 1997. The maintenance grant issue has also been largely sidestepped with students complaining in greater numbers about the increasing levels of debts they are incurring. There is also the complicating factor of the traditional four-year honours degree structure that has a larger financial impact on students in Scotland with potentially negative consequences for Scottish Higher education in general (Mooney and Poole, 2004). Combined, these factors have arguably worked as a

disincentive to some people from poorer working-class backgrounds from entering further and higher education.

Blackburn et al. (2016) come to the verdict that Scottish universities' efforts to widen access for students from poorer backgrounds have achieved only partial success. It is not evident from the data that divergence in tuition fee policy has contributed to allowing more students from less affluent backgrounds to attend university if compared to England. Further, the supply of university places in Scotland has not kept pace with rising demand and increased competition for university places, particularly in the most selective universities, has had a disproportionately negative effect on students from the most deprived backgrounds (Blackburn et al., 2016).

The term widening access does not only encompass plans to support students from low socio-economic backgrounds but also covers the variety of initiatives the Scottish government takes to provide equal access opportunities to other groups, like the disabled. In this context, Tinklin and Hall (1999) argue that disabled students face obstacles to their participation in five areas: the physical environment, access to Information, entrance to higher education, assumptions of 'normality' and levels of awareness.

Subject choice is yet another stronger mediator of social inequalities in HE entry and access to prestigious universities in Scotland as it is more differentiated (both in terms of number and type of subjects taken) and allocation of places in HE is less standardised and dependent upon the subjects studied at school (Iannelli, Smyth and Klein, 2016).

A vigorous approach to the 'widening participation' agenda was adopted, with a wide range of initiatives to encourage participation through improved student funding, location of courses and institutions, and attempting to develop links between higher education and further education courses (Universities UK, 2017). In terms of how best to conceptualise and categorise initiatives that have been designed with the direct purpose of widening participation to make them more amenable to further analysis, a report from Universities Scotland on access in Scottish HEIs is useful. The research was commissioned as a literature review of the evidence behind different widening access initiatives from the Centre for Research in Education Inclusion and Diversity (CREID), University of Edinburgh, which was led by Professor Sheila Riddell (Universities Scotland, 2014; Riddell et al., 2013).

Institutional developments are described in terms of how they address three issues affecting access and retention: academic (raising entry qualifications); cultural (raising awareness); and

internal (changing institutional structures). Three examples from Scotland show quite clearly ways in which these issues are being tackled with respect to young people. Summer schools at universities for school pupils from geographical areas with histories of educational disadvantage are viewed as a means of addressing the academic issue of raising students' qualifications prior to entry. Compacts between schools and universities within which structured arrangements for interchanges were planned for pupils from their early years in secondary education are seen as strategies to create the perception that HE is a possible route for individuals for whom this had either not seemed feasible or had not been considered (Osborn, 2003).

The majority of students in Scottish higher education establishments are women. According to data from the Higher Education Statistics Agency (HESA), women continued to make up the majority of students in UK higher education (56.7%), while men made up 43.3% of the student body in the 2018–2019 academic year. Scotland has the highest percentage of female students among the four UK countries, at 58.3% (University of St. Andrews, 2019). Thus, expansion by means of increased participation must come from other groups, such as disabled people, and those in deprived and rural areas. Expansion of this sort, alongside issues such as students who work as well as study, the drive for greater flexibility in entry and exit points and other societal movements, carry implications for the curriculum in terms of teaching and learning. The sector has been very successful in recruiting students from overseas and must continue to be, especially given the constraints resulting from recent financial crises and economic recession (SPICe, 2010b). It is against this demographic and financial backdrop that the Scottish Government produced its discussion paper “Building a Smarter Future: Towards a Sustainable Scottish Solution for the Future of Higher Education” in 2010 (Scottish Government, 2010a; SPICe, 2010b). This was followed a year later by a pre-legislative paper: Putting Learners at the Centre - Delivering our Ambitions for Post-16 Education (The Scottish Government, 2011a). It anticipated a White Paper in the second half of 2012. The paper and its predecessor were explicit in rejecting the fee model adopted in England, arguing that it is 'socially divisive' (Scottish Government, 2010a, p. 1). Instead, they offered a distinctive Scottish solution: the retention of public funding at the maximum sustainable level whilst also seeking new sources of revenue and enhancing existing ones (Scottish Government, 2010a).

In Scotland, it was assumed that free tuition would automatically lead to a more inclusive university system. Apart from the Conservatives, all political parties in the run-up to the Scottish parliamentary elections in May 2016 endorsed this policy. There are clear upsides to

this policy, not least in ensuring that one type of debt is removed from a generation of graduates facing high house prices and a tight labour market. However, it is equally important to recognise that the abolition of student tuition fees in 2000 and of the graduate endowment in 2007 did not have a significant impact on university participation overall, or by students from less advantaged backgrounds (Riddell et al., 2015; Riddell, Blackburn and Minty, 2016).

There are also a number of downsides to policy in the funding of higher education in Scotland. The commitment to resource universities from public funding has meant that the Scottish Government continues to cap university places. There is a need for a more nuanced discussion of Scottish higher education funding, recognising both the upsides and downsides of current policy choices. If the free tuition policy is retained, it is important that it is accompanied by a stronger focus on access with targeted support such as reserved places for disadvantaged students. This issue is not addressed in the report of the Commission on Widening Access, although it recommends that the Scottish Government should commission research on how student finance impacts on the participation of disadvantaged learners in higher education and recognises that the issue of system capacity falls to the Scottish Government (Iannelli, 2011). Major Initiatives including: More Choices, More Chances (Scottish Government, 2006), Skills for Scotland (Scottish Government, 2007a); New Horizons Scottish Government (2008) 16+ Learning Choices (Scottish Government, 2017a).

The rise in higher education enrolment nationally, particularly in colleges, has resulted in an overrepresentation of students from poorer backgrounds, which has contributed to improvements in participation. This is because the number of university places available in Scotland has not kept up with the growing demand, and the more competition for spots at the most selective universities has disproportionately harmed students from the poorest backgrounds (Blackburn et al., 2016).

3.3.4 HE Governance Reforms

In Scotland, HEIs are independent organizations, but in return for substantial funding from the Scottish Government through the Scottish Funding Council, they are required to carry out predetermined priorities. As charitable organizations, HEIs are also subject to the governance guidelines outlined in the 1995 Charities and Trustee Investment (Scotland) Act. A governing body overseeing finances, governance, and strategic management is present at every university. The governance structures of various university types vary slightly (SPICe, 2021).

The Universities (Scotland) Acts 1858 to 1966 provide a statutory foundation for ancient university governance structures. Every institution has three main bodies: the Senate, which is led by the principal; the Court, which is in charge of finances and operations and is led by an elected rector; and the General Council, which is led by the Chancellor. The Royal Charter, which was created in the 1960s, lays out the rules for chartered universities. They typically also have a Senate led by the Principal and a Court headed by a senior lay member. Former "polytechnics" that converted to universities after the Further and Higher Education Act of 1992 was passed are referred to as "post-92s." The Senate is in charge of academic affairs, the Privy Council typically makes arrangements for governance, and the Court oversees general governance. The governance structures of small and specialized universities combine the provisions of the Companies Act and the 1992 Act, which mandate the holding of an annual general meeting and the maintenance of an updated list of directors.

In 2011, Michael Russell, the Education Secretary, announced that a panel would be set up to review higher education governance after concerns from academics and students over funding and salary costs of the highest members of university staff (Denholm, 2012). Although the idea behind the review was widely endorsed, the membership of the review panel managed to cause an immediate backlash after Michael Russell revealed that Professor Ferdinand von Prondzynski, the Principal of Robert Gordon University Aberdeen, would chair the panel. Robert Gordon was in dispute with campus unions and no longer recognised the university's branch of the UCU Scotland lecturers' union. UCU Scotland announced that it welcomed the review but maintained that it had serious concerns about the choice of the chair, as he was neither independent nor appropriate given his university's anti-union stance (University and College Union Scotland, 2011a). Claire Baker, Scottish Labour's education spokeswoman, said the review was "in trouble" only hours after it was announced by Russell in a statement on the Government's educational priorities to the Scottish Parliament. Baker argued that the UCU's concerns were legitimate and deserving of a response (The Scotsman, 2011).

The review panel comprised Ferdinand von Prondzynski, Terry Brotherstone, Iain Macwhirter, Robin Parker and Alan Simpson. The panel, in the acknowledgments in its final report, thanked other expert officials for supporting the panel's work and providing expert advice and facilities, in particular Neil MacLennan and Stephen O'Connor. The panel also acknowledged the support and assistance it received from a variety of sources, including all those who contributed to the debate by making submissions to it and who gave oral evidence. The panel argued that those contributions were invaluable during the deliberations (Scottish Government, 2012).

The role of the expert panel was to synthesise the views of various experts and identify and characterise the uncertainties in their analyses. A structured approach was needed in order to find a balance and consensus between the arguments of experts representing different disciplines. The remit of the panel was to examine and evaluate whether the institutional governance arrangements in Scottish HEIs supply democratic accountability and transparency when dealing with public funding (Scottish Government, 2015).

An expert panel is also important in forcing the expert to discuss the bases of their argumentation among each other and the decision maker. The expert panel produced a report (Scottish Government, 2012) in which the members summarised the discussions and decisions from the panel sessions and explained the bases for the decision, an essential part for the tractability and transparency of the decision process (Pulkksnen and Simola, 2000).

The report made more than 30 recommendations for improving governance in HEIs, with a focus on increasing transparency. The report also covered a range of themes including the institutional and legal framework of universities; academic freedom and institutional autonomy; the role of governance; appointment and remuneration of principals; remuneration of senior management; role, composition and appointment of governing bodies; chairing of governing bodies; membership of governing bodies; training of governing body members; role, composition and appointment of academic boards; whistleblowing; evidence base and the role of stakeholders and other issues (Scottish Government, 2012; SPICe, 2015). The measures taken to implement these recommendations include publication of a Code of Good Governance for Higher Education in Scotland (Committee of Scottish Chairs, 2013) and the passing of the Higher Education Governance (Scotland) Act 2016 (Scottish Parliament, 2016), which introduced new rules for how HEIs should appoint Chairs of Court. It also provided that all Courts must include members who are trade union representatives, staff members and students (Scottish Parliament, 2016).

3.4 Conclusion

The chapter discussed pertinent issues related to the contexts and developments in key policy area in HEs in Algeria and Scotland between 1999 and 2020, namely. in Algeria BMD, Quality Assurance, and International Mobility while in Scotland concerning Funding, Widening Access and Governance. The first section of the chapter highlighted insights about Algerian HE, focusing on policy developments related to policy areas like the BMD system, improved

quality assurance and internationalization of HE associated with the 1999 Bologna Process, which also involved the multimillion-pound program to train 500 doctoral students in other countries preferably Western English speaking. The second section of the chapter focused on HE in Scotland. Scotland's distinct policy making approach was noted, along with the government's persistence on differentiating its tuition fee policy from that of the rest of the UK and England specifically. The chapter provided insights into other equally significant policy developments, such as the attention paid to quality assurance and the constant efforts made to increase access for a wider range of student demographics.

Chapter 4

Conceptual Frameworks

4.1 Introduction

This chapter discusses key concepts drawn from relevant literature related to policy making policy advice and expertise in HE policy making. These concepts are grouped under four categories with their corresponding sub concepts. The first category relates to policy making models, under which seven sub concepts are explored namely, institutionalism, systems theory, pluralist strategy, elitism, stages model, rationalism, and incrementalism. The second category is policy networks with four sub concepts viz., issue networks, policy communities, epistemic communities, and advocacy coalition framework. The third category combines research utilization and evidence use and are supported by seven interrelated sub concepts, which are: knowledge driven use, problem-solving function, interactive use, political use, tactical use, enlightenment, and social intellectual enterprise. The final category is policy advisory systems, with nine sub concepts: location and government control, speaking truth to power vs sharing influence, externalization of policy advice, politicization of policy advice, content, hot vs cold policy advice, role perceptions, short term reactive vs long term anticipatory advice, and policy ideational compatibility. The chapter also discusses the relevance of some these concepts to the present study.

4.2 Policy-making Models

4.2.1 Institutionalism

In policy making, institutionalism is a concept that represents the conventional, "classical" method of policy making where the organization, responsibilities, and roles of governmental institutions are the main topics of discussion (Hahn, 1987). The primary concern of institutionalism is on how social behaviour is shaped by rules, norms, and values as it delves deeper into the various social structures. The most general method of understanding how institutions influence policy output is to consider how the institutions both empower and constrain actors in policy making. This is because institutional theory focuses on institutions and how important they are in policy making (Marsh and Olsen, 2008). Stability is one of the basic features of institutions; this is true even when it seems that the underlying conflicts in society will lead to instability. The ability of institutions to generate equilibrium results in the analysis of the deep political divisions, and this analysis also applies to the institutions'

influence over policies. Working through institutions will result in policies that are significantly more stable and predictable than trying to make decisions without explicit institutional rules, such as through policy networks or other unofficial structures (Peters, 2016).

The legislative, executive, and judicial branches of government are the organizations that set the public policy and provide the policy with legitimacy. The government employs its legitimate powers to carry out policy implementation and applies its laws to everyone. There is a propensity to conceptualize institutions in terms of structure and formality (Peters, 2016). Institutions can also be characterized by the beliefs they hold and the dedication of their constituents to those beliefs. Institutional ideas influence how decisions are made within the organization, whether people join because they share the same beliefs or because they are socialized to them after becoming members. Though it may be more visible in social institutions, ideas play a significant role in influencing public policy (Peters, 2016). In his work, Peters (2000) identified seven variations of institutionalism yet the normative approach, the rational choice version of institutionalism, historical institutionalism, and empirical institutionalism are the four main institutional approaches that concentrated on.

Under the normative approach, instead of maximizing their own end goals, those involved in policy making follow the norms and procedures of the institutions they represent when making decisions. Here, the decision makers have a stronger allegiance to the organization and its regulations than to the results that a rational choice approach would predict. Whereas, under the rational choice institutionalism, those in positions of decision making pour their own values into the organization, only associating with organizations that share their beliefs. However, strong political party affiliations can lead an individual to support their chosen party despite opposing viewpoints (Hofer, 2022). Historical institutionalism on the other hand gives precedents inside an organization a lot of weight viewpoints (Hofer, 2022). Change is challenging because ideas, policies, and procedures are "baked into" the organization. While this is like the normative approach, it says that decisions made years ago still have an impact on policy decisions today.

An understanding of the origins of policy decisions in a value-based organization is necessary. This is comparable to the "deep state idea" in that long-term supporters or workers of an organization will resist any efforts to impose change in favour of holding fast to the principles they were taught in their early days. According to Peters (2000), the final form of institutionalism is called empirical. Subtypes notwithstanding, all suggest that scholars need to

consider how institutions function in relation to individuals as well. For instance, civic groups are establishments that serve as a middleman between the people and the government. It is necessary to consider both their influence and that of governmental institutions (Hoefler, 2022). Institutionalism is of importance because it emphasizes how structures persist even when people come and go. People who work for institutions alter their behaviour because of these structures (more so than individuals transform the institutions). Policy decisions are therefore more stable than they otherwise might be, and reform is more challenging than expected (Hoefler, 2022).

4.2.2 Systems Theory

The systems theory of David Easton (1953) can be characterized as a two-way flow of information between the ruling class and the ruled class. It is believed that demands and support from the social order are inputs, while influential decisions and policies are outputs. Parties and interest groups are viewed as gatekeepers who, in the end, control the flow of inputs into the system. Through these decisions and policies, the inputs are changed into outputs and a response from the public is sought. Public inputs, which include demands for particular policies, are taken by the political system as a manifestation of support for government, and these outputs respond to societies to influence the next cycle of outputs. Government work is regarded as an output. The key to evaluating the effectiveness of government policies is feedback. The policy decision may not be accepted as settled in order to improve the performance of the public policy; instead, it must be tested and examined (Olaniyi, 1998). In general, people support the government when their needs are met, and they tend to withdraw their support when those needs are not met. The relationships between the inputs and outputs are intricate and dynamic (Zeb-un-Nisa et al., 2021).

As a concept, systems analysis can be used in policy making in two primary ways. It can be used to generate concepts, ideas, and courses of action when policy makers try to make recommendations about policy problems (systems analysis 'for' policy). It can also be used to understand what is happening when policy is made (systems analysis 'of' policy) Stewart and Ayres (2001)

Policy analysts have not utilized many of the features of systems theory, either for understanding or prescribing (Stewart and Ayres, 2001). Since the mid-1980s, institutionalist approaches – which link policy outcomes to organizational norms, structures, and incentives – have been utilized far more frequently. However, systems theory has advanced beyond the ideas

of the 1970s. 'Soft' systems approaches, which emphasize the self-organizing and adaptive capabilities of well-designed systems, have supplanted 'hard' systems theory. The intentional use of networks as tools for developing and enforcing policy has been described as a “third way” (beyond markets and hierarchical authority) from the perspective of governance (Stewart and Ayres, 2001).

The goal of systems theory is to clarify the dynamic interactions and dependencies between system elements as well as the interactions between the environment and the organization. The structure and patterns of the relationships that result from component interactions are what define a system. These emergent patterns and relationships are what set each system apart from the others. Put another way, elements of social organizations have free will and intentional goals, in contrast to biological systems. The environment, the social organization as a system, and the individuals who make up the organization are the three levels of observations that systems theorists generally concentrate on (Lai and Lin, 2017).

According to open systems theory, a group of people and an organization are seen as a collective connected by networks of relationships. People interact with one another in the system through patterned activities that create networks of relationships, which ultimately lead to the creation and implementation of the entire organization (Katz and Kahn, 1966; Lai and Lin, 2017). Further, systems theory was used to examine how public institutions like zoos, parks, libraries, and schools could enhance their administration, communication, and general organizational effectiveness. Instead of resulting in unfair gains, success required an understanding of their environments and the proper combination of leaders to improve the organization's overall performance (Lai and Lin, 2017).

4.2.3 Pluralist strategy

Harold Laski was arguably the most well-known proponent of a new, pluralist theory in the early 20th century (Holyoke, 2020). Laski and other pluralists renounced the idea of a single, monolithic state with absolute authority, arguing instead that there were numerous power centres, or multiple decision-making points, making up the government (McFarland, 2004). Political behaviour in contemporary democracies is widely analyzed using pluralism theory, a well-known theoretical tradition. This theory is primarily predicated on the idea that citizens participate in political spheres through various interest groups, and that political power ought to be distributed to protect each group's own legitimate interests, with no group taking control of the system (Miller, 1983).

Though he acknowledged the existence of hundreds of interest groups, Holyoke (2020) believed that they were not the only entities that possessed political power. Baskin (1970) argues that a group's power in a policy domain will depend on its capacity to maintain control over the matter in order to prevent the number of participating groups from growing and curbing the value of the interested group's own resources of influence. Group theorists, as pluralists, contend that a variety of groups enter and exit policy politics at different rates of frequency and intensity, rather than the balance of power between two opposing groups, determines public policy (Holyoke, 2020).

The pluralist approach's first and possibly most fundamental premise is that no generalization about power in any community can be made. The idea that a particular group inevitably rules a community is rejected by. If anything, pluralist researchers seem to be under the impression that no one is in charge in a town; therefore, when they approach a local informant, their first question is probably not going to be, "Who runs this community?," but rather, "Does anyone at all run this community?" (Polsby, 1960, p476).

E.E. Schattschneider (1953) argued that even if one accepted the pluralist argument that political competition increases the number of interests organized for political advocacy and even brings new issues and problems to light, one could not claim that this resulted in a group community that became so diverse as to represent all group interests in society (Holyoke, 2020).

4.2.4 Elitism

In policy making, this theory implies that public policy is a creation of the elite, represents elite values, and serves elite purposes. This presumption implies that the masses, or general public, are ignorant and apathetic and do not shape or decide public policy through their demands or deeds (Dye, 1981). Further, elite theory makes it clear that all forms of government are fundamentally oligarchies that manipulate the consent of the ruled by using various values and principles to justify their power struggles (Mariotti, 2020).

Elites may be described as individuals who, by account of their prominent positions in large or otherwise critically important organizations and movements, are able to influence political outcomes consistently and significantly. In other words, elites are those who possess the organized ability to cause serious political disruption without rapidly facing repression. Their composition encompasses not only prominent and "established" figures such as prominent

politicians, business magnates, high-ranking civil servants, and senior military officers, but also, to differing degrees in various societies, relatively fleeting and less well-known leaders of mass organizations like trade unions, significant voluntary associations, and highly influential mass movements (Higley, 2010). The central claim of elite theory is that the ruling class, whose preferences are implemented by political officials and agencies, determines public policy. The elites' policies reflect their values; they value the status quo over radical change (Anyebe, 2018).

Despite its popularity, elite theory has faced criticism due to its cultural relativism and symptomatic nature, stemming from bureaucratic and non-democratic cultures. It is argued that the theory lacks empirical support. Further, values such as loyalty to the status quo, stability, political order, and minority dominance are among those that cannot be tested. The theory's polemical criticism of Marxism led to its rejection, and it should be mentioned that the source of this attack is the writings of classical theorists who consciously responded to the central ideas of Marxist political theory. The assumption of the self-awareness, coherence, and unity of the elite group in elite theory has also drawn criticism. Despite these claims, the theory is still applicable and quite fitting for comprehending public policy. Thus, the theory's validity is unaffected by either background or ideology (Salawu, 2023).

4.2.5 Stages Models

One of the two earliest models that has remained valid and widely used in public policy analysis is the stages model, which was first presented by Laswell in 1956 and has seven stages. Even though Laswell (1956) initially defined the stages model as seven stages, other scholars (e.g., Jones, 1970; Brewer, 1974; Anderson, 2014; Brewer and DeLeon, 1983) proposed a five or six stages process. There are essentially five stages in the stages model that is currently in use. Agenda setting, formulation, legitimation, implementation, and evaluation are the terms used to describe these phases (Brewer and D. Leon, 1983; DeLeon, 1999; Sabatier, 1999; 2007).

Ozgun and Kulaç (2017) put together a comprehensive review of these phases. The first step of the stages model, agenda setting, deals with topics like how problems develop and make their way onto the public agenda (Howlett and Ramesh, 1995). Furthermore, issues and potential solutions either attract or repel the public's and elites' attention during the agenda-setting process (Hill, 1997), which turns problems into policy declarations (Birkland, 2005). The particular priorities of policy makers influence the process of setting agendas (Macrea and Wilde, 1985). Although many issues are likely to be brought to the public agenda, only a small

portion of them are brought to the attention of governments and other actors (Howlett and Ramesh, 1995). Policy alternatives are developed during the formulation stage to address the pressing issues on the public agenda (Dye, 2008). This reduces the number of policy options and facilitates the policy makers' ability to make their final decisions (Howlett and Ramesh, 1995). Stated differently, a set of policy alternatives and solutions is generated and also narrowed to facilitate the final decision during the policy formulation stage, which is essentially the pre-policy decision stage (Sidney, 2007).

Numerous actors play important roles in the process of formulating public policy, which involves developing various mechanisms to address social problems (Jones, 1977; Peters, 1996). The government, parliament, public bureaucrats, political parties, think tanks, pressure groups, and the media are examples of these actors. Answers to some of the important questions are sought in the formulation stage, such as What is the strategy to address the issue? What are the priorities and goals? What are the advantages and disadvantages of achieving goals? (Cochran and Malone, 1999).

In the process of forming public policy, which considers various options and shapes policies accordingly, legitimation stage is crucial for the general public. According to Kraft and Furlong (2004), political actions are legitimized or given legal force by the decisions made by policy makers. It is challenging for policy makers to steer toward the legitimation stage apart from the widely held beliefs in society. In a similar vein, Anderson (1982) emphasizes that the public influences the legitimation stage, so policy makers must consider citizen requests and demands. Furthermore, Anderson (1982) reveals that if the needs and requests of the citizens are not taken into account during the process, the political future of the decision-makers may be brief. Over time, the efficacy of policies formulated by policy makers to address societal issues and needs may diminish. At this point, the regulations required to alter the policies are passed.

Following the conclusion of the legitimation process, public policies enter their implementation phase. According to Fitz, Halpin and Power (1994), during the implementation stage, policy objectives are translated into actions. Effective implementation is critical to achieving the policy's goals (Ripley and Franklin, 1986). In this situation, even well-crafted policies will not be able to achieve the desired results if they are not carried out effectively and coherently (Edwards, 1980). However, social, economic, technological, and political factors have a big impact on the public policy implementation stage (Grindle, Howlett and Ramesh, 1995). For public policies to be implemented smoothly, public support is also essential (Anderson, 2014).

The last phase of the stages model is evaluation. At this point, efforts are made to present and evaluate the outcomes of the policies that have been put into place (Dunn, 1981; Peters, 1996). Furthermore, the primary focus is on determining whether the policies and programs accomplish the established goals and objectives (Jones, 1977; Kraft and Furlong, 2004). Stated differently, the evaluation stage/process measures the overall effectiveness of the policies in achieving the goals and objectives of the national program (Peters, 1996; Dye, 2008). Mathematical models and techniques are applied in public policy analyses (particularly in the evaluation stage), and empirical research pertaining to the policy's affected sector is carried out (Jones, 1977). Surveys and/or interviews are the most popular and practical instruments/methods in empirical research to collect data from people regarding the policies that have been put into place. Furthermore, these techniques can be used to gauge people's attitudes toward policies. Because of this, the policies' advantages and disadvantages are noted, and comments are provided. The policy cycle may be reversed at the conclusion of the evaluation stage, and the procedure can begin from the first step of public policy analysis (Howlett and Ramesh, 1995).

The contributions and the influence of official, unofficial, and international actors on the policies are carefully examined in stages. Different actors have varied impacts and input at each stage. Think tanks, in particular, are important because they influence policy makers in both developing and developed countries in a variety of policy areas (Howlett and Ramesh, 1995; Yılmaz and Kulaç, 2016). To apply a policy, it is imperative to concentrate on the attitudes of the policy actors. In addition, it is highly functional to adhere to the relationships amongst policy actors to understand the fundamental elements of the policies (Ozgur and Kulaç, 2017).

In general, the scholars who discuss the processes model agree that while a policy may go through each of these stages during its creation, the stages are not always distinct from one another; in fact, they may run parallel to one another to the point where it becomes difficult to tell one stage from another (Bernier and Lachapelle, 2010).

4.2.6 Rationalism

As a concept, rationalism defines an effective decision-making process. Saint-Martin and Allison (2011) who draw a distinction between incremental analysis and incremental politics, argues that the latter refers to the practice of public officials, particularly those employed by independent bureaucracies, mobilizing the rational mode of analysis to publicly legitimize and justify their actions (p 20). When a decision is made based on knowledge of the potential

outcomes of each option and is selected using the logic of opting for the course of action most likely to fulfil one's goals or objectives, it is said to be more rational. Alongside this idea is a model that breaks down the decision-making process into a series of logical steps, beginning with the establishment of objectives or goals within a particular decision context, then identifying or designing alternatives, evaluating their potential effects, and selecting the best alternative in light of the objectives (Kørnøv and Thissen, 2000).

Due to their more focused nature, Anderson views incrementalism and rationalism as models of decision-making as opposed to policymaking. Both have had a significant impact on process models. Rationalism makes an effort to define an effective decision-making process. It usually consists of the following steps: defining and prioritizing the objectives; finding a range of options to achieve the objectives; projecting the outcomes of each option; contrasting the projected outcomes of the different options; and choosing the option that maximizes the achievement of the objectives. Critics of rationalism point out that it is unable to handle scenarios where objectives are unclear or contested and is unrealistic in terms of information and analytical requirements. It views making decisions as an intellectual process as opposed to a political one (Hahn, 1987).

4.2.7 Incrementalism

Incrementalism (anti-rationalism) is a concept put forth by Charles Lindblom and explains the idea that most issues could not be rationally decided upon because of conflicting goals and insufficient information. Instead, policies are created through a partisan mutual adjustment process that is pluralistic and involves a wide range of players. The emphasis of these proposals is on making slight changes to the status quo. If there is any significant policy change at all, it comes from a slow accumulation of incremental adjustments, a process Lindblom refers to as seriality (Hayes, 2017).

According to the incremental model, the public policy is considered as a continuation of a former policy with minor alterations, policies, programs, and expenditures. Partial and restricted addition and modification in existing policies are done by incremental decisions. Lindblom described that in pluralists societies, incremental policymaking is the adopted policy model i.e. United States (Zeb-un-Nisa et al., 2021).

However, Lindblom (1979) argues that incrementalism does not only refer to small changes occurring over time; it can also refer to significant changes (increments) occurring during the policy-making process. Nonetheless, a key component of incrementalism is whether the change

is radical or non-radical, that is, whether the actual policy change fits within broader trends or represents a more radical divergence from conventional policymaking.

4.3 Policy Networks

As a concept, a policy network refers to all state, private, and social actors operating within institutions at different levels (local, regional, national, and international) who have an impact on a particular policy area (Howlett, Mukherjee and Koppenjan, 2017). It is possible to think of the actors involved in each sector or issue area as a subset of that universe, or as a policy subsystem (Freeman and Stevens, 1987). Subsystems of this type are social networks that comprise the connections among constituents of the policy universe that are active in particular knowledge and political arenas. Subsystem actors engage in a range of activities during their interactions with other actors, including developing and contesting policy ideas and concepts about their sector as well as the larger social and political world in which these exist. They also bargain with one another over policy aims and measures (Howlett, Mukherjee and Koppenjan, 2017). Although these groups of actors go by many different names, such as issue networks, policy networks, and policy communities, the general subsystem family of concepts first appeared in the 1950s to help explain how discourses and interest play a part in the policy-making process. The aforementioned concepts recognize the intricate informal and formal interactions that transpire between policy actors from both state and non-state domains. They also enhance earlier research that highlighted the material and self-serving actions of a restricted group of actors. think tanks, interest groups, lobbyists, bureaucrats, and politicians participate in formal policy deliberations (McCool, 1998).

A policy network is ‘a cluster or complex of organisations connected to each other by resource dependencies and distinguished from other clusters or complexes by breaks in the structure of resource dependencies’ (Rhodes and Marsh 1992, p 182). According to the literature, the term "policy network" is used for a variety of analytical and semantic purposes. At least three aspects of the idea can be distinguished: (1) the network as an empirical tool and analytical framework; (2) the network as a social structure; and (3) the network as a form of governance. In addition to a discussion of a network theory as a fourth dimension.

The term “policy network” refers to groups of formal and informal institutional connections between governmental and other actors organized around common goals in the formulation and execution of public policy. There is interdependence among these institutions, and the members of the networks negotiate to create policies. Trade unions, large corporations, and the

professions are frequently the other actors (Rhodes, 1997). In this model, Rhodes assumes that three key variables determine what type of policy network exists in a specific sector: First, the relative stability of a network's membership: do the same actors tend to dominate decision-making over time or is membership fluid and dependent on the specific policy issue under discussion? Second, the network's relative insularity: is it a cabal which excludes outsiders or is it highly permeable by a variety of actors with different objectives? Third, the strength of resource dependencies: do network members depend heavily on each other for valued resources such as money, expertise and legitimacy or are most actors self-sufficient and thus relatively independent of one another? (Peterson, 2003).

The two main schools of thought in policy network research are the governance school (which views policy networks as a form of governance) and the interest intermediation school (which views policy networks as an analytical tool). Börzel (1998) defines policy networks in general terms "as power relationships between the government and interest groups, in which resources are exchanged" (p. 2) despite the fact that the same author highlights the Babylonian variety of definitions attributed to the concept of policy networks, which often causes confusion and difficulty when attempting to apply the concept (Börzel, 2002). According to Thompson and Pforr (2005), in the realm of public policy and administration, the policy network concept, however, encompasses a variety of particular approaches. The interest intermediation school and the governance school, respectively, are the two philosophical traditions from which these models originated. The interest intermediation school of analysis produced the "issue network" and "policy community" models, for example (Hecl 1978 and Richardson and Jordan 1979, respectively).

4.3.1 Policy networks and Power dependency

The concept of power dependence lies at the backbone of these inter-organizational interactions (Kickert, Klijn, and Koppenjan, 1997). These interrelations reflect structural relationships, interdependencies, and communications among political and policymaking actors (Knoke, 1994). Social relationships often entail a mutual dependence between individuals or groups as one party depends on another when seeking satisfactory outcomes that can only be delivered or achieved through the other party's contribution (Emerson, 1962). The author continues to highlight that these connections suggest that both sides have some capacity to either facilitate or hinder the other's ability to reach their objectives, which makes them eager to control and influence each other's behaviours. This ability to influence originates from having access to or

control over resources or outputs valued by the other which makes power rooted in the dependency of others (Emerson, 1962).

A traditional standpoint postulates that power is intrinsically associated with formal and authoritative positions and those who hold them but power is more easily grasped and understood as contingent and relational, framed and driven by the relative strength and influence of other actors (Rhodes, 1997). Through this lens, multiple typologies have emerged in the literature, most of these are aligned with Rhode's conceptualization of networks as configurations of power-dependent relationships between governments and interest groups which mobilise their resources to reach their goals (Rhodes, 1986). These typologies diverge from each other in terms of the criteria used to set apart the several forms of networks (see also Börzel, 2011).

Rhodes's prototype sorted networks based on one single facet: The degree of integration among network members. He later refined the model by supplementing two additional dimensions: the types of actors involved and the distribution of resources among them. Combined together, these three criteria produced a typology comprising five types of networks, arranged along a continuum and ranging from highly integrated policy communities to loosely connected issue networks with professional, intergovernmental, and producer networks positioned in between (Börzel, 2011; Rhodes and Marsh, 1992).

The power dependence theory supplies a much-needed theoretical lens for a deeper understanding of network behaviour, which perceives policy networks as assembled configurations of interdependent organizations that lean on each other for essential resources. Since no single actor is in possession of all the resources needed to achieve their targets independently, mutual dependence becomes the defining feature of these relationships. Therefore, actors find themselves obliged to engage in resource exchanges and working strategically within a framework governed by conventional rules and established norms that give the network behaviours game-like traits, with participants mobilising a variety assortment of resources (legal, organizational, financial, political, or informational) to maximize their influence while minimizing their reliance on others. The differences in the resources' distribution and the bargaining competencies of the actors determine the variations in outcomes within and between networks (Rhodes, 2006). Moreover, the power dependence approach places greater emphasis on how resources such as funding and authority are distributed within

the core executive when scrutinizing the dynamic and developing relationships of dependence among various actors (Rhodes, 1995; Rhodes, 1997).

Rhodes (1997) defines governance as comprising self-organizing, interorganizational networks that share several key features. First, organizational interdependence, which promotes the principle that governance extends beyond formal government structures to include non-state actors. Boundaries of the state shift blurring the lines between public, private, and voluntary sectors. Second, active continuous interaction, when network members who are bound together by mutual dependence participate in ongoing exchanges to negotiate their shared goals. Third, a strategic behaviour defined by reciprocal trust in the sense that the relationships have a tendency to look like a game nested in the principles of trust and agreed-upon guidelines. Fourth, autonomy from the government. These networks are highly independent and hold zero accountability to the state or its institutions despite the state's attempts to influence them, which remain at best limited and indirect. Interdependence within these networks enforce informal authority, rather than authoritative command, that stems from negotiation rather than coercion.

Governments function within a complex web of networks, organizations, actors and mutual dependencies but they often fail when attempting to govern through a purely top-down approach which excludes the fragmented and interdependent nature of policymaking. Efforts at centralization are frequently undermined by this complexity, which can, paradoxically, provoke even more attempts at centralization (Rhodes, 1997).

The following section will discuss the aforementioned actor constellations: Issue Networks (Heclo, 1978); Policy Communities (Jordan and Richardson, 1983); Epistemic Community Approach (Haas, 1992); Advocacy Coalition (Sabatier and Jenkins-Smith, 1993a, 1993b).

4.3.2 Issue Networks

Issue networks are individual groupings that are present in the policy process system, which “comprise a large number of participants with quite variable degrees of mutual commitment or of dependence on others in their environment; in fact, it is almost impossible to say where a network leaves off and its environment begins” (Heclo, 1978, p. 102). Critiquing a focus on elites, Heclo states “that looking for the few who are powerful, we tend to overlook the many whose webs of influence provoke and guide the exercise of power” (1978, p. 102).

Heclo contends that the traditional channels of negotiation between political actors, bureaucracy, and established interest groups had been undermined by the expansion of government reach and policy complexity, the blurring of policy borders, and the mobilization

of new group interests. Policy sectors have become disjointed and fragmented into a number of issue areas. Then issue networks emerge (Marshall, 1995). In the words of Heclo, "issue networks [...] comprise a large number of participants with quite variable degrees of mutual commitment or of dependence on others in their environment; in fact, it is almost impossible to say where a network leaves off and its environment begins" (Heclo, 1978, p. 102). He continues by stating that "participants enter and exit the networks on a regular basis" (Heclo, 1978, p. 102).

There are several issue networks, many of which overlap and have hazy borders. In that they typically involve a large number of participants as opposed to a precisely defined and constrained collection of established groups and political/bureaucratic actors, networks differ significantly from, for example, policy communities. Network members are not equally endowed with power and influence because some have easier access to decision-making processes and better resources than others. When conditions change or the problem is reframed, the network's makeup and the relative influence of its members may also shift (Marshall, 1995). Network representatives includes "powerful interest groups," "people with a reputation for knowledge in or out of government," and "issue-skilled [individuals] regardless of formal professional training" (Heclo 1978, pp. 102–103). It is "almost impossible to say where a network leaves off and its environment begins" because "participants move in and out of the networks constantly," which causes the so-called issue networks to vary in composition (Heclo 1978, p. 102). He continues by stating that because issue networks are founded on knowledge first, they do not always result in agreement or consensus and, consequently, they do not always form a coalition or what he terms a "shared-action group" or develop into an interest group where the importance of having similar beliefs is paramount (Heclo, 1978, pp.108-104).

According to Stone (1996, p. 90), "an issue network is characterized by participants with conflicting interests, a lack of common values, and little consensus regarding problem definition or the outcomes of policy interventions,". Furthermore, what qualifies them as an expert in the topic of discussion is not their professional training but rather their understanding of the subject. According to Heclo, while specific professions may be well-known, individuals who possess issue-skill, that is, are knowledgeable about the nuances of a given policy debate, independent of formal professional training are the real experts in the networks (Heclo, 1978).

Heclo describes issue networks more precisely as a. group of people sharing knowledge about a particular facet (or, as the network defines it, a problem) of public policy. As a result, it is

more precisely defined than, say, a shared-attention group or "public" because members of the networks are more likely to share a common knowledge base and comprehension of how to recognize policy issues (Hecl, 1978, pp. 103–104). He continues by stating that because issue networks are founded on knowledge first, they do not always result in agreement or consensus and, consequently, they do not always form a coalition or what he terms a "shared-action group" or develop into an interest group where the importance of having similar beliefs is paramount (Hecl, 1978, pp.108-104).

4.3.3 Policy Communities

Wildavsky (1984) argues that “Community refers to the personal relationships between major political and administrative actors, sometimes in conflict, often in agreement, but always in touch and operating within a shared framework” (P. 18) while he defines Policy as “the governmental action directed toward and affecting some end outside itself” and continues to stress that “There is no escaping the tension between policy and community, between adapting actions and maintaining relationships” (P. 18).

Kingdon (1984) understands experts in a particular policy domain, such as housing, health, or environmental protection, as comprising the policy communities. Therefore, rather than looking at party positions, manifestos, or parliamentary influence, Jordan and Richardson (1979) argue that it may be more accurate to look at the relationships that occur in committees, the policy community of departments and groups, co-optation practices, and consensual style. Generally, they depicted a clientelistic connection between government departments and the main insider groups where each party followed certain ground rules, leading to an accommodation process that produced a core network based on "negotiated order" (Jordan and Richardson, 1982). In this regard, Dudley and Richardson (1996) contend that the phrase "negotiated order" suggested that policy actors typically aimed to achieve continuity, which was frequently the outcome of their efforts. Policy communities are then typically thought of as stabilizing forces in the policy-making process (Dudley and Richardson, 1996).

Policy communities, which typically include the minister or secretary, government agencies, and significant interest groups, roughly correspond to the functional areas of government (such as education, health, and industry). They are confined to a comparatively small number of privileged bodies and are distinguished by distinct subject boundaries (Marshall, 1995). A relationship of dependency develops between the players. Clientele organizations are a valuable source of specialized advice, information, support, and legitimacy for ministers and

departments. Groups, on the other hand, need easy access to the government apparatus. As a result, creating policies becomes a collaborative exercise (Marshall, 1995).

Stone also claims that policy communities differ significantly from epistemic communities since an epistemic community "coalesces around `objectivity', `expertise', and `scientific authority' [...] policy communities are not characterised by shared principled beliefs" (Stone, 1996, p.91).

4.3.4 Epistemic Communities

An epistemic community denotes 'a network of professionals with recognised expertise and competence in a particular domain and an authoritative claim to policy-relevant knowledge' (Haas 1992:3). Haas continues by clarifying that professionals from a range of disciplines and backgrounds can make up an epistemic community. What unites them is that they all 1) have a shared set of normative and principled beliefs which provide a value-based rationale for the social action of community members; (2) share causal beliefs which are derived from their analysis of practices leading or contributing to a central set of problems in their domain and which then serve as the basis for elucidating the multiple linkages between possible policy actions and desired outcomes; (3) share notions of validity - that is, intersubjective, internally defined criteria for weighing and validating knowledge in the domain of their expertise; and (4) a common policy enterprise - that is, a set of common practices associated with a set of problems to which their professional competence is directed, presumably out the conviction that human welfare will be enhanced as a consequence (Haas, 1992, p.3). Sutton (1999) defines epistemic communities as "a group of technical experts who have access to privileged information and share and discuss ideas. Others do not have access to this information and are excluded. Individuals can be from the research community, NGOs, international organisations, or a range of other organisations. Epistemic communities can have powerful influences on policy making, some expressing certain political opinions and having links with governmental decision-makers" (p. 6).

According to Béland, Howlett and Mukherjee (2018), epistemic communities play a crucial role in steering and influencing the actions of other actors during the agenda-setting stage of the policy process by establishing the primary course that the process follows. Insofar as there are several possible equilibrium points, epistemic communities will assist in determining which one is chosen (Adler and Haas, 1992). The proponent of the concept claim that knowledge has

significant effect on subsequent policy discussions and other activities at later stages of the policy process.

The epistemic community members have common causal beliefs and cause-and-effect understandings, which sets them apart from interest groups. Unlike interest groups, they would leave the policy debate if presented with anomalies that contradicted their causal beliefs (Haas, 1992, p. 18). Furthermore, it is critical to comprehend how epistemic communities differ even more from the larger scientific community: [e]pistemic communities need to be distinguished not only from other professions and disciplines but also from the larger scientific community. Members of a particular profession or discipline may have a common knowledge base and set of causal approaches or orientations, but they do not share the normative commitments that characterize members of an epistemic community (Haas, 1992). Put differently, the common beliefs that glue the members of an epistemic community together, and at the same time set them apart from the other groups, are based on knowledge and cause-and-effect beliefs; and on intellectual rather than emotional beliefs.

For instance, while economists may be a profession, they are not always an epistemic community. Conversely, a subset of economists that adhere to a specific school of thought, like Keynesian economists, may be an epistemic community (Haas, 1992).

The focus of the epistemic community approach is on expert actors who seek change in particular policy areas and who share political projects, norms, and causal beliefs (Stone, 1996, p.86). She further argues that "the status and prestige associated with epistemic community expertise and their high professional training and authoritative knowledge regarding a particular problem is politically empowering and provides limited access to the political system" (Stone, 1996, pp. 88-89). When faced with uncertainties and issues that are becoming more complex and technical in nature, Haas (1992) claims that decision makers are increasingly looking to epistemic communities for guidance. According to this viewpoint, epistemic communities aim to influence politics in addition to producing knowledge. In fact, policy demands give rise to epistemic communities, and policy receptivity is a critical issue for these communities. They have to create "usable knowledge," which is knowledge that can be used to solve particular problems. Further, these communities not only create knowledge objects but also knowledge producers, defining, articulating, and shaping the identities of both current and future knowledge producers as well as the individual and collective paths they follow (Meyer and Molyneux-Hodgson, 2010).

Nevertheless, in order to effectively communicate their ideas, epistemic communities must take the initiative on the political front. They must engage with a wide range of other players, and it is reasonable to assume that influence will fluctuate and depend on the larger strategic games being fought. Under such circumstances, the epistemic community may require the participation of other, politically astute groups to fully realize the potential of consensual knowledge (Dunlop, 2000).

4.3.5 The Advocacy Coalition Framework

Developed initially by Paul Sabatier, the concept of advocacy coalitions has much in common with epistemic communities, as his definition indicates: 'Within the subsystem, it is assumed that actors can be aggregated into a number of advocacy coalitions composed of people from various organisations who share a set of normative and causal beliefs and who often work in concert' (Sabatier 1988, p. 133). The vital difference between advocacy coalitions and epistemic communities, however, is that the former are based on values, while the latter are based on knowledge. Sabatier makes it clear, therefore, that his emphasis is on ideologically based coalitions, and on the concept of the 'dynamics of policy-oriented learning' (Sabatier 1988, p. 134). Advocacy coalitions consist not only of interest groups, administrative agencies and legislative committees, but also include journalists, analysts and researchers with an interest in the policy sector (Sabatier, 1988, p. 138). Advocacy coalitions, like epistemic communities, are conceived not so much in terms of the core and periphery of a network, but as units which have the capacity to bridge policy arenas and even national boundaries - a phenomenon especially evident in the European policy process (Richardson, 1994).

The advocacy coalition framework (ACF) was further expanded by later by Paul Sabatier and Hank Jenkins-Smith to help explain how policy changes over time and in response to outside shocks to the system, like shifts in the macroeconomic environment or alterations in the political landscape. Advocates from a range of backgrounds (political and agency officials, interest group leaders, researchers, etc.) who share a specific belief system – that is, a set of fundamental values, causal assumptions, and problem perceptions –and who demonstrate a nontrivial degree of coordinated activity over time are the members of advocacy coalitions, according to Sabatier and Jenkins-Smith (1993a, p. 25). These actors, who frequently occupy important government decision-making positions, compete to have their preferred problem definitions and solutions accepted during the policy-making process. To this end, they work both with and against epistemic communities and other groups (Béland, Howlett, and Mukherjee, 2018).

The advocacy coalition framework (ACF), as the authors (Sabatier and Jenkins-Smith) describe, is based on at least four fundamental tenets: (1) that understanding the process of policy change, and the role of policy-oriented learning therein, requires a time perspective of a decade or more; (2) that the most useful way to think about policy change over such a time span is through a focus on “policy subsystems”, that is the interaction of actors from different institutions who follow and seek to influence governmental decisions in a policy area; (3) that those subsystems must include an intergovernmental dimension, that is, they must involve all levels of government (at least for domestic policy); and (4) that public policies (or programs) can be conceptualized in the same manner as belief systems, that is, as sets of value priorities and causal assumptions about how to realize them (Sabatier and Jenkins-Smith, 1993a).

This particular framework's emphasis on core belief systems as opposed to interests, as described by Sabatier and Jenkins-Smith, may be its most distinctive feature (Sabatier and Jenkins-Smith, 1988). This framework's central claim is that significant modifications to a policy's foundation are typically brought about by outside forces. The ACF's basic claim is that, while policy-oriented learning plays a significant role in policy change and frequently modifies secondary aspects of a coalition's belief system, changes to a policy's core are typically the consequence of disruptions to noncognitive factors that are external to the subsystem, like macroeconomic conditions or the rise of a new systemic governing coalition (Sabatier and Jenkins-Smith, 1993a).

The foundation of the framework is the presumption that members' fundamental beliefs are not only consistent with one another but also largely resistant to change. The idea of an advocacy coalition, as the writers clarify, is predicated on the idea that common values serve as the fundamental glue in politics. Additionally, it makes the assumption that people's fundamental beliefs are not easily changed (Sabatier and Jenkins-Smith, 1993b).

Since the advocacy coalition framework “synthesizes many of the major findings of the knowledge utilization literature - particularly those concerning the enlightenment function and the advocacy use of analysis - into the broader literature on public-policy making”, these two authors claim that it is consistent with the work of earlier social scientists (Sabatier and Jenkins-Smith, 1993a, p. 5). Four underlying presumptions form the basis of the framework itself: that policies are grounded in specific belief systems; that actors from different institutions and levels of government interact with one another; and that time is a factor.

The ACF assumes that those involved in policy have strong opinions and are driven to turn those opinions into actual policy. It assumes that researchers (university scientists, policy analysts, consultants, etc.) are among the key players in a policy process because it believes that scientific and technical information has a significant impact on changing the beliefs of policy participants. Changes in policy spanning ten years or longer are of interest to the ACF. It also presumes that participants in policy will hold very stable beliefs over this time, making significant policy changes exceedingly challenging. The ACF predicts that the networks among significant policy participants play a role in shaping policy making and that stakeholder beliefs and behaviour are embedded within informal networks. The ACF makes the assumption that those involved in policy work to transform elements of their belief systems into actual policy before their opponents can accomplish the same. They need to find allies, pool resources, and create complementary tactics if they hope to succeed. The ACF contends that individuals involved in policy making will look for allies among legislators, agency employees, leaders of interest groups, judges, researchers, and academics from various governmental levels who share similar core beliefs. (Sabatier and Weible, 2007).

Nevertheless, it has been argued that at any given time, certain factors will force coalitions to come together to form “effective coalitions” (Sabatier and Jenkins-Smith, 1993a, p. 26). The objective of these coalitions is to “translate their beliefs into public policies or programs (which usually consist of a set of goals and directions, or empowerments, to administrative agencies for implementing those goals)” Sabatier and Jenkins-Smith (1993a, p. 26). Advocacy coalitions within the subsystem try to transform their belief systems' secondary tenets and policy cores into legally binding initiatives. The effects of system-wide events, such as shifts in socioeconomic conditions, outputs from other subsystems, and modifications to the coalition that governs the system, constitute the second process, known as external perturbation (Sabatier and Jenkins-Smith, 1993a, p. 34). Stated differently, this theory presupposes that a coalition aspires to power in order to put its fundamental values into laws. Additionally, as they clarify, a coalition won't give up on these fundamental principles in order to maintain its hold on power (Sabatier and Jenkins-Smith, 1993a).

Belief systems and policy-oriented learning are prioritized in the ACF. The central tenet of the ACF is that policy is made in a policy subsystem populated by a number of multifactor advocacy coalitions vying to shape policy in accordance with the shared policy values of each coalition (Sabatier, 1998). By tracing the origin of the beliefs that underpin policy changes, the ACF aims to provide an explanation for those changes. Policy-oriented learning is produced

through advocacy coalitions competing with one another. Reflecting its US pluralist heritage, the ACF views policy change as a relatively open and competitive process between belief systems. It prioritizes agency over structure when providing change explanations. According to the ACF, policy-oriented learning occurs both inside and between coalitions, and the competitive process is more complex than a group attempting to outdo another in advancing its interests (Sabatier, 1998). This policy-oriented learning is problematic because the coalitions often engage in a deaf dialogue in which they disparage each other's premises and understandings due to their divergent policy philosophies. According to the ACF, learning can occur when there is little conflict and when debate is facilitated by a professional forum (Jenkins-Smith and Sabatier, 1993a).

With the help of knowledge gained from policy learning, advocacy coalitions can push for policy changes, though whether or not these happen will depend on a number of outside variables that give them the chance to succeed. Perhaps an abrupt shift in the socioeconomic landscape offers a chance for an advocacy coalition to persuade public officials to adopt its policies. Alternatively, a significant shift within a ruling coalition might indicate a renewed readiness on the part of government representatives to collaborate with an advocacy coalition. Put differently, it is improbable that fresh data alone results in a shift in policy. Instead, before newly learned information is incorporated into policy, a number of obstacles must be cleared, including veto points, institutional structures, and adversarial advocacy coalitions (Schlager, 1995).

The closest term to a policy entrepreneur is the policy broker, an actor, which Sabatier (1993) compares to the British high civil service, mediates the competition between coalitions. Finding a fair compromise that reduces conflict is the role of the policy broker (Sabatier, 1998). The broker's personal policy inclinations influence this compromise, which in turn influences the policy process. An essential part of ACF accounts of policy change is played by such policy brokers (Smith, 2000).

4.4 Research Utilization and Evidence Use

Weiss (1977b) claims that the definition of research utilization is vague and complicated overall. She further argues that attempts at definitions cover a broad spectrum of actions, from a generalized sensitivity to ideas emphasized by social science research to the direct and instantaneous implementation of study recommendations. The prevalent notion of research utilization emphasizes applying particular research findings to particular choices made during

decision-making. A problem is identified; research fills in the knowledge gaps; decision makers then arrive at a solution. Information or understanding is required to generate a solution to the problem or to choose among alternative solutions (Weiss, 1977b). Among Weiss's contributions to knowledge utilization (Weiss, 1979) is an early and frequently cited one that offers six conceptualizations of research utilization. Weiss (1979) has identified seven ways in which knowledge (of social sciences, although this can be extended to the natural sciences) can influence policies. These conceptualizations are explored in detail in this section.

4.4.1 knowledge-driven

The idea is that basic research uncovers opportunities that might be relevant to public policy; applied research is carried out to clarify and test basic research findings for real-world application; if all goes according to plan, appropriate technologies are developed to put the findings into practice; and then application happens. There are not many examples in the social sciences and there seem to be a few reasons for that. It is rare for social science knowledge to be so authoritative or persuasive that application is forced upon it (Weiss, 1979). Knowledge in social science is not easily translated into material or social technologies that can be replicated.

This however does not insinuate or suggest that fundamental social science research is unhelpful in the formulation of public policy as stressed by Weiss (1979). Undoubtedly, a large number of government social policies and initiatives are founded on fundamental scientific understandings in the fields of psychology, sociology, economics, anthropology, and politics, either overtly or covertly. It is unlikely that they will do so through the series of events suggested by this model when they emerge to influence policy decisions.

4.4.2 problem-solving

The most popular understanding of research utilization is the direct application of a particular social science study's findings to an impending decision. It is anticipated that research will yield empirical data and conclusions that aid in the resolution of policy issues. Although the steps in the problem-solving model are different from those in the knowledge-driven model, it is still linear. In this case, the application of research is driven by the decision. When there is a decision to be made regarding an issue, research fills in the gaps in knowledge by offering solutions or insights that could be used to solve the issue or choose among potential solutions. After the void is filled, a choice is made.

According to this definition of research utilization, social science research can generally be incorporated into policy making in two ways. Initially, the research precedes the policy issue and is motivated by necessity. When faced with a choice, policy makers might go out and look for data from earlier studies to narrow the question's scope or find a viable course of action. Alternately, social science researchers, staff analysts, colleagues, consultants, or assistants may bring the information to their attention. Alternatively, they might come across it at conferences, in news articles, magazines, agency newsletters, professional journals, or at conferences. Nevertheless, there is a chance that the information found is no longer relevant or not applicable to the current situation.

The deliberate commissioning of social science research and analysis to close the knowledge gap is a second path to problem-solving use. The presumptions here are that decision makers have a clear understanding of their objectives, a map of viable options, and that they have determined which particular pieces of information are necessary to support their decision. This time, they enlist the help of social scientists to supply the information, analytical generalizations, and potentially interpretations of these generalizations in the form of suggestions related to the case at hand.

The steps in the process are as follows: definition of pending decision, identification of missing knowledge, acquisition of social science research and interpretation of the research for the decision context - policy choice. Research generated in this sequence is expected to have direct and immediate applicability and be used for decision making, even more so than research found through search procedures. In fact, it is generally accepted that the particular study that the relevant government office commissioned will have an effect and that decisions made in the future will be influenced by its recommendations. Plans, programs, and policies are anticipated to change, especially in light of the extensive policy study that the government contracted and customized to meet the requirements set by government employees. It is believed that the research would have been used if it had truly satisfied the information needs of decision makers.

4.4.3 Interactive

Engaging in interactive knowledge-seeking is another avenue for social science research to get into the decision-making process. In addition to social scientists, those involved in policy development also consult a range of other sources, including journalists, administrators, practitioners, politicians, planners, clients, interest groups, assistants, and friends. The process

is not one of research to decision in a linear fashion, but rather a disorganized web of linkages and back and forth that eludes clear diagrams (Weiss, 1979).

Diverse stakeholders involved in a problem domain combine their skills, convictions, and knowledge to attempt to make sense of the problem. Social scientists are just one group of people involved. They hardly ever have conclusions at their disposal that directly and explicitly address the current problem. They hardly ever possess a body of convergent evidence. However, they can converse with each other in a way that gradually gets them closer to possible policy responses (Weiss, 1979).

According to this model, using research is just one step in a complex process that also involves judgment, political insight, pressure, social media, experience, and social technologies. It is applicable to both face-to-face situations and the various methods of gathering and applying intelligence that involve middlemen. It outlines a well-known procedure that decision makers use to familiarize themselves with the spectrum of viewpoints and knowledge in a policy area (Weiss, 1979).

4.4.4 Political

The many different and often conflicting interests surrounding a policy matter frequently have a strong influence over the stances that policy makers adopt, or in some other cases, when opinions become more hardened as a result of years of debate. Decision-makers are unlikely to be open to new information from social science research at this time. Their stance is unlikely to be changed despite research, as they have made it for reasons of intellect, ideology, or interest. However, research and evidence can still be useful in these situations. It turns into “ammunition” for the side that finds its conclusions agreeable and encouraging. Proponents exalt the evidence in an effort to discredit detractors, persuade doubters, and strengthen believers even if conclusions have to be ripped out of context (Weiss, 1979).

Social scientists are often unhappy about the use, sometimes in a selective manner, of research findings to support a stance that decision-makers have adopted for different reasons. They typically view it as an illegitimate attempt to "use" research for self-serving purposes of personal aggrandizement and agency justification. However, using research to support already existing policy positions is also research utilization and demonstrates that researchers and analysts do not have control over how their evidence and findings are used by those charged with policy and decision making. Insofar as correctly interpreted research favours a particular

group's position, it boosts the confidence of those who hold that view, allays their fears, and gives them a competitive advantage in the ongoing discussion (Weiss, 1979).

4.4.5 Tactical

There are times when social science research is applied for goals unrelated to the main focus of the study. The act of conducting research itself is cited, rather than the conclusions that are reached. When faced with demands for action, government agencies might reply, "Yes, we recognize that as a critical need." We are currently researching it." Research demonstrates how responsive they are. When pressed for time, they might utilize research as a strategy to delay taking action ("We are waiting until the research is completed) (Weiss, 1979).

Research is occasionally used by government organizations to deflect criticism. They might attempt to free themselves of accountability for unfavorable policy outcomes by arguing that their actions were guided by the implications and suggestions of social science research studies. Supporting a research program can also be used as a strategy to improve the agency's reputation by associating it with well-known social scientists. Certain agencies fund a significant amount of research and, in doing so, cultivate a base of scholars who defend them when congressional appropriations are being examined. (Weiss, 1979).

4.4.6 Enlightenment

The "enlightenment" process is arguably the most frequent way that social science research enters the policy sphere. In this instance, the findings of one study, or even a collection of related studies, do not directly influence policy. Rather, the concepts and theoretical positions that have emerged from social science research are what actually have an impact on the policy-making process (Weiss, 1979). Under this model of research utilization, Weiss (1977a) argues that research supplies the theoretical foundation for ideas, viewpoints, and empirical generalizations that guide policy. New ideas and data can gradually accumulate to alter the norms that decision-makers follow and rearrange the objectives and priorities of the policy world.

Through a variety of channels, including professional journals, the media, and conversations with peers, social science research gradually spreads, and over time, the generalizations and variables it addresses give decision-makers a means of making sense of a complex world. However, the enlightenment process is not without flaws. Research that spreads to the policy domain through unstructured and indirect channels disseminates both true and false generalizations (Weiss, 1979). According to Weiss (1979), this research use model differs from

the problem-solving model in that it does not presuppose that research findings must align with the objectives and values of decision makers in order to be valuable.

Weiss (1979) concludes many important findings from social science research are never adopted by decision-making institutions. Some findings are so slowly accepted that by the time they are published, more thorough research has altered or even refuted their conclusions, making the results outdated.

4.4.7 Social intellectual enterprise

The first step in allocating funds for social science research is frequently the emergence of policy interest in a particular social issue; social scientists are only drawn to investigate an issue once funding becomes available (Weiss, 1979). Early research may adhere to the guidelines established by the policy debate, focusing only on the facets of the problem that have attracted official interest. Subsequently, when social science research expands its scope, it might help policy makers rethink the problem. Simultaneously, the policy and research colloquies could either intentionally or inadvertently address prevailing concerns in popular and intellectual discourse, such as "citizen participation," "local control," spiraling inflation, and individual privacy. According to this perspective, research is a component of the integrated intellectual enterprise (Weiss, 1979).

4.5 Policy Advisory Systems

Policy advice relates to “covering analysis of problems and the proposing of solutions” (Halligan, 1998, p. 1686). The concept of a policy advisory system (PAS) was initially put forward by Seymour-Ure (1987) to refer to the various channels and sources of policy advice that governments can access. There was a differentiation made between formal and informal communication channels, as well as between government-external and government-internal sources of advice. In addition, civil servants, political advisers, consultants, and interest groups were recognized as the four primary categories of policy advisers (Hussain, Tsang and Rafique, 2023).

Later, Halligan (1995) developed the concept further to describe and examine the various sources of policy advice that governments use when formulating policies as he defined policy advisory systems as “the organizational configuration of advisory actors in a jurisdiction or a policy sector” (Halligan, 1995, p. 3). The emphasis on a "system" of policy advice shifts the

analytical focus from individual advisory actors examined separately to a broader strategy and recognizes that counsel is obtained beyond the purview of internal government competence and information exchange (Howlett, 2019; Howlett and Migone, 2013). This is in line with interpretations of the government's knowledge utilization system, which is thought to constitute a marketplace for policy ideas and information is made up of knowledge producers (academy, producers), knowledge brokers (consultants, NGOs, interest groups, and think tanks), and proximate policy makers (the government, parliament) (Howlett, 2011). An additional characteristic of the internal proximate advisory system is the presence of "incidental advisers," or "policy workers," who carry out various tasks related to the policy-making process (Vesely, 2017; Connaughton and Devane, 2023).

Overall, two primary "waves" of research focus have been identified in the literature on policy advice. Scholarly attention tended to concentrate on individual policy advice actors during the first wave. Halligan's attempt to frame policy advice within a policy advisory system, with an emphasis on government control and location, was a significant innovation. Craft and Wilder later called for a "second wave" of research that reflected the increasingly polycentric advice landscape while attempting to integrate elements like ideational compatibility, context, and policy content (Manwaring, 2019).

4.5.1 Location and Government Control

Location and government control are two important concepts in Halligan's writings as they co-determine why some advice is taken into account and other advice is ignored (Halligan, 1995). Location conceptualizes the impact of various policy advice providers by comprehending their position (internal or external to the government) within the larger policy advice system. It was observed that various groups of actors shape the supply of, and demand for policy ideas in the form of policy advice but with remarkable imbalance between supply and demand (Howlett, 2015). Three main groups of actors interact to shape the influence and impact of policy advice: decision-makers, knowledge producers, and knowledge brokers (Craft and Howlett, 2013; Manwaring, 2019).

The second concept is the exposure to government control (high or low), which was identified by Halligan (1995) in conjunction with spatial considerations as a critical factor influencing the influence and operation of advisory systems. His thinking about policy advisory system considers the fact that certain actors, internal or external, have more influence over policy making than others. However, this thinking is fundamentally still predicated on the insider–

outsider dichotomy because governments were traditionally believed to have greater control over internal actors than external ones. However, Halligan (1995) points out that some actors in every category (usually the internal actors) were more prone to government control than others and were therefore more likely to provide recommendations that decision-makers would find acceptable. However, compared to an "outside" actor, those "inside" government advisers enjoy a lesser degree of independence and autonomy (Craft and Wilder, 2017).

However, as Halligan acknowledges, location can provide a relatively limited amount of insight and explanation into the dynamics of a policy advisory system (Wilson 2006). For instance, location does not explain why some NGOs or other external agents have more or less influence, or why certain public servants or units are more effective than others. A drawback of Halligan's location-based approach is that it created a false dichotomy and ignored the possibility that policy actors could play both insider and outsider roles. As Howlett and Migone (2013) noted drawing on the work of Czarniawska and Mazza (2003), while some policy actors (such as paid consultants) may be regarded as external advisers, they function in a liminal space.

In addition, Halligan's theory of government control was predicated on the relatively rigid rationality theory, which holds that legislators intentionally and consciously mould the demand for policy advice (e.g. by publicly criticizing public service). On the other hand, Manwaring (2019) argues that the literature on network governance can help to deepen our understanding of government control in the sense that network governance approaches have replaced direct government control and action and as a result, the government's responsibility has turned to 'steering' rather than 'rowing' (Osborne and Gaebler, 1992). The main contention is that networks have replaced (or added to) markets and hierarchies as a means of securing policy agendas, and that this has resulted in a more fragmented work environment for the government. But the government can still use mechanisms of political demand management and control, even in the face of this dispersion and fragmentation of policy actors. The governance literature adds value by deepening our comprehension of the mechanisms through which government authority is expanded in a PAS. Network and participatory governance are perceived as being more horizontal, despite the fact that certain instances indicate that the "shadow of hierarchy" is present (Manwaring, 2019, p. 276). Halligan, on the other hand, identified a more conventional "command and control" style of government as the source of government control.

4.5.2 Externalization of Policy Advice

The concept of "externalization" describes how non-governmental actors are becoming more important in systems that advise policy. The bureaucracy has long been regarded as the most influential actor in policy advice studies in many Western government systems, despite significant empirical variation in the actual configuration of policy advisory systems across sectors and jurisdictions (Aberbach, Putnam and Rockman, 1983; Meltsner, 1976 in Howlett and Wellstead, 2011; Page, 1992). Nevertheless, in the last 20 years, a number of external advisors have challenged the bureaucrats' fundamental status as the most trusted (and therefore most powerful) advisors.

Thus, the increased participation and the use of external experts as providers of policy advice has challenged the position of that internal advisors have held vis-à-vis government for many years. This has given rise to the widespread belief that, in contrast to earlier times, a large portion of policy advice is now "externalized" (Bevir and Rhodes, 2001; Bevir, Rhodes, and Weller, 2003; Howlett and Lindquist, 2004; Mayer, van Daalen and Bots, 2004). Many authors propose that internal advisory processes and capacities may be fully replaced by outside sources of expertise (Boston, 1994; Dunleavy, 1995; Peters, 1996; Vesley, 2013). Not going as far as this claim, Diamond (2020) has argued that the deinstitutionalization of policy making has marginalised the civil service. Others, however, take a different viewpoint as they perceived this external expertise and advice as an asset to the civil service rather than a rival (Connell et al, 2023). Further, a healthy policy-research community outside of government can, as Anderson (1996) argued, play a vital role in enhancing public understanding and debate of policy issues and can act as a natural complement to policy capacity within government.

While some emphasise the shifting power distribution between external and internal advisors vis-à-vis the government, other urge caution as external advisors are structurally unlikely to enjoy the same access to decision makers in government and may only sometimes, in isolated cases, be able to exert more influence than internal advisors. This is because outsiders are often excluded from the deliberative processes in government so that their contribution is minimal or ignored (Van der Heijden and Ten Heuvelhof, 2012; Eversole, 2010, Sapeha et al, 2020). Further, other studies show that government policy workers do not interact much outside of their close work circle (Wellstead and Stedman, 2011; Howlett and Wellstead, 2011).

The rise of so-called "wicked" policy problems have weakened the public sector's perceived capacity to address modern policy issues. As a result, there has been a decrease in the demand

for advice from governmental sources and a corresponding rise in the demand for advice from nongovernmental sources (Peters and Savoie, 2000). Meltsner (1990) was among the scholars who discussed the hybrid nature of policy advisory system as he argued that the system of policy advice that provides governments with information is extremely complex and comprises a wide range of information sources, including close advisors, spouses, and friends. This supply network is made up of sources from both inside and outside the government, including political advisors attached to ministers' offices and central agencies, as well as professional policy analysts working in departments and agencies (Boston 1994; Boston et al., 1996). Research conducted across several polities has found that governments have become more permeable to a multitude of non-governmental providers of policy advice. In fact, the number of alternative sources outside of government that politicians and civil servants have access to is constantly growing (Eichbaum and Shaw, 2007a). These sources include advocacy groups, think tanks, consulting firms, policy researchers in academia, consultants from the private sector and experts from think tanks, universities, political parties, lobbyists, less formal or professional advice from coworkers, friends, and family non-governmental actors in NGOs, scientific, technical, and legal experts (Dobuzinskis, Howlett and Laycock, 2007; Eichbaum and Shaw, 2007a; Maley, 2000; Craft and Howlett, 2013; Craft and Howlett, 2012; Plowden, 1987; Howlett, 2009; Bakvis, 2000, Tiernan, 2011; Hussain, Tsang and Rafique, 2023).

4.5.3 The Politicization of Policy Advice

The concept of politicization is used to describe the growing importance of overtly political factors in advisory procedures that elected politicians demand in an effort to retake control of the government apparatus following the New Public Management (NPM) caused fragmentation (Dahlström, Peters and Pierre, 2011). Such advice is typically given by partisan ministerial advisors who are close to the minister. An increasing amount of research over the past ten years has revealed that these advisors, who go by various titles like special advisors or exempt staff, have increased in quantity and importance in many Western jurisdictions (Hustedt, 2018). The increased media's involvement in covering policy making related news, think tanks' partisan alignment, and political parties' policy work are some of the factors contributing to this trend. Politicians may use advice because they believe it will legitimize or support their preexisting policies, win over voters, or even influence divisive policy discussions. (Connaughton, Rice and Shaw, 2023).

It is worth keeping in mind that formal politicization in PAS outside of the Anglo-Saxon administrative tradition is a long-standing and ingrained characteristic of many administrations

(Hustedt, 2019; Connaughton and Devane, 2023). The unique and ever-changing policy roles that advisors play stem from their position in the government and the emerging challenges of the modern policymaking environment (Scott, 2005). The intersection of the horizontal links between policy actors, including interest groups, policy experts, senior department officials, cabinet ministers, and other stakeholders involved in policy making, is where advisers are situated. They participate in a minister's mutual relationships with other actors in policy and serve as informational intermediaries in these relationships (Maley, 2000). A related point is that this emphasizes the idea that influence in advisory systems goes beyond closeness and governmental control. Members of advisory systems can exert influence not only through their content-based policy advice but also through their procedural ability to draw from other sources of policy advice. That is, influence can result from members of the advisory system's capacity to influence policy recommendations in a favourable or unfavourable way, or from their capacity to do so for a variety of administrative, political, or partisan reasons. Advisors have access to two crucial resources because of their location: relationships and information. They possess knowledge of stakeholder positions and interests, as well as access to agendas and policy opportunities. They have connections to important figures in the executive branch and the larger political landscape. They have the ability to control information owed to the minister in addition to the authority of the minister in their interactions with others (Maley, 2000).

Some scholars express concerns about the politicization and erosion of public service capacity tinged with unease about the state of advice-giving (Craft and Wilder, 2017) while others contend that the current trend of politicization in policy work has weakened the overall capacity for policy making. The threat that political advisors pose to the impartiality of Westminster-style civil services has been discussed extensively, and much of it with fear (e.g. Eichbaum and Shaw, 2008). Concerns have been raised in both Ireland and the UK that the increasing power of special advisers may, if it has not already, politicize the policy-making process by reducing the importance of civil servants (Connaughton, 2005; Connaughton, 2006; Mountfield 2002; Neill 2000). Warnings were also voiced about the possibility of improper overthrow of executive authority due to political advisers' special access to ministers (United Kingdom Parliament, 2001; Wicks, 2002). Meanwhile, a commentary in Australia referred to political advisers as the "junk-yard attack dogs of the political system" (Weller 2002, p. 72).

Nevertheless, politicization is not exclusive to these actors as it has been debated by (McGann and Johnson, 2005; Rich, 2004). Craft and Howlett (2013) who contend that because of their potential partisan alignment and the way governments use them to garner support for political

policy agendas or existing policy preferences, nongovernmental sources of policy advice, like think tanks (Pautz, 2007, 2010, 2013), have also come to be seen as agents of politicization (Peters and Pierre, 2004)). Bleiklie and Michelsen (2022) contend that politicization manifests in the use of partisan political advice within government; the development of political acumen; the rise in the number and positions of political appointees in the executive branch; and the employment of ministerial advisors to assist elected officials. Further research (Eichbaum and Shaw, 2011; Gains and Stoker, 2011; Maley, 2011) has also highlighted the significant role that “political” advisers can play in the brokerage, coordination, and integration of diverse endogenous and exogenous sources of policy advice to decision makers (Craft and Howlett, 2013).

Despite the above-mentioned claims, there are some advantages associated with the recruitment of political appointees and special advisors. Eichbaum and Shaw (2007b) argued that the use of advisers is a reaction to the challenges that contemporary governments frequently encounter in managing the machinery of government. It also aligns with, and plays a role in, the dissolution of the public service's once near-monopoly on the provision of advice to ministers. In addition, advisors can help distinguish between issues that are partisan and those that belong in the proper purview of career public servants and should be the subject of free, frank, and fearless advice. They can also address the political aspects of policy discussions both inside and between parties. Overall, potential help in enhancing government responsiveness in terms of politics and policy can be provided by political advisers.

However, studies show that advisors' actions can reveal challenges in dealing with the minefield of duties that exists in the administrative and political shadowlands (Eichbaum and Shaw, 2010; Tiernan, 2007). Therefore, in terms of the structure and functionality of political-administrative relations, one could argue that advisers present both a problem and a solution (Connaughton, 2017). Further, the policy process has been described as pluralistic by a wide range of actors so which seems to provide a way to increase the inclusion of voices from actors and interests and democratize the process (Sapeha et al, 2020). It is important to remember, though, that the presumed diversity of non-governmental policy actors only serves to mirror the unequal distribution of resources and power in larger society. It has been praised that evidence-based policy making (EBPM) is becoming more popular as a way to ensure that "what works" checks narrow interests and depoliticize policy formulation. However, knowledge and evidence are entwined in a web of power dynamics (Sapeha et al, 2020).

4.5.4 Shifting the Focus from Content to Location

The locational model emphasizes that insiders and outsiders create and supply significantly different advisory products. However, as Craft and Howlett (2012) contend, advisory content is useful further conceptual dimension that helps to understand policy advice influence in increasingly complex and pluralistic advisory systems.

According to Hustedt (2018), incorporating the concept of "content" into the analysis of policy advice enables a more accurate conceptualization of advisory practices and specifically accounts for modifications to governance structures. For many years, the field of policy analysis was dominated by the "positivist" or "modern" approach, as noted by Radin (2000). This approach frequently assumed a clear conceptual distinction between non-governmental actors who lacked technical skills and knowledge and internal governmental advisors who possessed technical knowledge and expertise. Such a "political" vs. "technical" advisory dichotomy, though frequently implicit, frequently supports location models. It is assumed that advice becomes more technical as it approaches decision-makers in close proximity, with external actors offering political advice and internal actors offering technical ideas and alternatives. It is arguable whether or not there was ever a strict separation between political and technical advice, even in "speaking truth to power" systems, but it is undeniable that governments no longer have the exclusive right to provide technical advice, if at all (Hustedt, 2018).

When merely locational factors are considered when modelling the structure and behaviour of policy advisory systems, such patterns would remain undetectable. However, the concept and the models used to describe it are greatly enhanced when content is added. It does this, among other things, by bringing studies of governance shifts and policy advice and formulation closer together. Further, incorporating a content dimension into more traditional locational models demonstrates how governments have shifted from command and control to interactive, collaborative, and policy-making models. This has resulted in changes to governance and policy-making networks, as well as changes to the nature of policy advice and policy formulation (Scott, 2005). Rethinking locational models of policy advisory systems that rely on government control as a crucial aspect of policy formulation analysis is necessary in these sorts of situations (Craft and Howlett, 2012).

4.5.6 Role Perceptions

Connaughton (2010a, 2010b), working within the empirical framework of the Irish context, developed a set of what she terms “role perceptions”, Expert, partisan, coordinator, and minder, a set of conceptualizations for the policy advisors’ roles, explicitly addressing the content dimensions of policy advice. Her analysis of the activities of these various actors is based, notably, not on whether the advice was partisan or administrative, but rather on whether it involved substantive on-the-ground policy formulation/implementation activities, ranging from “policy advice” to “policy steering”, or more procedural “communications” functions, which could be “technical/managerial” or “political”. These distinctions resurrect some aspects of the debunked politics vs. administration dichotomies. This idea of separating content in terms of substance and process is in line with other studies examining the “politicization of policy making”, such as Eichbaum and Shaw’s work (2008). However, Connaughton’s model has drawbacks, primarily because it is unable to distinguish the two concepts in a way that is mutually exclusive. Important advisory work that falls under the “expert” category may also be “partisan”, and procedural policy advisory roles like coordinator may be both expert and partisan at the same time.

Nevertheless, in his research on Australian Royal Commissions (2006a) and more broadly (2006b), Prasser made a distinction between two sorts of advice "hot" advice, which is short-term and crisis-driven, and "cold" advice, which is usually long-term and proactive. The author further stresses that neither partisan nor civil service actors have a monopoly on any particular type of advice and that applying these “hot” vs. “cold” content dimensions to different non-governmental sources of policy advice would align policy advisory activity considerations with particular content considerations instead of role-based classifications that remain dependent on locational factors and/or conventional dichotomies like political vs. technical distinctions.

4.5.8 Policy Ideational Compatibility

Craft and Wilder (2017) provide a typology of policy advisory networks based on two key concepts, compatibility and access and develop four types of ideational compatibility for policies. The authors argued that by substituting "accessibility" for first-wave spatial considerations, one can effectively shift the focus from locational issues to an examination of whether policy advice has access to the relevant policy subsystem, or more specifically, how receptive a policy subsystem may be to policy advice. Considering that early advisory system

theory linked institutional arrangements such as presidential or parliamentary political systems to access opportunities, this is not a radical break from the earlier approaches. It was generally suggested that the former was more "open," with the US presidential system serving as an example, and the latter was more "closed," with the UK's parliamentary system serving as an example (Plowden, 1987).

Based on the Swedish case study conducted by Nohrstedt (2011), Craft and Wilder (2017) argued that the locational considerations of internal versus external policy advice supply become moot in policy fields that are closed, such as in policy domains like national security which are frequently restricted to specific sets of participants, as opposed to policy fields that more accessible, such as tourism (Nohrstedt, 2011). This bolsters the case for emphasizing accessibility. Distributional issues regarding "internal to government" supply may still be investigated, but this time the inquiry should go beyond locating the available internal supply and asking questions about how it is acquired within subsystems (Craft and Wilder, 2017).

When policy subsystems are highly compatible with the advisory components and are "open" to receiving policy advice, collaborative advisory networks are likely to arise. In other words, cooperation in this case might entail several advisory elements working together as well as with the components of the dominant policy subsystem (public service, interest group, citizen advisory boards, etc.). A subsystem that was receptive to policy advice would cooperate with an advisory network, which was also open to cooperation between its constituents (such as interest groups, governments, and small enterprises) in the course of policy work (Craft and Wilder, 2017).

Compatibility among adviser and advisee has been central to advisory system scholarship (Plowden, 1987). To facilitate a deeper examination of the origins and trends of influence among the component parts of advisory systems, Craft and Wilder (2017) have developed four archetypes of policy ideational compatibility based on advisory content, issue type, advisory purpose, and relational considerations (Halffman and Hoppe, 2005; Fleischer, 2009; Craft and Howlett, 2013).

4.6 Relevance and Application of Key Concepts to the Study

The significance of these concepts in the research lies in helping the researcher formulate and identify his or her worldview regarding the phenomenon under investigation (Grant and Osanloo, 2014). It highlights the benefits of a research topic, the researcher's presumptions, the scholars with whom the researcher agrees and disagrees, and the way in which the researcher

conceptually grounds his or her approach (Evans, 2007). According to Akintoye (2015), researchers primarily employ conceptual frameworks when pre-existing theories are insufficient or inappropriate for providing a solid framework for their research (Adom, Hussein and Agyem, 2018). In this study, the two countries have different ruling systems with different political backgrounds. While Scotland may fall under the traditional Westminster models, Algeria does not. This makes the application of a single conceptual framework on both countries an unfair advantage. Further, the study spans over twenty years. Algeria in the first decade of this historical period can be classified under the previously explained mode of governance referred to as sharing truth with power, with a strict elitist policy making model where few and selected figures of the Algerian government led the country. These political arrangements also meant and led to specific uses of research (section 2), which will be further discussed in the findings' chapters. In the second decade, Algeria started, reluctantly, to embrace the new governance model, sharing truth to influence, or at least move towards a more "hybrid" model. Such shift marked also the move towards a more open policy making environment allowing more policy advice channels to operate. This view was highlighted by Craft and Howlett (2013) as the scholars argued while many jurisdictions' current policy advisory practices may be characterized by the "sharing truth with multiple actors of influence" model, other countries, such as developing nations, may continue to function under the "speaking truth to power" or some other hybrid form. The conceptual frameworks also discuss these two models of advice giving and receiving as previously mentioned in this chapter (Speaking truth to power and sharing influence). The two models will also add another layer to the research as they both correspond to the political systems and their respective levels of openness and closeness when dealing with policy advice and have an indirect influence on the organization of networks. Speaking of which, these policy making models are all explained in the first section, and as put by Hahn (1987), instead of looking at these models as separate conceptualization of the policy making process, it is more useful to perceive them as representations of the political system from various viewpoints and vantage points.

As we will be noted in the findings chapters (6, 7 and 8), these concepts help in the theoretical analysis of several issues such as the advisory system by first categorizing advisory actors as either internal or external to the government and determining the level of control that the government can exercise over them. Further, the processes of externalization and politicization which have played a significant role in shaping the evolution of policy advisory systems as discussed above are also examined to comprehend how the political advisory systems have

adjusted to a new setting for decision-making, where fresh sources of counsel surface, in Algeria and Scotland to eventually determine the extent of government control exerted on them in both countries.

4.7 Conclusion

Relevant concepts in the field of policy making were analysed in this chapter. This discussion was organised so that four concept categories emerged. The first concept is that of the policy making model. Seven sub-categories were discussed here: rationalism, pluralist strategy, elitism, stages model, institutionalism, and incrementalism. Secondly, the policy network was discussed, comprising four sub concepts: issue networks, policy communities, epistemic communities, and the advocacy coalition framework. Research and evidence utilisation was the third concept, with seven sub-concepts: knowledge-driven use, problem-solving function, interactive use, political use, tactical use, enlightenment, and social intellectual enterprise. With nine sub concepts, the fifth concept discussed was that of the policy advisory system. Here, location and government control and location; externalization of policy advice; politicization of policy advice; role perceptions; hot and cold policy advice; short-term reactive versus long-term anticipatory advice; and policy ideational compatibility were outlined as sub concepts. The review of these concepts proved that the field of policy advice is a complex and evolutionary one, with new concepts being added every few years. These concepts will underpin the research on policy advice in Algeria and Scotland as evidenced in the findings' chapters by providing the right lenses for the analysis.

Chapter 5

Research Methodology

5.1 Introduction

This study explores how policy advice from a range of actors has shaped higher education policymaking in Algeria and Scotland between 1999 and 2020. It examines the dynamics of expertise, influence, and institutional context in two distinct policy environments, aiming to generate comparative insights into the role of knowledge and actors in policy development. Building on the set research objectives and research questions detailed in chapter 1, this chapter discusses the research methodology devised for the conduct of this study. First, it presents the philosophical underpinnings of this research by explaining the choice of the research paradigm. Once the epistemological, ontological, axiological, and methodological stances of the researcher are clear, the following section explores case study, generally, and comparative case studies, specifically, as the selected qualitative research method for the thesis. The next section? deals with the data collection tools, including in-depth semi-structured interviews and document analysis. Here, also the sampling methods and the process of conducting a pilot study to check the feasibility of the research are discussed. Further, the chapter discusses the data analysis process with thematic analysis designated for interviews and document analysis for documents. Then, any issues around trustworthiness in qualitative research are explored, including dependability, credibility, confirmability, and transferability. The chapter concludes with a discussion of ethical considerations around qualitative research, mainly informed consent, privacy and confidentiality, and anonymity in addition to the limitations of the study.

5.2 The Research Paradigm

Guba and Lincoln (1994) define a paradigm as a basic set of beliefs or worldview that guides research action or an investigation. Similarly, Denzin and Lincoln (2000) define paradigms as human constructions, which deal with first principles or ultimate indicating where the researcher is coming from to construct meaning embedded in data. Paradigms are thus important because they provide beliefs and dictates, which, for scholars in a particular discipline, influence what should be studied, how it should be studied, and how the results of the study should be interpreted. The paradigm defines a researcher's philosophical orientation, and this has significant implications for every decision made in the research process, including

choice of methodology and methods (Kivunja and Kuyini, 2017). A paradigm is thus a comprehensive belief system, world view, or framework that guides research and practice in a field.

The choice of the research paradigm has methodological ramifications that affect research questions, participant selection, data collection tools and procedures, and data analysis (Kivunja and Kuyini, 2017). In other words, there is a critical relationship between paradigm and methodology. The interpretivist paradigm, for instance, is compatible with research methodologies and techniques that generate and analyse qualitative data (Kivunja and Kuyini, 2017).

In the social sciences, there are several competing paradigms. Some propose that there are two paradigms, quantitative and qualitative. However, this may be an oversimplification that emphasizes data rather than foundational beliefs and assumptions (Willis, 2012). The exact number of world views (paradigms) and the names associated with a particular paradigm vary from author to author, but one generally accepted list includes three paradigms (Cupchik, 2019; Gephart, 1999; Greene, Benjamin and Goodyear, 2001; Guba, 1990; Smith, 1989): post-positivism, critical theory, and interpretivism.

Different paradigms inherently contain differing ontological and epistemological views; therefore, they have differing assumptions of reality and knowledge underpinning their particular research approach. This is reflected in their methodology and methods (Scotland, 2012). This research adopts an interpretivist approach. The central endeavour of the interpretivist paradigm is to understand the subjective world of human experience (Guba and Lincoln, 1989). Interpretivism strives to ‘get into the head of the subjects being studied’ and to understand and interpret what the subject is thinking or the meaning s/he is making of the context (Kivunja and Kuyini, 2017). Emphasis is placed on understanding the individual and their interpretation of the world around them. The key tenet of the interpretivist paradigm is that reality is socially constructed (Bogdan and Biklen, 1998) – for this reason, this paradigm is at times referred to as Constructivism. In this paradigm, theory does not precede research but follows it so that it is grounded on the data generated by the research act. This paradigm assumes a subjectivist epistemology, a relativist ontology, a balanced axiology, and naturalist methodology (Kivunja and Kuyini, 2017). These elements are briefly explained below.

5.2.1 Ontological Position: Relativism

Ontology is the study of being (Crotty, 1998; Levers, 2013). Ontological assumptions are concerned with what constitutes reality and research methods differ as a consequence of differing ontological assumptions. The ontological position of interpretivism is relativism – the view that reality is subjective, mediated by the individual's senses, and therefore differs from person to person (Guba and Lincoln, 1994). Reality is individually constructed; there are as many realities as individuals. Language does not passively label objects but actively shapes and moulds reality (Frowe, 2001). Thus, reality is constructed through the interaction between language and aspects of an independent world (Scotland, 2012).

5.2.2 Epistemological Position: Subjectivism

Every research paradigm is based upon its own ontological and epistemological assumptions (Scotland, 2012). Epistemology is concerned with the nature and forms of knowledge and of knowing (Cohen, Manion and Morrison, 2007; Scotland, 2012). Epistemological assumptions are concerned with how knowledge can be created, acquired and communicated, in other words what it means to know. Guba and Lincoln (1994, p. 108) explain that epistemology asks the, what the nature of the relationship between the would-be knower and what can be known is. Epistemology has been debated among social scientists and others. Here, the focus has been on two sharply contrasting views of how social science research should be conducted: positivism and social constructionism ((Easterby-Smith, Thorpe and Jackson, 2012).

The epistemology underlying interpretivism is that of subjectivism. Here, the world does not exist independently of our knowledge of it (Grix, 2004). Meaning is not discovered; it is constructed through the interaction between consciousness and the world (Crotty, 1998). To experience a world is to participate in it, simultaneously moulding and encountering it (Heron and Reason, 1997). Intentionality refers to the interaction between consciousness and phenomena. Regarding the same phenomenon, different people may construct meaning in different ways (Crotty, 1998), but truth is a consensus formed by co-constructors (Pring, 2000, p. 251). Therefore, knowledge has the trait of being culturally derived and historically situated. Knowledge and meaningful reality are constructed in and out of interaction between humans and their world and are developed and transmitted in a social context (Crotty, 1998, p. 42). Therefore, the social world can only be understood from the standpoint of individuals who are participating in it (Cohen, Manion and Morrison, 2007, p. 19). Further, interpretivism aims to bring into consciousness hidden social forces and structures (Scotland, 2012).

5.2.3 Axiological Position: Balanced

Constructivists assert that, since reality is mind constructed and mind dependent and knowledge subjective, social inquiry is in turn value-bound and value-laden. You are inevitably influenced by your values, which inform the paradigm you choose for inquiry, the choice of topic you study, the methods you choose to collect and analyse data, how you interpret the findings and the way you report the findings. As a constructivist researcher, you admit the value-laden nature of the study and report your values and biases related to the topic under study that may interfere with neutrality (Kawulich and Chilisa, 2012).

5.2.4 Methodological Position: Naturalistic

A methodology is the strategy or plan of action which lies behind the choice and use of particular methods (Crotty, 1998). Thus, methodology is concerned with why, what, from where, when and how data is collected and analysed. Guba and Lincon (1994) explain that methodology asks the question: how can the inquirer go about finding out whatever they believe can be known? In assuming a naturalist methodology, the researcher utilises data gathered through interviews, discourses, text messages and reflective sessions, with the researcher acting as a participant observer (Kivunja and Kuyini, 2017). Interpretive methodology is directed at understanding phenomena from an individual's perspective, investigating interaction among individuals as well as the historical and cultural contexts which people inhabit (Creswell, 2009, p. 8). Examples of methodology include case studies (in-depth study of events or processes over a prolonged period), phenomenology (the study of direct experience without allowing the interference of existing preconceptions), hermeneutics (deriving hidden meaning from language), and ethnography (the study of cultural groups over a prolonged period). Individual constructs are elicited and understood through interaction between researchers and participants (Guba and Lincon, 1994) with participants being relied on as much as possible (Creswell, 2009). Events are not reduced to simplistic interpretations; new layers of understanding are uncovered as phenomena are thickly described. Interpretive theory is usually grounded (inductive), being generated from the data, not preceding it (Cohen, Manion and Morrison, 2007). Interpretivists acknowledge that value free knowledge is not possible. For example, researchers assert their beliefs when they choose what to research, how to research and how to interpret their data (Edge and Richards, 1998).

5.3 Research Design

5.3.1 Research Approach: Qualitative

In a broad sense, any kind of social inquiry that primarily relies on verbal, non-numeric data is considered qualitative research or inquiry. This includes all textual analyses, including content, discourse, conversation, and narrative analyses (Jackson, Drummond and Camara, 2007). The present study adopts the qualitative approach for several reasons. First, according to Borzel (1997), the qualitative approach focuses less on the mere structure of interaction between actors and more on the content of these interactions using qualitative methods such as in-depth interviews and content and discourse analysis, which represents an asset for this study. Second, qualitative research challenges positivist "rules" and attempts to accept different realities by examining a limited number of in-depth cases. However, these procedures may be criticized for being arbitrary, subjective, biased, and value laden (Cavana, Delahaye and Sekaran, 2001; Creswell, 2014; Neuman, 2005; O'Leary, 2017). Third, as mentioned earlier in this paragraph, the qualitative approach is in harmony with the interpretivist paradigm chosen for the study.

This study adopted the qualitative approach because of its focus on comprehending the different aspects of the issue being studied to generate comprehensive and illustrative data to comprehend the different aspects of the issue being studied (Almeida, Faria and Queirós, 2017).

The goal of qualitative research is to better understand a particular issue, rather than focusing on numerical representativity. Thus, qualitative research focuses on understanding and explaining the dynamics of social relations while addressing aspects of reality that cannot be quantified. The overarching objective of the qualitative approach is (Almeida, Faria and Queirós, 2017). Further, the choice of a qualitative approach allowed the interpretation of the meanings of participants' actions and the generation of a thorough (detailed) account of their feelings, opinions, and experiences (Denzin, 1989). These accounts along the close interaction between the researcher and participants that qualitative methods require eventually enabled the researcher to gain a more comprehensive understanding of the setting and the context in which policy expertise were used to shape the higher education landscape in Algeria and Scotland (Sallee and Flood, 2012). Further, the qualitative approach gave the researcher the flexibility to adapt her way of thinking throughout the research and reframe some of the research questions as the research progresses (Creswell, 2007).

For this study, one disadvantage associated with qualitative research is its disability to generalize findings and although it has been demonstrated that qualitative research can enhance

and inform practitioners' and policymakers' decisions. When discussing how to incorporate research into practice, qualitative research is usually disregarded since quantitative methods are more easily utilized than qualitative ones (Sallee and Flood, 2012).

5.3.2 The Rationale Behind the Comparative Method

The decision to conduct a comparative analysis of policymaking within higher education in Algeria and Scotland is grounded in conceptual drives and methodological considerations as it seeks to analyse a parallel phenomenon, Policy advice and its influence over HE policy, in two distinct political, institutional, historical, and socioeconomic settings. The comparative approach aims at unravelling how policy advice is generated, transmitted and received by the wider policy communities of Algeria and Scotland.

The government systems under which Algeria and Scotland operate, their policy making historical trajectories, and institutional configurations differ significantly. Algeria, a country governed through a top-down centralized approach is put against Scotland's devolved system with its consultative approach that still operates under the broader UK policy structure. These divergence in governance systems and policymaking styles offer a fertile ground for comparison because despite their differences the two countries share, to a certain extent, the same type of policy actors, advisory forums, and they both prioritize their higher education systems through the attentive reforms and development schemes.

Further, Algeria represents a thinly researched Global South context, where evidence-based policymaking and policy advice research are in their preliminary phases. Scotland, on the other hand, is a sample of a well-documented case in a western democracy context, with a mature consultation process and a far-reaching stakeholder engagement. The comparison of these two contrasting cases will contribute to shifting the focus of policy advice to settings beyond the Anglo-American paradigms to provide original reflections on how power, authority, expertise, and networks come together to shape higher education policy in the two settings.

The comparative nature of the study is grounded in the theoretical and conceptual integration of a set of policy process theories (please refer to chapter 5). These theories explain how we compare different policy systems by looking at how they are structured, how power is shared

between advice-giving groups (supply) and decision-makers (demand), and how the advice is accepted, questioned, or ignored. The combination of conceptual frameworks and theories follows Gupta's (2012) logic who advances the view that synthesising comparative approaches with policy process theories enhances the analytical depth of research through identifying the applicability of these concepts and theories across diverse institutional settings.

The aim behind this comparative analysis is far from identifying who is the best at negotiating policy advice or whose higher education system is the best, but rather to understand how policy advice influence is shaped by political, institutional, and even historical circumstances and how this advice is communicated to the government, and how the government handle this advice. The comparative method determines when policy advice is peripheral or significant depending on the choices available, the political environment, the stakeholders involved and the government of the day. Finally, drawing on both a case that has been supported by extensive evidence (Scotland) and under-researched (Algeria) case allows the study to bring new empirical data as well as enter longstanding debates.

5.3.3 Comparative Governance and Policymaking

Policymaking is broadly seen the purposeful process led by governments, which entail decisions about how and if public authority and governmental resources should be used to address specific societal issues. Governments are often faced with the decision of defining the scope of their involvement placing themselves along a continuum that spans from minor to major participation (Vogel and Henstra, 2015). This involvement is further shaped by neoliberal reforms and globalization forces that have redefined the role of the state triggering a shift from government to governance, a shift marking a transition from rigid, top-down bureaucratic systems towards more flexible, interconnected forms of organization that also have implications on the relationship between the state and civil society fostering broader engagement and collaboration. Further, Unlike government, governance is tied to a move from a dependency on formal legislative processes to more adaptable and informal methods of regulation and policy implementation (Palumbo, 2017).

A great deal of the policy literature oriented towards governance seeks to improve the state's aptitude to manage the markets, bureaucracies, and networks that have expanded significantly since the 1980s. This view treats these configurations as stable structures that governments can regulate through proper policy instruments (Bevir, Rhodes and Weller, 2003).

In this context, it is noteworthy to highlight that despite the wide use of the governance as a term in both political science and across the social sciences., there is still a misunderstanding in the use and application of the term which can be at times contradictory (Peters and Pierre, 2016). Despite the issues revolving around the complexity of the term, a basic consensus does exist . First, the term reflects a new style of governing built upon the principle of cooperation across the public and private sectors. Second, the concept blur the conventional boundaries and what were once regarded as exclusive functions of the state are addressed as common and broad societal challenges that require input from a diverse sets of actors instead of the traditional formal political institutions (Nag, 2018).

Rhodes (1996) further notes that the term governance stretches over various meanings including the minimal state, corporate governance, new public management, good governance, systems-based social analysis, and self-organizing networks. For more precision, he defines governance as self-organizing, interorganizational networks that function alongside markets and hierarchies as essential mechanisms for allocating resources, exercising control, and ensuring coordination. Further elaborating this, Rhodes (1997) who defines governance through the lenses of public administration and public policy, identifies four core aspects related to the concept. First, interdependence is a dominant feature binding various organizations beyond the government to include non state actors. Second, these networks share ongoing interactions motivated by mutual resource exchange and a need to come to terms with their shared agendas. Third, these discussions are dominated by game-like features, and founded on mutual trust and regulated by mutually accepted principles among the network members. Fourth, a prevailing aspect present in governance networks is the degree of autonomy they enjoy from the state as these networks are predominantly self-organizing and not directly accountable to the state.

More recently, Pierre and Peters (2020) associated governance with three well defined perspectives. The first focuses on the contribution of the state as a central key actor which can fluctuate from being the dominant coordinator to operating as one of many other influential actors. The scale of this involvement is dependent on the State's historical positioning and its institutional authority. The second perspective emphasises the role of non-state actors such as civil society groups, NGOs, businesses, advocacy coalitions, local and regional authorities, and even international bodies like the EU in shaping governance. These groups supply important resources, knowledge, and expertise owing to their significance in the process. This position, however, challenges the traditional role of the government. The third standpoint brings the first

and second views together as it suggests that governance is a mutual effort by both state and societal actors, though their relative influence varies by policy area. The emphasis in this view is not who governs but rather how broad governance can be prompting reflection on the ability of these actors to coexist. Making sense of the public policy calls for the comprehension of the complex interplay among institutions, policy actors, and processes. These elements operate within a broader context governed by culture, history and global influences. In this context, adopting a cross-national comparative lens provides valuable analytical insight (Prakash and Potoski, 2012).

Comparative policy analysis contributes to the expansion of policy research, formulation, and evaluation beyond the borderlines of one single jurisdiction and improving the society's policy solving problems capacities. Looking across national contexts widens the exploration scope of policy ideas and options to identify and differentiate the "policy repertoire", that is, the range of policy tools and strategies that have developed within different political systems (Anderson, 1971, p. 129). Countries, or other geographic units under study, have their own unique characteristics which result in discrepancies that offer a key rationale for the conduct of comparative research. Nevertheless, some new governance literature has a blind angle that overlooks the power variations attributed to the state when it presumes that the central government has a limited governing capacity (Peters, 2000).

It has been put forward that democratic governance in the western hemisphere is struggling with the issue of legitimacy which resulted in an increasing dependence on international comparisons and global indicators to reassure the public and reinforce the idea that comparisons are a credible source for the evidence needed for rational political decisions (Nóvoa and Yariv-Mashal, 2003).

Comparative political research underscores three main factors in explaining policy change: Actors' policy preferences, institutional frameworks, and information. Since institutions are usually characterized by stability and persistence over long periods of time, the primary reasons for policy change are often attributed to the shifts in the governing coalitions following elections. Yet, far from election, new information that enter the policymaking arena and the transformations in the socioeconomic conditions can also induce policy change. For this very reason, it remains imperative that researchers scrutinize the policy dynamics over extended periods and across a wide array of issues in multiple settings (Baumgartner, Jones, and Wilkerson (2011). In accordance with this view, Scharpf (2000) further stresses that policy

change takes place despite stagnant institutional settings, because of the change in the way policymakers think and value. An example provided by Scharpf is how the rise of neoliberalism over Keynesianism as ideological frameworks can reconfigure policy without the need for changing institutional structures. In his approach, actor-centered institutionalism, Scharpf (1997) also address the notions of preferences (What actors desire including power, financial gains, values) and perceptions (the actors' understanding of a given situation) as he highlights that these two constructs are influenced to a certain degree but never entirely dictated by institutions.

Despite its prominence, comparative policy research is marked by intrinsic complexity in terms of its design, organization, and execution especially when the study involves more than one country. The collection and analysis of data beyond national frontiers incite further logistical and analytical pressures. Moreover, when comparing policies and their outcomes, deeper issues can emerge cannot uncover all the deeper issues further complicating the process (Cyr and DeLeon, 1975). Furthermore, it is important to mention that the adoption of network-oriented approaches, more specifically the idea of governance without government, can overlook important aspects of governance structure when predominantly focusing on societal actors and their relationship with the state. Thus, research on comparative politics and governance attributes its development and progress to the construction of analytical frameworks that take into consideration institutions, processes, and geographic contexts (Peters, 2000).

Comparative policy studies require the careful processing of diverse and complex sets of data to generate sharper and well contextualized understandings of policy dynamics to ultimately deepen both academic understanding and enhance future policy makers' capacities to do better (Cyr and DeLeon, 1975). Despite the growth in comparative policy research. Gupta (2012) notes that there is a gap between comparative policy researchers and policy process theorists due to the disparities in language, concepts, and focus.

Regarding comparative research in higher education, which remains consistent with comparative work in other social science domains, it still can be lacking institutionalisation as a subfield but the international comparison in the field (Higher education) also promotes the dismantling of certain assumptions and core concepts (Teichler, 2014).

5.3.3 Research Method: Comparative Case study

This research adopted a comparative case study method. Generally speaking, a case study is described by Yin (2009) as an empirical investigation that looks at a phenomenon in its actual

setting. As Yin (2009) further points out, a case study is a research strategy or design that is used to examine a social unit rather than a technique for gathering data. A clear and thorough definition of the case study strategy is also provided by Creswell (2014, p. 241). More importantly, a case study is a qualitative design in which a programme, event, activity, process, or one or more people are thoroughly examined by the researcher (Priya, 2021).

Comparative case studies, on the other hand, examine two or more cases to generate more broadly applicable knowledge regarding causal questions, i.e., the how and why of specific programs or policies that succeed or fail. Over time, comparative case studies are conducted with an emphasis on comparison both within and between contexts (Goodrick, 2014). In this study, the comparative case study method enabled the researcher to put Algerian and Scottish higher education in a comparative setting in terms of how policy advice and expertise were used. In the two contexts, the input provided by the key policy actors was examined with the major differences and similarities highlighted. Further, the present study adopted case study design because the study's goal is to provide answers to "how" question as in how policy advice and expertise influenced the shaping of higher education policies in Algeria and Scotland and because the researcher wants to cover contextual conditions due to their relevance to the phenomenon being studied (Yin, 2003).

The choice of research methods can be traced back, through methodology and epistemology, to an ontological position. It is impossible to engage in any form of research without committing (often implicitly) to ontological and epistemological positions. Researchers' differing ontological and epistemological positions often lead to different research approaches towards the same phenomenon (Grix, 2004, p. 64). The interpretative paradigm, which emphasizes individual interpretations of subjective experiences, is what distinguishes qualitative research. Accordingly, a researcher's subjective opinions regarding a specific circumstance are crucial to the study's findings. The definition and features of case studies are closely related to the interpretative paradigm as a paradigmatic foundation of qualitative research. The nature of a case study is therefore more qualitative than quantitative (Starman, 2013). Yin (2003) and Stake (1995) both base their case study methodology on a constructivist paradigm. This method has the benefit of allowing participants to share their stories while fostering a close working relationship between the researcher and them (Crabtree and Miller, 1999). The researcher can gain a better understanding of the participants' actions by using the participants' stories to explain their perspectives on reality (Lather, 1992).

Baxter and Jack (2010) contend that after deciding that a qualitative case study is the most appropriate method for answering the research question and after defining the case and its parameters, the researcher needs to think about the kind of case study that will be carried out. The overall goal of the study will direct the choice of particular case study design. Is the researcher trying to investigate, characterize, or contrast cases? Diverse case studies are referred to by distinct terms by Yin (2003) who argues that Case studies are classified as descriptive, exploratory, or explanatory further distinguishes between multiple-case studies and single. A multiple or collective case study will enable the researcher to conduct cross-setting and within-setting analysis. In a multiple case study, we look at a number of cases to identify the commonalities and differences among them. While the evidence generated by this kind of research is generally regarded as strong and trustworthy, the process itself can be very costly and time-consuming (Baxter and Jack, 2010). Comparative case studies examine and synthesize the similarities, divergences, and trends between two or more cases with a similar objective. The unique characteristics of each case should be thoroughly described at the outset of the study in order to accomplish this (Goodrick, 2014).

Bartlett and Vavrus (2017) contend that investigating the global aspect of educational practice, research, or policy seeks to study through phenomena in three dimensions: horizontally, vertically, and transversally. To put it another way, a comparative case study is based on an emergent research design and a strong process orientation that seeks to trace the "what," "why," and "how" of phenomena as they emerge and change. The authors explain how the three axes and comparison are arranged as follows: horizontal comparison calls attention to the ways in which historical and modern processes have shaped the "cases," which can be created by concentrating on "people, groups of people, sites, institutions, social movements, partnerships, etc" (Bartlett and Vavrus 2017, P. 53). When conducting a comparative case study, it is necessary to include multiple cases at the same scale and pay attention to "valuable contextual information" about each case. Horizontal comparisons avoid pressing categories resulting from one case being similar to another.

On the other hand, vertical comparison entails analysing networks and their relationships at various scales rather than just comparing levels. Vertical comparison, for example, would take into account how actors at various scales respond differently to a policy issued at another level, such as the subnational or inter- or supranational level, in the study of policy making in a particular case. By "tracing the formation and appropriation of a policy" at various scales and "by tracing the processes by which actors and actants come into relationship with one another

and form non-permanent assemblages aimed at producing, implementing, resisting, and appropriating policy to achieve particular aims," it would be possible to determine what constitutes context in such a study (Bartlett and Vavrus, 2017). Furthermore, because space and time are inextricably linked, researching the historical evolution of the social phenomena under investigation in a case study not only "allows us to assess evidence and conflicting interpretations of a phenomenon," but also challenges our preconceived notions about them in the present (Bartlett and Vavrus, 2017). According to Bartlett and Vavrus (2017, p. 93), when discussing the transversal axis of comparison, social phenomena of interest in a case study must be viewed in the context of their historical development because these "historical roots" had an impact on them and "continue to reverberate into the present, affecting economic relations and social issues such as migration and educational opportunities." Thus, in order to comprehend a case, one must first "understand how it came to be in the first place."

Consistent with Bartlett and Vavrus (2017) views, the study paid close attention to these three axes by examining the historical context through which the phenomenon of expert policy advice was shaped, the actors' constellations involved in the production and dissemination of such policy advice and the historical roots as well.

5.4 Data collection: The Methods

Data for the study will be collected through the use of two complementary research tools, namely, in-depth semi structured interviews and document analysis. In fact, using a variety of data sources is a trademark of case study research and increases the credibility of the data (Patton, 1990; Yin, 2003). Documentation, archival records, interviews, physical artifacts, direct observations, and participant observation are a few examples of possible data sources. Instead of being handled separately during the analysis process, the data from these various sources are then combined in the case study. Every data source is a component of the puzzle, and each component helps the researcher comprehend the phenomenon as a whole. As the various data streams are interwoven to provide a deeper comprehension of the case, this convergence strengthens the research's conclusions (Baxter and Jack, 2010). Priya (2021) claims that case study research gives the researcher the flexibility to use any data collection method that best serves their goals because a thorough analysis is conducted (as long as the method is practical and ethical). A variety of data collection techniques are used for a sound, pure, and unbiased study of the phenomenon under investigation, including surveys,

questionnaires, in-depth interviews, participant and non-participant observation, and document analysis (whether of books, archival manuscripts, or audio-visual records). Interpretive methods also yield insight and understandings of behaviour, explain actions from the participant's perspective, and do not dominate the participants (Willis, 2007). Examples include open-ended interviews, focus groups, open-ended questionnaires, open-ended observations, think aloud protocol and role-playing. These methods usually generate qualitative data (Scotland, 2012). Furthermore, Rutledge and Hogg (2020) contend that interpretative qualitative techniques like the semi-structured interview have become more popular in the social sciences as a result of the recent evolution away from rigorous adherence to positivist methodologies and toward recognition of a post-positivist lens. Post-positivist methodologies acknowledge that the phenomena under investigation are frequently intricate and do not conform to a singular interpretation.

5.4.1 Semi-structured Interviews

The main source of data for the study were semi structured interviews with key informants (n41). The interviews questions (appendix 1) permitted a deeper understanding of the phenomenon of policy advice and expertise in Algeria and Scotland in the area of higher education policy making (1999-2020). Semi-structured interviews allowed the researcher to obtain detailed information, as well as to delve deeper into the. issues and consider new perspectives. Since interviews are conversational in nature, they also build rapport and make follow-up and clarification easier. In their turn, participants are free to share whatever they think is relevant. During the interviews, the interviewer paid close attention to the tone qualities and bodily signs during the interviews as highlighted by Rutledge and Hogg (2020). Focusing on the body language of the participants such as the nervous half smiles, the seat shifting, and messing with facial hair (beards) were all cues given by the participants to signal uneasiness when certain questions were asked. In this case, the researcher chose to press harder for more information without making the interviewees uncomfortable.

Irani (2019) says that despite the technical or Internet connection issues that could impair the quality of the audio recorded file and interview, as well as the voice and image clarity, and the fact that due to the connection issue, interviewers and participants might be preoccupied with resolving the issue instead of focusing on the conversation being held, Videoconferencing for qualitative interviews has many merits. It supplies researchers with more chances to connect

with geographically scattered participants as it lessens the geographic restrictions connected with in-person interviews. It saves both interviewers and participants time and money on travel. Additionally, videoconferencing provides participants with more scheduling choices and versatility to fit the interview into their hectic personal and professional schedules. Finally, because they are being interviewed in a familiar setting of their choosing, participants are usually more at ease. In addition to these benefits, videoconferencing makes it easier to collect both nonverbal and verbal data (although limited, from waist up), and researchers can view (and review) the participant's visual cues on their screen (Irani, 2019).

Conducting in-depth interviews via Internet-based tools did present some difficulties such as the quality of the connection. To mitigate these issues, the researcher made sure the quality of the internet connection was on point (one of the perks of conducting the data collection in Scotland), but not the same could be said about some participants (Algerian ones). When the participants seemed to be struggling with establishing a valid internet connection, the researcher made sure they stay calm, repeated some of the research questions more than once, and used the chat box available on Teams when the problem was audio related.

In Scotland, all interviews with participants were conducted in English. In Algeria, participants, were given the choice to use Arabic (official language in the country), French (widely used foreign language in government and academia since colonial days) or English (new foreign language being used to replace French). University and government officials preferred the French. This is mainly because, in addition to Arabic, that is the language used in the university administrative settings and at the ministry. University lecturers chose the English language because it was the language they used to teach. None of the participants used Arabic in their interviews. However, in Algeria, there were cases of code switching where Algerian participants would mix French or English with Derja (Arabic dialect). This was done when the participants seemed to struggle to find the right word or expression in French or English.

Questions were open ended allowing to allow more room for follow up questions. As highlighted in the appendix, the questions were divided into three themes. The first set of questions revolved around the interviewee's involvement in the policy processes. The second was about the other actors and networks that the interviewees interacted with or knew of (The bigger picture). The third was about the strategies and tactics of policy process influencing. The final ones were labelled concluding questions, which gave space to the interviewees to

elaborate on previous questions, add comments, and when possible, name other people to interview.

Interviews were conducted online, using Microsoft Teams and Zoom (apart from one interview, which was done via WhatsApp, and another two where answers were received via email. All these cases were following the Algerian participants' requests). In the case of email interviews, the researcher followed the guidelines found in the literature by sending the interview questions to the participants (n2) as explained in Meho (2006). The author further argues that researchers can interview multiple participants at once using email, as it eliminates the need for synchronous interview times. In terms of the amount of time needed to gather data from email interviews, the two participants emailed the researcher back within a week.

Interviews were audio and video recorded, and participants gave consent verbally prior to the interview. Transcription was done automatically thanks to the latest Teams and Zoom features. The researcher covered all questions during the interviews to make sure there was no words omitted, or misspelled as the software would sometimes mix some words. In the code-switching cases, it was necessary to do the transcription manually as the software could not keep up. The length of interviews largely depended on the participants' schedules, with some interviews lasting up to two hours and other only 30 minutes. Some of those who has shorter interviews offered additional information through email exchanges with the researcher after the interviews.

The researcher transcribed all the interviews, including the group interview. For the interviews initially transcribed by Teams or Zoom, the researcher edited the scripts for accuracy. During the interviews, the researcher made notes. Taking notes allowed the researcher to record her impressions as soon as they happen, including capturing relevant context of each interview that helped data analysis process. Taking notes also allowed self-reflection, bias detection and helped with initial coding of the key issues emerging from the interviews (Philippi and Lauderdale, 2017).

5.4.2 Documents

The study used a variety of documents including but not restricted to consultation papers, newspaper articles from the Herald, the Guardian, Echorouk, Elwatan; reports (both digital and physical) (A Blueprint for Fairness: The Final Report of the commission on Widening Access), official reports documenting parliamentary sessions (Official report: Meeting of Parliament 16th March 2011. Debate on HE funding); government's calls for evidence and the subsequent

submissions made by the different key stakeholders such as Universities Scotland, NUS Scotland, UNISON; briefings (Universities Scotland, SPICe Briefing); official correspondences (Convenor of Universities Scotland, Sir Pete Downes' letter to Education Secretary on the Higher Education Governance Bill), newsletters, political parties and student organizations manifestos (Scottish National Party Manifesto, 2011), guidance (The Scottish Code of Good HE Governance: Governance Code and Supporting Guidelines for Members of the Governing Bodies of Higher Education Institutions in Scotland. 1st edition), Speeches (a speech delivered by Scottish Secretary Alistair Carmichael, arguing for the Union and against independence, at Edinburgh University in 2014); Press releases (UCU Scotland press release opposing university governance code); conference papers; bulletin; summary of workshops; cooperation agreements. These documents offered contextual details and historical perspective on the issues investigated in this study and also provided additional information and in some cases helped clarify areas where interview provided little or no useful data (Bowen, 2009).

5.5 Participant Selection and Sample Size

The study followed purposive sampling procedures because the selection of participants was intentional based on their knowledge and experiences of policy making in their various countries. Purposive sampling was complemented by snow-balling technique where participants already involved in the study suggested other individuals in their networks to be involved in the study (Bhardwaj, 2019).

In qualitative studies, 'appropriate' sample size (i.e., how many interviews is enough,) remains a debatable issue (Dworkin, 2012). The 'right' sample size is dependent on things such as scope of the study, type of approach used, research design used, researcher's experience, time, available to conduct the study and expectations of study examiners (Onwuegbuzie and Collins, 2007; Sarfo et al., 2021). With these variables in mind, a researcher must decide that the sample size is not to be too small as to impede the generalisability or rigour of the study and at the same time the sample shouldn't be too big that it becomes challenging to undertake the study (Sandelowski, 1995).

Regarding sample size, the initial target for this research was 50 participants (25 participants for each country). When comparing the response rates in the two countries, Scottish participants had a 100 per cent response rate (i.e., n26). In Algeria, the response rate was relatively low at 60 per cent (i.e., n15). In Algeria, many people requested to take part in the

study were reluctant to accept and that some of those who agreed refrained from commenting on issues related to the micro-politics of policy making. This was despite the researcher's assurance that all participants will be anonymised. This is mainly due to the old belief that it was still prohibited to talk about political issues in Algeria.

In Case studies, researchers typically do not concentrate on cases involving a larger population. Sample sizes in case studies are usually small, as is the case with the majority of qualitative research designs (Hammarberg, Kirkman and De Lacey, 2016; Vasileiou et al.,2018). Determining the sample size for qualitative case studies is typically, if not always, a function of the researcher's definition of the case and its parameters (Gerring, 2004; Hyett, Kenny and Dickson-Swift, 2014). This was described as "bounding the case" by Yin (2018). According to Mills, Durepos and Wiebe (2009), a multiple case approach (multiple case studies and comparative case studies are used interchangeably throughout this thesis) is advised when the researcher wants to use contrasting observations to offer more context for claims and replication of the findings. Cases should be added to a multiple case study approach until theoretical and information saturation is achieved. Nevertheless, the number of participants in a multiple case study is not limited by any particular rule (Paré and Elam, 1997). For a multiple case study, some literature suggests utilizing four to fifteen cases. Too many cases in a multiple case study may compromise the depth of information needed, given the focus of case study design (Mills, Durepos and Wiebe, 2009; Sarfo et al, 2021). Below is the number and categories of participants in the present study. At this point, it is worth mentioning that since the study's span is twenty years (1999-2020), some of the participants changed jobs and even careers in this period. Therefore, the researcher decided to ask the participants about their past and current (at the time of the interview) affiliations.

Table 4.5.1: Categories of Participants in the Study

Algeria (n=15)	Scotland (n=26)
1. Government official (1)	1. Independent scholars (6)
2. University officials (4)	2. Student representatives (1)
3. Quality assurance officer (1)	3. Think Tank members (2)
4. University lecturers (3)	4. Member of Statutory organisations (SFC, QAA, and SPARQS) (7)
5. Independent scholars (4)	5. Member of fair access practice (1)
6. Education consultants (2)	6. Trade Union members (3)
	7. Lobby group members (5)
	8. University official (1)

Participants in the study were a combination of university officials, former ministers, lecturers, think tanks' directors/members, senior academics, trade unionists, non-profit organization leaders, and student representatives. Some of the participants' affiliations and positions make them qualified to be called "elites", which marked a shift in the interviews' type to Elite interviews. There has been a small but growing body of literature on elites in the last 30 years. This is due in part to the growing interest among academics in comprehending the viewpoints and actions of leaders in industry, politics, and society at large, as well as the revival of ethnographic research techniques like focus groups, interviews, case studies, and participant observation (Harvey, 2011). These types of interviews can be a minefield for novice researchers. Because of their position as leaders, elites usually possess extensive knowledge and have sharpened their effective communication abilities. They are accustomed to leading strategic planning, taking the initiative, passing commands, and being assertive toward their coworkers (Liu, 2018).

In this research, Scottish participants showed flexibility in responding to the interview questions compared to Algerian participants who were relatively conservative or showed reluctance in their response to some questions. Participants particularly in Algeria requested to be sent the interview schedule in advance of the interview.

Most of the interviews (n37) were one-to-one interviews with the research while the remain (n4) was a group interview (also referred to as focus group). The group interview was a response to some Scottish participants who had requested this arrangement. The request came because the participants shared the same working environment and felt comfortable around each other (Morgan 1998; Fox, 2009).

5.6 Pilot Study

It is necessary to undertake a pilot study especially in the social sciences because it represents a tool to examine the research instruments, evaluate the viability and feasibility of a full-scale study (Van Teijlingen et al, 2001; Malmqvist et al, 2019). A pilot study with participants was undertaken with the aim of assessing the feasibility of the research design. The first interview was conducted with a Scottish Senior Academic and the second one with a member in the Algerian quality assurance committee. The pilot study indicated the suitability of the research design although the process also indicated the need for flexibility in terms of time participants needed to address the interview questions and, in some cases, encouraging participants to give

equal attention to all questions in their responses. For the data collected in the pilot study, the researcher decided to use it for the main study because it generated usable data, particularly in Algeria where the response rate was rather low (as explained in Van Teijlingen and Hundley, 2002).

5.7 Data Analysis

One of the less explored components of the case study methodology is the analysis of the case study. Thus, in order to present the evidence in a variety of ways and with a range of interpretations, the researcher must rely on experience and the literature (Tellis, 1997, Ebneyamini and Sadeghi Moghadam, 2018). Researchers who study case studies interpret the stage differently. Miles and Huberman (1994), for instance, define the phases of data analysis as data reduction, data display, and conclusion drawing and verification. Whereas there are three approaches identified by Yin and Campbell (1989) and Yin (1994) for this stage: time series, explanation building, and pattern matching. Two stages of data analysis are suggested by Eisenhardt (1989): analyzing data within cases and looking for cross-case patterns. Three methods are identified by Stake (1995): direct interpretation and naturalistic generalization, categorical aggregation, or correspondence and patterns. Six analytical techniques are listed by Merriam (1998) and include content analysis, analytic induction, phenomenological analysis, ethnographic analysis, and constant comparative method. Additionally mentioned by Dul and Hak (2008) as methods of data analysis are pattern matching and visual inspection. The most compatible strategy with according to the researcher is that of Miles and Huberman (1994). However, the researcher did not have access to this book, so resorted to more recent edition (3rd edition) that of Miles et al., (2014).

5.7.1 Document Analysis

One of the most important methods of data analysis in a case study research strategy is the documentary analysis (of manuscripts, audio or video records, etc.) (Priya, 2021). Through the examination of data gathered using multiple methods, the researcher can reduce the impact of potential biases that may exist in a single study by correlating findings across data sets. Compared to other research methods, document analysis is more efficient because it takes less time since it is more about “data selection, instead of data collection” (Bowen, 2009, p31). In this study, the researcher adopted Bowen’s (2009) frequently used method in social research (DalGLISH, Khalid and McMahon, 2020) that involves scanning the documents to obtain a summary, reading them to find pertinent categories of analysis for the entire collection, and then interpreting the body of the documents.

5.7.2 Data Analysis: Miles et al., (2014) Approach

The study adopts Miles et al., (2014) approach to data analysis in case studies. The authors perceived the process as three concurrent flows of activity: (1) data condensation, (2) data display, and (3) conclusion drawing/verification. This perspective holds that the process of analysing qualitative data is ongoing and iterative. As analysis episodes follow one another, issues with data condensation, display, and conclusion drawing/verification arise in turn.

Data Condensation

The first stage is data condensation, which refers to the process of filtering out, narrowing down, simplifying, abstracting, and/or rearranging the information found in the entire body—that is, the written field notes, interviews, documents, and other empirical materials—and implementing these changes. The authors preferred to avoid using the term "data reduction" because it suggests that something is being lost or weakened) and argue that the data becomes stronger when condensed.

In this study, the researcher experienced what the authors referred to as “Anticipatory data condensation” which took place even before the data are actually collected as the researcher chooses (often without full awareness) which conceptual framework, which cases, which research questions, and which strategies for gathering data to select.

At the condensation phase, the researcher started the data analysis process by making herself acquainted with the data by reading and rereading the transcripts, as well as listening to audio/video recordings more than once, in order to get a deep understanding of it. The researcher also went back to the notes taken during the interviews. The researcher then proceeded to the coding of the data. the codes developed by the researcher were able to capture and highlight pertinent aspects of the data that was deemed pertinent to the study questions. The next step was the theme development, a process which the examination of coded data leading the researcher to detect similarity and overlap which made the clustering of codes together to form themes a more manageable task. In some cases, more complex codes were upgraded to independent themes. The researcher made sure the names and labels did capture the main idea encapsulated in the theme. The process of crafting theme definitions was especially helpful as it streamlines the creation of an intricate and multifaceted analytical story. Each theme's history, main idea, boundaries, and relationships to the other themes and the research question were explained in the theme definitions. The themes identified were the following: Higher education policy in Algeria 1999-2020 (defining policy milestones), the

principal policy actors involved in the shaping of higher education policy, the major active networks in advising the policy makers, levels of influence, a comparison between the first and the second decade in terms of higher education policy developments, keys to influence the higher education policy making. The government's use of evidence and consultative approaches, the participatory vs the top down approach when making higher education policies, the impact of nepotism and regionalisation on access to the policy making arena in Algeria, the impact of race and ethnicity on access to higher education policy making in Scotland, the involvement of policy actors at the different stages of the policy making process, strategies of influence, dynamics and intersectoral linkages among the leading policy actors in Scotland and their implications on the making of higher education policy. There were other emerging themes that the researcher decided to reject due to their irrelevance to the research questions: Freedom of speech, other ways for Funding, The Flaws in the system (Sub themes included Lack of means, Lack of initiative, Lack of autonomy, Lack of research integrity, Brain drain), The peculiarity of the Algerian context, career choices.

The authors explain that analytical decisions are made by the researcher when deciding which data chunks to code and which to extract, which category labels best summarize multiple chunks, and which developing narrative to present. Information Condensation is a type of analysis where data is honed, sorted, focused, eliminated, and arranged so that conclusions can be verified and finalized.

The researcher chose to put each interviewee in a distinct folder labelled Interviewee 1 for example, with the data collected about the participant before the interview, the interview schedule, the transcript, and the field notes. These individual folders were then grouped into one master folder.

Data Display

By “display” the authors mean a methodical visual presentation of data that enables the user to make inferences and take necessary action. They identify two modes of this visual presentation: matrix or network form. The researcher opted for the network form (Appendix 5 and 6). A network is an arrangement of nodes or points connected by links or lines that show streams of participant actions, events, and processes. Networks are well suited to a case-oriented approach that recreates the “plot” of events over time and illustrates complex interrelationships between variables; they provided the researcher with the kinds of narratives that are typically broken up

analytically in matrices. Further, networks are particularly useful when to easily analyze information at a glance.

Miles et al., (2014) maintain that displays that are organized methodically to address the research questions at hand and sufficiently focused to allow viewing of the entire data set in one place are essential for credible and reliable analysis. Naturally, a "full data set" does not refer to the entire collection of documents, field notes, transcripts from interviews, and other sources. Instead, the full range of people, things, and processes that are the subject of the study are represented in the shortened, distilled data that are presented. Extended text readily allows for "selective stacking" of the data. An orderly display prevents this issue.

During this stage, the researcher used started considering the connections among possible themes and their relation to the research question as displays assisted the researcher in condensing and contrasting results within and between cases. Most importantly, because the display is coherently arranged to allow for careful comparisons, detection of differences, noting of patterns and themes, seeing trends, and other activities, the likelihood of drawing and verifying conclusions is significantly higher than for extended text. Consistent with the authors views, the researcher was indeed able to make preliminary analytical findings. The strategies that helped the researcher draw those initial conclusions are observing themes and patterns and drawing comparisons and contrasts.

The systematic presentation of the condensed data had a significant implication for the researcher's comprehension. It allowed her to consider the research questions and the subsets of the data that are necessary to address them; it demanded thorough analyses that take into account all pertinent information, and it brought the research information into focus.

Drawing and Verifying Conclusions

Drawing and verifying conclusions constitute the third stream of analysis activity. The qualitative analyst deciphers meaning from the outset of data collection by taking note of patterns, justifications, causal flows, and propositions. These conclusions were there, albeit vague at first, then more explicit and grounded, provided the competent researcher maintains. In this study, the researcher did maintain openness and scepticism and preferred that "Final" conclusions are left until after data collection is complete. This decision came as a result of the size of the field note corpus, the researcher's skill level, the coding, storage, and retrieval techniques employed, and the deadlines that needed to be met.

Verification can be as quick as the analyst having a fleeting thought during writing and quickly going back to the field notes, or it can be comprehensive and detailed, involving extensive deliberation and peer review to create "intersubjective consensus" or after making significant attempts to duplicate a discovery in a different data set. It is necessary to assess the validity of the meanings that emerge from the data in terms of their plausibility, robustness, and confirmability. If not, all that's left are intriguing tales about what transpired that may or may not be useful.

when examining a display of qualitative data, the researcher focused on what distinguishes the Algerian case from the Scottish one and what do they have in common. Comparing two sets of items—persons, roles, activities, variables, cases as a whole—that are known to differ in some other significant way is a time-tested, traditional method of testing a conclusion. The researcher also took into account the authors' warning about falling into the elite bias trap, which is the practice of underrepresenting data from less articulate, lower status participants and overweighing data from articulate, well-informed, typically high-status participants. Thus, the researcher made sure data from all participants was equally represented and that the selection of relevant data was dependent on the content not the person behind.

5.8 Ensuring Data Quality and Trustworthiness

The criteria of credibility, transferability, dependability, and confirmability were introduced by Lincoln and Guba (1985) to improve the concept of trustworthiness (Nowell et al., 2017). The Interpretivist paradigm maintains that analyses are the researchers' interpretations; consequently, researchers need to make their agenda and value- system explicit from the very beginning. Research is considered good if it provides rich evidence and offers credible and justifiable accounts (internal validity/credibility), can be used by someone in another situation (external validity/transferability), and the research process and findings can be replicated (reliability/dependability) (Ritchie and Lewis, 2003; Cohen, Manion and Morrison, 2007).

5.8.1 Dependability

To address the dependability issue more directly, the study's procedures should be documented in detail so that a future researcher can replicate the work, albeit perhaps not with exactly the same outcomes. The study design could therefore be seen as a "prototype model." The reader can also evaluate how closely appropriate research procedures have been adhered to thanks to such thorough coverage. The research report should contain sections devoted to the following in order to help readers gain a comprehensive understanding of the methods and their efficacy

(Shenton, 2004, P9). Based on the aforementioned criteria, dependability was achieved for the current study for the following reasons: (1) suitability of the research methodology employed; (2) audit trail since case study research can achieve dependability through a process known as the "auditing approach," according to Lincoln and Guba (1985). Auditing entails making sure that all research records, including problem formulation, fieldnotes, interview transcripts, data analysis, and so forth, are organized and kept up to date (Priya, 2021); (3) triangulation of data collection methods and sources of data; (4) reasonable sample size used for interviews; (5) type of sample used (i.e., a representative sample of people with vested interests in HE policy making); (6) dependability and high status of the data providers (i.e., "key" informants); (7) analytic and coding procedures followed.

5.8.2 Credibility

According to Guba and Lincoln (1989), a study's credibility is established by the researchers' or readers' ability to identify the experience when it is presented to them. The "fit" between respondents' opinions and the researcher's portrayal of them is a key component of credibility (Tobin and Begley, 2004). To boost credibility, Lincoln and Guba (1985) proposed a number of strategies, including prolonged engagement, persistent observation, triangulation of data collection, and researcher triangulation. They also suggested peer debriefing as a way to verify preliminary findings and interpretations against the raw data and to examine referential adequacy as a way to offer an outside audit of the research process, which might improve credibility. Additionally, credibility can be operationalized by using member verification to validate the conclusions and interpretations with the participants. In this study, methodological triangulation (the combination of in depth semi structured interviews and document analysis) was used to ensure the credibility of the research.

The researcher has also made sure that all areas of ambiguity have been noted (Miles et al., 2014) and refrained from drawing conclusions when the evidence is weak or in the case of Algerian hard to find due to the paucity of data.

5.8.3 Confirmability

Here, actions must be taken to help guarantee that, to the greatest extent possible, the ideas and experiences of the informants, rather than the traits and preferences of the researcher, led to the findings of the work. To lessen the impact of investigator bias in this situation, it is important to emphasize the role that triangulation plays in fostering such confirmability (Shenton, 2004). In this study, triangulation was the main procedure used to ensure the confirmability of the

research. The researcher used the document analysis as a tool to minimize the likelihood of biases and gather more data to cross-check their conclusions across data sets (see Bowen, 2009). Regarding the sample size of these documents, the researcher at the beginning of the study could not decide how many documents to choose. The research questions and other elements of the investigation process determined this figure. Further, finding a point of redundancy was the necessary paramount to determine if the sample is large enough (Morgan, 2022). Both internal and externally produced documents related to the different targeted organizations (SFC, HEPI, NUS, HE Ministries) were reviewed since official publications may yield more information about the larger context in which the organization operates (Shenton, 2004).

Further, the fundamental question here is one of relative neutrality and a reasonable degree of freedom from unaccountable researcher biases, or, at the very least, of being open and honest about the biases that are unavoidable (Miles et al., 2014). The researcher followed the proposed ways to ensure confirmability which are the following: The general procedures and methods of the study are clearly and thoroughly explained. We believe we have all the necessary details, even "backstage." The precise order in which the data were gathered, examined, condensed in size, or transformed, and displayed for a given conclusion drawing is clear and can be easily tracked. Finally, the data from the study are kept and made available for re-examination by others (Miles et al., 2014).

5.8.4 Transferability

Naturalistic Inquiry is arguably one of the most cited references in terms of transferability (Rodon, 2008). Lincoln and Guba (1985) contend in their seminal book that the degree of transferability is directly related to how well two settings fit or are similar. In other words, the degree of similarity between the research setting where the phenomenon under study occurs and the settings in which the results are anticipated to be transferable determines whether research findings are applicable in different contexts. In this study, transferability was applied through the following means: (a) a thorough description of the methods; (b) a description of the study's limitations; and (d) a thorough and comprehensive description of the study's descriptive adequacy.

The researcher outlined the restrictions on sample selection and evaluated the sample's generalizability to various contexts and settings but made sure the sampling is diverse enough to allow applicability when appropriate (Miles et al., 2014).

5.9 Ethical Considerations

The study was given ethical approval by the University of the West of Scotland's ethics committee (see appendix 4).

5.9.1 Informed consent

Following the UK's research guidelines (UK Government, 2018) the researcher made sure that all participants were provided with a detailed Informed Consent document to read and sign before the interview. The consent form has some information with a tick box against it, asking individuals to tick to agree to some key information that will take place in the research before finally signing the document. In this document, the researcher outlined the following: who was conducting the research, her affiliation, the right to participate or not, restrictions on or implications for withdrawing consent or in this case the lack of thereof as the researcher explains that the participants had the freedom to withdraw at any time without any complications, information on data processing, management, and storage, the guarantee that their identities will remain confidential, and their consent to be digitally recorded. Further, potential participants were given time to consider the request to take part. The researcher explained that she will be available to answer any questions or concerns they may have. In addition to the informed consent, the researcher supplied the potential participants with an information sheet which provided details about the study and participation (see appendix 2).

5.9.2 Privacy and Confidentiality

No matter how careful researchers are, there will always be situations when it is impossible to fully protect the privacy and anonymity of participants when research is conducted on-site. This could be because they are among the few people in a particular field of activity or identifiable workplace, in which case they will always remain partially visible. On the other hand, the Internet has been perceived as a place where people can share and reveal private information while maintaining their visual anonymity and privacy (James and Busher, 2007). During the interviews, the researcher made sure not to probe on matters that were not relevant to the research, or the areas where the interviewee would prefer to keep private (Allmark et al., 2009). The researcher was aware of the need to ensure that any information gathered from the interviewee is kept private and confidential, by preventing unauthorized access to the raw data. Further measures were also taken to fully protect the participants' confidentiality via encrypting

computer-based files, store documents (i.e., signed consent forms) in a locked file cabinet and remove personal identifiers from study documents as soon as the study is completed.

5.9.3 Anonymity

According to Wiles et al. (2008), granting interviewees anonymity entails that no personal information, including name, address, email address, or other crucial details that could be used to identify the interviewee, are disclosed. To protect the identities of the participants, the researcher developed a coding system where the identifying information were replaced by pseudonyms and initials (Richards and Schwartz, 2002). To ensure anonymity, a set of codes were given to the interviewees.

5.9.4 Debriefing

Building on Willig (2003), following data collection, the researcher should make sure that participants are aware of the full objectives of the study. Ideally, they should also be able to access any publications that result from the research in which they were involved.

5.10 Strengths and Weaknesses of the Methodological Approach

A major strength of this study lies in its comparative design, which allows for an in-depth understanding of how similar policy processes from two different social, cultural and economic contexts develop across distinct political and institutional settings (Ragin, 2014). Comparative case studies can help identify both patterns and broader analytical insights (Hantrais, 2009). Furthermore, comparative analysis deepens one's understanding of their own society by examining its structures and routines in relation to those of other systems. It also broadens our awareness of different cultures, practices, and ways of thinking and discourages overgeneralizations based on personal or culturally specific experiences, challenging ethnocentric or overly universal assumptions (Esser and Vliegthart, 2017). It also allows for learning through cross-border comparisons and contributes to shaping policy and decision-making at both national and international levels (Blair-Walcott, 2023). In this study, the comparative approach brought out both the areas of convergence and those of divergence between Algeria and Scotland in terms of how policy advice was implemented, discarded, or modified to influence the higher education debates. The comparative design had also highlighted the postcolonial history of Algeria against the devolved governance mechanisms in Scotland; the Algerian centralized system against the Scottish consultative approach to present a case of high contrast between two institutionally distinct settings and allowed the research to investigate the implications of such contrast on how policy advice was used. Such

comparison strengthened the analytical aspect of this study and allowed evidence-based conclusions to be drawn, conclusions that span from answering the research questions to shedding light on areas that need further investigation. Overall, the comparative approach allowed for better understanding of the higher education policy intricacies.

Further, the research adopts a cross disciplinary lens as it draws on themes from the fields of public policy, political science, higher education studies, and comparative analysis. These disciplines blend seamlessly together to paint this holistic picture on how policy advice influenced higher education policymaking. This blend allowed the researcher to dive deeper into the complex dynamics of institutional heritages, policy actors' strategies, and governance models to come up with conclusions that would not be possible with one lens thus adding value to the study and depth.

Data triangulation also represents a strength point for this research, the study's use of document analysis provides access to official accounts of historical events and policy documents. Document analysis is particularly useful in public policy research for uncovering meaning, structure, and intent (Bowen, 2009). It allows the researcher to explore both the explicit content, and the underlying assumptions embedded in texts that reflect the positions of influential actors. However, history can cover some views while burying others. Therefore, the researcher relied on a primary source of data, semi structured interviews. The combination of the two made sure that all standpoints are verified and cross checked to give an evidence-based narrative.

The cases selected for the study (Algeria and Scotland) themselves represent an original attempt to explore hidden truths and compare two distinct contexts. In a scholarship dominated by studies from the Global North especially Western Europe, North America, and Anglophone countries (Tight, 2012; Shahjahan and Kezar, 2013) including a Global South country is a fresh breath of air into the academic scene. Algeria's higher education system operates within a postcolonial, centralised governance framework shaped by a complex mix of bureaucracy and international influences, such as those from UNESCO and the Bologna Process (Mazawi, 2005; Nokkala and Bacevic, 2014). These factors make Algeria a specimen worth the investigation of researchers, yet it remains absent from comparative higher education studies. Therefore, the inclusion of Algeria in recent debates represent an original attempt to challenge the dominance of Eurocentrism. On the other end, Scotland, a devolved country that still strongly attached to the wide UK context all while preserving its unique higher education system with its history

and values. The post devolution period has seen Scottish higher education policymaking increasingly reflect local priorities, especially in relation to widening access, quality assurance, and public accountability (Gallacher and Raffe, 2012). Put side by side, the case selection is a significant step in comparative studies that proves that despite the distinct governance structures, historical trajectories, and institutional variations Algeria and Scotland remain comparable.

The choice of the topic itself, with its complex web of themes ranging from policy advisory systems to comparative governance, evidence-based policy to policy learning is another key strength that did not limit itself to the examination of the two countries higher education systems and the reforms they undergone but critically explored how policy advice is produced and implemented. This extends the analysis to include both formal and institutionalized forms of networks such as specialized commissions set by the government to informal networks and the strategies the network members used.

Conceptually, there are three pitfalls identified by different scholars. First, the literature revealed that the theorization of policy advisory systems is grounded in studies conducted in Westminster-styled administrations, specifically in Australia, Canada, New Zealand, and the UK (Craft and Halligan, 2017; Hustedt and Veit, 2017; Craft and Halligan, 2020). The phenomenon came to be known as the “Westminster bias”, which could result in deceptive perceptions of the ways that policy advice is organized in different administrative traditions (Hustedt, 2019). Second, as argued by Hustedt (2019), despite the blooming scholarly interest in policy advice and the proliferation of research on policy advice systems, theoretical work on the influence of advice and systematic variation in policy advice system configuration is still missing from scholarly debates. Third, Policy advice in Westminster systems is a commonly studied topic, with studies on Europe following closely behind (e.g. Craft and Halligan 2017; Fraussen and Halpin 2017; Kelstrup, 2017; Van den Berg, 2017; Veit, Hustedt, and Bach 2017; Veselý, 2016). Yet, there is still a dearth of comparative studies and research on other systems, particularly in transitional and developing nations (except for Nachiappan, 2013; Saguin, 2018). These gaps made the task of situating the research in a well-defined scope harder and limited the analytical dimension of the research since there was curbed understanding of how policy advice can be applied to a country that do not belong to the traditional cases examined which made the choice of the appropriate theoretical and conceptual groundings more challenging.

The methodological limitations manifested in the sample size. Despite the researcher's awareness of the need to oversample in case of withdrawal, the response rates among the Algerian participants were still low due to several reasons that are thoroughly discussed in the methodology chapter. To reiterate, those invited to take part strongly believed that "the political" aspect of the study is too problematic and preferred to stay in the clear. Other reasons include the lack of the culture of participating in research and the workload. Moreover, during the interviews, some participants were reluctant to answer specific questions (sensitivity of the question or lack of familiarity with particular aspects of the research) despite the researcher's attempts to probe.

Interviews are a primary source of data in this research, yet during the analysis, the researcher was aware of issues related to self-reported data. Although this approach is excellent for giving people the freedom to narrate their story in their own words, People who self-report their opinions and describe their own experiences, attitudes, or behaviours also depends on memory and is susceptible to social desirability bias, which is the human tendency to avoid saying the wrong thing (Teh et al., 2023). But occasionally, it's the only type of information that can provide insight into specific questions especially questions related to the extent of some interviewees' involvement and contribution. While this limitation can be dangerous if overlooked, the researcher made sure the data was always doubled checked against credible academic sources (triangulation).

The researcher is aware that conclusions presented in this thesis have been limited by the lack of data from some groups in the two countries. In Algeria, civil servants did not have reliable info on their profiles to establish a valid contact. Former student representatives decided to withdraw after giving their consent, while trade unionists chose to deliberately ignore the researcher's attempt to establish contact. In Scotland, governmental agents are missing due to their agendas and hectic schedules. This was mitigated by resorting to commissions' reports, parliamentary minutes, transcripts and reaching proximate actors who did not belong to these groups but still had close contact with them. Further, when making conclusions that relied almost exclusively on these members' perspectives, the researcher either refrained from making such claims or explained that the conclusion is provisional.

Despite the fact that this study yields valuable and original insights, the findings should not be considered as representative of other populations, settings or contexts beyond the ones investigated as a commonly cited limitation of case studies is their lack of statistical

generalisability. However, the goal here is not to produce broadly representative findings but to enable analytical generalisation, theoretical insights applicable to other similar contexts (Yin, 2018; Flyvbjerg, 2006). Still, readers must be cautious in applying the findings directly beyond the studied cases.

The selection of Algeria and Scotland as two cases which differ substantially in terms of their political systems (centralised with a top down approach vs a devolved system with stronger stakeholder engagement), economic status (Developing resource based economy vs developed economy), higher education systems (Historically state controlled vs autonomous institutions with strong governance) raises methodological challenges regarding how to compare them meaningfully and at the same time provided a ground for applying Przeworski and Teune's (1970) Most Different Design System as a lens to compare the two. MDSD is a comparative logic that selects cases with maximum contextual differences to isolate causally relevant factors that may produce similar outcomes across divergent systems (Przeworski and Teune, 1970). Thus, MDSD allowed this research to assess whether policy advice functions the same way across different systems in shaping higher education policy, or whether its effectiveness is conditioned by set of specific factors. To resolve the limitations around comparability, scholars of comparative policy stress the need for conceptual equivalence and contextual sensitivity when comparing dissimilar cases as they argued that the absence of careful contextualisation may lead to a risk of drawing false parallels or overinterpreting similarities (Hantrais, 2009; Sartori, 1991). To mitigate such issues, measures such as choosing comparable set of commissions and committees in both countries to scrutinize the role and input of institutionalized advisory forums (Examples include the Cubie commission in Scotland and the Benzaghoul Commission in Algeria), using the same analytical tools to observe the supply and demand of policy advice in the two countries, focusing on the policy advice dimension instead of comparing the outcomes of higher education policies which could be problematic for a number of reasons, the way the research looks (perspective) at the high contrasts as a plus for the study instead of an obstacle for instance the striking difference between the steering of the Algerian HE and the Scottish one provided context to better understand why policy advice in Scotland had better chances to influence the policymaking. Finally, data triangulation was also a means to mitigate bias in data interpretation.

In contexts like Algeria, access issues are a significant constraint in research especially when official archival documents are an essential source of data, due to low transparency or limited public archiving practices. Therefore, navigating these issues was a persistent and sometimes

a nerve wrecking aspect of this journey especially that the study relied on the inputs from key stakeholders and official documents. However, persistence, not taking no for an answer, and thinking outside the box were the key steps taken to overcome the aforementioned barriers.

5.11 Conclusion

The research methodology for this study is covered in this chapter. It begins by giving a detailed explanation of the philosophical foundations of this research and how the paradigm selection determines the researcher's stance and shapes important choices. The next section discusses case studies in general and comparative case studies in particular as the chosen qualitative research method for the thesis based on the researcher's epistemological, ontological, axiological, and methodological stances. The data collection instruments, such as in-depth semi-structured interviews and documents, are addressed in the following section. In order to determine whether the research would be feasible, the researcher also described the process of conducting a pilot study and her sampling strategies. The chapter goes on to explain the data analysis procedure, using document analysis for documents and thematic analysis for interviews. Next, the topics of reliability, credibility, confirmability, and transferability related to trustworthiness in qualitative research are examined. The main ethical issues, informed consent, privacy and confidentiality, anonymity and debriefing, are discussed along the strengths and weaknesses of the methodological approach as the chapter comes to a close.

Chapter 6

The Role of Policy Advice and Expertise in Higher Education Policy making in Algeria and Scotland

6.1 Introduction

This chapter addresses how policy advice and expertise shaped higher education policy making in Algeria and Scotland. The chapter compares how and to what extent policy advice offered to the Algerian and the Scottish Governments informed the decision-making in a number of policy areas. The BMD introduction (2003-2020), the shift towards quality assurance in higher education (2008-2020), and the international mobility, the PhD scheme in particular (2014-2019). In Scotland, the analysis follows the policy advice that shaped the funding developments (1999-2016), the Widening access policies (2014-2019) and the higher education governance reform (2011-2016).

6.2 The Role of Commissions

Commissions, committees and inquiries have different status and take various forms, but they all seek to broaden the basis of public policy making beyond governments, parliaments and interest groups, through engaging a wider range of participants in a public arena to generate new ideas, develop consensus or to confer legitimacy upon controversial government policy plans (Peters and Barker, 1993; Rowe and McAllister, 2006). In this regard, Algeria and Scotland were similar in their ways of seeking policy advice to inform their higher education policy choices in most of the designated areas of study for this research as the two governments set up two commissions and two committees. The Algerian government set up the CNRE (2002) also known as the Benzaghou Commission for the BMD and a steering committee to advise on the international mobility in Algeria while the Scottish Government established the Cubie Committee for the tuition fees and the Commission on Widening Access (COWA) in Scotland. However, beyond the similarities were also many differences as the analysis will show.

Scottish devolution brought about the question on how Scotland would finance its higher education sector, now that this responsibility was fully devolved to the new Scottish Parliament and the new Scottish government, in 1999 still called the Scottish Executive. The first Scottish government was formed by the Scottish Labour Party and the Scottish Liberal Democrats – in a marked difference to Westminster politics, the Scottish proportional electoral system was

likely to produce the need for coalition governments. The two coalition partners disagreed on the method of higher education financing. The Liberal Democrats wanted to see tuition fees abolished, a stance rejected by the Labour (BBC News, 1999). As political parties have distinct preferences how to steer a public sector and how much autonomy professional communities should enjoy, it can be expected that these also play a role in their positions in higher education policy (Jungblut, 2014). In order to save the newly formed coalition, the Scottish Executive set up the Cubie Commission in July 1999 to advise on how to tackle this issue. The Cubie Committee published its report on 21 December 1999 (Steve, 1999; UK Parliament, 2001).

The Scottish Executive commissioned Andrew Cubie, a lawyer an ex-chairman of the Scottish Confederation of British Industry (CBI). Other committee members, there was a total of fourteen, included leading trade union and education officials, a former corporate vice-president of Motorola, a senior partner with accountants KPMG, and one student representative (BBC News, 1999a).

The commission's terms of reference were as follows: To conduct a comprehensive review of tuition fees and financial support for students normally resident in Scotland participating, part-time or full-time, in further and higher education courses anywhere in the UK. To have regard to the desirability of promoting access to further and higher education, particularly for those groups currently under-represented, while taking account of the need to maintain and to develop quality and standards, and the position of Scottish further and higher education in the wider UK system. To make recommendations for any changes to the current system, and provide costed options where these may require additional resources. To present a report of its findings to the Executive by the end of 1999 (Times Higher Education, 1999b).

Similarly, and around the same time in Algeria, and in order to underpin renewed reform efforts, policy advice was needed in several areas starting with the introduction of the Bachelor/Masters/Doctorate system. For that end, the 'National Commission for Reform of the Educational System' (Commission Nationale de Réforme du Système Educatif, known by its French initials as the CNRSE) was set up to outline the main thrusts of the reform on the 13th of May 2000 by President Abdelaziz Bouteflika (The Algerian Ministry of Education, 2000). The Commission was one element of an extensive endeavour to reform the educational system (The Algerian Ministry of Education, 2000). The Commission was given the task of evaluating the current educational system using scientific and pedagogical criteria in order to establish a comprehensive and objective diagnosis of all the component parts of the education, vocational

training, and higher education systems. Based on the results of this assessment, the Commission was then to investigate what a comprehensive overhaul of the system should look like. The commission's task was centred around three primary pillars: improving supervisory qualifications, modernizing pedagogy, and restructuring the educational system (The Algerian Ministry of Education, 2000). The Commission was, by all standards, set out to be a large and resource-intensive undertaking. It comprised a total of 170 members recruited by the office of the President of the Republic. The Commission was chaired by Benali Benghazaou, a well esteemed rector and academic. The commissioners were, in the main, eminent personalities with expertise from the education sector, academics, higher education professional and managerial staff, civil service educational inspectors and representatives from different sectors. Some of the individuals had very public links to political parties (Ferhani, 2006). It appears that the Commission was to involve not only the broadest possible range of stakeholder types, but also sought to give space to a large diversity of voices and views in order to develop analysis and policy recommendations based thereupon. Certainly, the inclusion of distinguished figures was to demonstrate an authentic desire from the government to not only generate a momentum for change but also to do so the basis on what could be presented as a broad and evidence-based, non-ideological consensus. The rationale behind the choice of the commissions' members, along with its chair, was that the expectation that they would bring epistemic value, knowledge, skills and expertise to the debate. This resonates with prior findings from Hunter and Boswell (2015) who argue that governments set commissions to reflect their disposition to both allocate more resources to address a specific issue and yield some control over the outcomes of the commissions.

An examination of the composition of these two commissions shows that both commissions had a diverse membership, although the Cubie Committee had far fewer members compared to what appears an overly large and therefore possibly difficult-to-manage Benzaghoul Commission. Clearly, both arrangements drew from a pool of expertise -individuals, anchored in the epistemic community of the policy field in their respective country. As the literature suggests, epistemic communities can help analyse problems and formulate policy options to provide advice on the likely results of various courses of action (Haas, 1992). Epistemic communities are mostly likely active in the early policy design stage of the policy cycle when the uncertainties around policy problems are at their peak (Dunlop, 2012), which was the case in both contexts. Both governments struggled with highly complex higher education issues and chose to call for the expertise of the commissions' members to advise at an early stage (the

formulation stage as explained in the conceptual framework chapter) of the policy making process on the best path to follow. The practical consultation procedures may vary considerably in terms of inclusiveness (closed versus open), and more precisely with respect to the types of interests that gain representation, for instance businesses or citizens (Arras and Beyers, 2020). Both commissions seem to include actors from a variety of backgrounds, students, trade union members, academics, and members of the business community, which reflects the two governments' openness to the different interests represented.

In terms of how higher education policy was impacted by the work and output of these two commissions and how far the two governments did make use of the commissions' findings to adjust policy, both commissions were met with a positive attitude with regards to their recommendations. In Algeria and despite the criticism dominating the media (Benelhadj Djelloul, 2022) and echoed by the participants, it seems that the Algerian government listened to the Commission's recommendations when deciding to move forward with the adoption of the Bachelor-Masters-Doctorate system. The Commission noted that for years the Algerian university has chosen to act in isolation of the rest of the world and continued that such stance had had serious bearing on the Algerian students and led to severe strategic delays. The commission explicitly recommended opening the higher education system to the world and suggested the creation of a further commission to investigate how this could be done best (La Commission nationale de réforme du système éducatif, 2002, p. 48).

However, the participants in this study have had reserved to suspicious opinions about commissions in general and the Benzaghrou Commission in particular. Furthermore, they were sceptical regarding the 'true' intentions of the government. Commenting on the general concept of commissions, a senior academic said "I'm sceptical of the Commission word because I say if you want to kill something you do a Commission and then it goes nowhere" (Algerian education consultant 2). In the literature, Hesstvedt and Christensen (2021) assert that when decision-makers consult commissions and expert groups for guidance, they are faced with a basic conundrum. On the one hand, experts have information that can assist governments in creating policies that better tackle societal issues. External experts can also boost a policy's public legitimacy and credibility by demonstrating that decisions were made on the basis of objective and impartial knowledge rather than because of personal or political agendas and gain. However, there are significant political hazards involved. Experts may disagree with the government's definition of the issue and suggest alternative policy solutions to those the government finds most desirable. In the case of the Benzaghrou Commission, the secrecy

around the commission's report triggered much concern among the interested parties. While, when announced, the government's interest in publicising the establishment and workings of the commission seemed clear and promising, when it came to reporting the findings, it seemed that the government was no longer interested in the commissions' findings or had other reasons why the report produced by this commission was not published fully and widely at the time (El Watan, 2013). Even today, it is very difficult to obtain a copy of the report. An investigative look at this instance reveals the possible tactical use of research as explained in the conceptual frameworks chapter. Weiss (1979) argued that social research can be used to comfort the public that actions are being taken to handle a specific issue, in this case the education sector. Such use depends and prioritize publicizing the setting of commissions for examples instead of focusing on the output of these bodies.

The media was also keen to understand what was happening at the moment and even years later. In an article titled "What happened to the Benzaghoul report" that was published in the EL Watan newspaper on July 14, 2009, Belkacem Mohamed Cherif, Director General of the Ecole Supérieure de Gestion (ESG) wondered what became of the report generated by a commission made up of distinguished experts. More than 11 years after it was submitted, still little was known about the content of the report. For unknown reasons, the Republic's presidency declined to make the document available to the public. Both in 2013 (El Watan, 2013) and 2014 (El Watan, 2014) when being interviewed, Benali Benzaghoul himself, chair of the commission and then rector of the University of Sciences and Dechronologies, Houari Boumediene, said that "there is nothing secret" in the document, and he, himself did not understand why the office of the Presidency of the Republic did not make the report public (Elwatan, 2014). A point addressed by the participants, who expressed serious concerns over the extent to which the policy recommendations made by the commission members were taken into consideration when implementing the BMD system. A senior academic stated that "the CNRSE issued a report in 2002, but it was never published. Did the decisions taken by the government really come from this report? I doubt it" (Algerian independent scholar 1).

Turning to Scotland, when the Cubie Committee (formally known as the Independent Committee of Inquiry into Student Finance) was established there were promising cues that the commission would have an impact on the Scottish higher education policy landscape as the Scottish Executive's Labour and Liberal Democrat members made suggestions that they were ready to use the conclusions of Andrew Cubie's report as a basis for discussions. The consensus amongst politicians of both coalition partners on how to use the outcome of the commission

was important, some observers noted at the time, to assure the coherence or even survival of the governing coalition (Seenan and MacAskill, 1999; Seenan and Carvel, 1999). Clearly, Scotland's supposedly 'distinctive' way of consensus-based policy making was at this point still in its infancy and politicians still had to get used to the idea of consensus and how this would lead to compromises that, sometimes, would satisfy neither side. However, the Cubie Committee did offer a solution to put an end to a potentially threatening conflict between Labour and Liberal Democrats. In terms of influence, the Cubie report advised on a "mixed economy" where the state would pay for the undergraduate fees and students would help with what came to be known as the graduate endowment (Cubie, 1999). For this arrangement, the Scottish Executive would pay the tuition fees to the universities and students would be required to pay £3,000 of it back when their post-degree earnings reached £25,000 a year. The Scottish Executive accepted these key recommendations from the committee, although a few details were changed after consulting a ministerial working group (UK Parliament, 2000). The main change concerned the graduate endowment, in the final policy decision, students would pay back only £2,000 but would start repaying once their earnings reached £10,000 (The Guardian, 2000).

The Cubie Committee undertook efforts to formulate its problem analysis and policy recommendations in ways that allowed both Labour and the Liberal Democrats to claim that much of their respective positions on the issue were considered. Labour could claim victory in preserving the principle of loans, as opposed to grants, whilst the Liberal Democrats could claim that they abolished tuition fees as one of their main campaign commitments.

When placing the Cubie Commission and the Benzaghrou Commission into the conceptual frameworks and concepts discussed earlier, it becomes clear that the former served a problem-solving role, to use Weiss' terminology as discussed in an earlier chapter. The Scottish Executive had a clear understanding of their objectives, so they recruited the help of social scientists (experts in general) to supply the information, analysis, and potentially interpretations in the form of suggestions related to the case at hand. Further, under the problem-solving model, Weiss' claim that there is a general consensus that the specific study the relevant government office commissioned will have an impact and that its recommendations will influence future decisions is absolutely true in the case of the Cubie Commission.

A second example for a commission was the Commission on Widening Access established in 2014, after the Scottish First Minister, Nicola Sturgeon, declared that widening access was to be a priority for her government. She delivered perhaps the ambitious goals around attainment and widening access to education by announcing that that a ‘child born today in one of our most deprived communities will, by the time he or she leaves school, have the same chance of going to university as a child born in one of our least deprived communities’ (Scottish Government, 2014a, p1). The Commission was established to advise ministers on how to meet this ambition as it was asked to synthesise the evidence about un/fair access, suggest short- and long-term targets, identify best practice; data and information requirements and to draw a roadmap on how to reach the objectives set by the Government in terms of removing barriers for students (The Scottish Funding Council, 2014). The commission chaired by Dame Ruth Silver, had a diverse membership. With the Institute for Public Policy Research (IPPR), an analyst of a centre-left think tank sat next to two university principals and vice chancellors, a member of a database management company, the president of the National Union of Students, a representative of the Scottish Funding Council (SFC) and government representative, representatives from a trade union and two charities, in addition to an academic and an advocate of widening access in Further education as a chair governmental official. Universities Scotland as the sector’s representative association was invited later (The Scottish Funding Council, 2014). Also, it seems as if relatively few academics were part of the commission and that the choice of chair, an obvious supporter of widening access policies, gave the commission a certain steer towards a direction of travel that would align with the government’s declared agenda.

The committee chair claims that for developing the commission’s recommendations, evidence was gathered from a wide range of sources that approached the commission after a Call for Evidence was issued in in June 2015 and through reviewing existing evidence and the literature (Riddell, Blackburn and Minty, 2016). A further tool was a a series of consultation events and meetings across Scotland to take presentations from key stakeholders at Commission meetings including students, care leavers, experts and practitioners. While this phase constitute the early efforts of establishing an overview of the problem and of existing or possible approaches that could be taken to widen access into higher education, the second phase of the Commission’s activities was characterised by holding a series of expert meetings which brought together practitioners and professionals from a range of sectors and specialisms, ‘to test and enrich our thinking as we began to shape our recommendations’ (The Scottish Government, 2016a). This

consultation sought to involve students and their representatives in the shaping of widening access policies and listening more to the views they were eager to give since, in 2011, the National Union of Students claimed that two thirds of universities did not sufficiently consult students on their access agreements (Grove, 2012).

COWA's final report, 'A Blueprint for Fairness', was published in 2016. For widening access to higher education, the Commission made 34 recommendations (The Scottish Government, 2016a). While the Commission noted the importance of all its recommendations, it chose to highlight a small number of foundational recommendations which reflected the action it believed would be necessary to deliver a step change in progress. These were the appointment of a Commissioner for Fair Access ; the development of a Framework for Fair Access to provide Scotland with an authoritative, evidence based framework to guide future access work and set the benchmark for access interventions going forward; the introduction of access thresholds for all degree programmes, and more transparency and promotion of these and wider contextual admissions policies; a guaranteed offer of a place and a full bursary for students with a care experience who meet the minimum entry requirements; and the implementation of targets to drive forward equal access to higher education in Scotland. Similarity

The Scottish Government responded positively to COWA's recommendations, and it seems that most of the recommendations were taken on board and enshrined in policy in the following years. For example, the Government appointed Professor Sir Peter Scott as first Commissioner for Fair Access in December 2016 and allowed new and continuing care experienced students undertaking an eligible undergraduate course became to apply for a funding package of tuition fees and a non-income assessed Care Experienced Students Bursary. Further, the Government outline a set of expectations related to the contribution of Scotland's colleges and universities to the targets set by the Commission through OA. The SFC carried out its recommendations through establishing five work streams and acknowledge the SFC's role in supporting wider delivery: Evidencing improvements in the admissions and selection processes (Recommendations 11-12, 14, 15 and 21-23); Engaging with schools (Recommendations 4, 15, 16, 18) Effective pathways and transitions into higher education (Recommendations 5-10) Funding, targets and regulation (Recommendations 24-27, 32) Measurement and reporting (Recommendations 30-31) (The Scottish Government, 2017b).

As the COWA reports acknowledge, many Scottish universities were already operating some form of contextualised admissions. However, this was not universal practice, and reductions in

academic entry requirements for disadvantaged learners were typically of the order of just one or two grades (Boliver, Gorard and Siddiqui, 2019).

The government stated that the COWA recommendation represented a call for “more radical action” than ever before (Scottish Government, 2016a, p. 37) and it appears that the Commission’s findings were taken seriously and largely enacted. No doubt, what the commission recommended was fully aligned with the Scottish Government’s declared wider access agenda. Nonetheless, the adoption of much of what the commission suggested shows that the Scottish Government was willing to use experts’ policy advice in order to solve a particular problem (Weiss, 1979).

One key feature of the two commissions, the Cubie committee and the COWA commission, was the representation of students’ organised interests. This may signify the government’s awareness of the students’ importance but also of how younger people matter as current and future voters. Moreover, the student voice was appreciated in its own right as one which could contribute useful expertise and legitimacy to the commissions. A Scottish think tank analyst who was also an active student representative stated that,

the power of having elected students, you know the voice of students delivered by students was incredibly strong...So the power of having people that are currently talking about their experience and what they believe would fix it is much more powerful than others doing that... ensure that got heard at least if not listen to (Scottish Think Tank member 2).

In terms of influence, a senior academic and an advocate for fair access in Scotland confirmed that the Scottish Government listens to students because they hold the power to vote and decide for the country’s future:

In Scotland, everything is viewed through the lens of independence and the struggle for independence. So the NUS, for example, the National Union of Students, would be quite an influential body and that's partly because the youth vote would be important to the government and because the NUS would be a largely middle class voice, they would want to keep that constituency (Scottish Independent Scholar 1).

Student unions (NUS Scotland and Coalition of Higher Education Students) and students in general played a key role in shaping the tuition fees policy in Scotland as these groups contributed to the government’s agenda of scrapping of the graduate endowment fee proposed by the Cubie committee in 1999 through a variety of ways that will be discussed in Chapter 7.

In addition to the policy expertise offered by students, interest groups in Scotland also contributed to the public debate, and to that behind closed doors, on which avenue to choose in terms of higher education policy by taking a direct part in the aforementioned committees as members and by contributing their views and insights through the consultation process (The Scottish Government (National Union of Students Scotland, 2007; University and College Union Scotland, 2015; UNISON, 2015; Universities Scotland, 2015a; Universities Scotland, 2015b; Universities Scotland, 2016; Universities Scotland, 2017; Universities Scotland, 2018). This active participation demonstrates how interest groups, generally speaking, are able and to participate in consultation processes (Rasmussen, 2014) thanks to their organizational expertise. In the Scottish context, policy developments around higher education governance were shaped by the strong presence of two rivalling interest, trade unions and Universities Scotland. Both Universities Scotland and trade unions hold a variety of resources such as financial means, legitimacy, representativeness. But most importantly, these interest groups have knowledge, expertise and information that can support decision-makers (Dür, 2008). These privileges allowed trade unions (EIS, UNISON, STUC but mainly UCU Scotland) and Universities Scotland to influence the major policy developments in higher education. It seems that Universities Scotland, i.e. the universities' umbrella pressure group, provided the government with key inside perspectives by providing evidence and mobilising its expertise to hold the Scottish Government accountable to its actions, expand the debate on issues or angles that might get overlooked, and present a fresh view on ongoing practices:

Universities Scotland, from my perspective, do a great job of supplying that evidence and where government might be going down one route. It does a very good job of stopping it if it's using the wrong approach or interpreting a set of evidence wrong (Member of a Scottish statutory organisation 6).

Trade unions' input and impact on major higher education policy developments in Scotland were described as slightly restricted to the role of an opposition force as a think tank member explained: 'You can often see quite strong opposition from particularly the trade unions from education providers' (Scottish Think Tank member1).

Turning back to Algeria, a further example of the Algerian government needing policy advice elucidates how expertise is used and for which purposes. One of the main objectives of the introduction of the BMD system was to facilitate the movement of students from one university to another and between countries and to thereby align Algeria's higher education system to the

Bologna agreement of which mobility is an important principle (The Bologna Declaration, 1999). In this new context, the challenge for Algeria's higher education system was raised to beyond 'only' satisfying the demands of the Algerian labour market and to offer a further dimension that sought to satisfy Algerian students' demands for increased international mobility and to also welcome qualified foreign students by recognizing degree credentials. Policy makers, on their part, hoped that the new system would make programme offerings from Algerian universities more compatible with those around the world, thereby increasing international mobility of Algerian faculty and students (Zitouni and Djaileb, 2014). In reality, Algeria faced a mismatch between what was theoretically outlined and what is practically doable in terms of human resources and infrastructure (Ghiat, 2023).

In 2013, the British Council in Algeria announced the Ministry of Higher Education and Scientific Research in Algeria intention to sponsor a fully funded scholarship for PhD students to the UK over the next five years in a multi-million Pound programme (British Council, 2018). The programme was part of an ambitious Algerian plan to collaborate with the UK to build capacity in British universities and to diversify its international partnerships into the Anglophone world.

Once the decision was made, the Algerian Government put together an expert committee to conduct the negotiations with their UK counterparts and discuss a framework for cooperation at a workshop in London. The British Council arranged the workshop and visit, the first of its kind in decades. Commenting on the membership of the delegation, a former senior British member of the British council said that

it was good to see the representation from many different Algerian universities, so they did have a voice... the rectors, but also the senior academics...or respected people and they had a good voice in shaping this programme (Education consultant 1).

In the case of the PhD scheme as an example of how the Algerian government chose to mobilize its expertise to advise on how best to achieve the goals set at the beginning of the discussions, it can be argued that once again the decision to launch such a big programme was decided at the highest levels of the country, the presidency in cooperation with the Ministry of Higher Education and Scientific Research. The involvement of the British Council in Algeria demonstrated that a bilateral, inter-governmental agreement needed to be open to expertise from the country partner rather than being restricted to Algerian experts only, as had been the

case with earlier commissions. The British Council acted also as a knowledge broker between policy makers and academics in Algeria and their counterparts in the UK:

It's important to bring the right people together in an open and engaging way to facilitate exchange and I think this is why the British Council is very well placed to do that. You have to have the connections to the key decision makers, and in this case it was a decision of the Algerian government (Algerian education consultant 2).

Knowledge brokers are usually defined as intermediaries between knowledge producers, (i.e. academics) and knowledge users (i.e. policy makers). A knowledge broker's strategy might be a way of responding to a perceived problem, for example insufficient communication due to professional cultures and the barriers they may impose. The solution, in this case, could consist of the provision of a synthesis of the evidence base so that academics are better understood by policy makers and vice versa if academics require help to better understand the needs of policy makers (Bennett Institute for Public Policy, 2020). The influence of knowledge brokers on policy formulation, therefore, cannot be separated from the circumstances in which advice is given. Social and political contexts are often more important determinants of whether evidence can impact policy than the quality of the advice itself (Smith, 2013; Bandola-Gill and Lyall, 2017). In the case of the PhD scheme, the social and political contexts stressed the need for a body such as the British Council, whose primary task was to provide a bridge between the two countries and to help clarify or avoid misunderstandings. This was probably a more important task for the British Council than getting involved in policy detail. This shows that the functions of this committee went beyond liaising between two sets of actors to introduce a certain higher education initiative. As a British consultant said,

there was a real lack of expertise and capacity and also international linkages. I think it's fair to say, I mean before the Civil War in the 80s, that there were quite a lot of British academics working in Algeria, in fact, some of the experts on our programme...were people who had been in Algeria before the war. My role was important because, I actually had to, I think to some degree, change perceptions in the UK...there was and there probably still limited understanding of Algeria in the UK because of this isolation or this lack of contact (Algerian Education consultant 1).

In the area of international cooperation and mobility, and in particular the case of the “the PhD scheme”, the British Council was a very active actor. It seems that the Council had a dual position, as a knowledge producer whose advice was well received by the Algerian government and as a knowledge broker when providing a bridge between academics and policy makers.

Experts and consultants from the British Council contributed to the debate and raised a number of points, an important one, and one where the Council's expertise failed to make an impact, was the one around the age set for the students to benefit from the scholarship and the concerns around the high potential of brain drain. One interviewee said that the Council had argued for,

a limit for the age of 26 ...there were many students that were the top three of their cohort in the different universities, but they were excluded because they went beyond the 26 years...So we were trying to influence this, but we were not successful no matter how much we advocated for this. But there was also a risk that we highlighted right from the beginning, when you send these young people who have never been overseas with all the economic problems, socioeconomic problems, that the country is going through that they will not return...this is something that could have been mitigated with different ways because at a certain time we suggested doing other things in order to be able to limit this. But quite often the decision making is really top down (Algerian Education Consultant 2).

According to Lipton (1994), knowledge brokers are most useful where policy makers do not have sufficient time to commission original research or lack expertise in certain areas. However, it is noteworthy to highlight that research evidence and policy advice can be used in multiple ways in the policy making process (Nutley, Walter and Davies, 2007; Weiss, 1979) yet not all of the situations where policy makers interact with research might be seen as 'influence'. Sometimes the input provided by knowledge brokers may influence the policy process only by drawing attention to certain issues (Bandola-Gill and Lyall, 2017), which was the case with the British Council trying to shape the scheme's outlook with regards to the age set for the candidates. In this situation, the suggestions provided by the consultants were ignored.

Commenting on the way the initiative was decided upon and carried out, the participants complimented the transparent and open participatory approach through which the ministry conducted the discussions and consultations. The participants also highlighted that the discussions were open on how to operationalize and implement the initiative since the decisions related to the strategy and budget were taken at the higher levels of the ministry and the presidency:

The ministry had the decisive role in a way in deciding on the level of investment and the strategy, but how it was operationalized was involving, all the universities and responding to specific needs and they were able to go

back and report on the discussions. And how they perceived it...in that sense it was quite open and transparent and participatory and there were lots of different discussions that could happen between the Algerian university representatives and the British University representatives (Algerian Education Consultant 1).

Moreover, following a symposium organized by the Ministry of Higher Education and Scientific Research (MESRS), the National Evaluation Committee (CNE) whose main task is “to evaluate the activities and actions of higher education institutions in terms of governance, training and research with respect to the objectives that are set for them” and the Commission for the Implementation of a National Quality Assurance Framework in Higher Education Institutions (CIAQES) whose main tasks are quality assurance training in higher education, the development of a national QA framework, and the meeting of the conditions for the creation of QA in Algerian HEIs (Guessoum, 2019) became the two leading experts’ groups designated by the Ministry of Higher Education in Algeria to advise on quality assurance matters. The CIAQES had a number of experts selected based on their expertise and merits. In this regard, one of the participants recalled that

we were a team working and there were international-level competencies that were members of the commission. We have really teamed up. It wasn’t just the training aspect, because all the quality assurance people were informed. But we have also developed a national quality assurance framework that we have worked really hard on (Algerian Quality Assurance Officer).

The Algerian government implemented the CIAQES recommendation mainly through the adoption of the National Reference (framework) for quality assurance in higher education (RNAQES), which was developed by the QARs supervised by members of the CIAQES to serve as a tool for quality assessment at the level of HEIs (Kourache, 2019). The implementation faced several constraints such as the underdeveloped legal framework of quality assurance and the lack of experience among the quality assurances managers (Musette, 2019). To support the implementation, European think tank of Higher Education Reform Experts, which was part of the network of Higher Education Reform Experts (HEREs) were invited to design and deliver training courses for experts who were actively involved in promoting higher education reforms in their own country. They provided advice to higher education institutions in the field of quality assurance (European Commission, 2017). The NTO

(National Tempus Office) also assisted MESRS in competence building via the training of Quality Assurance Representatives for higher education institutions and through the organization of conferences to advise on HE related issues (Benstaali, 2013).

Experts from other countries can foster greater externalization as suggested by Schneider (2015) who found that international academics in economics and political science from advanced economies are increasingly involved in development policy consultancy. These consultants are regarded as essential for both addressing capacity gaps and increasing the capabilities of local workers to carry out policy-related tasks.

The participants further argued that the fact that the government keenness on pursuing a n evidence-informed approach to policy making is a good step, but they also raised questions about who is accepted as a provider of evidence, for example through participation in commissions. A senior academic and consultant said that

in their [the Algerian government's, the author] defence I see them reaching out more and more to the experts etcetera. Now, of course, who are these experts, you can have question mark over that, because who gets in there and who does not. It's a different story, but at least the idea the philosophy behind is there or the thinking behind is that they are looking and seeking expertise from the from the experts and from the specialists (Algerian Education Consultant 2).

In Scotland, the establishment of a code of governance was among the recommendations embedded in the final report of the committee. To this end and following the publication of the review (2012), the Committee of Scottish Chairs (CSC) was entrusted with the responsibility for the production of the code following an agreement between the Scottish Funding Council and the then Cabinet Secretary for Education and Lifelong Learning, Michael Russell. To deliver this, the CSC established a steering committee, chaired by Lord Smith of Kelvin, which in turn commissioned consultants to collect evidence that would inform the formulation of the code. The steering group was instructed to take account of the recommendations from the von Prondzynski review, incorporating standards of good practice, identifying the separate duties (Scottish Government, 2013b; Committee of Scottish Chairs, 2013). In developing the code, the steering group consulted widely, including holding face to face meetings at each Scottish higher education institution and putting out an invitation to submit written evidence. At each HEI, separate meetings were held with student representatives, staff and union representatives,

governors (including lay members) and members of senior management. Over 360 people participated in over 78 meetings at institutional level. In addition, meetings were held with trade unions, the Scottish Government, and Scottish Funding Council (Committee of Scottish Chairs, 2013). These meetings were considered crucial by the steering group as it recognised that it needed to engage widely with institutions to gauge the opinions of staff and student representatives and existing governing body members. A draft Code was published for open consultation in April 2013 and the responses around the consultation were diverse. UCU Scotland objected fiercely to the consultation document and argued that it did not address the recommendations of the government's independent review of governance but instead raised questions which had already been answered in that report (University and College Union Scotland, 2013). Student unions that were not affiliated with NUS Scotland also took part in the policy debate. The student union of Glasgow University expressed serious concerns about the wording of the proposal and argued that it was an assault on universities' autonomy. They argued that requiring an institution to comply with principles of good management that "appear to Scottish ministers to constitute good practice" is vague and could vary depending on which government is in power (Glasgow University, 2013).

The code in its final form was published in July 2013 and came into force on 1 August 2013. UCU Scotland continued to have reservations about it as they argued that it drifted away from the panel review recommendations. In 2016, UNISON revealed that member feedback indicated that the code has made no difference to the way universities were run or the issues raised in their submissions to the Von Prondzynski review (UNISON, 2016) and further proposed that concrete examples of how the code identified failures in the sector and how amendments are going to take place should be highlighted. In this case, one can argue that the advice, opinions, and objections of those who were invited to contribute were largely ignored despite the fact that those policy actors expressed their frustration both publicly and at the earliest occasion (once the first draft was published) allowing sufficient time for amends, but that did not happen. Such indications strongly suggest that, in this case, policy advice was used in a symbolic mode (Weiss, 1979). This also further confirms Keating's (2010) claims that in Scotland Consultation does not always equate to influence.

Overall, the findings also contradict Halligan's (1995) admonition that: "The conventional wisdom appears to be that a good advice system should consist of at least three basic elements within government: a stable and reliable in-house advisory service provided by professional public servants; political advice for the minister from a specialized political unit (generally the

minister's office); and the availability of at least one third-opinion option from a specialized or central policy unit, which might be one of the main central agencies (p. 162)". Policy advice in Algeria as well as in Scotland was highly externalized as it relied on the expertise offered by external policy actors. This, however, did not mean that in house (internal) policy advisors were marginalized. The composition can be described as a healthy mix of both types.

6.3 Work of Panels

Many governments aspire to evidence-based policy and practice and the predominant, conventional approaches to using experts are either to seek the advice of one highly regarded individual, or to convene a panel with diverse expertise across relevant areas (Sutherland, W., Burgman, 2015). Thus, when academics and students at the universities of Strathclyde and Glasgow raised serious concerns in 2011 over the way their institutions have consulted on proposed cuts to courses and jobs at the time and the spiralling salaries of Principals and their management teams (Denholm, 2012). Michael Russell, the Education Secretary, announced that a panel would be set up to review higher education governance. The panel members, working under its chair Professor von Prondzynski, were Terry Brotherstone, STUC Nominee; Iain Macwhirter, Rector, University of Edinburgh; Robin Parker, President, NUS Scotland; Alan Simpson, Chair of Court, University of Stirling. Reflecting on the membership of the panel, a Scottish participant said,

Prondzynski, a very unusual one. He was a genuine intellectual and really quite interested in finding out more about Scots and working with them. So he was to chair this review. He was also clearly very favourable to the nationalists, and they appointed Ian McWhirter who was rector of the university and a prominent journalist who has written a lot about universities and so on. And then a student leader, Robin Parker, and then an early university trade unionist. So it was a very extraordinary panel (Member of a Scottish trade union 1).

Alastair Sim, director of Universities Scotland on behalf of the university principals, also supported the review as an opportunity to bring the sector together to discuss a highly important aspect, that of governance. "Universities Scotland has already been talking very constructively with NUS Scotland and UCU Scotland about governance arrangements and the review is an appropriate way to take these initial soundings forward". Alastair Sim welcomed, more

specifically, the cabinet secretary's decision to hold the review at "at arms-length from Government" describing the approach as "right" for the HEI autonomy (Universities Scotland, 2011).

NUS Scotland hailed the review and remained so afterwards as the body believed that there were clear areas in which the governance of Scottish institutions can be improved, with the aim of building on the traditional strengths of Scotland's universities (National Union of Students Scotland, 2013). Trade unions were also in favour of the decision and did not shy away from expressing their minds. The EIS applauded the formation of the Review and urged the Government to act on the increasing concerns arising from the current university governance system. The EIS responded to the Scottish Government's Review into Governance in Higher Education consultation (Educational Institute of Scotland, 2011).

The panel was entrusted with the following tasks: determining and assessing proposals for change that acknowledge the advantages of an autonomous sector while also reflecting the significance of complete transparency; evaluating the efficacy of management and governance, the clarity of the strategic purpose and its efficient implementation; and assessing whether the current institutional governance arrangements in the Scottish higher education sector deliver an appropriate level of democratic accountability given the public funding in place. The panel published its review and recommendations in February 2012 (Scottish Government, 2012). It made 17 recommendations relating to a variety of governance issues. Several of the recommendations have informed the provisions of two important legislative pieces: the Post-16 Education (Scotland) Act 2013 and the Higher Education Governance (Scotland) Bill. The Bill was introduced by the Cabinet Secretary for Education and Lifelong Learning on 16 June 2015 (Scottish Parliament, 2015). Two recommendations from the Prondzynski review are of particular importance to the provisions in the post-16 Education (Scotland) Act 2013: Recommendation 2.3, which requires the Scottish Parliament to "enact a statute" setting out the key principles of governance and management that would serve as the legal basis for the operation of HEIs. Recommendation 7.4, which states that the Scottish Funding Council (SFC) should commission a code of good governance for higher education institutions. Measures to respond to these recommendations are set out at section 2 of the Post-16 Education (Scotland) Act 2013: "The Scottish Ministers may, under section 9(2) [of the Further and Higher Education (Scotland) Act 2005], impose a condition that the [Scottish Funding] Council must, when making a payment to a higher education institution under section 12(1), require the institution to comply with any principles of governance which appear to the Council to

constitute good practice in relation to higher education institutions.” The key differences between the von Prondzynski review recommendations and the provisions at Section 2 of the 2013 Act are: The recommendation that the key principles of governance and management be set out in statute was replaced by a requirement that HEIs comply with “any principles” of governance that are thought to offer a model of good practice. The focus on establishing principles of good management and governance was replaced by a focus only on governance. The recommendation that the SFC lead on the development of a code of good governance was replaced by a provision simply saying that SFC could impose, as a condition of funding, a requirement for HEIs to comply with recognised principals of good governance, not that the SFC has to establish or maintain a set of principles. The von Prondzynski review recommendation to develop a code of good higher education governance for Scottish HEIs was supported by HEIs. At the request of the Cabinet Secretary for Education and Lifelong Learning, the Committee of Scottish Chairs took the lead in developing the new code.

Scottish Ministers held a consultation on November 7, 2014, to gather more feedback on proposals that would be included in a higher education governance bill, and they also proposed legislation to advance some of the review's recommendations. By January 30, 2015, comments on the proposals were requested, and those comments shaped the clauses that would be included in a Higher Education Governance Bill. Out of the 125 responses to the consultation, 53% came from individuals, 25% from universities and university representative bodies and the remaining responses came from various organizations, including local authorities, business and industry associations, unions, and student representative bodies (Scottish Government, 2019a).

The responses to the consultation were analysed by an independent consultant (Scottish Government, 2015). In the period between the consultation and the Bill being introduced, some of the proposals were either significantly revised or even removed. For example, the von Prondzynski review recognised the value of the Privy Council (a formal body of advisers to the Queen. Members include senior politicians and other senior public officials. Among its many functions, the Privy Council is responsible for advising the Queen on proposals from HEIs seeking to amend their royal charter). The review, however, suggested that “it is probably time to replace it with a framework that is operated entirely within Scotland and is capable of functioning both expeditiously and in a way that maintains existing safeguards” (Scottish Government, 2012; p6). The Scottish Government, in the consultation for the Bill, proposed establishing a Scottish Committee to replace the functions of the Privy Council. It argued that

a Scottish Committee could adopt a more flexible approach with this structure also potentially reducing the time taken to make amendments to governance instruments (Scottish Government, 2014b). The consultation responses on this issue were mixed. Some supported changes to the current arrangements, while others urged caution as the case for making such a significant change had not been fully made. On the basis of this feedback, the Scottish Government decided not to introduce measures to change the role of the Privy Council at this point. The Policy Memorandum notes that a further review of the role of the Privy Council in relation to higher education governance is needed before taking any legislative steps on this issue (Scottish Parliament, 2015a).

Post-16 Education (Scotland) Act 2013 (Scottish Parliament, 2013) did not prescribe specific principles or measures that HEI's should pursue to achieve good governance. However, in its consideration of the bill that preceded the 2013 Act, the Education and Culture Committee noted that the Scottish Code of Good HE Governance offered an appropriate mechanism to fulfil this requirement (Scottish Parliament, 2013).

6.4 Influence of Think Tanks

The commissions discussed earlier were visible to the public. Some of those participants who provided policy advice with the aim of shaping major higher education developments in Algeria and Scotland came from within the government itself. This claim is consistent with the literature on policy advice, which argues that most existing conceptual models of policy advice systems associate different levels of influence with the location of advisors either inside or outside government (Halligan, 1995) as explained in the Conceptual Frameworks chapter. Further, existing research indicates that it matters whether the nature of exchange is formal or informal (commissioned research, positions on advisory bodies or committee of inquiry, invitations to parliamentary committees versus informal networking, telephone calls (Brans, Timmermans and Gouglas, 2022)). Advice systems were thought of as arrayed into three general “sets” of analytical activities with participants linked to the positions actors hold in the “market” for policy advice. The first set of actors was thought to comprise the “proximate decision-makers” who act as consumers of policy analysis and advice – that is, those with actual authority to make policy decisions, including cabinets and executives as well as parliaments, legislatures and congresses, and senior administrators and officials delegated decision-making powers by those other bodies. The second set was composed of those “knowledge producers” located in academia, statistical agencies and research institutes who provide the basic scientific, economic, and social scientific data upon which analyses are often

based and decisions made. And the third set was those “knowledge brokers” who served as intermediaries between the knowledge generators and proximate decision-makers, repackaging data and information into usable form (Lindvall, 2009). In Scottish higher education, civil servants are seen by the participants as the backstage actors whose expertise and advice allow them to be key knowledge producers and knowledge brokers. One of the participants maintained that

the civil servants developed the policy and they give the politicians choices. But sometimes civil servants don't understand the complexities of the system. They may well put forward suggestions that have unintended consequences (Scottish Lobby Group Member 5).

Think tanks are one actor in policy advisory systems. The prominent examples, and most visible ones in the identified policy areas for this research, are those of IPPR Scotland and Reform Scotland. The former is, ideologically, rooted in the centre-left while the latter finds its ideology on centre-right grounds. Furthermore, SPICe (the Scottish Parliament's Information Centre) has played a role here too even though it is not, strictly speaking, a think tank given that it was set up to support Members of the Scottish Parliament. IPPR Scotland was part of the COWA committee as mentioned earlier in this chapter. IPPR also published a number of research papers, including a discussion paper on funding widening participation in higher education (Brown and Piatt, 2001) and on the skills system in Northern Ireland and Scotland with a set of recommendations on how to better improve the sector to meet the ever-increasing demands of the market Callander, Gunson and Murray, 2018).

Think tanks can provide detailed reports with policy recommendations as a readily available resource for policy makers in search of a solution. In addition, think tanks are a repository of “independent” and “scholarly” experts who can provide expertise that frequently represents a credible alternative to information coming from government or from the corporate sector. This information is used readily by the media, interest groups, business associations, trade unions, churches, NGOs, and social movements; it is often made available as a “public good” (Fischer, Miller and Sidney, 2007). Nevertheless, the level of influence depends on how close think tanks members can get to the government as stated by a board member of a British think tank who contended that

public policy is always kind of determined by a relatively small group, and I certainly benefited from that in that I was a part of that small group...within

the higher education landscape, the ones that get the greatest hearing are a select few (Scottish Think Tank member 1).

The Scottish Parliament's internal research centre on the other hand, is what McGann (2020) describes in his typology as a quasi-independent think tank, independent of the government but under the oversight of a donor, interest group, or contracting organization that supplies most of the funds and exercises considerable control over the think tank's daily operations. The SPICe team are information and subject specialists on a range of policy issues, who carry out research on behalf of the Parliament's committees and Parliament staff. The centre offers a confidential enquiry service to Members and their staff, create electronic resources and graphics as well as reports and briefings, help to commission and manage research from external providers, maintain and publish parliamentary data and information (The Scottish Parliament, 2022). SPICe's staff falls under what Haas (1992) describes as an epistemic community, which is a network of professionals with recognized expertise and competence in a particular domain and an authoritative claim to policy-relevant knowledge within that domain or issue-area. Think tanks are structured as permanent bodies and often act as a bridge between the academic and policy making communities and between states and civil society. They often claim to serve the public interest as an independent voice that translates applied and basic research into a language that is understandable, reliable, and accessible for policy makers and the public (McGann, 2020).

In terms of influence, think tanks are engaged in policy making at various phases. Based on John Kingdon's agenda-setting theory of the multiple streams framework, think tanks can be viewed as "policy entrepreneurs" who are most likely to have influence during the stages of problem framing, policy solution search, and promotion of particular solutions to legislators and the public (Pautz, 2020)

When assessing for example the influence of SPICe and IPPR Scotland, it can be argued that both have had a certain curbed influence. Mackenzie (2015) argues that government think tanks have several benefits over external think tanks, including their strong understanding of government programs and priorities (which helps them to tailor advice to actual needs) and an ability to coordinate across government departments. Government think tanks can become briefing machines focused solely on reacting to requests, rather than producing analysis and strategy that help inform policy.

This view was endorsed by Scottish participants who claimed that think tanks do provide knowledge and information, but would not enjoy direct access to policy makers, at least not at a regular basis. The participants also explained why the expertise and advice provided by think tanks do not enjoy enough attention in Scotland. First, think tanks were a new phenomenon, and the politicians simply did not know what to do with what they had to offer. Second, they were limited in their numbers.

Overall, to answer one of the most vexed questions concerning think tanks on whether or not they have policy influence, Fischer, Miller and Sidney (2007) argue that attempting to broker policy analysis to decision makers does not equate with immediate policy impact on forthcoming legislation or executive thinking. The authors further argue that relatively few think tanks make key contributions to decision making in local, national, or regional global fora, or exert paradigmatic influence over policy thinking. This is due mainly to two reasons as explained by a think tank member. First, the fact that the Scottish government has its own sources of information (the civil service). The second reason is that think tanks are a relatively new phenomenon in Scotland. Nevertheless, the situation has its advantages as it gave the think tanks available a strong voice. The shortcomings, are the lack of funding as explained by one participant:

The politicians and the officials aren't necessarily used to working with think tanks because there are so few...in terms of those influential organizations that sit around the system and...they haven't had the option of think tanks until recently and therefore often don't know how to use them and work with them...likewise in a similar way there is less funding in Scotland. Funders aren't switched on to funding think tanks in Scotland because there haven't been very many in the past (Scottish Think Tank member 2).

The literature partially agrees with the statements (in terms of funding) made by the participant as, according to Hernando, Pautz and Stone (2018), think tanks have faced three main obstacles since the late 2000s: limited funding in an austerity-driven world; heightened competition between think tanks and other policy research organizations; and a growing public discontent with the role of the "expert" itself.

In Algeria, think tanks are primarily governmental-dependent organisations or associated with official sectors. Often, they are intellectually and organisationally constrained by a number of governmental procedures regarding funding and senior appointments. They cover all policy

fields and have been said to have played a crucial role in guiding and rationalizing Algerian policies at the internal and external levels (Sahki, 2023). According to the General Directorate for Scientific Research and Technological Development (DGRSDT), there are currently about 29 think tanks and 12 research and development centres, in addition to 26 research units affiliated with universities and research centres in Algeria (The Algerian Ministry of Higher Education and Scientific Research, 2022b).

While there is a comparatively lively think tank landscape, the question is whether they matter when it comes to governmental policy making. Participants took very different standpoints on this question. Some participants were certain that the government is conducting a consensus approach for higher education policy development by inviting a diversity of policy advice sources into the deliberation process. A senior academic and a former university official in Algeria asserted that

I would say, frankly speaking, as professor for 20 years or so, the government run the sector in very interactive way. They have their own consultant and expert within their ministry, in their cabinet. Besides that, they have to develop a contact with others. And therefore, and I won't say it's authoritarian work, it's always consultative interactive (Algerian Independent Scholar 2).

Others disagreed with such claim, as they maintained that the government holds total control of the policy making in the country under the aegis of the Ministry of Higher Education:

On the outside, it seems purely democratic and involving every party and every agent. But for me, the reality is that policies are still going through a top-down process... the government agrees on the policy. I don't know if they pretend or it's real that they do consult the main agents of the higher education sector. Teachers, stakeholders, all of them. But I do believe that it is mainly top down. It's the government and then the stakeholders execute (Algerian Lecturer 2)

Despite the disagreement among the Algerian participants, the findings reveal that the Algerian Government did consult, at least for the designated policy areas for this study. These consultative efforts manifested in the setting of the commissions with a selection of experts pooling from different backgrounds, launching special electronic forums for the members of the HE sector to share their views and take part in the making of higher education policy, and

organizing conferences and symposia to bring all the interested parties together in a collegial air. This point is further investigated in the upcoming section.

6.5 Conferences and Symposia

Unlike the Scottish Government, which tends to set commissions with relatively small numbers of participants, the Algerian government seems to prefer conferences and symposiums as locations for the production of policy advice. Certainly, this approach signifies a change from a closed doors decision making format dominant up to the late 1990s. With regards to higher education policy, this more open and deliberative approach manifested in a national conference in 2016 to discuss the BMD system. Twelve years after its initial adoption in 2004, the BMD continued to be subjected to a series of criticisms by university officials and academics (e.g. Idri, 2005; Metatla, 2016), seeking to put pressure on the government to take action in the form of a comprehensive review of the system. Students also complained that Algerian universities were distributing degrees rather than nurturing excellence and producing competent graduates (Zaghlami, 2016). Commenting on the aspect of ignoring the feedback and advice provided by the sector, a senior member of the Ministry of Higher Education and Scientific Research admitted that “we started to see some difficulties...looking back, we didn't react in time to some negative evaluations. When we did react, we reacted late. In the meantime, the problem was still there.” (Algerian Government Official)

Confronted by growing criticisms of the BMD system, the higher education ministry organised a national conference to assess the system in 2016 and to develop ideas to improve it (Zaghlami, 2016). Within policy studies, conferences are theorized as sources of learning and as mechanisms for the movement of ideas and policies (Cook and Ward, 2012). They are places where policy actors build trusted relationships (McCann, 2011) and establish or maintain networks (Stone, 2012; Glaser and Brömmelstroet, 2022). Conferences can be defined as ‘periodic or one-off gatherings of people, often professionals, experts and those in positions of power, drawn from diverse places and organisations, with aims of producing knowledge or agreement on particular topics’ (Craggs and Mahony, 2014, P. 415). Conferences bring ideas, policy makers and sites into relational proximity. They offer opportunities for policy makers from different places to come together and share knowledge as well as to reflect on whether what they hear about can be emulated in their own localities (Andersson and Cook, 2019). These temporary events allow those with shared values and interests the opportunity for face-

to-face communication and knowledge exchange and influence decision-making processes (Temenos, 2016).

In Scotland, at the wake of the governance reforms, one of the decisive moments in the modern history of Scottish Higher education, and just before the government consultation closed, UCU Scotland and EIS held a joint Conference in 2011 where mass participation, globalisation, privatisation and the decrease in collegiality, in addition to the impact of English tuition fees on Scotland were heavily discussed (University and College Union Scotland, 2011b).

In Algeria, at the 2016 National Conference of Universities, the analysis of the BMD system extended to the socioeconomic sector regarding the implementation of the BMD system. Around 800 participants devised a series of recommendations to amend the shortcomings detected in the performance of the BMD system. The two-day conference saw the participation of the various actors in the sector, namely student representatives, social partners and university rectors as well as socio-economic partner establishments in the higher education sector (Algerie Solidaire, 2016).

The 2016 conference witnessed the participation of representatives of the national evaluation commission, the national university qualification commission and the commission responsible for establishing and guaranteeing quality in higher education, in addition to representatives of the Academy of Sciences and Technologies (a national independent advisory institution established in 2015). The preparation of the conference began two months before the designated date through the organization of polls on the ministry's website, part of which was intended for the public invited to express themselves on the "BMD" system. The Ministry had also distributed questionnaires at the level of university establishments and at the level of socio-economic sectors on the efficiency of the BMD system and its adequacy with the requirements of the job market. The results of this survey were the subject of the two-day examination to assess the higher education system in Algeria and the effectiveness of the reforms to which the sector has been subjected. In addition to the meeting, four workshops were organized and devoted to pedagogy, the relationship of the economic sector with the university, corporate governance and international cooperation in the context of reforms (DK News, 2016). Interestingly, during the opening of the conference works, Pr. Tahar Hadjar, former Minister of Higher Education and Scientific Research who chaired the National Conference of Universities pointed out that that system 'is not to be questioned' and stressed that the objective of the conference was to assess in order to 'correct' the approach by introducing recommendations

for the coming academic year. He also noted that the frequent use of BMD evaluation « is not the Algerian university characteristic » but it is a common practice for all universities operating with this system (Amina, 2016). Though policy makers rarely directly base new policies on evaluation results, evaluation has much to offer them (Weiss, 1999). Policy makers are exposed to evaluation results through a variety of channels, and they pay attention not only for guidance but also to demonstrate their modernity and expertise, defend policies, and balance out conflicting information. Some countries are generally more receptive to evaluation than others, owing to factors such as an open political system and a thriving evaluation community (Weiss, 1999).

The established diagnosis from the conference was that although the BMD system offers many benefits, it should be monitored more closely due to the potential for unintended consequences from the proliferation of pathways, specializations, and training opportunities (The Algerian Ministry of Higher Education and Scientific Research, 2018). Based on these conclusions, the Algerian Government decided to continue with the full adoption of the BMD system. Furthermore, the conference also raised some concerns over the socio-economic sector related to the employability of new graduates. Acting on these claims, the MESRS focused on the development of new educational programs, such as bachelor's and master's degrees that meet employer expectations; student mobility through a national credit system; the establishment of university spaces devoted to innovation and creation, such as technology institutes, technological platforms, and business incubators; new pedagogical practices centred on the future of graduates in the labour market. The other tactic used to meet the skills and training challenge is the creation of poles of excellence. These include the opening of technology institutes, university courses with national recruitment, master's programmes with integrated bachelor's curricula, and master's programmes in direct collaboration with the socioeconomic sector. Lastly, the MESRS has suggested institutionalizing this relationship in order to improve the integration of higher education institutions into their surroundings (The Algerian Ministry of Higher Education and Scientific Research, 2018).

As discussed earlier in this chapter, the Ministry of Higher Education sought the evidence at relatively the early stages of the policy cycle when formulating the policy as well as at the implementation stage, but it is not unusual for the policy advice to be needed at a later stage of the policy making process like the case with the BMD system in Algeria. In fact, Rutter (2012) maintains that it is possible to distinguish between two types of evidence (which merge into each other): pre-existing “evidence” which can help inform decisions and post intervention

evaluations which look at the impacts of policy and whether it is having the desired impact and what the unintended consequences might be. Well-designed evaluations can then inform the future evidence base (Rutter, 2012). This was the case of the BMD system, where the government chose to listen to the feedback and recommendations provided by the population. The concept of policy feedback refers to the variety of ways in which existing policies can shape key aspects of politics and policy making (Béland and Schlager, 2019) whereas the term evidence covers a wide spectrum including the emerging ‘qualitative’ feedback from citizens which open the way both to change policy and ‘collaborative co-design’ of services (Rutter, 2012). A view further endorsed by Fischer, Miller and Sidney (2007) who argued that the consideration of a broader range of expertise in assessing different policy options might lead to better outcomes as more evidence (lay knowledge, perceptions, and preferences) is considered to be part of the decision-making process. Nevertheless, despite the spaces open to all the actors to contribute their views, some felt excluded as they maintained that only high university officials like the rectors or the vice rectors were the ones who got a hearing. A lecturer at one of the Algerian Schools argued that

the director of the School, the rector of the university, I'm sure they have been maybe or they are usually consulted on some policies and maybe they meet and discuss certain policies. But to have us, I mean teachers and other administrators and researchers, directly consulted and knowledgeable about what is going to happen and maybe, for example, vote for something....this doesn't happen. We hear only of the change as such. So there is a new policy. OK, just adopt the CBA, adopt the LMD our points of view are not really discussed. Unfortunately, policies were just thrown at us like this and you have to adopt them and if they work or not, you take the full responsibility of that (Algerian Lecturer 2).

The same method for seeking policy advice was used in the field of quality assurance when the Algerian government needed a quality assurance system to fulfil the principles of the BMD system. The BMD system officially adopted in 2003 included requirements related to quality and standardization (Belimane and Chahed, 2021). The first initiatives were taken during two important meetings held in 2008. The first was at a symposium organized by the Ministry of Higher Education on June 1 and 2, 2008 in Algiers. The meeting was a collaboration with the World Bank, and involved all heads of higher education establishments, accompanied by teachers appointed to assist heads of establishments in setting up and promoting quality assurance systems, researchers from the OECD (Organisation for Cooperation and Development Economics), UNESCO and managers of quality assurance systems in the Arab

world. The question discussed during this symposium was: How should we proceed to successfully set up a Quality Assurance System at the level of higher education institutions in Algeria? The second meeting was held on June 3 and 4, 2008, which brought together officials from the MESRS, national academics and international experts in quality assurance. The official objective of this meeting was to design a "roadmap" essential for the establishment of a quality assurance system in higher education in Algeria (Kouraiche, 2019).

The OECD, an inter-governmental think tank, played an interesting role here. Generally, the OECD provides non-binding support to countries to inform policy making and implementation, building on evidence from reform experiences of other countries. Support ranges from ad-hoc expert input to events to OECD member, non-member countries and international organisations that enable policy dialogue to technical support and advice during the process of reform implementation. In this case, the OECD acted as an external policy advisor by providing technical support to draw up a strategy paper and action plan with the country's stakeholders to act as a tool for the reform implementation (OECD, 2022).

This gathering was unique in a number of aspects. First, the hybrid composition and the large numbers of stakeholders who shared their grievances and insights. Second, the recruitment of foreign policy actors and advisors. The Algerian Ministry of Higher Education and Scientific Research translated its attention to quality assurance through the creation of two previously discussed committees in 2010.

6.6 Conclusion

Looking back at the areas where policy advice was solicited by the Algerian and the Scottish Governments, several conclusions can be drawn as the two governments' approaches converged and diverged in some areas. First, it seems that the two governments were trying to mobilize external expertise to inform their higher education policy choices. Second, not every policy advice can influence the shaping of higher education in Algeria and Scotland due to the circumstances and the governments' agenda. Third, when looking at the two sets of actors (knowledge producers and knowledge consumers), it seems that the two communities shared the view that expertise is crucial for shaping higher education policies. However, in Algeria it can be noted that these two communities in particular do not speak the same language which makes the communicative and consultative efforts less efficient. It seems that the Algerian

government was willing to listen if those involved managed to come up with sensible recommendations instead of merely criticising the system. In that sense, it was important that the policy advice was tailored to meet the needs of the policy makers. For example, in the case of the BMD, the government insisted on keeping the system, whereas students and academics insisted on going back to the classical system, which created an irreconcilable rupture between the two communities (Caplan, 1979).

Chapter 7

Strategies Employed by Policy Advisers and Experts in Higher Education Policy Making in Algeria and Scotland

7.1 Introduction

This chapter analyses specific strategies used by policy advisers and experts in higher education policymaking in Algeria and Scotland touching on the identified policy areas discussed in the previous chapter (chapter 6). The first section addresses ‘evidence use’ as a strategy used by policy advisers and experts in policymaking between the two countries. The second section discusses the ways in which networks and relationships were used as strategies to influence policy directions towards policymaking in Algeria and Scotland. The third section highlights how expertise and epistemic authority contributed to delivering policy advice in both contexts. The fourth section examines the influence of engaging with government consultations and calls for evidence to shape higher education policies. The fifth section explores how public pressure and Lobbying influenced higher education policy in both contexts. The sixth strategy depends on communication Skills and a Belief in the Cause. The final strategy identified in this chapter is horizon Scanning and Policy Learning. Bringing the chapter to a close, a reflection on what makes a strategy works is explored.

7.2 The Use of Evidence

The interest and attention governments show towards particular issues is attributed to a combination of factors among which is expert opinions, including from consultants and commissions (Head, 2008). Under the administration of Tony Blair (1997–2007), the UK government sought to reinforce its policy development processes as it promoted Evidence Based Policy (EBP) as part of a broader plan to reform and improve the government by grounding its decision making in rigorous evidence instead of ideology and tradition (UK Cabinet Office, 1999). EBP principles are vested in the pursuit of vigorous and well-founded evidence and the subsequent rational integration of such evidence into the policy process as well as enhancing the quality and credibility of advice (Head, 2010a).

Policymaking is characterised by its complexity as it does not take place in a linear and predictable cycle instead it unrolls within intricate and multilayered environments characterised by a multiplicity of actors operates across various levels and branches of government, settings with unique rules and norms, connections between policymakers and influential stakeholders, a certain belief system or ideologies dominating the environment, and

sudden shifts prompted by particular events or conditions (Cairney, 2017). Despite these challenges, policymakers are steering research towards the identification of solutions in a demonstration of the advancement of the principle of “what works”, a universal movement originating from North America, and later influencing other regions (Ozga and Jones, 2006).

The surge in EBP practices is bound to certain circumstances. First, the shift in the broader societal and economic contexts which favours and values the systematic use of knowledge to ground decisions in evidence resulting in a culture that is more inclined towards demonstrable outcomes. Second, unlike past generations, the public has become more enlightened and better informed as citizens themselves are consistently basing their daily choices on evidence and expect their governments to follow the same path. Third, the early 21st century is marked by political pragmatism and governments are more oriented to choose what works, more receptive to successful policies and initiatives from other countries, and more ideologically flexible. Finally, the constant evaluations of performance by organizations such as the UN, World Bank, OECD, and EU tend to affect how governments are perceived both domestically and internationally which pressures governments to adopt proven solution to preserve their public reputation and keep attracting investments (Mulgan, 2005).

Evidence based policymaking, as set out in significant government publications (e.g., Cabinet Office, 1999), requires incorporating two types of knowledge: Academic or research knowledge (Episteme) which revolves around the insights produced by scholars and policy researchers, suggesting theoretical or causal explanations about what works best. The second type is Professional and institutional knowledge (Techne) which spans practical know-how about effective policymaking acquired through experience (Parsons, 2002). Whereas for some scholars like (Head, 2008, 2010a), there is a broader selection of sources which include political knowledge, which champions persuasive messaging and building coalition over objective evidence; Professional expertise which relies on the practical expertise needed to assess what is feasible in the real world; and experiential knowledge gained from the feedback of stakeholders. This knowledge is rooted in both domestic and international sources and evidence-based governance necessitates the methodical scanning for success experiences and lessons from other contexts following a well established tradition of borrowing policy ideas from abroad (Mulgan, 2005).

However, it is noteworthy to stress that when dealing with evidence-based policymaking, some types of evidence are prioritized than others creating hierarchies of evidence where randomized

controlled trials and systematic reviews are seen as more reliable and legitimate than other types of evidence (Deeming, 2014). This categorization of evidence sparked substantive discussions among scholars as some argue against the construction of such rigid hierarchies since the selection of the appropriate evidence depends on the specific context while others advocated the idea that what counts as applicable is driven by human judgement which makes it prone to bias towards certain types of evidence (Espey, 2023).

Evidence can come in different shapes ranging from policy briefs (concise and user friendly documents), blogs and social media posts (aims at a variety of audiences), Opinion pieces and press releases (to increase visibility), Engagement events (Roundtables, workshops, town halls, and media interviews to promote more engagement with stakeholders), to tools like the inverted pyramid (presenting the most important information first) and the message box (summarizing the core message) that works best into converting technical research into accessible content (Aiyede, 2023).

EBP's success prerequisites a set of conditions ranging from a reliable information system with accessible and updated data on economic, social, and environmental patterns provided by the government for better transparency and accountability, skilful human resources that can transform this data into applicable findings, a supportive political and organisational culture where policy makers support evidence based approaches, to mutual understanding and cooperation between researchers and policymakers (Head, 2010b).

The choice of the evidence depends heavily on the nature of the problem. Problems that are well defined with a curbed scope, which involves specific types of information and actors often calls for technical expertise provided by specialists. More complex problems that stretch over different sectors demand a collaborative approach that brings together different networks and partnerships each with their own type of evidence spanning from factual data to varied interpretations (Head, 2008). Yet, in practical terms, policy is rarely founded exclusively on objective scientific data but rather influenced by a combination of systematic arguments, professional judgement, stakeholder viewpoints, and political considerations. These variables led some experts to favour the term evidence-informed policymaking rather than evidence-based (Head, 2013).

Moreover, educational and social science research, more broadly, are often reshaped by contemporary "travelling" policy agendas which strive to make this research more applicable to policy making, an objective that seem more challenging in practice as the translation of

research into policy is both complex and problematic and far from straightforward (Ozga, 2004, p 3).

Mayne et al. (2018) support the argument that policymaking can never be 'evidence based'. At best, it is evidence informed. Using evidence by policy actors aspiring to make an impact on the policy was cited by the Algerian participants as well as their Scottish counterparts as one of the most effective and popular strategies to influence higher education policy. In Algeria, participants affiliated with Ministry of Higher Education insisted that the government is committed to evidence informed higher education policy making processes. One participant noted:

Yes, we know very well that any policy must be based on reliable data. That's clear and we have always worked to identify the information, because it's from reliable information that we can build our database, that we can also determine your strike force (Interview Algerian government official 1).

However, contribution through evidence use can be more effective if policy actors are included as part of the commissions advising the government. The success of this strategy in particular depends heavily on access first and being part of the right circles. Interviewees who themselves took part in different commissions or had colleagues who told them about the process, strongly believed that the higher education decision making in Algeria is not an arbitrary act but grounded in data and expertise as explained by a former Algerian vice rector:

We are in the process of commenting on figures... We have to do analyses to say why, for example, this or that. It's based on figures...The data are there. First of all, how do you explain that data and how do you then exploit it? I think that policies are not made like that in a random way, especially for higher education... I contributed to it because I worked in several commissions sometimes to draft a bill, for example, or to revise a bill (Algerian University Official 1).

The success to influence policy making is frequently highly context-dependent; and developing an evidence base for the type of asset-based, participatory initiatives favoured in the Scottish policy environment is difficult (Coutts and Brotchie, 2017). NUS Scotland, for example, had a specific department devoted to putting together reports, press statements, and conduct research to support the leadership of the organization. As a Scottish participant mentioned, and similarly to the words of an Algerian interviewee, contributing positively to the policy making is not only about pointing out the problem but about providing solutions and

alternatives. A former NUS affiliated student further emphasized that to make sure the policy advice is heard and well received “certainly high-volume research activity. We just need to do a lot of survey work and a lot of consultation to have good evidence for the policies we want to see” (Scottish Student Representative).

One example of evidence production and use to argue for policy change is the NUS work around student financial hardship. In 2008, NUS Scotland published a report examining the financial hardship many students were facing. The study showed that more than a third of students have considered dropping out because of financial hardship. Two-thirds of those were non-traditional students, or students whose parents did not have degrees (Lipsett, 2008). Based on the surveys conducted by NUS Scotland, UCU Scotland warned that students were seriously underestimating the basic costs of living at a time when student debt was reaching record highs. The two surveys backing the UCU’s claim were from NUS Scotland, and another survey of student finance by Push.co.uk, a non-profit organisation that supports school-leavers and students, particularly those from disadvantaged backgrounds (University and College Union Scotland, 2008). UCU Scotland argued that these surveys would make grim reading for students about to embark on their university careers (University and College Union Scotland, 2008). Two years later, in 2010, NUS Scotland issued a comprehensive piece of research, entitled ‘Still in the Red’. This report examined the student support system in Scotland, pointing out shortcomings of the system, but also its successes (National Union of Students Scotland, 2010). The evidence compiled by NUS Scotland served as a basis for other policy actors to form their understanding of the financial hardships Scottish students were facing. While in 2012, NUS Scotland led a survey following the students’ dissatisfaction with the consultation efforts around access, which concluded that 67% of Scottish universities ignored students’ views in terms of access agreement or paid little attention which contradicts the Office for fair access’ guidelines stressing the importance of consulting (Grove, 2012).

In 2011, the somewhat selective use of evidence caused a backlash between the policy actors opting for the same strategy in Scotland. In the run-up to the 2007 elections to the Scottish Parliament, First Minister Alex Salmond pledged to keep university education free for Scottish students, if his party were returned to government. The First minister, in doing so, dismissed concerns of university principals that Scottish higher education could fall behind (Black, 2011). Universities Scotland criticised the pledge and called again for the reintroduction of a graduate tax using one of the highest figures based on the impact of inflation (The Guardian, 2011). Scottish ministers provided counter-arguments by choosing different figures which

demonstrated that their policies work (The Guardian, 2011). Alex Salmond's officials believe Universities Scotland has been highly selective with the report's findings, by using a figure that included inflation and by ignoring the Scottish government's plans to charge English students up to £6,500 a year to study in Scotland (The Guardian, 2011). A funding model described by a Scottish participant as simply flawed,

I think the free tuition fee policy is reasonable if you actually cover the cost of the tuition as far as universities are concerned. But the Scottish Government doesn't do that. Therefore, the unit of resource that Scottish universities get to pay for the tuition of Scottish domiciled students is not sufficient to cover the cost of educating them, and that requires those universities to subsidize that post from other income sources. For many, in many cases, that would be through international students and that's a very potentially vulnerable business model and we regularly point this out to the Scottish Government (Interview Scottish Lobby Group Member 3)

This is an example of how evidence is produced and chosen to suit existing policy agendas and of how other expertise, presented as 'the evidence', is ignored. As mentioned in the conceptual frameworks chapter, this use of research was described by Weiss (1979) as the political use of research where policymakers resort to the selective use of evidence which serves best their political interests. In this scenario, the evidence becomes "an ammunition" for its holder (Weiss, 1979, p. 429). In other cases, the most compelling evidence can be ignored if it goes against the decision makers' values, beliefs, or political priorities or even selectively interpreted to align with what is politically suitable (Simmons, 2015).

However, as the literature indicates, for this strategy to work, evidence must also be tailored to meet the needs of policy makers as it is highly important for the research to provide concrete suggestions which explicitly consider implementation, economy and equity impacts (Vogel et al., 2013). Further, the conceptualisation of evidence based policy as a straightforward process where policymakers directly use the evidence generated by experts is neither realistic nor effective (Nutley, Davies and Walter, 2002).

Both Algerian and Scottish participants on the whole demonstrated a good understanding of these elements as they argued that evidence in its purest forms, detached from the context, is not the only criterion used by policymakers to decide on higher education policy related issues as other considerations must be taken into account. Independent academics and researchers harness their expertise and knowledge to produce and publish well-evidenced reports in an attempt to convince both the public of the policy and the policy makers.

Following this logic, an evidenced-based narrative on policy problem and policy solutions is helpful as it gives policy advocates a more powerful position from which to argue. When asked about the secret to influence the HE policymaking, a Scottish academic argued that,

I think it's having an evidence base behind you. So actually, laying out what this is, this is what's happening or this is the problem and having the data there and the evidence behind you (Scottish Independent Scholar 2).

This notion was further discussed and highlighted by Algerian interviewees who, in some cases, had experience both of seeking policy influence and of having power to make decisions:

If we want our policies to be listened to, to be implemented and promoted and financed, then we cannot present a project that is completely theoretical, we cannot present a project that has no immediate impact on society, an immediate impact on the economy, an immediate impact on the decisions made in this or that sector. That's the key to success. You have to convince the decision makers; you have to give them practical cases to show them how the university can be influential (Algerian Government Official).

This view was also echoed by another Algerian participant who contended that hard work and getting involved in the policy making world can and will eventually lead to success and influence as long as the case is well made,

You have to be enterprising because you have to be in a state of mind that says, 'Now the world belongs to the people who are directly involved in the field', and it is very important to say that not only verbally, but exactly, and by proposing, for example, demos, research, etc. Personally, I have set up research projects as part of the university training cluster and it worked because I was able to fit it a little with the existing orientations (Algerian University Official 1).

It is almost imperative to bring think tanks into the discussion around evidence use as these organizations house a pool of experts (Fischer, Miller and Sidney, 2007) who can provide services to both state and non-state actors. Further, think tanks do communicate ideas solely through the policy professional domains of seminars, conferences and publications. For example, in a 2013 conference on Higher Education, the Devolution Settlement and the Referendum on Independence, the Think Tank on widening access to higher education, which was part of the ESRC-funded Future of the UK and Scotland programme, raised a series of questions regarding inequality in higher education in Scotland (De Mowbray, 2013). In the briefing, a cluster of scholars including Sheila Riddell, David Raffe, Linda Croxford, Elisabet

Weedon and Sarah Minty outlined those policy developments which have focused on combating such inequality and reviewed debates on who should be included in widening access initiatives while placing Scotland in comparative perspective (Riddell, Hunter Blackburn, and Minty, 2015). Such contribution may not equate for immediate influence, yet it can inform the debate as explained in the Conceptual frameworks chapter under the Enlightenment model developed by Weiss (1979). This model makes no assumptions about the receptiveness or awareness of particular research conclusions among decision makers, nor does it assume that they will actively seek out social science research when faced with a policy issue. The idea here is that of social science orientations and generalizations seeping through to educated audiences and influencing how people approach social issues. Through a variety of channels, including professional journals, the media, and conferences with peers, social science research gradually spreads and, over time, equip decision-makers with a lens through which they can make sense of a complex world (Weiss, 1979).

Different strategies may be needed to be heard at each stage of the policy process, and the advice users at different stages may be receptive to different types of information packaged in different ways (Rich et al., 2011). An interviewee, a trade union board member, affirmed this by highlighting that evidence also needs to be presented in the right way to ‘do the job’:

So that's research and then that's really packaging the information out to the government, and we can do that by surveys or a number of other ways... the way in which we capture and then disseminate our policy objectives (Interview Member of a Scottish Trade Union 2).

In this regard, i.e. presenting evidence-based narratives and arguments as a strategy of influence, both Scottish and Algerian participants seem to show an air of awareness of how important it is for policy makers in both countries to receive a policy advice that is backed up by valid evidence and tailored to suit the needs of the cases they have at hand.

It remains contested that politicians often seek and strive for power, and their actions once in a power position are framed by ideological beliefs and the wider social, economic, and political context in which they operate (Harrison and Boyd, 2018). The mid-20th century witnessed a policy making environment charged with a competition between conservative, liberal, and socialist ideologies when each of these paradigms tried to provide an explanation of the foundation of policy. As a reaction of these views, EBP rose to challenge these views and sought to swap ideology with a more pragmatic, evidence-driven approach (Cairney, 2017; Espey, 2023). Moreover, grounding policymaking in evidence aims at advancing a dual agenda

to “modernise and depoliticise” the policy process through scaling down bias in decision making (McConnell, 2010, p. 128). Public policies rooted in empirical knowledge and informed by systematic and rational throughout the policy development and implementation tend to yield more effective outcomes than the ones guided exclusively by ideology (Demir, 2020). These views challenge some of the long-standing cultures of policy making since for scholars like Bevir and Rhodes (1999, 2003) who advocate for a governance practised through and with networks, policies embedded in governance are influenced by a mixture of traditions, narratives, beliefs and dilemmas instead of being driven merely by evidence. Based on their interpretive approach, policy is a lot more than a simple technical response to evidence, but rather a contested process negotiated among constellations of stakeholders, each with his/her own divergent values and unique personal world views (Bevir and Rhodes, 2006). Bevir and Rhodes (2003) in their discussions around a decentred approach, argue that in order to better understand people’s actions and beliefs, one must resort to learning through story telling as listening and sharing narratives can unveil what people think. In Bevir (2013), he further stresses that data, models, and expert knowledge are instrumental in these stories, but they remain interpretations stemming from assumptions about human behaviour. The author further explains that the success or failure of policy is heavily reliant on how different actors perceive and react from within their own cultural and institutional backgrounds where beliefs, traditions, and actions are core elements. (Bevir, 2013).

Furthermore, the decentred view emphasises how individuals call upon their inherited traditions to respond to specific challenges as competing actors promote different beliefs and courses of actions for the same problem crafting a mosaic of contested ideas shaped by peoples’ beliefs and experiences (Bevir and Richards, 2009).

This perspective is further endorsed by Ozga (2020) who contends that data are shaped by underlying policy choices and must be interpreted which strips it from its objectivity and self-explanatory features. The interpretation has political implications, but this is often concealed to protect the scientific legitimacy and authority embedded in the label “expert”. This view also triggers an overlooked issue in the literature of who gets to assess and decide what counts as reliable or sufficient evidence as critics argue that evidence is selected based on its suitability to advance certain agendas (Standring, 2016). This further highlights the need to examine whose interests are being served and what voices are being silenced when cherry picking the evidence which reinforces the idea that despite the fact that ideology is seen as an obsolete

feature of contemporary decision making, it still is an influential force (Harrison and Boyd, 2018).

A rigorous assessment of these competing views reveals that evidence-based policy culture does challenge existing cultures that are grounded in ideology and belief systems yet at the same time it layers into these previous practices. This is explained in Pahlman (2014) who contends that evidence does add a depoliticizing effect to the policymaking process and scientific research can inform and drive the decision-making process towards better outcomes, but evidence cannot be free from conflict and cannot eliminate the political dimension. Moreover, the use of evidence is inherently political and cannot be neutral or solely rational. These views highlight raise serious concerns about the selective use of knowledge to legitimize already made decisions and promote while limiting certain research agenda based on their alignment with specific policy goals (Ozga, Grek and Lawn, 2009). Hence, the term evidence informed policymaking is a preferred term in scholarly circles because it reflects how a mix of reasoned arguments, professional judgment, stakeholder perspectives, and political considerations shape policy (Head, 2013).

7.3 Networks and Interdependencies

As noted in chapter 4, the network approach to policy making is predicated on the idea that the relationships of influence among policy actors are the primary factors that shape policy making (Knoke, 1994). Actors influence others through a variety of interactions, such as information gathering and dissemination (Leifeld and Schneider, 2012), policy discussion, position-exchanging, or ally collaboration (Weible and Sabatier, 2007). The interviews maintained that policy actors in general usually find themselves motivated to create or join strong networks with other interested parties since personal relationships with politicians are challenging to establish and maintain (Lamont, 2021). Especially that if, when, and how evidence reaches policymakers in a way they can comprehend, trust, and use is determined by a complicated and context-specific mixture of players, institutions, and processes. The actors in the policy ecosystem require frequent opportunities to interact with one another, form bonds of trust and respect, and share knowledge in order to understand one another (The Hewlett Foundation, 2018). One interviewee, a senior academic from Algeria, stated that attempting to influence

policy making by building relationships and joining networks is not strictly unique to Algerian policymaking:

Of course, there is a question of having good relations with people and I think it's worldwide the same thing. If you know the person who is at a certain position, then this will help you to express yourself better (Algerian University Lecturer 1).

Governments in the Arabic speaking world have very tight relationships with universities, both public and private, given the centralised system of education which manifests in the planning, organisation, regulation, funding mechanisms, selection and hiring of leaderships, and decision-making through governing bodies (Sharaf and Helal, 2020) and Algeria is no exception to this statement as the ministry of higher education and scientific research sits at the centre of a complex nest of relationships executing the national policy for higher education including designing the national curriculum for both higher education and research in line with existing laws and regulations while coordinating and evaluating higher education across the country (The Government of Algeria, 2019). Universities depend on the ministry for full funding although they are also allowed to generate their own financial resources (Benstaali, B. (2013). This centralised oversight limits the institutional autonomy of universities, restricting their ability to innovate, differentiate themselves, or pursue distinct missions beyond the predefined directives of the ministry (Zidane, 2025). Despite the adoption of several reform measures, achieving true institutional autonomy is still far ahead since universities are still unable to define their own missions and objectives independently nor do they have the authority to allocate their financial and human resources freely based on their own strategic goals (Mezache-Bensaidane, 2017). This results in a high dependency from universities on their guarding ministry.

Despite its powerful position due to the centralised and bureaucratic nature of the Algerian system (World Bank, 2012; Schoelen, 2024), the ministry does not act in isolation from other actors. University officials such as rectors, deans, and vice-rectors act as mediators, taking ministerial decrees into institutional policy. Further, they have the responsibility to articulate and represent their universities' interests during the course of CRU and CNU deliberations. The conferences afford university leaders the opportunity to influence national policy decisions, lobby for funds, and consolidate their institutional representation in the sector and provide a rich pool of ideas and expertise (University of Boumerdes, 2023).

Data from relevant documents indicates that in Algeria, the Regional and National Conferences of Universities (CRU and CNU) provide the key policy field actors with the best opportunities to sharpen their networking strategies in order to advance their cases. As also discussed in Chapter 6 of this thesis, these conferences are spaces created by the Algerian Ministry of Higher Education for the exchange of ideas. In terms of connections, a senior consultant at the British Council distinguished two ways through which connections can be acquired; those who were born into them and those who forged them by means of previous collaborations and mutual principles:

Having the connections that help is important. But sometimes it depends on how you get to have these connections – because you may already be privileged, sort of born into these connections. But sometimes you can develop the connections and you develop them through a meritocracy because sometimes you work with some people in the decision making, then you can influence. You can advise them and then when they do have other opportunities or when they are working on other initiatives on other policies, they can come back to you and use you as a critical friend or as an expert again or they can ask you to recommend people (Algerian Education Consultant 2).

In Scotland, a similar view was raised by an interviewee who suggested that networking inhabits some form of negatively acquired power. The participant refused to attribute their success to joining networks and was even offended by the idea that she believed to be gendered and purely a man's perspective:

The connections, no! I don't think women see it this way. I think this is quite gendered, actually. I've got where I am not from who I knew, but from the fact that I worked really hard and that gave me a voice. I do not accept that it's about connections. I didn't prescribe to the sort of conspiracy theory that somewhere out there are a lot of people deciding it, all poor us. Not in Scotland anyway (Scottish Lobby Group Member 3).

This view was contradicted by another (male) fellow Scottish participant, who claimed that despite the Scottish consultative manifestos, Scottish public policy is the product of a narrow circle of people,

The public policy is always kind of determined by the entire on a relatively small group, and I certainly benefited from that in that I was a part of that small group. Within the higher education landscape, the ones that get the greatest hearing are a select few (Scottish Think Tank Member 1).

Algerian participants in the study stressed the importance of relationship building as they argued that networks, in a country like Algeria, can be easily forged, especially if positive personal relationships exist as a foundation. This was the personal experience of the vice rector of one of the Algerian universities who spoke about how a casual meeting over coffee turned into an international collaborative project in the area of international mobility:

To have projects of cooperation and external relations, everything depends on the relationship. It is the relationship that will then be institutional. For example, I go to France, Belgium for a colloquium and I meet the officials of cooperation, for example Paris University and in discussing together over coffee or lunch. I say my university has fields and subdomains, branches, departments, etc. They ask: 'Do you want us to do a project together?' I agree. It means that all that was the friendly relationship between us turned into an official project (Algerian University Official 2).

The literature suggests that instead of attempting to contact decision makers directly, it could be quicker and more productive to approach powerful people. Think tanks, for example, aim to connect research on interesting themes to individuals who can put it into practise since they have strong ties to decisionmakers (Thorpe, 2020). The same frequently applies to businesses, charitable organisations, and lobby and interest groups. By collaborating with these organisations to plan events or publish reports, one can gain access to their networks and contribute to the development of his/her own (Thorpe, 2020).

Networks are crucial for think tanks as they help them build liaisons with more influential players and expand their base of supporters, potentially enhancing their impact. Such connections, however, also push think tanks in the direction of advocacy, ideological confrontation, or partisanship and politicisation. The authority and credibility of organisations as impartial (or at least balanced) knowledge sources can be substantially undermined by too close a relationship with the government, a political party, or NGOs, and this might potentially erode key distinctions between the research institute and advocacy group (Fischer, Miller and Sidney, 2007). Such considerations explain why the Scottish interviewees stressed the fact that the think tank they were affiliated to was and continues to be neutral. The same goes for trade unions, as a former UCU member who took an active lead during the governance reforms in Scotland mentioned that the union had a good relationship with the Education. Such connection may explain, to a certain degree, the success UCU Scotland has had in terms of influencing the policy developments around governance, and the subsequent events leading to the drafting of the 2016 governance act.

Michael Russell, the education secretary who we got a good relationship with and who actually quite thought it would be quite a good idea to show the vice chancellors who was boss as it were, because...vice chancellors were becoming notorious in terms of the enormous salaries that they were getting (Member of a Scottish Trade Union 1).

In Algeria, some participants linked the act of acquiring or building such relationships with the decision makers to being loyal to the Ministry of Higher Education and Scientific Research. In other words, those who show loyalty and more support to the decisions of the ministry, will have higher chances be included in the consultative discussions. This was discussed in chapter 4 where, under the normative approach (a variant of the institutionalist theory), policy actors tend to have strong allegiance to their institutions. An independent academic and a prominent figure claimed that:

the rector of the University of Constantine has been one of the main influential "leaders" for almost 20 years. But he owes this role more to his loyalty to MESRS than to his discourse which is always limited to the application of ministerial programmes (Algerian Independent Scholar 1).

A similar stance was adopted by a senior Scottish academic who asserted that “the Scottish Government has a narrow range of bodies that mostly agree with them. They don't like to hear disagreement” (Scottish Independent Scholar 1).

In Scotland, the regulation of Scottish higher education involves several interdependent actors, each with defined roles but closely linked through linkages of accountability and mutual collaboration. The Scottish Government’s Lifelong Learning Directorate (LLD) leads the development of higher education policy and provides overarching oversight of the sector whereas the SFC is directly accountable to the Scottish Government through the LLD. The SFC acts as the primary implementer of government policy, converting policy into actionable regulation and tracking progress. This direct accountability reflects a clear top-down dependency from SFC to the government. The SFC’s regulatory role is enacted through its Outcomes Framework, with performance monitored via direct engagement with institutions or through partnerships with sector organisations (QAA Scotland and the Higher Education Statistics Agency) (Cobbett, 2025). This interwoven set of interactions highlight the interdependencies in the Scottish sector, where Universities are held accountable to the SFC through outcome agreements, and the latter reporting back to the government. This however does not undermine the institutional autonomy of Scottish universities. In 2023, the European University Association (EUA) published the University Autonomy Scorecard where Scotland

scored a 100% in terms of organisational autonomy, 80% for financial autonomy, 96 for staffing autonomy, and 89% for academic autonomy (Edinburgh Global, 2023). In Scotland, Universities Scotland as a network is responsible for shaping policy on behalf of the sector and publicly advocating on key higher education issues while working in collaboration with Universities UK (Universities Scotland, 2022).

These insights can be viewed through the lenses of the institutional setting of the country and its political system. Metz and Brandenberger (2023) who scrutinized the issue of the political system where these networks operate, maintained that political systems both facilitate and restrict actors' capacity for power concentration and cooperation, which in turn shapes policy networks. These results imply that institutional structures in which actors act also influence policy making, in addition to actors' steering capacity. Through its facilitation and restriction of negotiations between opposing political camps, the institutional context shapes the behaviour of actors within the network.

In the Scottish higher education context, building networks to support certain causes or to influence the policymaking in certain areas is a key strategy. However, in terms of efficiency, the interviewees were sceptical about the actual degree of influence these networks have in real life but quite assertive on how open these networks are. A trade union member stated that:

there are definitely networks. I would say that those networks in higher education are more pronounced... if you look at the royal Society of Edinburgh...you find senior civil servants, senior college, university and college people come together and just maybe one or two trade union people, senior Funding Council people. So, I would say that there is a nexus, if you like, of senior college people, senior university people, senior civil servants and senior Members of staff from the Scottish Funding Council. Is it open? No. Is it effective? Who knows? (Member of a Scottish Trade Union 2).

When discussing the openness and closeness of policy networks, Marsh and Rhodes' work is instructive.. They distinguish between different types of networks according to the closeness of the relationships within them (Marsh and Rhodes, 1992). In terms of the extent to which the interviewees regard such networks as ideologically closed or open, the answers differ significantly. Those who belonged to these networks argued that these were open for anyone willing to join. One participant claimed that "I would characterize that network as being collegial, mutually supportive, well informed and uncompetitive" (Scottish University Official 1). Those outside the network argued otherwise. A former Scottish Funding Council member stated that "It is exclusive and ideologically narrow" (Member of a Scottish Statutory Organisation 1).

A final aspect in being part of a network is what members can gain from such affiliation. In this study, interviewees argued that the key to policy influence is having a person's name dropped frequently. This act will give the person in question a popularity among policy makers who will eventually use their services. An academic who worked closely with the Scottish Government stated that "you get that first leg up. Because somebody in your organization was on a committee and then recommended you. That's what happened with me. But it was because there was already that network between senior people" (Scottish Independent Scholar 2).

Nevertheless, the probable and inevitable personnel turnover is one particular downside for the networking as it can take years for a policy actor to build the needed liaisons or gain acceptance among a specific network only for the members to change or shift careers. This notion was brought up by the Scottish respondents, as explained by a former member of the Scottish Funding Council who argued that

in terms of personnel, so you might have convinced one or two people and then you turn around and then they've got a different job or they're no longer in the Parliament and you've got to start again. So it's a bit difficult (Scottish Lobby Group Member 1).

This is consistent with the literature, as it has been argued that with high levels of staff turnover mean that once you have found a useful contact, they are unlikely to be in position for long. On top of this, there is considerable movement of staff between or within departments, often with officials moving to new policy areas (Thorpe, 2020).

In Both the Algerian and Scottish context, student unions seem to share a similar relationship with the main actors in the sector, mainly their respective governments, as in both countries, the governments offer recognition and a communication channel whereas student unions provide representation, feedback and engagement. In Algeria, MESRS enjoys a reciprocating relationship with student unions. Student unions play an influential role as they act as a channel through which students can engage in monitoring and contributing to the implementation of educational policies and practices and pursuing quality and excellence (Yahiaoui and Addad, 2025). On the other hand, the ministry offers institutional recognition. However, the relationship between these groups and the university officials is a bit strained as university administrations often fail to recognize the importance of student organizations and safeguarding them from administrative or faculty interference or intimidation. This usually means a minimal influence on decision-making despite the fact that student unions are granted the right to participate in institutional processes (Yahiaoui and Addad, 2025). In Scotland, NUS

has played a leading role in securing major victories for students and has driven progress on wider social issues as explored in previous chapters such as urging the Scottish government to fully adopt the Cubie report recommendations (BBC News, 2000) and warning the government that they are way behind in terms of widening access (BBC News, 2012). Beyond campaigning, NUS Scotland also works to protect student interests, particularly when they are at risk of being overlooked. During the COVID-19 crisis, the organisation united to demand safeguards for student tenants, improved digital access, and support for those facing financial hardship (National Union of Students Scotland, 2022). NUS Scotland had its ways in holding the government accountable to its promises and made sure students' best interests are a priority for the government through collaborative partnership with trade unions especially UCU Scotland as explored under the strategies subsection (University and College Union Scotland, 2010). Algerian trade unions evolved in a politically charged context (Djabi et al., 2020). This led to the creation of a complex relationship with the Algerian MESRS as these bodies despite their history and influence still need recognition from the MESRS to operate in the sector. For example, in 2019, the ministry published a well-defined list of six accredited unions: The National Union of University Professors (SNEU), The National Council of Higher Education Professors (CNES), The National Union of University Hospital-Based Research Professors (SNECHU), The National Federation of Workers in Higher Education and Scientific Research (FNTES), The National Federation of Public Administration Employees in the Sector (SNAPAP), The Independent National Union of Higher Education Employees (SNAPES) (Echourouk online, 2019). This variety of unions reflect a democratic space for influence whereas the list provides the unions with the necessary legitimacy to negotiate and represent the workers in the sector. The relationship between these two can be described as adversarial at times especially when the unions feel left out of the policymaking process in major reforms like that of the LMD (Echourouk online, 2014a). Unions have the power of paralyzing and disrupting through continuous waves of strikes as a mean of showing dissatisfaction with the ministry as it was the case in 2014 when negotiations between the unions and the ministry failed (Echourouk online, 2014a). Even in that scenario, the ministry still had the upper hand as it threatened to illegitimize the strikes under existing laws. Trade unions in Algeria often describes the ministry as dismissive of their demands which made the relationship even more troubled. However, the ministry would acknowledge the grievances and show willingness to meet and discuss as the case when the previous Minister of Higher Education and Scientific Research Tahar Hadjar acknowledged the issues raised by university communities and their

unions in 2018 (Bensouiah, 2018). These examples demonstrate the push and pull characterising the relationship.

In Algeria, think tanks are often overlooked as policy development relies more on internal governmental expertise than on external analytical or strategic input (Sahki, 2023). The same goes for academics who often experience personal uncertainty about whether or not to engage in research. This hesitation is driven their frustration and dissatisfaction with the ministry's policies and its ways in running the sector as they were when the state decided to operate with two distinct systems (i.e., LMD system and Classical one) (Shoelen, 2024). Moreover, academics depend on their universities for funding which comes predominantly from the ministry of higher education (El-Ouahi, 2024) Yet, the rigid procedures often come in the way. These factors resulted in a rupture in the relationship between academics and think tank members and the ministry. The case for Scottish think tanks is a bit similar as these organizations often suffer from a restricted influence over policy debates (Fawcett, Sloan, and Gunson, 2021).

7.4 Expertise and Epistemic Authority

McCready and Winterstein (2017) address the issue of why we trust what other people say, and form beliefs on the basis of their speech. This is mostly because they have epistemic authority. This implies that in relation to a specific topic, the other person (or institution, or group) is considered to be authoritative in what they say. This view was widely adopted among the interviewees who maintained that 'competence imposes respect' (Algerian University Official 3). Further, the participants argued that the expertise a certain actor possesses, and displays is an important venue (an arena or organisation in which people come together to make and influence authoritative decisions as defined by Mayne et al., 2018) through which he/she can be recognized in the field of higher education policy. The actors' expertise becomes their distinctive trademark, which sets them apart from the crowd and allow them to be selected to take part in closed consultations and issue-specific commissions. The quote illustrates this notion:

You have to show some kind of expertise and knowledge and the good command in your area of expertise, and you are asked to contribute. I was involved in the Commission by the Ministry of Higher Education to introduce English (Algerian Independent Scholar 2).

Similarly, Scottish participants asserted that “being able to demonstrate your authority in your expertise and then in turn being able to use that to influence the right people” (Interview Scottish Think Tank Member 1).

Algerian participants perceive being summoned as experts by the Algerian President's Office as the most compelling recognition of their significance, expertise and epistemic value. A former minister of higher education explains:

First of all, I was called because of my experience in the sector, I brought my experience. The difference for me is that I only worked on the higher education aspect and those that I solicited, they are also actors of education who have succeeded in this mission and it is with this community of actors who succeeded in this mission that we set up the action program [...] I was also speaking with knowledge. It is not someone who is disconnected from the sector and who comes to speak or make proposals about the sector, while he himself is disconnected from the sector (Algerian Government Official).

The participants also mentioned persistence and not taking no for an answer, among other personal qualities, as a fundamental strategy for success, and that success can come from small steps and not being afraid of trying new moves, or what Mayne et al. (2018) referred to as the tactic of embracing trial and error:

I think having the patience, the resilience, being able to bounce back because sometimes you may work on initiative and so if it doesn't work and maybe you contribute it and you say no, no, no, my input was not valued and it was not, taken into consideration you may just give up. Some people, they just lose faith and they think no matter what you do, you will not change things. Other people have done small steps than they did a few changes and it did work and so this can encourage them to pursue more changes and to invest more. In the end, I think it will boil down to who the person is, what they think, what motivates them (Algerian Education Consultant 2).

In this regard, Sutherland and Burgman (2015) for instance argue that experts who are routinely close to the right answer and confident in their knowledge tend to be called upon to supply more information to decision makers than experts who are infrequently off-target or lack confidence.

Counter to these claims, Hufen and Koppenjan (2014) point out that scientific knowledge, experts, and knowledge institutions increasingly have difficulty gaining authoritative and influencing policies with the proliferation of knowledge sources, offered by media platforms,

which provide an alternative source for critical review of scientific results for both laymen and policymakers. A view discussed by some of the Algerian participants who maintained that

there are so many factors that can play a role in being heard... hard work for sure But, unfortunately, the hard-working class of teachers and of academics and of practitioners are just marginalized sometimes, which is a pity. They are marginalized because they don't have power, they don't have money. Maybe they don't have a position in a political party, they are not close to the government. These are the considerations I see as more important in my country (Algerian Lecturer 2).

The literature on political parties seem to agree with such views. Burstein and Linton (2003) for example argued that Political parties are heavily involved in the policy making process. They identify issues facing society, put forth solutions, compile public policy preferences, energize voters, place demands on elected officials, inform their supporters and the general public about government actions, and enable reasonably coherent legislative action. In Algeria, political parties have come under fire from civil society actors for their lack of transparency and weakness in upholding their own internal democratic processes, despite their rhetorical promotion of democracy (Bertelsmann Stiftung, 2022). One persistent issue is the limited availability of information to the public and media about public procurement, party and campaign financing, and the state budget. It is only since the 2019 presidential elections that candidates have been compelled to disclose their funding sources (Bertelsmann Stiftung, 2022).

7.5 Engaging with Governmental Consultations

One of the most effective strategies of influence in consensus seeking countries like Scotland is by policy actors getting involved in the consultation process launched at the formulation or evaluation phases of the policy process. When the Scottish Government decided to review higher education governance policies in 2011, a call for evidence was launched which witnessed the participation of a variety of stakeholders (UCU Scotland, NUS Scotland, Universities Scotland, CREID, among others). Although taking part in the panel itself would be the ideal opportunity to influence the policy first hand, expressing the views and opinions of those who are members of the policy community through submissions and presenting oral evidence can also inform the policy debate. For example, in this case, the panel's final report included several Universities Scotland recommendations. In the area of widening access to higher education in Scotland, the von Prondzynski review recommended "the drawing up of a code of good governance for Scottish higher education" (Scottish Government, 2012, P. 6). This mission was entrusted to the Committee of Scottish Chairs and led by a Steering Group

Convened by Lord Robert Smith of Kelvin, which consulted widely and extensively during the formulation stage. From November 2012 to January 2013, all Scottish higher education institutions participated in a comprehensive consultation process. To gather the opinions of people involved in and impacted by governance in the higher education sector, 80 separate meetings with staff members, including trade unions, students, governors, and senior management, were scheduled. Further meetings were scheduled with NUS Scotland and the recognized trade unions, which included the STUC, UNISON, EIS, UCU Scotland. Stakeholder input was also solicited during another eight-week consultation period on a draft Code (Scottish University Governance, 2013). In addition to what the Committee of Scottish Chairs described in the 2013 code preface as “a direct engagement with the Education and Culture Committee of the Scottish Parliament” (Committee of Scottish Chairs, 2013b, P. 1). The consultation responses were classified into three categories: Anonymous; individual such as Professor Thomas Munck, Professor Stephen White, and academic Paddy Lyons among others; and organization responses such as the National Union of Students Scotland, Quality Assurance Agency for Higher Education (Scotland Office), Scottish Funding Council, The Educational Institute of Scotland, Royal Conservatoire of Scotland, Royal Society of Edinburgh and UNISON among other Scottish universities as well Scottish Government (2012a).

On the outside, the consultations seemed to reflect the participatory nature of the Scottish policy making style (Cairney, Russell and St Denny, 2016). However, the publication of the code in its final form caused a serious backlash and criticism from both academic and student unions and trade unions who described the code as meaningless, vague, and incredibly disappointing and urged the government to reject the code and implement the recommendations of a 2012 review by Ferdinand von Prondzynski (Mathews, 2013; UNISON, 2016). It is noteworthy to highlight from the Scottish experience in the case of the early forms of the code of governance that engaging in the consultative calls launched by the government does not guarantee direct influence over the higher education policy. This view is echoed in Keating (2010, p. 108) who claimed the wide range of consultations in Scotland does not necessarily reflect influence or yield “concrete results”.

The same consultative principle was applied when Scottish Ministers held a consultation on November 7, 2014, to gather more feedback on proposals that would be included in a higher education governance bill, and they also proposed legislation to advance some of the review's recommendations. By January 30, 2015, comments on the proposals were requested, and those

comments shaped the clauses that would be included in a Higher Education Governance Bill. Out of the 125 responses to the consultation, 53% came from individuals, with many indicating that they were affiliated with a higher education institution (HEI). Universities and university representative bodies provided 25% of the responses. The remaining responses came from various organizations, including local authorities, business and industry associations, unions, and student representative bodies (Scottish Government, 2019a). In 2015, and based on rigorous analysis of these submissions, a report was made public by the Scottish Parliament's Education and Culture Committee (Scottish Parliament, 2015) followed by proceedings for stage 2 and stage 3 which detailed the final amendment (Scottish Parliament, 2016a; Scottish Parliament, 2016b).

In 2010, the Scottish Government launched a green paper on higher education, entitled 'Building A Smarter Future' in the Scottish Parliament (Scottish Government, 2010a). The intention with this paper was to stimulate a debate on how to find a 'Scottish solution' to the funding of higher education in Scotland. In total there were 115 formal responses to the green paper. These responses included 28 responses from individuals such as students, parents, staff and people who used to work in the sector and 87 group responses from institutions and other organisations including a local authority; business organisations such as CBI Scotland; student representative organisations such as NUS Scotland; youth organisations including Scottish Youth Parliament; subject specific representation; wider access forums; sector skill representatives; and trades unions. Based on these responses, the key aspects of the policy were to close any funding gap without resorting to the imposition of tuition fees, upfront or deferred (Scottish Government, 2010b).

Overall, participants did not seem satisfied with the nature of the consultation. A scholar in the field argued that the government offered them a specific list of boxes to tick instead of a free space to articulate their demands:

We are consulting on our policy about student fees for example...there may be fairly open questions, but quite often they're not dealing with the fundamental issues. And yes, at the end there will be a space for any other comments. So, an awful lot of the reporting about the consultation is reporting in response to a predetermined question that they've decided are the important questions which I have always found really frustrating because you think no, no, no, no, that's not actually what's required here. You're asking the wrong questions, or you're not asking enough of the right questions, at any rate (Scottish Independent Scholar 5).

The consultative approach in Scottish higher education policy making seems to be a plus for the sector despite the criticism it received as evidenced by the findings of the study. The disappointment expressed by the Scottish participants is legitimate and stemming from their devotion to the higher education sector and the people involved and impacted by the policy developments.

7.6 Lobbying and Pressure

Lobbying was another strategy policy actors in Algeria and Scotland used to contribute to or influence policymaking. Lobbyism seeks to exert pressure on decision-makers and persuade them to act or decide in certain ways. Resisting such pressure carries the danger of ruining one's reputation or losing votes (Hanegraaff, De Bruycker and Beyers, 2016; De Bruycker and Beyers, 2018). Gaining access (insider lobbying) and going public (outsider lobbying) are the two primary lobbying tactics. The goal of getting access is to directly influence decision-makers to support and, if feasible, approve the interest group's preferred policy. Conversely, going public is a more covert tactic that seeks to exert pressure on decision-makers through media campaigns or by organizing people for demonstrations (Weiler and Brändli, 2015). A vital aspect of insider lobbying is information. Politicians struggle with time constraints and the resulting lack of sufficient information because they have limited resources and time. Interest groups provide information that gives policymakers quick access to expert knowledge, which is typically well-researched and summarized. For this reason, the information is widely valued (Weiler and Brändli, 2015). Further, expert committees, agencies, and advisory bodies are the enclosed spaces where the technical merits and demerits of policies are thoroughly examined. Policy actors wishing to enter arenas must demonstrate their legitimate and reputable expertise (Beyers, 2004). Outside lobbying efforts speak to legislators in a roundabout way. Rather than pursuing direct access, advocates use a variety of public media platforms to spread their political message and mobilize a larger audience (Hanegraaff, De Bruycker and Beyers, 2016). Consistent with the literature, Scottish participants brought up outside lobbying as one potentially promising strategy in Scotland due to the size of the country. Instead of speaking with officials directly, outside lobbying uses public avenues for policy change advocacy. Amongst these avenues are media engagement, the issue of press releases, awareness campaigns, and protest rallies or publicity stunts (Hanegraaff, De Bruycker and Beyers, 2016). Within the Scottish context, it seems that lobbyism via the media, both electronic and print, has worked well for some interviewees: A trade union board member maintained that

I do think there is an element of size when it comes to the media influencing the government. There is the perception that if the Scottish Government, which is relatively small player, you know which is susceptible to public opinion, which is susceptible to a few headlines and in one or two newspapers such as the BBC website, the Herald, maybe the National, if there's some impact in those small media players, really the Scottish Government I think is more susceptible to pressure than a larger government such as the UK (Member of a Scottish Trade Union 2).

Algerian participants talked with more caution about the influence lobbyists can take via the media on policy makers. They differentiated between the presidency of Abdelaziz Bouteflika, between 1999 and 2019, where a severely limited number of media channels existed, and today's more diverse and pluralistic media landscape:

And of course, you do have the 4th power and the media because then this also can influence and play a different role. Of course, you will have some triggers and some of the actors I just named who can be behind the media, but who can also use the media, you know, for their own sake or to influence some decisions. The opening of all these private channels and media outlets... So it's no more the mainstream media, but all these private media which itself is not that innocent because themselves... they have behind them political parties or oligarchs at a certain time before the fallout of the former president (Algerian Education Consultant 2).

It is noteworthy to highlight that it was not until 2011 that three independent broadcasters were authorized Echorouk TV, Ennahar TV, and El Djazaïr TV. These platforms operate unhindered in Algeria despite having their transmitting stations located abroad. The government is close to all of the broadcasters. The state monopoly in the broadcast industry was officially broken in 2014 by new legislation (Bertelsmann Stiftung, 2022).

Examples of outsider lobbying from Scotland encompass demonstrations and publicity stunts organised by students and NUS Scotland. The pressure NUS Scotland exerted paid off as the SNP 2007 manifesto set out an intention and included a pledge to scrap the graduate endowment scheme while also replacing “the expensive and discredited Student Loans system with means-tested student grants” to meet everyday living costs while studying. The emphasis was on students “ability to learn, not ability to pay” (Scottish National Party Manifesto programme, 2007).

In 2010, snowballs were thrown towards the Scottish Parliament by students as part of nationwide protest actions against tuition fees. On the same day, a march of about 300 people

stopped at the council city chambers with a homemade coffin with the words "RIP education" written on it (MacLeod, 2010). These limited outsider lobbying attempts followed a period when NUS Scotland relied on insider lobbying. When a new NUS president, Liam Burns, was elected in 2011 the union adopted an approach that flipped into more, hard campaigning (Interview Scottish Student Representative). Under Burns, the NUS decided to switch from insider to outsider lobbying, Burns was enthusiastic about direct action for as long as it was not violent or law-breaking: Speaking after his election he said there would be more local protests and "civil disobedience", in the form of sit-ins, occupations and demonstrations (Coughlan, 2011). NUS Scotland under Burn's leadership priority was to put dismantling the fee regime into the political parties' manifestos, which eventually happened (Morgan, 2011). In the following years, the NUS pursued an approach that prioritised outsider lobbying over insider lobbying as explained by the participants. Outsider lobbying is about public advocacy of ideas – these ideas are, usually, based on some form of evidence which the organisers of outsider lobbying use to promote their perspectives. NUS campaigned in fairly traditional way, through demonstrations and publicity student. But the demands which were vocalised at the events were based on evidence – and interviewees found that outsider lobbying could only benefit from a sound evidence-base:

That evidence led campaigning was backed up, of course, by stunts and demonstrations and leafleting and that sort of thing. And again, that's been a debate within the student movement. Do we go out on the streets and campaign? Or do we lobby government from the inside?" (Scottish Independent Scholar 4).

Most participants argued that choosing the right strategy was a constantly relevant discussion at the organization. A former NUS member claimed that "it was very technical. What do we do? Or it was marching and protesting or getting front pages on newspapers or into manifestos commitments" (Scottish Think Tank member 2).

Funding was not the only area where NUS Scotland sought to use lobbying strategies for influence. In 2012, NUS Scotland announced that student representatives were not consulted "adequately" in the debate around the financial support for undergraduate students (Grove, 2012). Following the publication of the COWA report, NUS Scotland tried to keep pressure on the Scottish Government to make progress on widening access targets and ensure full implementation of the Commission's recommendations. NUS Scotland also expressed support for students' associations to see the recommendations implemented on their campus and lobby

their institution for greater progress (National Union of Students Scotland work plan, 2016/2017).

A similar strategy was adopted both by Algerian student unions and by trade unions in reaction to the implementation of the BMD system. A prominent example manifests in 2014 when students of the “BMD” system (as opposed to those of the previous system) paralyzed the various institutes and universities, protesting the ambiguity that accompanied the application of the certificates obtained and their inconsistency with the conditions of competitions in public employment, not to mention the various problems facing students in the lack of pedagogical supervision. The Secretary-General of the National Organization of Algerian Students, Fares Ben Jaghlouli, told Al-Shorouk that the majority of students from 48 states such as Batna, Annaba, Oran, Medea, and Djelfa participated in the protest movement, pointing to the recording of many abuses by university officials in an attempt to put pressure on students to return to study. The protesters called for addressing the problem of framing graduation notes, reconsidering the strategy of evaluating professors and holding them accountable in the event of a high failure rate, and submitting objective reports on the phenomenon of failure in some universities and majors. Ben Jagholi threatened to continue protesting if university presidents did not comply with the minister's instructions to open the door to dialogue and involve students in various decisions (Echourouk, 2014b).

Students hold the power to shape higher education policy when they come together under one unified body with the mission to represent and defend the interests of their fellow students (Klemenčič, 2012). They are also political institutions with a system of rules, norms through which collective student interests are aggregated and intermediated to other actors within the higher education or wider political context. Governments are aware of the political potency of organised student interest groups on the national level as history offers ample lessons of organised students forming an influential oppositional force (Klemenčič 2014). In Algeria, student unions seem to lose sight of what matters most in their agenda. In 2011, Djamel Boukzata, representative of the Ministry of Higher Education and Scientific Research, confirmed that the ministry has received more than 500 students since the beginning of the student protests movement, and all of them are representatives of the students. Students on the other hand insisted that these people do not represent them and asked for a hearing in the ministry which created a state of chaos. Students present at the symposium replied that they are aware and have a degree of responsibility to organize themselves and do not need student organizations, which they confirmed that most of their leaders are not students, but rather left

universities years ago, but they still speak on behalf of students for other purposes (Echorouk, 2011b). The Algerian participants pinpointed the same issue claiming that there was a general disinterest in the policy developments taking place in the country and a sick obsession with the individual gain such as getting good grades and getting away with absenteeism just because they are affiliated with a given student.

Despite the efforts, the President of the Republic made it clear that the choice of the BMD was irrevocable, responding firmly to the pressure exerted by many student organizations who oppose membership in this system by giving the green light to the government to implement the Bachelor-Master-Doctorate system in all universities and asked the Minister of Higher Education, Rachid Haraoubia, to pursue its application resolutely (Echorouk, 2008).

Another incident was registered in 2019 where the National Federation of Higher Education and Scientific Research Workers decided to protest in front of the headquarters of the Ministry of Higher Education and Scientific Research, provided that a national strike would be launched for 3 days in the event that their demands were not met (reviewing the compensation system for workers and employees of the higher education and scientific research sector in a way that allows improving the monthly salaries of employees of the sector, as it is considered the weakest compared to all other sectors) (Echorouk, 2019).

Another tactic of outside lobbying identified after the data analysis, is joint campaigning. According to Hojnacki (1997), forming coalition with other interests in a diverse and congested environment is often seen as a promising strategy because it is more challenging for any one group to influence decisions making (Baumgartner and Jones, 1993) so that pooling resources, even when this may mean agreeing on compromise positions among the coalition partners, may increase the chance of influence. In accordance with this view, a trade union member stated that ‘sometimes we work with other people to get the things that we need, but the thing that always governs that is what's in the interests of our members and will work with whoever we need to work with to forward that agenda’ (Interview Member of a Scottish Trade Union 3). NUS, as one of the key actors in the policy debate about tuition fees and widening access policies, has frequently joined forces with academic trade unions such as UCU Scotland and EIS in order to reinforce its views and policy demands.

A former NUS president brought up the opposition as the fastest strategic venue for policy influence or at least for the recognition of the issues raised by NUS Scotland as he explained that it is also common for student unions to join forces with the opposition. The participant

who was himself affiliated with the labour party argued first that his political affiliation was never a problem. In fact, the participant in question enjoyed a great relationship with the cabinet secretary at the time (an SNP). A former NUS member noted that, ‘...all you need it then was one or two of the opposition parties to take up your cause as their cause, and it became very easy to influence what went into the budget at any given time and that ultimately is how we won...’ (Scottish Student Representative). The opposition is anticipated to play the role of a constant check on both the parliamentary majority and the government. Examining a variety of government efforts, criticising the policy agenda, and presenting persuasive counterarguments to official ideas are all important responsibilities of the opposition (Helms, 2008). The opposition can persuade the government to embrace its own policy agenda or force the administration to change it when the opposition is seen of as the government's main policy opponent (König, Lin and Silva, 2023).

In 2015, Students’ union and opposition parties called out the SNP to have abandoned 2007 pledge to ‘dump the debt monster for good’. Student leaders challenged the Scottish government’s decision to dramatically increase student borrowing at the same time as it championed its policy of offering free university tuition. NUS warned that people were being forced to leave university or take on part-time work to fund their living costs. Opposition parties accused Nicola Sturgeon’s government of breaking a guarantee to voters when the Scottish National party won power in 2007 that it would abolish student debt by “dumping the debt monster for good” (Carrell, 2015).

The interview data show that the Algerian participants believe that being representative or part of a population can be a great leverage and asserted that numbers matter in exerting pressure on the government with regards to influence. This claim conforms to the literature on the influence of public pressure on public policy. For example, Burstein (2003) argues that the majority of social scientists who investigate public opinion and public policy in democracies concur that public opinion does shape public policy. The participants further contend that the likelihood of a stronger link between public opinion and influence increases as an issue becomes more important to the public.

We are listened to because we represent a segment of the population. We are listened to because we have the power. For example, if teachers have one association that is quite strong, and it goes to the minister to tell him that we do not accept this status, that we have to change the status. Having strength means you have the masses behind you (Algerian University Official 2).

Indeed, as Finger (2019) argues, teachers' unions have been consistently ranked by scholars as among the most effective state interest groups as they possess the characteristics envisioned to influence and because of their perceived strength and advantages, teachers' unions represent an easy case in which interest groups should shape policy outcomes.

This viewpoint was also shared by another academic, who further asserted that there is power in numbers: "I think the number of influencers is important. If I am a lecturer, another lecturer believes in the same thing I believe in and others also, then we do have a say. Obviously, then we do have a say in terms of policy making" (Algerian Lecturer 2).

One interviewee stressed the power of society, parents, and individual students themselves in the shaping of higher education in Algeria as she gave the example of transfers (when students choose to shift majors) and that of lowering the success requirements,

There is also the street, the parents, the society itself. It also has, as I give an example, there are transfers. Sometimes accelerated transfers. If parents impose certain decisions. Go to the department, complain. There is a text signed by the minister...for example all students want to succeed. But there are those who succeed and those who do not. But the one who do not, will see the minister [...] For example, for credits, there is a text. We have 30 credits per semester to move on to the next semester. Sometimes, the student has 25 credits and we receive, for example. End directives from management [...] Even for 25, you can go, even for 18, you can go. All this came how? It's because the students, the ones who didn't get the 30 credits, complained and the department took the grievances and accepted them (Algerian university official 2).

In this regard, Buzasu (2020) contends that innovative forms of social mobilisation, self-organization, and civic engagement have grown in popularity in recent years. Citizens no longer want to be mere spectators; instead, they want to influence outcomes and take an active part in decision-making. As a result, local groups of people are forming on their own initiative to discuss and resolve particular issues. Although there is a great deal of potential for citizen groups and civil society organisations to improve societies and economies, they also face significant challenges, such as limited resources, inadequate funding, and in some countries, poor information access as well as restrictive political and legal environments (Buzasu, 2020).

7.7 Communication Skills and a Belief in the Cause

It is a general assumption that those in charge of making policy actively seek out data, information and independent and credible advice that pertain to the pressing issues of the day

(Thorpe, 2020). However, the reality of policy making looks very often very different, as the literature discussed throughout the thesis has shown. The resources, for example, time, of policy makers are limited and they are facing pressures that limit their ability to perceive and use a great variety of advice, data and information. Therefore, experts of any kind need to develop ways to convey their views to policy makers in ways that make it easy for them to use them (e.g. Thorpe, 2020). According to the Scottish and Algerian interviewees, establishing contact with policy makers to facilitate relationships and exchange requires adequate communication skills that allow the articulation of expert views in a clear and straightforward manner. In this respect, one participant claimed that “those that can articulate their case in words and language which resonate with the political policymakers are more able to influence the policy debate itself” (Scottish University Official 1).

According to the interviewees, it is also important for gaining access and therefore at least the opportunity to shape views that the expert is dedicated to the policy problem and therefore considered as giving credible advice. This was brought up by an interviewee who was actively involved in Scotland’s discussion around widening access. The interviewee argued that the most important part of her work was to get the people in power to care about the cause instead of looking at it as just ‘another problem’. She stated that

I think you need a story to it as well because some of it is in appealing to people to care about something and to make it their priority. Here is the big picture but here's how this might affect an individual, and then having some kind of story through it was always quite effective (Interview Scottish Independent Scholar 2).

Lamont (2021) claims that the information overload most policymakers receive on a daily basis means that only messages that are powerful and clear are heard and acted upon. The author further argues that getting through to those with the power to make decisions over policy may work best when leveraging emotional shortcuts, often related to the potency of storytelling.

Policy actors often combine strategies to maximize their impact. In the case of NUS Scotland, evidence-based research was combined with other strategies as explained by Mike Day, director of NUS Scotland between 2007 and 2012, who said: “Our strategy was to produce solid research and target decision-makers, backed by activity like email campaigns, and to keep communications open with all parties” (The Scottish Council for Voluntary Organisations, 2022).

The Scottish experience proved that mixing strategies can be the key to influence as it was the case for NUS Scotland and their endeavours to shape the tuition fee discourse to their favour.

7.8 Horizon Scanning and Policy Learning

The devolution has created opportunities for policy convergence and divergence and also for policy learning among the devolved nations (Gallacher and Raffe, 2012; McGuinness et al., 2015). Keating, Cairney and Hepburn (2012) argue that the term "policy learning" should be understood as the voluntarily adoption and adaption of concepts from other sources. Such policy learning can be conducted in one of several directions: from the centre to the periphery, from the periphery to the centre, all around the periphery, or internationally. The first type has dominated in the UK (Keating, Cairney and Hepburn, 2012). Policy learning, i.e. taking advice from 'elsewhere', was something that Scottish interviewees reported about more frequently than their Algerian counterparts. The close ties to the 'rest of the UK' explain this, as does the fact that funding for even the devolved policy areas is highly dependent on decision taken by the Westminster government. The participants argued that policy learning does not mean replication but that looking elsewhere helps to devise policy ideas that pre-empt or at least are cognisant of future developments that happen elsewhere and will also occur in Scotland:

We don't necessarily know that if it's happening in England, it's going to become a conversation in Scotland, but it is helpful...It almost gives us a bit of a clue as to what could be coming our way, and that means we can kind of upskill ourselves, become knowledgeable, speak to students about it before even it's kind of on others agendas, which I think has really helped in the past (Member of a Scottish Statutory Organisation 7).

In the Scottish context, policy learning allowed deeper understanding of the policies implemented in the south, their effects and how best to adapt these policies when and if needed. The process also provided an opportunity to draw "valid policy lessons from cross-national comparisons" (Raffe, 2011, p2),

7.9 The Foundations of a Successful Strategy

Many of the interviewees pointed out that the degree of success of all the strategies depends heavily on who is in charge of making decisions. They reported that especially getting messages through to the intended audiences and marketing the research in the right way can be quite difficult (also see Porter, 2010). This view is in line with the literature – for example, the Hewlett Foundation report (2018) argues that the generation and the sharing of evidence is not

sufficient by itself as it is imperative that policy makers are motivated to use evidence in policy making. Individual and institutional incentives influence whether government officials incorporate data, research, or evaluation findings into decision-making (Hewlett Foundation, 2018). And indeed, interviewees have spoken about how the success of the strategies is highly dependent on the government of the day and its openness to hearing opinions:

I think it depends on how receptive the government is. I think that some governments are seeking to work in partnership. And or willing to amend their changes in light of feedback. But other governments are this is what we want to do and therefore we deliver it (Interview Member of a Scottish Trade Union 2).

Scottish and Algerian interviewees agree, as one Algerian academic said that those at the decision-making levels also hold the power to invite certain people to be part of the commissions set to advise on higher education matters. This means their judgement on who to include comes first, thus limiting the scope of influence of some over the others:

It depends on who you are. It depends of course on your expertise, your motives...And then it depends also on your vis a vie. who is there listening to you because you can have sometimes your visa vie, from the policymaking that are very open and very receptive and they want to understand, they want to see, they want to take other people's perspective, they want to listen to different voices and others they do not. And sometimes some people would involve you, but definitely they will not listen to you (Algerian Education Consultant 2).

Many of the Algerian participants seemed content with how some ministers of higher education dealt with the supply of evidence provided by the sector in recent years:

When you take the initiative, the university follows, and if you have innovative projects, The Ministry of Higher Education will follow because the Minister of Higher Education knows who is a former rector, we did meetings, we spoke the same language. If you take, for example, the new Minister of Higher Education, it's the same thing. We met at a seminar in Amman there, and we discussed it together. He is a person of spirit, he is quite open. Every time we have a project. They never refused projects (Algerian University Official 2).

In Scotland, an academic who has worked closely with the Scottish Government advised that the strategies developed to influence policy making through expertise should not be standardized. Instead, those seeking influence should adapt their strategies to those in power: "I think you take different approaches depending on who it is you're speaking to" (Interview Scottish

Independent Scholar 2). A point related to this area is discussed in Dunlop and Radaelli (2018) as the authors stress that political knowledge and scientific evidence must be aligned, otherwise the evidence would be automatically rejected.

7.10 Conclusion

This chapter has analysed some of the key findings of the study related to the various strategies policy actors in the two countries utilised to influence or shape policy making. In both It showed how Algerian and Scottish actors used a combination of different strategies. Algerian actors used and cited the use of evidence, the power relations, expertise and epistemic authority, public pressure and civic engagement. The latter had a continuum ranging from dialogue and taking part in consultations around the major developments, when offered the opportunity, to demonstration, mobilizing the public through the use of media, and finally engaging in political action. For Scotland, policy actors took advantage of Scottish devolution and the fact that higher education is a devolved policy domain whilst the other parts of the UK provided material for policy learning and therefore scope for divergence and convergence. The policy actors took an active lead in informing the Scottish Government through participating in the calls for evidence, which brings us to the use of evidence as a tool to give more legitimacy to the proposals advanced by the policy actors. The use of opposition, networking, and the importance of a real dedication to dealing with vexed and wicked policy problems were also strategically important in both countries.

Chapter 8

Convergence and Divergence in policy advice dynamics

8.1 Introduction

This chapter critically examines key themes drawn from the findings of the study pertaining to policy advice and expertise informing and shaping policymaking in higher education in Algeria and Scotland. The chapter discusses how both governments utilised expert advice and the reactive feelings of policy actors towards the governments' practices in this regard. It further analyses the impact of micro-politics and access to policy advisory arenas affecting policymaking in the two countries. It highlights the implications of strategies informing policy advice and expertise and also identifies the barriers that hindered the efforts to influence higher education policy, indicates the effects the two distinct governance systems have had on policy advice and expertise, highlights the variety of policy advice sources and timing, examines the bearing of policy packaging and delivery channels on the success of the policy delivery, and finally the transparency in the diffusion of inside policy developments.

8.2 The Pursuit of Common Objectives

As noted in chapter 4, policy knowledge gives decision-makers the "background of ideas, concepts, and information that increased their understanding of the policy terrain" (Weiss, 1999, p. 146). According to this viewpoint, the main role of information in the formulation of policy is to "provide insights into the nature of social problems" (Weiss, 1995, p.141). On the other end, political use (or symbolic use) supports "a predetermined position" (Weiss, 1977b, p. 15). Similarly, Whiteman (1985 quoted in Daviter, 2015) defines this as the "use of analytical information to advocate and reaffirm policy positions after they have been determined" (p. 206).

In Scotland, the Cubie committee was charged with conducting a comprehensive review of tuition fees and the finances of Scottish students. The committee made recommendations for several changes to the system (Dobson, 2000). The widening access Commission membership comprised education officials, think tank director, Former Chair of the SFC Access and Inclusion Committee, Head Teachers, representation from the Scottish Trades Union Congress and Glasgow City Council, Principals and Vice-Chancellors, Sutton Trust representatives, NUS Scotland President, and government officials. The review panel had a principal and vice chancellor, a trade unionist, an NUS Scotland president, and a journalist. The reason for

discussing the membership of these commissions is to identify the type of knowledge use as based on institutional entanglement, government actors have the authority to direct and even choreograph advisory processes. If government representatives are on the committee, especially if they occupy influential positions within the committee or its management and are in charge of public relations, they will have power over the advisory process and the committee's appearance (Boswell, 2008).

An overtly biased composition of a committee or an open government orchestration of the advisory process might be detrimental to its validity. To be regarded as instrumental for the making of policy solutions that are implementable, advisory approaches must lead to substantial policy decisions and assist in conflict resolution in the broadest sense (Moffitt, 2010). The commissions and committees, as discussed, did so to a certain extent. In the BMD developments in Algeria, the quality assurance's two committees and the commission the Ministry of Higher Education put together to advise on how to move forward with the PhD scheme, the proposals did go beyond just restating the government's already existing positions and preferences. The recommendations were, indeed, the outcome of sincere discussion that contributed to policy changes.

Data from relevant documents indicate that there were two instances of what may fall under the symbolic use of expertise, where conflict resolution was insignificant. This took place with the implementation of the BMD system, where the Algerian government declared, singlehandedly, and despite the voices against the new system, to still carry out the reform. In 2019, the National Council of Professors of Higher Education and Scientific Research "Cnas", the representative trade union of Algerian lecturers represented by Abdel Hafeez Milat, launched a referendum through His official Facebook page asking his followers about their opinion on abandoning the "BMD" system and returning to the previous classical system. The result of the vote came in favor of the second proposal, as 91 percent of the voters called for abandoning the "BMD" system, compared to 9 percent calling for maintaining it. In this regard, University Professor Bin Brik Yasser confirmed, in contact with Echourouk, that the "BMD" system, has been introduced since 2004 despite the voices rejecting it at the time and was applied without even consulting the students. He further stated that even after years of its implementation it is still subject to controversy and discussion because of its failure in many respects, especially in the aspect of employment after graduation, and that the period of three years of study "is not considered sufficient" (Slimani, 2019).

In Scotland, the establishment of a code of governance was among the recommendations embedded in the final report of the committee. To this end and following the publication of the review (2012), the Committee of Scottish Chairs (CSC) was entrusted with the responsibility to produce the Code by agreement between the Scottish Funding Council and the Cabinet Secretary for Education and Lifelong Learning. To deliver this, the CSC established a Steering Committee, which recognised the need to engage widely with institutions to gauge the opinions of staff and student representatives and existing governing body members. A draft Code was published for open consultation in April 2013 and the responses around the consultation were diverse. UCU Scotland objected fiercely on the document set for consultation as the union argued that it does not address the recommendations of the government's independent review of governance but instead raises questions which were already answered in that report (University and College Union Scotland, 2013).

Student unions that were not affiliated with NUS Scotland also took part in the policy debate. The student union of Glasgow University expressed serious concerns about the wording of the proposal. In a statement to the Glasgow Guardian, Jess McGrellis, President of Glasgow University Students' Representative Council (SRC) contended that although on the outside it seemed that the students' views were fundamental, the drafting of the Code of Governance proved otherwise (Wigglesworth, 2013).

The Code in its final form was published in July 2013 and came into force on 1 August 2013. UCU Scotland continued to have reservations about it as they argued that it had drifted away from what the review panel had recommended (University and College Union Scotland, 2013). In this case, one can argue that the advice, opinions, and objections of those who were invited to contribute to the discussion around the shaping of higher education governance were ignored even though those policy actors expressed their frustration both publicly and at the earliest occasion, when the first draft was published. However, it is mandatory to mention that the code of higher education governance has undergone several reviews since 2013. In 2016, an extensive evidence-based review was conducted by a steering group that included representatives of students and the staff trade unions, other major stakeholders leading to the publication of an improved Scottish Code of Good Higher Education Governance (2017 edition) built on the 2013 Code's foundations but with fresh and forward-thinking aspects.

These occurrences show that both Algerian and Scottish governments resorted to the instrumental and symbolic uses of policy advice depending on the issue and the circumstances

surrounding the cases discussed. The two governments, deliberately, ignored some of the voices in the sector that showed dissatisfaction and disappointment with the policies. However, this is expected as it is almost impossible to satisfy everyone's demands and still follow a specific governmental agenda.

8.3 Good Intentions vs General Distrust

The findings strongly suggest that both Algeria and Scotland are aware of the importance of having evidence informed higher education policy and giving more access to the policy actors to contribute their expert advice. For this end, both governments, with varying degrees of commitment and thus success, pursued several routes to reinforce this principle.

Scotland has, arguably, based its higher education policy making on the principles of consensus and consultations since the formation of the Scottish Parliament in 1999. Whereas Algeria showed a sense of exclusivity in the making of higher education policy mostly in the first half of the first decade (1999-2009) as the policymaking was limited to few policy actors mainly the government and the ministry of higher education and scientific research with the marginalization of other groups mainly lecturers and student unions. However, the Algerian approach to using a wide range of expertise in higher education policy making started to change towards a more inclusive and collegial manner with more policy actors welcomed to express their views as pointed out by the participants. By the second decade (2009-2020), both Algeria and Scotland showed a high level of willingness to incorporate diverse views into their decision-making. The membership of the committees established to advise on higher education policies is the proof of such statement. In the two countries, the commissions would usually comprise university officials, student union representatives, trade union representatives, members of the economic sector, and even journalists to ensure the transparency of the process as previously discussed. In Algeria, the process and outcomes of the commissions' gatherings also became more publicised with better media coverage and less discretion on behalf of the government. Finally, that good intention can also be seen at the level of commitment expressed by both governments in terms of implementing the recommendations and policy advice provided by those experts.

Despite the increase in plurality when it comes to inviting experts and their differing views on policy problems, interviews show there was some dissatisfaction and distrust among those involved with regards to how their advice was used and some distrust in the role that governments tried to ascribe to advisors. The dissatisfaction came primarily from academics

and researchers from both countries who shared the feeling that their policy advice or contribution was not strongly effective or taken into consideration and who felt that interest groups such as those of employers or the trade unions were more successful in influencing government thinking. These findings mirror those of previous studies that have examined this topic. For example, Cairney and Oliver (2018) tried explaining the lack of efficiency among researchers and academics by pointing out how there are numerous venues, or arenas, in which authoritative choices are made and how researchers compete with a great variety of actors to present their evidence and win the attention of policy makers.

Further, academics attempt to influence policy makers through publishing written work in scholarly journals that policy makers rarely (or are unable to because of their schedules and commitments) access, a view pinpointed equally by Algerian and Scottish participants. Nevertheless, the literature also provides some remedies such as regular interactions with reliable acquaintances, typically from within their own organisation, which can have a significant impact on policymakers (National Institute for Health and Care Research, 2019) as narrowed by one of the widening researchers who took an active lead in the widening access efforts. One participant noted:

It was at senior level between the Directorate of Higher Education at the time and my own institution. My Chief Executive officer thought of me as somebody who could probably benefit from experience of seeing how policies made and how government works. And he also thought that I would have the insight into the student experience and the way that institutions function. He then approached me to see if I'd be interested. I was, because I thought it would be really interesting thing to see and then I was interviewed by the Scottish Government and they took me on from there (Interview Scottish Independent scholar 2).

Put differently, academics can exert bigger influence when recommended by someone in their organization or institution to someone in a higher position. This was also highlighted by the Algerian interviews who shared similar views on the topic. In addition to access, the distrust and frustration also stemmed from the wording of some consultation papers in Scotland. The participants argued that first, those consultations did not only control their scope of contribution by limiting them to answering a specific and often less important set of questions while other significant issues were more deserving of the government's attention as stated by the

participants. Second, they questioned the aims behind such consultations as they maintained that their governments would not act on those suggestions anyway.

Participants in both countries used strikingly similar expressions when discussing the extent to which the two governments take into considerations policy advice and expertise offered to them, for example, in statement such as: “I've always been asked to give my opinion, either through questionnaires or through group work and share our point of view with the Ministry of Higher Education. Definitely yes. They take into account now to what extent this is something else” (Algerian lecturer 1)

“Up here in Scotland, they do consult both through formal and informal, both through the people in the room and who they bring into the room. I think where there's much more of a question mark is whether they act on those consultations” (Scottish Think tank member 2).

Based on these insights, one can say that participants from the two countries share similar reservations about the extent to which their governments take their views, attitudes, and inputs into consideration when making higher education related decisions. Consistently, the participants also shared similar views regarding why such occurrences happen as they argued that there are other considerations – political, economic, and social– that must be balanced instead of making a decision based purely on evidence and policy advice. This will be discussed in the next section.

7.4 Political considerations

In both countries, the findings show that higher education policy, like any other policy area, can never be stripped from political considerations. Certainly, the Scottish and Algerian broader contexts differ in nature and extent to which political considerations affect the making of higher education policy and at the same time limit the contribution and influence of other actors. The Scottish interviewees spoke about the funding policy (the no tuition fees policy) as the prime example of a political choice in Scotland. A former NUS member who was heavily involved in the developments around this policy area at the time reflected on the issue saying that “if you were to look at its impact, it's probably been a higher impact political policy than a has educational policy” (Scottish think tank member 1). Higher education policy making being influenced and shaped by the bigger political atmosphere of the country was sometimes understandable by the Algerian participants as put by one participant ‘the decision to give access to all the students to do an MA program, it's basically to absorb unemployment for at

least two years and not to have young people in the streets. So sometimes, some of the decisions are influenced by policy or by politics' (Interview Education Consultant 2).

The importance of 'politics' was also noted when a member of a trade union talked about the freedom they enjoy when discussing higher policy matters without the need to be careful around certain people and particular issues. The trade union was independent from political party and that cleared space for autonomous thinking:

I think politically and because in the academic trade unions, at least, there isn't an affiliation to a political party. We don't tend to have a problem from any of our positions in calling out whichever party as we need to call out when we think they've got education policy wrong. That's a little bit different for UNISON because they do have affiliations to the Labour Party, and GMB as well do, so they're coy about saying things (Interview Scottish trade union member 3).

In Algeria, the findings indicate that trade unions and student unions were distrusted by Algerian lecturers because of their obvious political affiliation. Nevertheless, in Scotland and despite the importance of politics, being affiliated to a certain political party did not seem to present a problem to a former NUS member, who argued that his link to the labour party was irrelevant when doing his job and insisted that he had a great relationship with the cabinet secretary at the time. Besides political affiliations, the Scottish participants focused on the issue of independence as they argued that everything the Scottish government decided to do prior 2014 (i.e., referendum about independence from the UK) and post 2014 (the plans or aspirations for another referendum) is viewed through the lenses of independence.

The White Paper on Scottish independence, Scotland's Future (Scottish Government, 2013a), stressed that higher education would remain free of charge for domestic students in Scotland. However, in a speech delivered by Scottish Secretary Alistair Carmichael, arguing for the Union and against independence, at Edinburgh University in 2014, he argued that all of the promises were already in place as part of a constitutional arrangement that gives the Scottish people "the best of both worlds" (UK Government, 2014a).

Despite the 'no' in the referendum, Scottish independence remained a widely discussed topic. One interviewee argued that the Scottish Government is careful to not 'overdo' it while using its commitment to independence as a political instrument, too:

Sometimes they say a lot about independence. Other times they don't. They don't always emphasize it and that's partly because they know that it's not universally popular, so they know if they bang on too much about, we only exist to get to get independence from the UK, that will turn off some of their voters. They also know if they don't say enough, that'll turn off some of their other voters (Scottish Independent scholar 3).

Scottish participants in the study further expressed their candid views regarding the independence discourse's impact on higher education policy making in terms of whose policy advice gets listened to. They asserted that what the government chooses to do or not to do is aimed at keeping the people, the future voters, happy to guarantee their votes when the time comes for leaving the United Kingdom. In other words, the Scottish Government is so focused on doing what is reputationally good to preserve the independence coalition. A senior researcher argued that,

In Scotland, everything is viewed through the lens of independence and the struggle for independence. The NUS, for example, the National Union of Students, would be quite an influential body and that's partly because the youth vote would be important to the government and because the NUS would be a largely middle-class voice, they would want to keep that constituency (Scottish independent scholar 1).

The Scottish interviewees shared that the Scottish Government's reluctance to make far-reaching or even 'radical' decisions is related to a keen awareness of having to address quite diverse constituencies in its attempt to maintain support for the SNP and its government. A staff member of a Scottish lobby group argued that the government is ready to do nothing in fear of making a decision that would cost it votes. He noted:

We're always trying to balance a lot of stakeholder interests so they actually shy away from doing anything radical because it's in danger of alienating some of the people whom they need to support an independence vote in the hope that if they don't make any decisions, nothing terrible will happen on their watch until they've got through an independence referendum" (Interview Member of a Scottish lobby group 2)

The findings also indicate that the independence discourse can be one of the reasons behind the complex and often uneasy relationship between the universities' principles and the Scottish government. A former think tank member explained that,

I think the independence referendum had a bearing on that...the fear of things going wrong. The hope that you can get people onto your side on that debate or begin to diminish the power of those that are on the other side of that debate, and I think university principles as

a collective are seen as very much on the stay in the UK side of things rather than independence in the main (Scottish think tank member 2).

On the Algerian side, political considerations when making a decision had a substantial influence over higher education policies as well. In fact, some participants stressed the fact that politics are the number one influencer over higher education policy making and argued that this feature pertains specifically to underdeveloped countries:

Personally, I think that politics has a great deal to do with such decisions, and African countries, all underdeveloped countries are not always free to take decisions according to their population. There are a lot of political factors that interfere in the educational system, either higher education or in education in general. It's not purely based on academic considerations, there are other considerations that interfere (Algerian University Lecturer 1).

The Algerian participants pointed out that the political aspect is everywhere, as the minister himself would usually, but not always, when supposedly 'technocratic' appointments were made, have a political affiliation to one of the political parties in Algeria. As an education consultant said:

You do have the minister himself because he has a political position because He's a politician by nature because you would have other people in his cabinet that take different roles and different advisors. Generally, in Algeria, government ministries always come from political party, and they had to have a political affiliation and quite often, if you do not have a political affiliation, it will be difficult for you to access these positions or to be appointed (Algerian Education Consultant 2)

Some Algerian interviewees denied that higher education making in Algeria should be thought about within the broader context of 'politics. However, they acknowledged that while politics were 'invisible', they did seem to matter for making sense of the fact that non-academic actors often enjoyed more influence over policy making than their academic counterparts. Whereas other participants explained that the policy makers showed interest in the higher education policy because of its impact on the other sectors as they are always on the lookout for what the higher education sector can offer for the Algerian society. In terms of support from the policymakers, the participants contended that those in power were nothing but supportive for the initiatives and proposals made.

One of the biggest manifestations of how impactful the political situation can be is what Algeria went through during the 1990s, historically known as the Black Decade (Willis, 2023; Kilavuz, Grewal and Kubinec, 2023). Due to the turmoil Algeria witnessed, it became challenging to restore Algeria's reputation internationally as it is paramount to have Political stability, which is most commonly understood to mean that there is no civil unrest at home or violent behaviour. A stable polity is then defined as a law-abiding, tranquil community where political and social change originates from institutionalized, functional processes rather than anomic processes that settle disputes by force and violence (Hurwitz, 1973). The lack of these principles in Algeria meant that in terms of international mobility, not all countries were enthusiastic to sharing their expertise with Algeria:

The black decade hit and close ties with everyone in the borders and so forth. So, there were, something like 15-20 years where no one was hearing about Algeria in all the fields, etcetera. So, it was difficult to engage with these people but there were some representatives from the universities that attended who for example they used to be teachers and visiting scholars in Algeria in the 1970s and in the 80s. So there was some nostalgia for them (Algerian Education Consultant 2).

8.4 Who Gets Invited?

A finding which both countries share relates to commission of research. When this was done in the cases analysed, both the Algerian and the Scottish governments made sure to invite the people who were in agreement with their general policy objectives. In Algeria, the higher education policy architecture is governed by some hardwired principles such as the free access to university for all students holding a baccalaureate certificate. Therefore, every policy idea must be aligned to this principle despite the limits that this principle imposes on policy developments:

This entry, which must be governed by an entrance examination or a placement test, must be achieved without touching on the question of the democratization of higher education. For each student with a baccalaureate, there must be an educational internship. We must not touch that, but for the rest, we can propose solutions. We can propose legislation or guidelines and that can be taken into account in future legislation (Algerian Government Official).

Other participants went further with their views as they argued that one's "loyalty" to the Ministry's agenda is the key to being a close member who gets an invitation to the decision-

making circles and be able to deliver his/her policy advice. Still, this influence is curbed to the implementation phase. As an Algerian scholar said

Throughout the implementation period [of the BMD] from 2003-2004 to the present, the author], the MESRS has given itself regional "leaders" who, over time, have become spokespersons for the "reform. For example, the rector of the University of Constantine has been one of the main influential "leaders" for almost 20 years. But he owes this role more to his loyalty to MESRS than to his discourse, which is always limited to the application of ministerial programmes (Algerian Independent scholar 1).

The same goes for Scotland. In a more explicit way, the participants argued that the government would invite those who share the same views as it does. A think tank member linked the success of one's endeavours to influence the policy to their positions as he claimed:

I don't want to say if you're on the right side of government, if you're on the right side of government opinion that you will have good success (Scottish Think tank member 1).

This view stresses the fact that if a policy actor's stance and beliefs are aligned with those of the government, it is most likely that they will see their agenda taking place and encounter less handicaps in their attempts to influence the policymaking.

8.5 Barriers to Influence

A recurrent theme in terms of policy advice and access to higher education policy making is that around the barriers to influence higher education policy making highlighted by the participants. Due to the historical and social differences between the two countries, the barriers look different for each. In Scotland, and during the first decade (1999-2010), one participant (who dealt with finance) shared that her background hindered her attempts of inclusion in certain higher education networks and contribution to the policy making. She argued that her participation, as a woman of colour, was not as unproblematic as it would be for someone from a traditional background because she did not fit in the networks that held the power to influence the higher education policy at the time. When asked to elaborate on the topic she said:

The networks are exclusive and ideologically narrow, and I think by and large still somebody like you and I don't fit in to that framework, so we have to earn membership. We're not naturally brought into it. We have to push the door and just shout and be heard (Member of a Scottish Statutory Organisation 1).

Comparison of the findings with those of other studies, such as Dunlop's (2018), confirm that the existing system has encouraged universities to invest primarily on stories of heroic scientists, mostly white male professors, overcoming the obstacles to effect, while resources and chances to seek impact are not equitably distributed. Consistent with Dunlop's views, Cairney and Oliver (2018) contend that the least likely groups to participate in professionally fulfilling impact activities, such as providing access to parliaments, are women and those from Black, Asian, and Minority Ethnic (BAME).

Scottish participants argued that the ethnic backgrounds of BAME students did not make their life easier. Being from a BAME background meant that they had to work harder than others and earn their positions. The same participant also mentioned nepotism as a possible barrier and linked that to the small nature of the country. In Algeria, the participants also pointed out that, based on their experience, regionalism and nepotism are possible barriers that bar some experts from advising on higher education related policies:

I think this is how I have seen with some people who are very consensus colleagues who are really working hard and seriously and have seen others who were relying more on nepotism, on regionalism, would be excluding other people or at times would even involve the right expert to work with them. But then when it comes to some privileges, they would exclude them and keep only their networks and their friends and people from their regions (Algerian Education Consultant 2).

8.6 A Central System vs Scottish Policy Style

One of, if not the biggest, area of differences between the two countries lies in the two sectors' ways of governance. As thoroughly discussed in chapter 2, Scotland's policy making approach can be recognized as a case of "multi-level governance" (MLG) referring to the sharing of authority between the national central government, different levels of government (thus the term multi-level) and non-governmental entities (hence the term governance rather than government) (Hooghe and Marks, 2003). The policy advice comes from different levels and is not linear. In Algeria, the participants insisted repeatedly that the top-down approach adopted by the Algerian government prevents non-governmental actors from fully accessing the policy making arena.

Since 1999, numerous scholarly investigations have focused on the broad concept of a "Scottish policy style," which describes the supposedly distinctive processes by which the Scottish

Government develops policy after consulting and bargaining with pressure organisations such as interest groups, local government organisations, and unions (Cairney, Russell and St Denny, 2016). This, in comparison to the 'rest of the UK', consultative approach Scotland uses when making higher education policy can be traced back to the Scottish Constitutional Convention (1995). Cairney (2012) argues this Convention, preceding actual devolution by a few years, proposed a new kind of pluralist democracy in which consultation with affected interests would be as broad as possible, not only with established interest groups but also with previously excluded groups with limited voice and ability to organise (Cairney, 2012). When compared to Algeria it seems that Scotland at least partly owes its distinctive policy style to the country's size and the limited range of devolved powers (Keating, 2005). Both the Scottish Parliament (MSPs and committees) and the Scottish Government (ministers and civil servants) are comparatively easy to establish contact because of their openness and willingness to engage, for example with policy advocates and experts require. One concrete example, dating back to 2004, is the concordat between Scottish Trades Union Congress (STUC) and the Scottish Government that was to ensure that access to civil servants will remain the same even in the event of a change in the party in power (Cairney, 2012).

In contrast, Algeria needs to manage a huge system of more than 114 institutions (Algeria' National Report, 2022) including universities, university centers, and schools (higher normal schools, higher national schools, preparatory schools, integrated preparatory schools) (Galal, 2008). In this context, detailed central planning or close links with individual institutions can be difficult and complex possible. Moreover, making public policy is a complicated interactive process that is influenced by a variety of socio-political and other environmental influences. These environmental factors that shape the policy context cause variety in policies and have an impact on their production and outcomes. Public policies in developed countries diverge greatly from those in developing nations as a result of contextual differences (Osman, 2002).

The Algerian higher education system is distinguished by a high level of centralization reflected in direct involvement of the government in the appointment of the highest universities' officials (Hamdy, 2007). These arrangements mean that the major decisions happen at the level of the ministry and then passed to the universities where not much resistance is expected. This also means that the room available given to policy advice from external sources of expertise is significantly smaller compared to that of Scotland. Top-down processes, which refer to the transmission of policy choices from the national level to lower levels, regard policy designers as the primary actors (Mataland, 1995).

The top-down approach's strength is seen in its ability to create generalizable policy recommendations and to identify consistent and recognised patterns in conduct across policy domains (Matland, 1995). This may explain why the Algerian Government maintains this approach. However, top-down approaches are criticised for ignoring political issues and treating policy implementation as merely an administrative operation. Another point of criticism is the focus on the central decision-makers and the exclusion of local actors (Cerna, 2013). Matland (1995) argues that top-down practices often seek to reduce the number of participants in the policy process and assign implementation duties to an organisation that is known to support the policy objectives.

In contrast, the Scottish approach stresses professional autonomy, consensus, egalitarianism, and policy learning (Cairney, 2020). This has led to change, in Scotland, to originate from professional non-governmental network and in collaboration with government, whereas in Algeria change processes were started directly by governmental agencies. In general, the characteristics of the Algerian Government relations with the HE system entail a 'state-centric approach' to making policy. According to George (2006), for a higher education system to fall under the 'state-centric approach' it must be principally state-funded or receive state directed funding and have its policy directions set by the government. Indeed, the Algerian Government delegates all higher education tasks to the network of its fully state-funded universities.

This understanding of Algeria's higher education system as falling into the type of a 'state-centric' system is relevant to the discussion of the influence and use of policy advice and expertise in order to clarify how little bottom-up directionality exists when it comes to participation of stakeholders. One interviewee stated that she barely has any involvement in even the institutional micro level so that she has no expectation to be involved, through consultations or as expert in her own right, in policy making processes on the macro level (Interview 27). This perception aligns with Faguet (2011) claims that decentralisation can actually lead to good governance when promoting accountability and inclusion and with what Weiss advocates about knowledge having a better chance of influencing policy change in "competitive political systems" and under circumstances where policy is "decentralised," leaving government control spread across various levels (1999, p. 480).

8.7 Variety of Policy Advice Sources

There are various sources of policy information in contemporary politics and policy environment. This includes the stances of local actors such as interest groups, social movement

organisations, bureaucratic agencies, universities, think tanks, and journalists, as well as the specific pragmatics and contingencies of the policy situation, which have been classified as non-research evidence (Strehlenert et al., 2015; Daviter, 2015).

In Scotland, as discussed in the two previous chapters, policy advice comes and flows from a significant variety of sources, often in high quality, and in more different directions compared to Algeria. Think tanks, relatively new in Scotland, represent one source of policy expertise (Pautz, 2007). These organizations provide well detailed analysis of higher education policy related issues. The other interesting aspect is that these bodies can also be used by other policy actors to prepare research. An individual or organization keen to influence the discourse surrounding a particular policy domain may commission policy research. As put by Young and Quinn (2012), the "classic" customer is a decision-maker who commissions an expert to conduct a study and identify solutions to a pressing policy issue. Clients hire researchers and analysts to assist them in assuming leadership positions or to influence a policy process. This involves much more than just coming up with a solution to the particular policy problem at hand and typically includes justifications, arguments, rationales, and evidence to back up every component of a policy position.

Whereas some policy actors choose to commission a research organization to do the work, other policy actors such as NUS Scotland depend on a highly internal qualified team whose job is to prepare reports, organize online surveys, and take care of submissions when the government calls for evidence. If we take a closer look at these documents, the first impression is how well articulated the demands are, how inclusive to represent the views of the students affiliated with the organization and most importantly how they manage to provide alternatives and solutions for the government to meet those demands. The same but in a more mature and professional manner goes for Universities Scotland, with an executive group, Convener, Vice-Convener and Director, to decide on the strategic direction of the organization. The organization develops its funding and policy positions by working very closely with Principals and other senior staff in all higher education institutions. The thinking happens at the level of the policy committees, where the members meet regularly four or five times a year. The committees make recommendations on policy which then pass to the Main Committee of all Principals to be discussed and decided upon. In addition to these committees, Universities Scotland also have a number of smaller policy groups to focus on other issues (Universities Scotland, 2022). Such level of professionalism and devotion allows Universities Scotland to be and remain one of the most powerful sources of policy advice.

Of course, the organization discussed here and in earlier chapters did not always succeed in persuading policy makers to accept their views on a policy issue, but often managed to make its claims heard because they were well supported by evidence. Trade union EIS, for example, has used its own expert team to oversee the media aspect (Educational Institute of Scotland, 2021). These sources of advice are all communicated to the government both in a solicited and unsolicited way. Overall, the scenery in Scottish higher education implies the existence of what the literature refers to as the externalization of policy advice.

Halligan (1995) argued that the number of sources of advice has increased, and actors inside and outside of the political system have become more involved. These sources include advocacy groups, think tanks, consulting firms, policy researchers in academia, and many more (Bakvis, 2000, Tiernan, 2011). However, in recent years, the increased participation and the use of outside consultants and commissions to provide policy advice have challenged the priority given to internal actors. This has given rise to the widespread belief that, in contrast to earlier times, a large portion of policy advice is now "externalized" (Bevir and Rhodes, 2001; Bevir, Rhodes and Weller, 2003; Howlett and Lindquist, 2004; Mayer, van Daalen and Bots, 2004). Although Howlett, Migone and Tan (2014) contend that external advisors can have a complementary role when working alongside internal advisors challenging existing assumptions of a duplicative or adversarial relationship between the two sets.

As has been established, in Algeria, research informing policymaking is primarily done at the level of the ministry, by the specialized department of the General Directorate for Scientific Research and Technological Development and its four sub directorates: a sub directorate for research programming and foresight, a sub directorate for evaluation and analysis, a sub directorate for international research programs and a sub directorate for the coordination of intersectoral research (The Algerian Ministry of Higher Education and Scientific Research, 2022a). Interestingly, when describing the department's mission, the official web page states that under the authority of the minister in charge of scientific research, the directorate-general "implements", within a collegial and intersectoral framework, the national policy for scientific research and technological development as defined by the law. The participants who were formerly affiliated with the Ministry of Higher Education argued that this body is responsible for the provision of evidence to underpin any move made by the ministry:

Within the Ministry of Higher Education and within the reorganization of the Ministry, we have set up a development and foresight department. And this directorate of development. It has been entrusted with this mission. It is a mission that allows to evaluate all the actions that are carried out by the ministry... It is a department for study, synthesis, evolution and evaluation (Algerian Government Official).

This was the internal advice giving. As discussed in the conceptual framework chapter, advisors working inside the government possess knowledge of stakeholder positions and interests as well as access to agendas and policy opportunities. They have connections to important figures in the executive branch and the larger political landscape. They have the ability to control information owed to the minister in addition to the authority of the minister in their interactions with others (Maley, 2000). This supports insights gained through Halligan's analytical frame which associates different levels of influence with the location of advisors, either inside or outside government (Halligan, 1995).

In Algeria, looking at other available sources of policy advice, one will struggle to identify these. Except of the publications made by Algerian scholars in different languages (Metatla, 2016; Bouchikhi and Barka, 2017), there was very limited contribution and involvement from the other policy actors (trade unions, students, interest groups), especially between 1999 and 2009, which signals an absence of policy advice externalization discussed in the conceptual framework chapter. The relative diversity of student unions in Algeria has contributed to a weakening of their potential influence and policy contributions. One example would be the case with the discussions around the BMD system when different student unions made different and opposing demands to the Ministry of Higher Education which resulted in utter chaos (Echourouk, 2011)

The media has also exposed that many of these organizations (student unions) are corrupt, and in disobedience with the legal texts governing the organization and its jurisdictions (Echorouk online, 2017a; Akhbareelwatane, 2021). In contrast to Scotland, Algerian Student unions have not yet developed significant capacities for contributing positively to policy developments.

The second source of policy advice and probably the most important is that of the regional conferences (East, West, and Centre) and the National Conference. Radaelli (1995) maintained that the study of policy change and advocacy coalitions proceeds from the understanding that coalitions, in which policy experts play a key role, are the most common way that professional expertise influences policy decisions. The Algerian network of rectors and vice-rectors, both

in its structure and organization, can be compared to Scotland. In terms of efficiency in supplying policy advice, the extent of these conferences' contribution cannot be fairly measured as some participants insisted that the members were only entrusted with the implementation of the policies instead of debating them. The interviewees who were part of this network claimed that such community represents a pool of experts who know the sector better than anyone else, and therefore able to give good advice. This aligns with the literature which highlights that researchers are often brought in only after decisions have been made to help with implementation, which downplays the influence of evidence on the policymaking process (Ozga, 2004).

Overall, it is fair to say that there is a very limited repository for both solicited and unsolicited advice in Algeria compared to an abundance of sources of policy expertise in Scotland.

At this point it is necessary to explore why Algeria has some established and capable experts, but when it comes to contributing to higher education policy making processes, those names rarely appear. When we speak about knowledge production, it is important to discuss knowledge use by policy makers. In Scotland, research organizations and other stakeholders like student unions can see that their reports and publications are taken into consideration, and to a lesser degree known to exist to policy makers even if the latter choose to not accept the advice given. As Garrett and Islam (1998) contend, the primary means by which a research institution influences policy makers is via disseminating knowledge, but it is up to government decision-makers to put this information into policy. In Algeria, the participants who were both lecturers and researchers did not feel that their work was noticed let alone employed to inform the decisions made by government. However, other full-time researchers argued that they were encouraged by the Algerian Ministry for Higher Education to be more interactive. The findings show that there is a gap between policy makers and knowledge producers. One theory to justify such rupture is the lack of knowledge brokerage and policy entrepreneurship (Gunn, 2017). Communities of knowledge producers and knowledge users are sometimes at odds (Caplan, 1979), and policy makers do not always build their actions purely on evidence that itself can be ill timed, communicated in the wrong way or through the wrong channel (Keating, Stone and Maxwell, 2001). This means that the application of research evidence in educational practise can have specific challenges. The practise of knowledge brokering, also known as knowledge translation or knowledge mobilisation, has been cited as a vital remedy for such rupture. People or organisations with the specific purpose of transferring and transforming information between communities do so because they have in-depth knowledge of both

communities (Rycroft-Smith, 2022). Bandola-Gill and Lyall (2017) argue that knowledge brokers, who may simultaneously undertake advocacy or policy entrepreneurship tasks as well as knowledge brokerage tasks, have the capacity to contribute at every stage of the policy making process by facilitating the adoption of evidence into policy.

However, because they typically provide policy alternatives and evaluate them in light of the available research, it is expected that they will be most active during the policy formulation stage. Though the line between knowledge brokers and other policy intermediaries, such as government agencies or non-governmental organisations (NGOs), is often blurred, examples of organisations performing knowledge brokerage roles in the policy advisory system include think tanks (UK Government Office for Science, 2013), advisory committees, and advisory institutions with explicit knowledge brokerage goals.

Unlike Scotland, Algerian higher education policymaking seems to lack the policy brokers closing the "know-do gap" and promoting more use of research findings and evidence in policymaking through knowledge brokering focuses on structuring the dialogue between those who generate knowledge and knowledge consumers so that they can jointly develop workable and evidence-based policy solutions. Knowledge brokerage aims to promote researchers to do research that is important to policy, as well as to encourage policymakers to utilise existing research findings and raise awareness of research among policymakers (Van Kammen, de Savigny and Sewankambo, 2006).

8.8 Timing of Policy Advice

James and Jorgensen (2009) argued that in an expertise market saturated with policy relevant data, other considerations other than expert knowledge raise into prominence when attempting to influence policy making. They discuss the policy process steps of problem identification, formulation, and implementation, which inform experts what type of knowledge is needed by policy makers in government. Based on the data available and the interviewees' insights, it seems that a key difference between Algeria and Scotland lies when in the policy process policy advice and expertise are most needed. In Algeria, the input from experts is limited to advising on the best pathways to implement a policy solution, and another opportunity exists when policy evaluations are needed. In Scotland, it seems as if experts are involved at earlier stages in the policy process, namely already at the step of agenda setting. Student unions and the media played an instrumental role in highlighting the need for student support and advocated

heavily for putting the topic of tuition fees onto the agenda in Scotland. In later stages such as the policy formulation, the number of players was restricted to members of commissions – the Cubie Committee, the Commission on widening Access, and the higher education governance review panel - but still, there was a fair representation of the interested parties. A common belief is that policy formulation is dominated by those with specialised knowledge, preferred access to decision makers, or a paid position in a specific government agency or department, as opposed to the agenda-setting stage, in which the media, politicians, and the public may be more transparently involved (Turnpenny et al., 2015).

Policy formulation activities can be done internally or externally. Departmental inquiries, government committees, and policy analysis units are examples of internal venues that are primarily occupied by serving officials or ministers. Open external forums rely on unofficial sources of knowledge (Turnpenny et al., 2015). In Algeria, the policy formulation stage did follow the same patterns as in Scotland, but there was a lack of transparency as explained in previous chapters. At the level of implementation, both countries had to involve the higher education institutions to carry out the policies. It is widely acknowledged that policy implementation is a crucial phase of the policy process that shapes the nature and impact of the policy while also bridging the divisions between politics, policy, and the public (Sager and Gofen, 2022).

The implementation of public policy is of the utmost significance due to the expanding number of interested parties and the conflict between them. Studies have shown that it is challenging to adopt policies because they attempt to resolve societal issues that are inherently conflictual. The process of implementing a policy encompasses numerous levels of institutions, organisations, and people, and it calls for understanding differences and balancing them with the goals of the policy (Abdullahi and Othman, 2020). In Algeria, the BMD implementation was described as “disastrous” by the participants and the publication written by both Algerian and foreign scholars. These circumstances called, in a premature way, for the next stage of the policymaking process, that of evaluation (Echorouk Online, 2017b).

Radaelli (1995) argues that evaluation research is the broad term attributed to the type of knowledge, which includes not only expert opinions and social research but also the transformation of expert ideas into the knowledge used by political actors; a knowledge in which research, data from public administration bureaux, and even media opinions are all intertwined. This means that policy advice and expertise is still needed at this level. Both

countries engaged in what can be termed “ongoing evaluation”. The goal of ongoing evaluation is to pinpoint the (temporary) effects and outcomes of policies, programmes, and measures while those activities are still being implemented and realised. To adapt, rectify, or reroute the implementation process or even underpin important policy decisions, ongoing evaluation is crucial. This is done by feeding appropriate information back into the implementation process at the right time and place (Wollmann, 2007).

Another difference was depicted at the level of the evaluation types. In Algeria, the first BMD evaluation was internal, and the government singlehandedly decided to carry out the reform due to the lack of data on the progress whereas the second evaluation from 2016 admitted external voices inclusive. The same happened in Scotland, with the widening access policies and the review of governance in 2011. Evaluations can result in a variety of policy-learning patterns, each with its own consequences for feedback systems and the possibility to restart the policy-making process (Fisher et al., 2013).

In Algeria, another instance of policy advice shaping the implementation of a major policy was the decision to implement the BMD system on a pilot scheme, a recommendation made by the commission set by the government in 2002 starting with only 10 universities first and without touching the hard sciences. As Raudla et al. (2025) explain, pilot projects may serve as tools for conflict avoidance rather than advancing evidence-based policymaking; contested measures are instead taken on as pilot projects and subsequently delayed until the political climate is favourable for a more long-lasting course of action, which was the case in Algeria.

8.9 Policy Transfer: Packaging and Delivery Channels

Since the policymaking process involves so many varied individuals, any of whom may be a potential audience, there is rarely a single audience for a product (policy advice). The word product is a generic term here used to cover in a stretchy manner all types of policy knowledge and policy advice, from written evidence like analytical reports to verbal communications. It is necessary to identify the primary target markets and to modify the product as necessary (Garett and Islam, 1998). Both the content and packaging of the research output are essential components. Format is one of the most crucial aspects of packing (reports, policy briefs, videos). Further, the way the material is presented has a certain style. The presentation's clarity, the use of technical jargon, and comprehension level are all examples of style elements. The intended audience must be identified with clarity, and the structure and style must be adjusted to meet their requirements. The packaging of the product will influence how 'user-friendly' it

is perceived to be and, consequently, the likelihood that it will attract the audience's attention (Garett and Islam, 1998; UK Government Office for Science, 2013; Lavis et al., 2003).

In Algeria, the packaging of the information is rarely taken into consideration when trying to contribute or influence the higher education policymaking. Although the participants who were senior staff at their respective higher education institutions did mention a number of formats mainly reports detailing their action plans. Student unions often resort to organizing workshops (examples with the LMD System) to discuss relevant issues to both students, university officials, and policymakers, yet these workshops are perceived as a time-consuming event that not all policymakers will be interested in. In their part, academics often publish articles that rarely provide solutions instead of restating the same problems. In Scotland, those involved in influencing the policy developments around higher education examine first the target audience, his/her political position, their party history, and their political preferences before embarking on the packaging process. The choice of the strategy is given much thought as shown through the data analysis, and the more care is given to this area, the bigger success rates get.

Now the optimum communication route for the product will rely on how it is packaged. A few examples of channels are newspapers, radio, the internet, lectures, and training sessions. The choice of channel will be influenced by the size, demographics, and message to be delivered to the target audience. How much time is given to the user to process the data? Can the user fit in a one-day training, watch a video, read a report, or skim a policy brief? (Garett and Islam, 1998). In Algeria, newspapers, both traditional paper ones and electronic ones represent a delivery channel to express the complaints and discontent of both university officials such as rectors, and students at the same time. The proliferation of private media channels also became a popular way for the actors to publicly discuss their proposals and holding the policymakers accountable.

In Scotland, the rallies organized by NUS Scotland represented a good opportunity for socializing with policy makers, trade unionists, and opposition and thus to approach the target audience directly with no need for intermediaries. In such events, the packaging of the information is the most crucial part. The information can be disseminated casually but with a lasting impression. It can also be argued that the calls for evidence launched by the Scottish Government are ready-made channels for policy information delivery.

8.10 Transparency in the Diffusion of Inside and Outside Interactions

Transparency and accountability go hand in hand in democracies where citizens delegate decision-making authority to produce the data that citizens need to assess and verify the functioning of their governments, thus providing an ongoing basis for the consent of the governed (Harrison and Sayogo, 2014). Although, openness at times can be a double-edged sword when there is too much information shared with the public that the process becomes chaotic (Norbert and Marklund, 2014).

Information, transparency, accountability, and participation are among the interactions that help build and sustain the trust between the governor and the governed. Transparency in the context of higher education policy making in Scotland and Algeria is a particularly important indicator of a government's commitment to openness and transparency. It is noteworthy to mention that Algeria has made recent efforts to use e-government mechanisms to increase levels of transparency, participation, and accountability, as many of their advocate's hope (Idoughi and Abdelhakim, 2013). However, with this research dating back to 1999, it seems that there is, compared to today, relatively little archival data, including parliamentary session's minutes and committee meetings available. Furthermore, Algiers' OBI (Open Budget Index) in 2012 was 13 out of 100, significantly lower than the average score of 43 for all 100 countries surveyed by the Open Budget survey, which evaluates whether governments grant the public access to information (International Budget Partnership, 2012). This score suggests that Algeria's government gives the public little information about its finances and budget, making it difficult for the public to monitor how the government is managing public funds.

This section follows Medaglia's (2012) lead and refers to e-participation as the use of ICT (information and communications technology) to support democratic decision-making where e-participation is related to the issues of enabling opportunities for consultation and dialogue between government and citizens by using a range of ICT tools. It was not until recent years that the Algerian Government made use of the electronic platforms to gauge the reactions of the different stakeholders in higher education policymaking. The highlight of such shift was the 2016 BMD evaluations where all those involved including students, lecturers, and university officials were given the chance to express their views via an electronic platform to help inform the upcoming national conference taking place at the same year. In Scotland, the transparency in policymaking is much more developed and much more present in almost every aspect of higher education policymaking.

The process starts with a public declaration made by the prime minister where he/she clearly states the aims behind opting for a given policy, for example, Nicola Sturgeon's (Scottish First Minister, 2014-2023) aspiration for more equality in Scottish higher education in 2014, and Alex Salmon's commitment to a tuition free higher education (for undergraduates). In such instances, the government launches a call for evidence and publishes a document on its official website with a set of questions and a bar at the end for further comments. Once the concerned policy actors submit their responses, the government then asks for their permissions to publish these responses on its official website.

These records provide a reliable and neutral source of information for historical and contemporary studies, especially when the study dates to twenty years back or more. Arnstein (1969) asserts that knowledge is essential for genuine public participation. Unfortunately, Algeria is taking very slow steps in the direction of information sharing. For example, the parliamentary records (for higher education related sessions) go back to 2017 and stop there. Up until now, the report produced by the commission responsible for introducing the BMD system is not on the official website of the ministry of higher education where it belongs, but rather on a website that most laptop firewalls would prevent those interested in the content published there from accessing it. Information transparency is achieved when citizens have access to the information and documents that are pertinent to the actions and choices taken by government actors (Florini, 2007). Thus, citizens are better able to hold their governments to account when information is provided in this manner (Harrison and Sayogo, 2014). Yet, Algeria' OBI (Open Budget Index) in 2012 was 13 out of 100, significantly lower than the average score of 43 for all 100 countries surveyed by the Open Budget survey and even lower than that of Morocco, Jordan, and other nations in the Middle East and North Africa (Open Budget Survey, 2012). In their report, it has been concluded based on the score achieved by Algeria that the Algerian government gives the public little information about its finances and budget, making it difficult for the public to monitor how the government is managing public funds. For the record, The Open Budget survey evaluates whether the public has access to important budget documents that are released by the central government of each of the countries it surveys, as well as whether the information in these documents is timely, accurate, and comprehensive.

For example, one of the participants who was a lecturer at the time of the introduction of the BMD system maintained that he had never heard of such reform and had to do his own research to know what the fuss was about and to be able to use its principles in teaching. However,

recently and in terms of conferences, workshops, and committees, the Algerian government is being more transparent in terms of who gets invited, and the topics discussed.

It is noteworthy to mention that media coverage is also doing a good job in supporting such openness when broadcasting these meetings and reporting, sometimes live, what was happening. Consistent with this view, is Götz and Marklund's (2015) argument that the development of the openness principle around the world is supported by broadcasting and the rapidly evolving Internet. Brunswicker, Pujol Priego and Almirall (2019) also contend that the media and civil society organisations have evolved into equally potent forces in the management of modern society as they carry out this job more regularly (holding the governments accountable). Transparency and openness are also key for a governments to understand what the current thinking is regarding the policies, their implementations, and the rates of their success through those e-platforms. Digital technologies allow governments to act as platforms to gather, aggregate, interpret, and also disseminate rich behavioural insights about citizens who are active producers but also users of policy-related information, the quantity and quality of civic participation is a key indicator of transparency success (Brunswicker, Pujol Priego and Almirall, 2019). In Algeria, demands for transparency came because of democratic governments routinely failing to meet the expectations of their voters.

8.11 Conclusion

The analysis in this chapter brought Algerian and Scottish policymaking dynamics into sharper focus between the two countries. As would be expected, the two country-settings also diverged in several areas. Despite the existence of two different governance structures in Algeria and Scotland (i.e., centralized vs consultative systems), and the subsequent implications of such systems on the timing when policy advice was needed and solicited, its source, and the way such advice influenced the making of higher education policy, the two countries shared the humane aspect in the experience. Feelings of marginalization, distrust and caution towards the government experienced by some participants were present in both contexts. These reflections provide another angle to better understand how policy advice shaped higher education and a learning opportunity for students, academics, policy actors, and decision makers.

Chapter 9

Conclusion

9.1 Introduction

This is the concluding chapter of the thesis, and it has two main objectives. First, it presents a summary of the key findings for the study, and secondly, highlights the contribution of the study, including some suggestions for future research.

9.2 Summary of the Findings

Through policy advice and expertise, the findings of the study reveal the influence of a large diversity of policy actors on policy making in higher education in Algeria and Scotland. In both countries the activities of policy actors through commissions, committees and panels were instrumental to the directions which various policy developments took. As discussed in chapter 6, the knowledge and advice provided by these experts was used either to propose a roadmap on how to proceed in a given policy area, here, the examples of widening access policies in Scotland and the quality assurance policy regime in Algeria stand out – or to advise on how to achieve a certain policy objective as was the case for the Benzaghou Commission in Algeria which led to the shift to the BMD system. The findings have highlighted that unlike Scotland, Algeria had also a unique way in soliciting policy advice in an open way through the organization of symposiums and conferences to elicit discussions and allow a multiplicity of views to be heard.

The study has revealed different strategies used by the various policy actors to influence the course of higher education policy making. In chapter 7, what could be called the ‘toolkit’ used by these policy actors was discussed. The two sets of actors seem to share a number of strategies, such as the use of evidence to back their policy advice as it was clear to them that a case rooted in legitimate and credible evidence has better chances to influence. Networking and the importance of having the right liaisons and relationships also came at the top although the participants went the extra mile to explain that not all relationships must hold that pejorative stigma. Engagement with the consultations launched by governments was also discussed as an important avenue for the actors to deliver their messages. In addition to the above, inside and outside lobbying, exerting pressure and making sure the public opinion is on the actors’ side, and having decent communication skills mixed with a true belief in the case they are advocating were yet another set of strategies actors in both countries seem to share. Due to the particularity

of Scotland being a devolved nation, the Scottish participants used the term “horizon scanning” – a useful term to describe the act of paying attention to what was happening in the ‘rest of the UK’. This strategy allowed the Scottish actors to understand what could happen next in Scotland.

The findings of the study also demonstrate that in their use of policy advice, Algeria and Scotland had common aspects despite their unique geographical, cultural, and political peculiarities. As explained in chapter 8, the two governments harnessed the expertise of the policy actors with the aims of getting a better understanding of the policy area they were working on to advise on the right path to follow as was the case for the international mobility scheme in Algeria and the widening access in Scotland and to propose how to carry out the policy that was already decided by the highest authorities in the two countries. The findings also identified that there was a display of readiness to listen to the views presented by the policy actors yet on the other hand a shared feeling of distrust among both Algerian and Scottish participants who were mostly academics and lecturers. As expected, the political considerations when making higher education related policies were another common area between the two contexts, with Scotland’s focus on the independence discourse and Algeria on staying careful when criticizing the government. Further, in both countries, those who got a hearing and a warm welcome to the discussion table were a select few who mostly agreed with the government’s agenda. As mentioned earlier, policy actors when giving policy advice resorted to similar strategies that are explained in chapter 7. The findings also reveal that both Scottish and Algerian actors experienced some barriers with Scottish participants struggling to fit into given networks because of their skin colour, and Algerian participants battling nepotism and regionalism. Of course, the biggest trigger of the differences between the two contexts was the way the higher education sector was run, with the open consultative approach in Scotland and the highly centralized method in Algeria and the implications of these systems on the policymaking. Chapter 8 also points out that although there is a variety of policy advice sources in the two countries, the quality of the advice, the timing when its most needed (agenda setting, policy development, policy feedback...), the packaging of the advice and its delivery channels do differ. Finally, unlike the Algerian way, Scotland has been more transparent with the communications taking place between the government and its policy community.

9.2 Contribution

This study is important to the fields of policy advice and expertise and higher education policy studies equally because it puts, for the first time, Scotland and Algeria into direct comparison. Usually, Scotland is compared to England and the other devolved nations, while Algeria is compared to other Middle East and North Africa countries. This uniqueness adds value to existing literature in this field and will encourage future researchers to explore other uncharted areas in higher education between western and non-western countries.

The study sheds light on the fact that despite their cultural and historical differences, Algerian and Scottish higher education had a lot in common in terms of how policy advice and expertise were used to influence the policymaking developments. Further, with the comparative aspect aside, data from Algeria provides a blueprint for other researchers to examine similar and related issues and help novice researchers overcome the scarcity of data.

The study represents a policy learning opportunity for both countries. Despite their areas of divergence, Algeria and Scotland share common aspects in terms of how they handled policy advice and expertise, how they used it, and how these impacted the respective higher education systems between 1999 and 2020. Policy makers in the two countries shared similar struggles when deciding which policy advice and forms of expertise to share given the micro-politics of policymaking in HE. This peculiar situation provides an opportunity for policy learning in whatever country can be facilitated for and by policy actors for maximum benefits towards successful policymaking in HE.

Another significant contribution lies in providing original empirical data concerning how policy advice is produced, translated and implemented in two distinct settings. In the Algerian case, the study voiced debates and higher education processes that are not properly documented in the English language scholarship. While in Scotland, the study explored the implications of the widely discussed Scottish consultative approach on policy advice in higher education, a topic that has received relatively restrained coverage.

Methodologically, the comparative case study between a global south (Algeria) context against a global north setting (Scotland) adds to the scholarship on comparative research and case study research to provide a roadmap on how multiple sources of data can be combined to identify the influence of policy advice.

9.4 Limitations of the Study

Despite the fact that this research offers original contributions to the scholarship available on policy advice and policy advisory systems in higher education policy, it has encountered a set of limitations.

The originality of the topic came with a flagrant lack of data in Algeria regarding the developments surrounding the use of policy advice in the major policy areas chosen for the study and a scarcity of literature. This is partly due to the absence of digitization in the country which makes accessing archival data more difficult. Key reports, confidential discussions, and internal records remain inaccessible, which constrained the research ability to fully understand the circumstances within which higher education policies took their final forms.

Also, the theme of policy advice in Algerian policymaking in general and in higher education policy in particular is a topic that was not addressed before. On the contrary, Scotland is blessed with an open access to extensive archival material ranging from well documented parliamentary sessions, consultation responses submitted to the Scottish government, official reports, and historical books written by prominent figures in the field. This imbalance in the data across the two settings also raised methodological issues that were solved through the comparative approach. Given the limitations of the data collected for this study, the conclusions drawn from this analysis should be treated with caution. While these weaknesses limit the generalizability of a study's conclusions, they also present a foundation for future research.

As any type of research, the positionality of the research might come in the way. Being an outsider kept the researcher attentive to small details and provided an objective and a naked eye to the discussion. Yet, this position made it hard for the researcher to establish contact with the participants first to secure interviews and second to make them feel safe enough to open up about their involvement and personal views regarding their fellow actors without fearing misunderstandings or misapprehension due to the researcher's cultural background. Some interviewees also seemed to withhold particular information when asked about the discussions happening backstage or abstain from certain questions when others let go of their prejudices once the interview questions started rolling.

The scope of the study also brings its own limitations. The research concentrated on specific policies in Algeria (The BMD system, quality assurance and the internalisation of higher education through the examination of the PhD scheme) and Scotland (tuition fees, widening access and the higher education governance reforms) and examined the work of specific

commissions related to these areas (The Benzaghoul Commission for the BMD system, The Cubie commission for tuition fees in Scotland, the CoWA for widening access, and the Prondzynski panel review for governance reforms). Although the researcher did analyse the input from other stakeholders, the design did exclude other higher education policies and the subsequent policy advisory forums associated with these initiatives. The focus on specific policies prioritized depth over breadth and therefore the conclusions primarily address how policy advice shaped the aforementioned policies instead of the entire higher education policy dynamics.

Finally, the researcher also needs to highlight factor of time and financial constraints as impediments of the current study. It is worthy to highlight that the research did not enjoy the smoothest start due to the COVID pandemic, which forced the adoption of distance learning. This impacted, negatively, the progress of the research and had severe psychological ramifications on the researcher's mental health as well.

Notwithstanding these limitations, the findings presented in this thesis are expected to make a much-needed contribution to the existing literature in this field. It presents an empirical basis for conceptual understandings of research utilisation and policy advice in higher education policymaking, thus addressing a gap identified by previous researchers.

9.5 Implications

The research findings hold important implications in empirical, practical, and theoretical aspects as these implications have a valuable and impactful contribution to both academia and the real world.

At the empirical level, the findings from this study offer new insights into the topic of policy advice in Algerian and Scottish higher education policy. These insights are grounded in qualitative data that are evidence-based offering conclusions that will hopefully expand the body of knowledge around the topic. The primary data collected from the interviews represent original data that can serve as a foundation for future research.

From a Practical standpoint, the findings can help bridge the gap between policymakers and other policy actors as the two can find a shared and common language to bring more efficiency to policy. Further, this research can have real world implications by testing the findings in reality. For example, the most efficient strategies outlined in the thesis can be tested by the stakeholders to maximize their influence. Policymakers can also benefit from this research by

carefully considering what works well and what triggers the other players to enhance the collegiality within the policymaking environment.

The study shows that the Algerian Government should pay more attention to the grievances of the people. Lecturers are feeling left behind in terms of the governmental agenda as they believed that their opinions are not needed and that they are mere puppets that must abide the government's decisions without taking part in making them. This distress can be dangerous due to the pivotal role played by this group. Left untreated, lecturers' tendency to engage in strikes to make their demands louder is more likely to grow and this will have terrible consequences on the academic output of their students.

There is a need to organize workshops for the policy community on how to approach policymakers and communicate effectively as it seems that there is a gap between these two communities. The language used by the policy actors in Algeria does not seem to be the same as the one spoken by the policymakers in the country. Such rupture gives the impression that the government does not care about their views, which is not always the case. The workshops can be a constructive way to educate the policy community on what the government needs, provide them with the skills and toolkits to listen and deliver their messages in a way that matches the government's resources and agenda at the time instead of the random toss of ideas at the wrong timing. The delivery would also mean training courses on how to choose the "suitable" format of the policy advice and its packaging.

For the policy actors, there is this distorted idea held by many policy actors (mainly independent scholars) that the Algerian government is acting alone in running the sector. This scenario might have been true at a given time, but a lot has changed recently. Unfortunately, the same prejudices are being held against the government, despite the substantial efforts made by the government to create more spaces for the society (students and parents) to engage more in making decisions related to future higher education policies.

Trade unions should be considered as a useful change agent, and not as a force of obstruction being. Another preconception is that joining a trade union is somehow a dangerous path to reach influence. While some participants argued that novice lecturers do not even know what a trade union means or does. In the race for influence, trade unions can be a strong platform for lecturers to be heard better.

Think tanks in Algeria are relatively a new phenomenon. This means that most policymakers do not even know that such bodies do exist and if they did they do not know fully their

capacities. In this case, the media can help introduce these organizations to the field and liaise them to policymakers.

Regionalism is a problem that long existed in the Algerian society as the Southern part of the country, despite its strategic significance to the country's economy and political stability, had always complained from the uneven attention given to the North (Keenan, 2003). The fact that the higher education policies decided upon by the North will be applied to the entire country, with the South included, made it difficult to have a unified satisfied response to the government's actions.

In Scotland, despite the consultative Scottish approach in monitoring the higher education sector, some issues need to be addressed. First, the power of Universities Scotland seems to be a worrying topic for the other members of the policy community in Scotland. The growing influence of principles had triggered many conflicts over the past twenty years. Such matter needs to be settled firmly by the Scottish Government as the dominant idea is that principles are the select few running the sector.

Think tanks, despite their newness to the political scene, remain a vital yet underused source for reliable policy information and cheap policy advice. However, it is important to mention that think tank board members did get representation in many policy developments as explained in the discussion chapters.

The Scottish Government should also pay more attention to the wording of its consultation papers and the room given to the experts to express their views. Questions regarding a certain policy area should focus more on the issue in hands instead of drifting away to less important elements. The section devoted to additional remarks should be bigger and must receive the greatest attention as it represents the honest and raw responses of those who care enough to respond to those consultation papers.

9.6 Recommendations for Future Research

Due to the scope of the study and the time constraints, the study has given uneven attention to some issues that are worthy of better attention. First, the emphasis of the study was on how policy advice shaped higher education policy developments in three areas in each country. Of course, there are more ongoing key events taking place in the field that were too recent to focus on such as the introduction of the English language as a language of instruction in Algerian Universities. Such huge detour is a rich area for other researchers to explore.

The study did not fully investigate issues related to the quality of policy advice and expertise that exists in policymaking. While this has received some attention in other national contexts, it is recommended that future research in Scotland or Algeria must pay attention to this important issue.

Third, another important yet underexplored theme in this study is the reference to the recent efforts made by the Algerian government in being more open and transparent in terms of publicising the discussions around certain HE policy developments and the input (policy advice) provided by the different members of the policy community. This shift is also a fertile area for future research especially that Algeria had had a contrasting way in running the sector for the past few decades.

While this study chose to focus on Algeria and Scotland, this research opens venues for researchers to look at other countries from the Global South and have it compared to the ones from the Global North. These future comparative studies can expand and widen the scope of this type of research and offer original insights into cross-national policymaking and generate new learning opportunities.

Future research can build on the findings from this study and dive deeper into each group (student unions, think tanks, trade unions) to capture their views regarding the legitimacy and influence of commissions without the comparative lens. This will allow the emphasis to be purely concentrated on the views of these stakeholders allowing more time for the interviewees to reflect on matters related to their involvement. For example, a research on how policymakers deal with the policy advice, how they base their judgment when choosing to select, put on hold, or simply ignore the evidence presented to them. Once this area is explored, the research can move to how this evidence is used.

The international dimension for Algeria and the multilevel governance within which Scottish higher education evolved and continue to operate provide a good ground for further investigation. There remains a scope for examining how domestic policy advice is handled when it's negotiated at an international level. International organization such as the EU, World bank, UNESCO and international processes such as the Bologna process will add an additional layer of complexity to the supply and demand of policy advice.

The views, grieving, and dissatisfaction of some groups can be a significant variable that calls for an interdisciplinary approach in the Future. The field of psychology as an example can

provide valuable insights into the many ways policy actors think about their involvement and their worth.

Future research can also engage in an investigation of how policy advice influence one specific Higher education policy at different times using the policy stages model. The researcher can start by identifying how the experts' input vary from Agenda setting, to policy formulation, legitimation, implementation, until the policy evaluation. Such examination can generate significant findings and assess when policy advice is the most influential.

References

- Abdullahi, M. and Othman, N. (2020) 'Bridging the Gap between Policy Intent and Implementation' *Journal of Science, Technology and Innovation Policy*, 6(1), pp. 24–33. doi: 10.11113/jostip.v6n1.49.
- Aberbach, J.D., Putnam, R.D. and Rockman, B.A. (1983) *Bureaucrats and politicians in Western democracies*. Cambridge, MA; London: Harvard University Press.
- Adams, J. (2022) *The marketisation of international student mobility in the UK*. London: Higher Education Policy Institute.
- Adler, E. and Haas, P.M. (1992) 'Conclusion: Epistemic communities, world order, and the creation of a reflective research program', *International Organization*, 46(1), pp. 367–390. Available at: <https://doi.org/10.1017/s0020818300001533> (Accessed: 23 November 2022).
- Adom, D., Hussein, E.K. and Agyem, J.A. (2018) 'Theoretical and conceptual framework: Mandatory ingredients of a quality research', *International Journal of Scientific Research*, 7(1). Available at: [Theoretical and Conceptual Framework: Mandatory Ingredients of a Quality Research | Semantic Scholar](https://doi.org/10.1017/s0020818300001533) (Accessed: 20 July 2022).
- Aiyede, E.R. (2023) 'From research to policy action: communicating research for public policy making', in Aiyede, E.R. and Muganda, B. (eds.) *Public policy and research in Africa*. Cham: Palgrave Macmillan. Available at: https://doi.org/10.1007/978-3-030-99724-3_11 (Accessed: 19 July 2025).
- Akhbareelwatan (2021) 'Student organisations: suspicious roles [أدوار المنظمات الطلابية: مشبوهة]'. Available at: <https://akhbareelwatane.dz/المنظمات-الطلابية-أدوار-مشبوهة/> (Accessed: 5 August 2025).
- Akintoye, A. (2015) 'Developing theoretical and conceptual frameworks', in *EDMIC Research Workshop*. Ile-Ife: Faculty of Environmental Design and Management, Obafemi Awolowo University.
- Algérie Solidaire (2016) *Conférence nationale d'évaluation du système LMD à Alger*. Available at: <https://algeriesolidaire.net/conference-nationale-devaluation-du-systeme-lmd-a-alger/> (Accessed: 16 August 2025).
- Alkubaisi, H. and Rasool, N. (2020) 'Financing higher education in Arab countries: Challenges, constraints and solutions', *Journal of Education and Training Studies*, 8(8), pp. 38–45. Available at: <https://doi.org/10.11114/jets.v8i8.4708> (Accessed: 23 November 2022)..
- Allmark, P., Boote, J., Chambers, E., Clarke, A., McDonnell, A., Thompson, A. and Tod, A. (2009) 'Ethical issues in the use of in-depth interviews: Literature review and discussion', *Research Ethics*, 5(2), pp. 48–54. Available at: <https://journals.sagepub.com/doi/pdf/10.1177/174701610900500203> (Accessed: 5 August 2023).

Almeida, F., Faria, D. and Queirós, A. (2017) ‘Strengths and limitations of qualitative and quantitative research methods’, *European Journal of Education Studies*, 3(9). Available at: <https://www.researchgate.net/publication/319852576> (Accessed: 9 June 2021).

Amina (2016) ‘Conférence d’évaluation du LMD: adaptation “urgente” du système d’enseignement supérieur’, *Algerie360* [online]. Available at: <https://www.algerie360.com/conference-devaluation-du-lmd-adaptation-urgente-du-systeme-denseignement-superieur/> (Accessed: 16 August 2022).

Anderson, C.W. (1971) ‘Comparative policy analysis: the design of measures’, *Comparative Politics*, 4(1), pp. 117–131. Available at: <https://doi.org/10.2307/421437> (Accessed: 2 July 2025).

Anderson, G. (1996) ‘The new focus on the policy capacity of the federal government’, *Canadian Public Administration*, 39(4), pp. 469–488. Available at: <https://doi.org/10.1111/j.1754-7121.1996.tb00146.x> (Accessed: 23 November 2022)

Anderson, J.E. (1982) *Cases in public policy-making*. New York: Holt, Rinehart and Winston.

Anderson, J.E. (2014) *Public policymaking: An introduction*. 8th edn. Stamford, CT: Cengage Learning.

Andersson, I. and Cook, I.R. (2019) ‘Conferences, award ceremonies and the showcasing of “best practice”: A case study of the annual European Week of Regions and Cities in Brussels’, *Environment and Planning C: Politics and Space*. Available at: <https://doi.org/10.1177/2399654419825656> (Accessed: 23 November 2022).

Antunes, S. (2015) ‘The Scottish referendum 2014: The political process before and after the “no” vote’, *e-Journal of International Relations*, 6(2), pp. 44–60. Available at: <https://www.researchgate.net/publication/298646574> (Accessed: 17 March 2021).

Anyebe, A.A. (2018) ‘An overview of approaches to the study of public policy’, *International Journal of Political Science*, 4(1). Available at: <https://doi.org/10.20431/2454-9452.0401002>

Arnott, M. and Menter, I. (2007) ‘The same but different? Post-devolution regulation and control in education in Scotland and England’, *European Educational Research Journal*, 6(3), pp. 250–265. Available at: <https://doi.org/10.2304/eej.2007.6.3.250>

Arnstein, S.R. (1969) ‘A ladder of citizen participation’, *Journal of the American Institute of Planners*, 35(4), pp. 216–224. Available at: <https://doi.org/10.1080/01944366908977225>

Arras, S. and Beyers, J. (2019) ‘Access to European Union agencies: Usual suspects or balanced interest representation in open and closed consultations?’, *JCMS: Journal of Common Market Studies*, 58(4), pp. 836–855. Available at: <https://doi.org/10.1111/jcms.12991>

Asante, R. (2018) ‘China and Africa: model of South–South cooperation?’, *China Quarterly of International Strategic Studies*, 4(2), pp. 259–279. Available

at: <https://www.worldscientific.com/doi/pdf/10.1142/S2377740018500124> (Accessed: 30 August 2025).

Badran, A., Baydoun, E. and Hillman, J.R. (eds) (2019) *Major challenges facing higher education in the Arab world: Quality assurance and relevance*. Cham: Springer International Publishing. Available at: <https://doi.org/10.1007/978-3-030-03774-1>

Bakvis, H. (2000) 'Rebuilding policy capacity in the era of the fiscal dividend: A report from Canada', *Governance*, 13(1), pp. 71–103. Available at: <https://doi.org/10.1111/0952-1895.00124>

Ball, S.J. (1998) 'Big policies/small world: an introduction to international perspectives in education policy', *Comparative Education*, 34(2), pp. 119–130. Available at: <https://www.tandfonline.com/doi/pdf/10.1080/030500698282225> (Accessed: 9 July 2025)

Ball, S.J. (2009) 'Privatising education, privatising education policy, privatising educational research: network governance and the "competition state"', *Journal of Education Policy*, 24(1), pp. 83–99. Available at: <https://doi.org/10.1080/02680930802419474>.

Ball, S.J. (2012) *Global Education Inc.: New policy networks and the neoliberal imaginary*. 1st edn. Abingdon: Routledge. Available at: <https://doi.org/10.4324/9780203803301>.

Bandola-Gill, J. and Lyall, C. (2017) 'Knowledge brokers and policy advice in policy formulation', in Howlett, M. and Mukherjee, I. (eds) *Handbook of policy formulation*. Cheltenham: Edward Elgar Publishing Ltd, pp. 249–264. (Handbooks of Research on Public Policy series)

Bartlett, L. and Vavrus, F. (2017) 'Comparative case studies: an innovative approach', *Nordic Journal of Comparative and International Education*, 1(1). Available at: <https://doi.org/10.7577/njcie.1929>

Baskin, D. (1970) 'American pluralism: Theory, practice, and ideology', *The Journal of Politics*, 32(1), pp. 71–95. Available at: <https://doi.org/10.2307/2128865>

Baumgartner, F.R. and Jones, B.D. (1993) *Agendas and instability in American politics*. Chicago: University of Chicago Press.

Baumgartner, F.R., Jones, B.D. and Wilkerson, J. (2011) 'Comparative studies of policy dynamics', *Comparative Political Studies*, 44(8), pp. 947–972. Available at: <https://doi.org/10.1177/0010414011405160>.

Baxter, P. and Jack, S. (2008) 'Qualitative case study methodology: Study design and implementation for novice researchers', *The Qualitative Report*, 13(4), pp. 544–559. Available at: <https://doi.org/10.46743/2160-3715/2008>.

BBC News (1999) 'Scotland Wallace remains firm on tuition fees', *BBC News*, 16 October. Available at: http://news.bbc.co.uk/2/hi/uk_news/scotland/476885.stm (Accessed: 3 July 2021).

- BBC News (1999a) ‘Scotland students press for fees change’, *BBC News*, September. Available at: http://news.bbc.co.uk/2/hi/uk_news/scotland/441301.stm (Accessed: 9 July 2022).
- BBC News (2000) ‘United plea for fees compromise’, *BBC News*, 6 January. Available at: <https://news.bbc.co.uk/1/hi/scotland/592497.stm> (Accessed: 24 March 2022).
- BBC News (2007) ‘Graduate endowment fee abolished’, *BBC News*, 13 June. Available at: http://news.bbc.co.uk/2/hi/uk_news/scotland/6744559.stm (Accessed: 7 July 2022).
- BBC News (2011) ‘Students march to Holyrood in education protest’, *BBC News*, 23 March. Available at: <https://www.bbc.com/news/uk-scotland-12819043> (Accessed: 6 October 2021).
- BBC News (2012) ‘Fair access to Scotland's universities “decades away” says NUS’, *BBC News*, 24 July. Available at: <https://www.bbc.com/news/uk-scotland-18968849> (Accessed: 12 January 2021).
- Bedaida, I., Benguerna, M. and Meyer, J.-B. (2022) ‘Emergence of private higher education in Algeria: actors and pathways’, *Economics and Business*, 36, pp. 85–104. Available at: <https://doi.org/10.2478/eb-2022-0006>
- Béland, D. and Schlager, E. (2019) ‘Varieties of policy feedback research: Looking backward, moving forward’, *Policy Studies Journal*, 47(2), pp. 184–205. Available at: <https://doi.org/10.1111/psj.12340>
- Béland, D., Howlett, M. and Mukherjee, I. (2017) ‘Instrument constituencies and public policy-making: An introduction’, *Policy and Society*, 37(1), pp. 1–13. Available at: <https://doi.org/10.1080/14494035.2017.1375249>
- Belhocine, H.H. (2022) ‘Aperçu de l’enseignement supérieur en Algérie de l’indépendance à aujourd’hui’ (Overview of higher education in Algeria from independence to present), *Paradigmes*, [online] 5(3), pp.17–33. Available at: [Aperçu de l’enseignement supérieur en Algérie de l’indépendance à aujourd’hui | ASJP \(cerist.dz\)](https://www.cerist.dz/ASJP/cerist.dz) (Accessed: 22 April 2023).
- Belimane, W. and Chahed, A. (2021) ‘The limits of leadership as a barrier to quality assurance in higher education in Algeria’, *Economics and Business*, 35(1), pp. 215–228. Available at: <https://doi.org/10.2478/eb-2021-0015>
- Bell, R.E. (2000) ‘Scotland’s universities’, *Comparative Education*, 36(2), pp. 163–175. Available at: <http://www.jstor.org/stable/3099865> (Accessed: 22 April 2023).
- Benchikh, H. (2018) ‘Governance of higher education institutions in Algeria: inventory and assessment’, in Farazmand, A. (ed.) *Global encyclopedia of public administration, public policy, and governance*. Cham: Springer. Available at: https://doi.org/10.1007/978-3-319-20928-9_2992
- Benelhadj Djelloul, S. (2022) ‘Réforme et représentations du français en Algérie: Analyse sociolinguistique des articles de presse’, *Développement des sciences sociales*, 15(1), pp.

303–311. Available at: <https://www.asjp.cerist.dz/en/article/201367> (Accessed: 15 February 2023).

Benjelloun, W. (2019) ‘Quality-assurance agencies in the Maghreb countries: Challenges and opportunities’, in Badran, A., Baydoun, E. and Hillman, J.R. (eds) *Major challenges facing higher education in the Arab world: Quality assurance and relevance*. Cham: Springer, pp. 325–333. Available at: https://doi.org/10.1007/978-3-030-03774-1_16

Bennett Institute for Public Policy (2020) *Engaging with knowledge brokers: A guide for academics*. Cambridge: Bennett Institute for Public Policy. Available at: <https://tinyurl.com/2p8jzj7v> (Accessed: 16 August 2025).

Bennett, M., Fairley, J. and McAteer, M. (2002) *Devolution in Scotland: the impact on local government*. [technical report] Joseph Rowntree Foundation. Available at: <https://doi.org/10.13140/RG.2.2.20737.76644>

Benouar, D. (2013) ‘Algerian experience in education, research and practice’, *Procedia - Social and Behavioral Sciences*, 102, pp. 361–367. Available at: <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.sbspro.2013.10.751>

Bensouiah, A. (2018) ‘Higher education union threatens strike over “injustices”’, *University World News*. Available at: <https://www.universityworldnews.com/post.php?story=20181009141100790> (Accessed: 1 August 2025).

Benstaali, B. (2013) *English and French Tempus Assessment Report: Algeria 2002–2013*. El Oued: National Tempus Office Algeria. Available at: : <https://old.univ-eloued.dz/stock/univ/pdf/English-and-French-Tempus-Assessment-Report-Algeria-2002-2013.pdf> (Accessed: 19 August 2025).

Benstaali, B. (2019) ‘Higher Education Partnership between Maghreb and European Higher Education Institutions during the 2002–2013 Decade’, in Woldegiorgis, E.T. and Scherer, C. (eds.) *Partnership in Higher Education*. Leiden: Brill, pp. 103–119. Available at: <https://brill.com/abstract/book/edcoll/9789004411876/BP000015.xml> (Accessed: 1 September 2025).

Benziane, A. (2004) ‘Economic reforms in Algeria and their impact on higher education and student benefits’, *The Journal of North African Studies*, 9(2), pp. 102–114. Available at: <https://doi.org/10.1080/1362938042000323374> (Accessed: 7 August 2021).

Bernier, L. and Lachapelle, G. (2018) ‘Chapitre 1. L’étude des politiques gouvernementales’, in *Analyser les politiques publiques*. Montréal: Presses de l’Université de Montréal, pp. 9–35. Available at: <https://doi.org/10.4000/books.pum.6256> (Accessed: 7 August 2025).

Berrouche, Z. and Berkane, Y. (2007) ‘La mise en place du système LMD en Algérie, entre la nécessité d’une réforme et les difficultés du terrain’, *Revue des sciences économiques et de gestion*, 7(7), pp. 1–14. Available at: <https://www.asjp.cerist.dz/en/article/6050> (Accessed: 11 June 2021).

- Bertelsmann Stiftung (2022) *BTI 2022 Country Report — Algeria*. Gütersloh: Bertelsmann Stiftung. Available at: https://bti-project.org/fileadmin/api/content/en/downloads/reports/country_report_2022_DZA.pdf (Accessed 25 Aug. 2025).
- Bevir, M. (2013) *A Theory of Governance*. Berkeley: University of California Press. Available at: <https://escholarship.org/uc/item/2qs2w3rb> (Accessed: 16 August 2025).
- Bevir, M. and Rhodes, R.A.W. (1999) 'Studying British government: reconstructing the research agenda', *The British Journal of Politics and International Relations*, 1, pp. 215–239. Available at: <https://doi.org/10.1111/1467-856X.00012>.
- Bevir, M. and Rhodes, R.A.W. (2001) 'Decentering tradition', *Administration & Society*, 33(2), pp. 107–132. Available at: <https://doi.org/10.1177/00953990122019703> (Accessed: 7 August 2025).
- Bevir, M. and Rhodes, R.A.W. (2003) *Interpreting British governance*. London: Routledge.
- Bevir, M. and Rhodes, R.A.W. (2006) 'Defending interpretation', *European Political Science*, 5, pp. 69–83. Available at: <https://doi.org/10.1057/palgrave.eps.2210059>
- Bevir, M. and Richards, D. (2009) 'Decentring policy networks: a theoretical agenda', *Public Administration*, 87, pp. 3–14. Available at: <https://doi.org/10.1111/j.1467-9299.2008.01736.x>
- Bevir, M., Rhodes, R.A.W. and Weller, P. (2003) 'Traditions of governance: Interpreting the changing role of the public sector', *Public Administration*, 81(1), pp. 1–17. Available at: <https://doi.org/10.1111/1467-9299.00334>
- Beyers, J. (2004) 'Voice and access: Political practices of European interest associations', *European Union Politics*, 5(2), pp. 211–240. Available at: <https://doi.org/10.1177/1465116504042442>
- Bhardwaj, P. (2019) 'Types of sampling in research', *Journal of the Practice of Cardiovascular Sciences*, 5(3), pp. 157–163. Available at: https://doi.org/10.4103/jpcs.jpcs_62_19 (Accessed: 7 August 2025).
- Birkland, T.A. (2005) *An introduction to the policy process: Theories, concepts and models of public policy making*. New York: Routledge.
- Black, A. (2011) 'SNP conference: Salmond in free education pledge', *BBC News*, 12 March. Available at: <https://www.bbc.com/news/uk-scotland-12711509> (Accessed: 7 August 2025).
- Blackburn, L., Kadar-Satat, G., Riddell, S. and Weedon, E. (2016) *Access in Scotland: Access to higher education for people from less advantaged backgrounds in Scotland*. Edinburgh: University of Edinburgh.
- Blair-Walcott, K. (2023) 'Comparative Analysis', in Okoko, J.M., Tunison, S. and Walker, K.D. (eds) *Varieties of Qualitative Research Methods: Selected Contextual Perspectives*. Cham: Springer International Publishing, pp. 79–84.

- Bleiklie, I. and Michelsen, S. (2022) ‘The new abundance of policy advice: The advisory roles of political scientists in Norway’, in Brans, M., Timmermans, A. and Gouglas, A. (eds) *The advisory roles of political scientists in Europe*. Cham: Springer, pp. 225–251. Available at: https://doi.org/10.1007/978-3-030-86005-9_11
- Boliver, V., Gorard, S. and Siddiqui, N. (2019) ‘Using contextual data to widen access to higher education’, *Perspectives: Policy and Practice in Higher Education*, 25(1), pp. 1–7. Available at: <https://doi.org/10.1080/13603108.2019.1678076>
- Bolton, P. and Hubble, S. (2018) *Higher education tuition fees in England*. House of Commons Library, Briefing Paper Number CBP-8151. Published: 25 June 2018. Available at: <https://researchbriefings.files.parliament.uk/documents/CBP-8151/CBP-8151.pdf> (Accessed: 7 August 2025).
- Börzel, T.A. (1998) ‘Organizing Babylon – on the different conceptions of policy networks’, *Public Administration*, 76(2), pp. 253–273. Available at: <https://doi.org/10.1111/1467-9299.00100>
- Börzel, T.A. (2002) ‘What’s so special about policy networks? An exploration of the concept and its usefulness in studying European governance’, *SSRN Electronic Journal* [Preprint]. Available at: <https://doi.org/10.2139/ssrn.302706>
- Börzel, T.A. (2011) ‘Networks: reified metaphor or governance panacea?’, *Public Administration*, 89, pp. 49–63. Available at: <https://doi.org/10.1111/j.1467-9299.2011.01916.x>
- Boston, J. (1994) ‘Purchasing policy advice: The limits to contracting out’, *Governance*, 7(1), pp. 1–30. Available at: <https://doi.org/10.1111/j.1468-0491.1994.tb00167.x>
- Boston, J., Martin, J., Pallot, J. and Walsh, P. (1996) *Public management: The New Zealand model*. Auckland: Oxford University Press.
- Boswell, C. (2008) ‘The political functions of expert knowledge: Knowledge and legitimation in European Union immigration policy’, *Journal of European Public Policy*, 15(4), pp. 471–488. Available at: <https://doi.org/10.1080/13501760801996634>
- Bouchikhi, F. and Barka, Z. (2017) ‘Higher education in Algeria: Achievements and challenges – 1963 to 2017’, *Revue Algérienne des finances publiques*, 7. Available at: https://www.researchgate.net/publication/330819979_Higher_Education_in_Algeria_Achievements_and_challenges-1963_to_2017 (Accessed: 6 October 2020).
- Bouherar, S. and Salem, S. (2025) ‘A review of Algerian higher education reforms, 1962–2019’, in *Sustainability in Algerian higher education*. Cham: Palgrave Macmillan. Available at: https://doi.org/10.1007/978-3-031-81347-4_3
- Boulerias, S. (2013) ‘(نبذة عن تطور التعميم العالي والبحث العممي في الجزائر 1962–2000) An overview of the development of higher education and scientific research in Algeria (1962–2000)’. Available at: <https://asjp.cerist.dz/en/article/18797> (Accessed: 9 May 2025).

- Bourke, A. (1997) 'The internationalisation of higher education: the case of medical education', *Higher Education in Europe*, 22(1), pp. 41–50. Available at: <https://doi.org/10.1111/1468-2273.00050>
- Bouzid, N., Berrouche, Z. and Berkane, Y. (2013) 'Higher education in Algeria: Evolution and perspectives', *Semantic Scholar*. Available at: <https://www.semanticscholar.org/paper/Higher-Education-in-Algeria-%3A-Evolution-and-Bouzid-Berrouche/f60ed5e6140001b36321540314af1bb58366b8ae> (Accessed: 6 April 2020).
- Bowen, G.A. (2009) 'Document analysis as a qualitative research method', *Qualitative Research Journal*, 9(2), pp. 27–40. Available at: (PDF) Document Analysis as a Qualitative Research Method (researchgate.net) (Accessed: 20 May 2022).
- Brans, M., Timmermans, A. and Gouglas, A. (2022) 'A theoretical perspective on the roles of political scientists in policy advisory systems', in Brans, M., Timmermans, A. and Gouglas, A. (eds) *The advisory roles of political scientists in Europe*. Cham: Springer, pp. 15–39. Available at: https://doi.org/10.1007/978-3-030-86005-9_2
- Brennan, J., King, R. and Lebeau, Y. (2004) *The role of universities in the transformation of societies: An international research project. Synthesis report*. London: Association of Commonwealth Universities [online]. Available at: <https://www.acu.ac.uk/focus-areas/transforming-societies/>
- Brewer, G.D. (1974) 'The policy sciences emerge: To nurture and structure a discipline', *Policy Sciences*, 5(3), pp. 239–244. Available at: <https://doi.org/10.1007/bf00144283>
- Brewer, G.D. and DeLeon, P. (1983) *The foundations of policy analysis*. Monterey, CA: Brooks/Cole Publishing Company.
- Briggs, S. (2006) 'An exploratory study of the factors influencing undergraduate student choice: The case of higher education in Scotland', *Studies in Higher Education*, 31(6), pp. 705–722. Available at: <https://doi.org/10.1080/03075070601004333>
- British Council (2014) *Algerian Higher Education delegation visits UK*. Available at: <https://www.britishcouncil.org/contact/press/algerian-higher-education-delegation-visits-uk> (Accessed: 1 September 2025).
- British Council (2018) *Algerian Doctoral Initiative*. Available at: <https://www.britishcouncil.dz/en/programmes/education/algerian-doctoral-initiative> (Accessed: 1 August 2023).
- Brown, R. and Piatt, W. (2001) *Funding widening participation in higher education: A discussion paper*. London: Council for Industry and Higher Education; Institute for Public Policy Research.
- Browne, J. (2010) *Securing a sustainable future for higher education: an independent review of higher education funding and student finance*. London: Department for Business,

Innovation & Skills. Available at: <https://dera.ioe.ac.uk/id/eprint/11444/> (Accessed: 21 May 2025).

Brunswicker, S., Pujol Priego, L. and Almirall, E. (2019) 'Transparency in policy making: A complexity view', *Government Information Quarterly*, 36(3), pp. 571–591. Available at: <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.giq.2019.05.005>

Buckner, E. (2011) 'The role of higher education in the Arab state and society: Historical legacies and recent reform patterns', *Comparative and International Higher Education*, 3, pp. 21–26.

Bunoti, S.N. (2011) *The quality of higher education in developing countries needs professional support*. Available at: <https://www.intconfhighered.org/FINAL%20Sarah%20Bunoti.pdf> (Accessed: 7 August 2025).

Burnhill, P., Garner, C. and McPherson, A. (1988) 'Social change, school attainment and entry to higher education 1976–1986', in Raffe, D. (ed.) *Education and the youth labour market*. Falmer, pp. 66–99.

Burstein, P. (2003) 'The impact of public opinion on public policy: A review and an agenda', *Political Research Quarterly*, 56(1), pp. 29–40. Available at: <https://doi.org/10.2307/3219881>

Burstein, P. and Linton, A. (2002) 'The impact of political parties, interest groups, and social movement organizations on public policy: Some recent evidence and theoretical concerns', *Social Forces*, 81(2), pp. 380–408. Available at: <https://doi.org/10.1353/sof.2003.0004>

Buzasu, C. (2020) 'The role of civil society in policymaking', *Apolitical*, 19 June. Available at: <https://apolitical.co/solution-articles/en/the-role-of-civil-society-in-policymaking> (Accessed: 10 September 2022).

Byrne, D. and Ozga, J. (2008) 'BERA review 2006: education research and policy', *Research Papers in Education*, 23(4), pp. 377–405. Available at: <https://doi.org/10.1080/02671520701755457>

Cairney, P. (2012) 'Chapter 8 – Pressure politics and the “Scottish Policy Style”', in *Scottish Politics*. 2nd ed. Available at: <https://dspace.stir.ac.uk/bitstream/1893/16409/1/Scottish%20Politics%202nd%20ed%20Chapter%208%20Policy%20Style.pdf> (Accessed: 8 November 2021).

Cairney, P. (2013a) “Majoritarian Versus Consensus Policymaking” or a “Common European Policy Style”? The Case of the UK and Scotland', presented at the Japanese Political Science Association Annual Conference, Hokkai Gakuen University, Sapporo, September 2013. Available at: <https://paulcairney.wordpress.com/wp-content/uploads/2013/08/cairney-jpsa-2013.pdf> (Accessed: 16 August 2025).

Cairney, P. (2013b) 'Territorial policy communities and the Scottish policy style: the case of compulsory education', *Scottish Affairs*, 82(1), pp. 73–97. Available at: <https://doi.org/10.3366/scot.2013.0004>

Cairney, P. (2017) 'The politics of evidence-based policy making', *Oxford Research Encyclopedia of Politics*. Available at: <https://oxfordre.com/politics/view/10.1093/acrefore/9780190228637.001.0001/acrefore-9780190228637-e-268> (Accessed: 20 July 2022).

Cairney, P. (2020) 'The "Scottish approach" to policymaking', in Keating, M. (ed.) *The Oxford Handbook of Scottish Politics*. Oxford: Oxford University Press, pp. 462–480. Available at: <https://doi.org/10.1093/oxfordhb/9780198825098.013.24>.

Cairney, P. and Oliver, K. (2018) 'How should academics engage in policymaking to achieve impact?', *Political Studies Review*, 18(2), pp. 228–244. Available at: <https://doi.org/10.1177/1478929918807714>.

Cairney, P., Russell, S. and St Denny, E. (2016) 'The "Scottish approach" to policy and policymaking: What issues are territorial and what are universal?', *Policy & Politics*, 44(3), pp. 333–350. Available at: <https://doi.org/10.1332/030557315x14353331264538>

Callander, R., Gunson, R. and Murray, C. (2018) *The future is coming: ready or not? Further education, the Scottish labour market and skills system*. London: Institute for Public Policy Research. Available at: <https://ippr-org.files.svdcn.com/production/Downloads/scotland-fetl2-september18.pdf> (Accessed: 16 August 2025).

Caplan, N. (1979) 'The two-communities theory and knowledge utilization', *American Behavioral Scientist*, 22(3), pp. 459–470. Available at: <https://doi.org/10.1177/000276427902200308>.

Carasso, H. and Gunn, A. (2015) *Tuition fees in the UK: research and policy*. London: Routledge.

Carrell, S. (2015) 'Scottish universities warn over new measures by Sturgeon government', *The Guardian*, 10 September. Available at: <https://www.theguardian.com/education/2015/sep/10/scottish-universities-warn-over-new-measures-by-sturgeon-government> (Accessed: 9 January 2021).

Castro Torres, A. and Alburez-Gutierrez, D. (2022) 'Why demography matters for understanding global inequalities', *Genus*, 78(1), pp. 1–9.

Catania Declaration (2006) *Euro-Mediterranean Area of Higher Education and Research*. Catania.

Cavana, R.Y., Delahaye, B.L. and Sekaran, U. (2001) *Applied business research: Qualitative and quantitative methods*. Milton, Qld: John Wiley & Sons.

Cerna, L. (2013) *The nature of policy change and implementation: a review of different theoretical approaches*. Paris: OECD. Available at: <https://docslib.org/doc/11658304/the->

nature-of-policy-change-and-implementation-a-review-of-different-theoretical-approaches (Accessed: 5 August 2021).

Chachoua, K. and Schoelen, L. (2019) Higher education systems and institutions: Algeria. In: Teixeira, P.N., Shin, J.C., Klemenčič, M., Goastellec, G., Amaral, A., Magalhães, A., Choi, E., De Wit, H., Hunter, F., Rumbley, L., Unangst, L., Nokkala, T., Välimaa, J., Kehm, B.M., Langa, P., Mohamedbhai, G., Yang, R., Balbachevsky, E. and Bernasconi, A. (eds.) *The International Encyclopedia of Higher Education Systems and Institutions*. Dordrecht: Springer. Available at: https://doi.org/10.1007/978-94-017-9553-1_436-1

Chakrabarty, D. (2000) *Provincializing Europe: postcolonial thought and historical difference*. Princeton, NJ: Princeton University Press.

Chandrashekhara, B.E. (2018) 'Post-colonialism and its impact on political identity in the Global South', *International Journal of Research and Analytical Reviews (IJRAR)*, 5(1), pp. 131–136. Available at: <https://www.ijrar.org/IJAR19D6222.pdf> (Accessed: 12 July 2025).

Chekouri, S.M., Chibi, A. and Benbouziane, M. (2017) 'Algeria and the natural resource curse: oil abundance and economic growth', *Middle East Development Journal*, 9(2), pp. 233–255. Available at: <https://doi.org/10.1080/17938120.2017.1366772>

Chen, L. and Barnett, G.A. (2000) 'Research on international student flows from a macro perspective: a network analysis of the world system', *Higher Education*, 39(4), pp. 435–453.

CIAQES (2017) *National Commission for the Implementation of Quality Assurance in Higher Education. Formation intensive des nouveaux RAQs (7 et 8 déc 2016)*. CIAQES - Algérie. Available at: <https://www.ciaques-mesrs.dz> (Accessed: 23 June 2022)

Cobbette, T. (2025) *Mapping the regulatory landscape for higher education in Scotland*. AHEP Consulting, for Academic Registrars' Council, January. Available at: https://arc.ac.uk/cdn/uploads/files/Overview_of_Regulation_in_Scotland_%281%29.pdf (Accessed: 12 July 2025).

Cochran, C.L. and Malone, E.F. (1999) *Public policy: perspectives and choices*. Boston: McGraw-Hill.

Cochrane, A. (2023) 'Scottish independence: How did we get here and what happens next?', *BBC News*, 15 October. Available at: <https://www.bbc.com/news/uk-scotland-scotland-politics-67063555> (Accessed: 11 February 2024)

Cohen, L., Manion, L. and Morrison, K. (2007) *Research methods in education*. 6th edn. London: Routledge.

Collyer, F. (2016). Global patterns in the publishing of academic knowledge: global north, global south. *Current Sociology*, 66(1), 56-73. <https://doi.org/10.1177/0011392116680020>

Colonna, F. (2004) “‘What has become of my friends?’ Questions regarding the new Algerian “diaspora” in France’, *The Journal of North African Studies*, 9(2), pp. 126–139.

Committee of Scottish Chairs (2013) *Scottish code of good higher education governance*. Edinburgh: Committee of Scottish Chairs. Available at: <https://www.scottishuniversitygovernance.ac.uk/wp-content/uploads/2013/07/Scottish-Code-of-Good-HE-Governance.pdf> (Accessed: 19 August 2025).

Committee of Scottish Chairs (2013) *The Scottish Code of Good HE Governance: governance code and supporting guidelines for members of the governing bodies of higher education institutions in Scotland*. Available at: <http://www.scottishuniversitygovernance.ac.uk/the-2013-code-2/> (Accessed: 26 August 2021)

Connaughton, B. and DeVane, C. (2023) “‘Best advice available” – Challenge and change in developing an optimal policy advisory system in Ireland’, *Administration*, 71(3), pp. 35–61. Available at: <https://doi.org/10.2478/admin-2023-0016>

Connaughton, B. (2005) ‘The impact of coalition government on politico-administrative relations in Ireland 1981–2002’, in Peters, B.G., Verheijen, T. and Vass, L. (eds) *Coalitions of the unwilling? Politicians and civil servants in coalition governments*. Bratislava, Slovakia: NISPAcee.

Connaughton, B. (2006) ‘Relegating civil servants to the periphery? The institutionalisation of special advisers as carriers of political-administrative roles’. Paper presented at the 14th Annual NISPA Conference *Public Administration and Public Policy in Emerging Europe and Eurasia: Professionalism, Impartiality and Transparency*, Ljubljana, Slovenia, 11–13 May.

Connaughton, B. (2010a) ‘Ireland’, in Eichbaum, C. and Shaw, R. (eds) *Partisan appointees and public servants: an international analysis of the role of the political adviser*, pp. 151–179. Aldershot: Edward Elgar.

Connaughton, B. (2010b) “‘Glorified gofers, policy experts or good generalists”’: A classification of the roles of the Irish ministerial adviser’, *Irish Political Studies*, 25(3), pp. 347–369. Available at: <https://doi.org/10.1080/07907184.2010.497636>

Connaughton, B. (2017) ‘Political-administrative relations: the role of political advisers’, *Administration*, 65(2), pp. 165–182. Available at: <https://doi.org/10.1515/admin-2017-0020>

Connaughton, B., Rice, C. and Shaw, R. (2023) ‘The Westminster tradition’, in Shaw, R. (ed.) *Handbook on ministerial and political advisers*. Cheltenham: Edward Elgar, pp. 296–311. Available at: <https://doi.org/10.4337/9781800886582.00030>

Connell, A., O’Toole, L., Greer, S.L. and Jarman, H. (2023) ‘Externalising policy advice within subnational governments’, *Policy & Politics*, 51(4), pp. 628–646. Available at: <https://doi.org/10.1332/030557321x16883943592187>

Cook, I.R. and Ward, K. (2012) ‘Conferences, informational infrastructures and mobile policies: the process of getting Sweden “BID ready”’, *European Urban and Regional Studies*, 19(2), pp. 137–152. Available at: <https://doi.org/10.1177/0969776411420029>

Coughlan, S. (2011) ‘Liam Burns elected as new students’ union president’, *BBC News*, 13 April. Available at: <https://www.bbc.com/news/education-13060765> (Accessed: 7 September 2022)

Coutts, P. and Brotchie, J. (2017) *The Scottish approach to evidence: a discussion paper*. Carnegie UK Trust. Available at: <https://carnegieuktrust.org.uk/publications/scottish-approach-evidence-discussion-paper/> (Accessed: 17 December 2020)

Crabtree, B.F. and Miller, W.L. (1999) *Doing qualitative research*. Thousand Oaks, CA: Sage.

Craft, J. and Halligan, J. (2017) *Advising Governments in the Westminster Tradition: Policy Advisory Systems in Australia, Britain, Canada and New Zealand*. Cambridge: Cambridge University Press.

Craft, J. and Halligan, J. (2020) *Advising Governments in the Westminster Tradition: Policy Advisory Systems in Australia, Britain, Canada and New Zealand*. Cambridge: Cambridge University Press. Available at: <https://doi.org/10.1017/9781108377133>

Craft, J. and Howlett, M. (2012) ‘Policy formulation, governance shifts and policy influence: location and content in policy advisory systems’, *Journal of Public Policy*, 32(2), pp. 79–98. Available at: <https://doi.org/10.1017/s0143814x12000049>

Craft, J. and Howlett, M. (2013) ‘The dual dynamics of policy advisory systems: the impact of externalization and politicization on policy advice’, *Policy and Society*, 32(3), pp. 187–197. Available at: <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.polsoc.2013.07.001>

Craft, J. and Wilder, M. (2017) ‘Catching a second wave: context and compatibility in advisory system dynamics’, *Policy Studies Journal*, 45(1), pp. 215–239. Available at: <https://doi.org/10.1111/psj.12133>

Craft, J., Head, B. and Howlett, M. (2024) ‘Expertise, policy advice, and policy advisory systems in an open, participatory, and populist era: New challenges to research and practice’, *Australian Journal of Public Administration*, 83, pp. 143–155. Available at: <https://doi.org/10.1111/1467-8500.12630>

Craggs, R. and Mahony, M. (2014) ‘The geographies of the conference: knowledge, performance and protest’, *Geography Compass*, 8(6), pp. 414–430. Available at: <https://doi.org/10.1111/gec3.12137>

Creswell, J.W. (2007) *Qualitative inquiry & research design: choosing among five approaches*. 2nd edn. Los Angeles: Sage Publications.

Creswell, J.W. (2009) *Research design: qualitative, quantitative and mixed methods approaches*. 3rd edn. Thousand Oaks, CA: Sage Publications.

- Creswell, J.W. (2014) *Research design: qualitative, quantitative and mixed methods approaches*. 4th edn. London: Sage Publications Ltd.
- Crotty, M. (1989) *The foundations of social research*. London: Sage.
- Cupchik, G. (2019) ‘Constructivist realism: an ontology that encompasses positivist and constructivist approaches to the social sciences’, *Forum Qualitative Sozialforschung / Forum: Qualitative Social Research*, 2(1). Available at: <https://doi.org/10.17169/fqs-2.1.968>
- Cyr, A. and DeLeon, P. (1975) ‘Comparative policy analysis’, *Policy Sciences*, 6(4), pp. 375–384. Available at: <http://www.jstor.org/stable/4531615> (Accessed: 8 July 2025)
- Czarniawska, B. and Mazza, C. (2003) ‘Consulting as a liminal space’, *Human Relations*, 56(3), pp. 267–290. Available at: <https://doi.org/10.1177/0018726703056003612>
- Dahlström, C., Peters, B.G. and Pierre, J. (2011) *Steering from the centre*. University of Toronto Press eBooks. Available at: <https://doi.org/10.3138/9781442687066>
- Dahmani, M.D. and Rekrak, M. (2015) ‘Revisiting the relationship between unemployment rate and economic growth in Algeria, 1970–2014: Co-integration approach using ARDL model’, *Journal of Quantitative Economics Studies* [Preprint]. Available at: <https://www.semanticscholar.org/paper/Revisiting-the-Relationship-between-Unemployment-in-Dahmani-Rekrak/7d3da225969f1856dc983bb700da35d8cb273973> (Accessed: 9 July 2022)
- DalGLISH, S.L., Khalid, H. and McMahon, S.A. (2020) ‘Document analysis in health policy research: the READ approach’, *Health Policy and Planning*, 35(10), pp. 1424–1431. Available at: <https://doi.org/10.1093/heapol/czaa064>
- Daoudi, A. (2020) ‘Algerian Civil War’, *Oxford Research Encyclopedia of African History*, 30 July. Available at: <https://oxfordre.com/africanhistory/view/10.1093/acrefore/9780190277734.001.0001/acrefore-9780190277734-e-667> (Accessed: 21 August 2025)
- Davis, M.H. (2011) ‘Algeria as postcolony? Rethinking the colonial legacy of post-structuralism’, *Journal of French and Francophone Philosophy*, 19(1), pp. 31–54. doi:10.5195/jffp.2011.510.
- Daviter, F. (2015) ‘The political use of knowledge in the policy process’, *Policy Sciences*, 48(4), pp. 491–505. Available at: <https://doi.org/10.1007/s11077-015-9232-y>
- De Bel-Air, F. (2016) ‘AHDR 2016 on Arab Youth – Chapter 7: Exclusion, mobility and migration’, in *Arab Human Development Report 2016 – Youth and the Prospects for Human Development in a Changing Reality*. UNDP. Available at: https://www.researchgate.net/publication/313403883_AHDR_2016_on_Arab_Youth-_Chapter_7_Exclusion_Mobility_and_Migration (Accessed: 14 July 2023)
- De Bruycker, I. and Beyers, J. (2018) ‘Lobbying strategies and success: Inside and outside lobbying in European Union legislative politics’, *European Political Science Review*, 11(1), pp. 57–74. Available at: <https://doi.org/10.1017/s1755773918000218>

De Mowbray, C. (2013) *CREID Briefing Paper 3 – Think Tank 2: Widening Access to Higher Education – Scotland in UK Comparative Context*. Centre on Constitutional Change. Available at: <https://www.centreonconstitutionalchange.ac.uk/publications/creid-briefing-paper-3-think-tank-2-widening-access-higher-education-scotland-uk> (Accessed: 26 November 2021)

De Wit, H., Deca, L. and Hunter, F. (2015) *Internationalization of higher education—What can research add to the policy debate?* Springer. Available at: <https://hdl.handle.net/10993/25368> (Accessed: 1 August 2024)

Deeming, C. (2014) ‘Trials and tribulations: the “use” (and “misuse”) of evidence in public policy’, in Greener, I. and Greve, B. (eds.) *Evidence and evaluation in social policy*. Oxford: Wiley Blackwell.

DeLeon, P. (1999) ‘The stages approach to the policy process: What has it done? Where is it going’, in Sabatier, P.A. (ed.) *Theories of the policy process*. Boulder, CO: Westview Press, pp. 19–32. Available at: https://www.researchgate.net/publication/313441026_The_stages_approach_to_the_policy_process_What_has_it_done_Where_is_it_going (Accessed: 20 February 2021)

Demir, F. (2020) ‘Evidence-based policy-making: merits and challenges’, in Farazmand, A. (ed.) *Global encyclopedia of public administration, public policy, and governance*. Cham: Springer. Available at: https://doi.org/10.1007/978-3-319-31816-5_3901-1 (Accessed: 10 March 2022)

Denholm, A. (2012) ‘University principals to face greater scrutiny over pay’, *The Herald*, 2 February. Available at: <https://www.heraldscotland.com/news/13046251.university-principals-face-greater-scrutiny-pay/> (Accessed: 15 October 2021)

Denholm, A. (2013) ‘Abolition of graduate endowment has failed to widen access’, *The Herald*, 11 June. Available at: <https://www.heraldscotland.com/news/13108847.abolition-graduate-endowment-failed-widen-access/> (Accessed: 26 January 2023)

Denzin, N.K. and Lincoln, Y.S. (2000) *Handbook of qualitative research*. London: Sage.

Denzin, N.K. (1989) *Interpretative interactionism*. Newbury Park, London and New Delhi: Sage.

Department for Education (DfE) (2016) *Teaching Excellence Framework: technical specification for year two*. London: Department for Education.

Diamond, P. (2020) ‘Externalization and politicization in policy advisory systems: a case study of contestable policy-making 2010–2015’, *Public Money & Management*, 40(1), pp. 42–51. Available at: <https://doi.org/10.1080/09540962.2019.1583890>

Djabi, N., Akkache, F., Zobiri, H. and Larabi, S. (2020) *Trade Unions in Algeria: History, Survey and Options*. Friedrich Ebert Stiftung. Available at: <https://library.fes.de/pdf-files/bueros/algerien/16908.pdf> (Accessed: 14 April 2022)

- Djebbar, A. (2007) 'Le système éducatif algérien: miroir d'une société en crise et en mutation', in *Codesria*. Available at: <https://codesria.org/spip.php?actionapi-docrestreint/chap8-djebbar.pdf> (Accessed: 12 March 2021)
- Dobson, A. (2000) 'The Cubie Report explained', *The Guardian*, 28 January. Available at: https://www.theguardian.com/education/2000/jan/28/tuitionfees.highereducation?CMP=share_btn_url (Accessed: 09 January 2021)
- Dobuzinskis, L., Howlett, M. and Laycock, D. (2007) 'Policy analysis in Canada: the state of the art', in Dobuzinskis, L., Howlett, M. and Laycock, D. (eds.) *Policy analysis in Canada*. Toronto: University of Toronto Press, pp. 1–18. Available at: <https://doi.org/10.3138/9781442685529-003>
- Dolowitz, D. and Marsh, D. (1996) 'Who learns what from whom: a review of the policy transfer literature', *Political Studies*, 44(2), pp. 343–357. Available at: <https://doi.org/10.1111/j.1467-9248.1996.tb00334.x>
- Dolowitz, D. (2017) 'Transfer and learning: one coin two elements', *Novos Estudos - CEBRAP*, 36(1), pp. 35–58. Available at: <https://doi.org/10.25091/s0101-3300201700010002>
- Dudley, G. and Richardson, J. (1996) 'Why does policy change over time? Adversarial policy communities, alternative policy arenas, and British trunk roads policy 1945–95', *Journal of European Public Policy*, 3(1), pp. 63–83. Available at: <https://doi.org/10.1080/13501769608407018>
- Dul, J. and Hak, T. (2008) *Case study methodology in business research*. Abingdon: Routledge.
- Dunleavy, P. (1995) 'Policy disasters: explaining the UK's record', *Public Policy and Administration*, 10(2), pp. 52–70. Available at: <https://doi.org/10.1177/095207679501000205>
- Dunlop, C. (2000) 'Epistemic communities: a reply to Toke', *Politics*, 20(3), pp. 137–144. Available at: <https://doi.org/10.1111/1467-9256.00123>
- Dunlop, C. (2000) 'Epistemic communities: a reply to Toke', *Politics*, 20(3), pp. 137–144. Available at: <https://doi.org/10.1111/1467-9256.00123>
- Dunlop, C. (2018) 'The political economy of politics and international studies impact: REF2014 case analysis', *British Politics*, 13(3), pp. 270–294. Available at: <https://doi.org/10.1057/s41293-018-0084-x>
- Dunlop, C.A. and Radaelli, C.M. (2018) 'The lessons of policy learning: types, triggers, hindrances and pathologies', *Policy & Politics*, 46(2), pp. 255–272. Available at: <https://doi.org/10.1332/030557318x15230059735521>
- Dunlop, C.A. (2012) 'Epistemic communities', in *Routledge Handbook of Public Policy*. London: Routledge. Available at: <https://ore.exeter.ac.uk/repository/handle/10036/4098> (Accessed: 21 August 2025)

- Dunn, W.N. (1981) *Public policy analysis: an introduction*. Englewood Cliffs, New Jersey: Prentice Hall.
- Dür, A. (2008) 'Measuring interest group influence in the EU', *European Union Politics*, 9(4), pp. 559–576. Available at: <https://doi.org/10.1177/1465116508095151>
- Dworkin, S.L. (2012) 'Sample size policy for qualitative studies using in-depth interviews', *Archives of Sexual Behavior*, 41(6), pp. 1319–1320. Available at: <https://doi.org/10.1007/s10508-012-0016-6>
- Dye, T.R. (1981) *Understanding public policy*. 4th edn. Englewood Cliffs, NJ: Prentice-Hall.
- Dye, T.R. (2008) *Understanding public policy*. 12th edn. Upper Saddle River, New Jersey: Prentice Hall.
- Easterby-Smith, M., Thorpe, R. and Jackson, P.R. (2012) *Management research*. 4th edn. London: Sage.
- Easton, D. (1953) *The political system: an inquiry into the state of political science*. New York: Alfred A. Knopf.
- Ebneyamini, S. and Moghadam, M.R.S. (2018) 'Toward developing a framework for conducting case study research', *International Journal of Qualitative Methods*, 17(1), p. 160940691881795. Available at: <https://doi.org/10.1177/1609406918817954>
- Echorouk Online (2008) 'Algerian president Bouteflika orders the High Education Minister to apply LMD system', *Echorouk Online*, 12 September. Available at: <https://www.echoroukonline.com/algerian-president-bouteflika-orders-the-high-education-minister-to-apply-lmd-sytem> (Accessed: 20 January 2023)
- Echorouk Online (2011) 'Independent committee to evaluate the LMD system, student representative elections, and a basic law for higher schools' (مستقلة لتقييم "أل أم دي" وانتخابات (لاختيار ممثلي الطلبة وقانون أساسي للمدارس العليا), *Echorouk Online*, 8 March. Available at: <https://www.echoroukonline.com/لجنة-مستقلة-لتقييم-أل-أم-دي-وانتخابات> (Accessed: 23 October 2022)
- Echorouk Online (2017a) – سعد الله، أبو بكر خالد، المنظمات الطلابية: ما دورها في الجامعات؟ Student organisations: what is their role in universities?', *Echorouk Online*, 5 June. Available at: <https://www.echoroukonline.com/المنظمات-الطلابية-ما-دور-ها-في-الجامعا> (Accessed: 20 January 2023)
- Echorouk Online (2017b) 'The student union "Atajdid Tolabi" calls for the implementation of reforms to the LMD system' (التجديد الطلابي يدعو إلى تطبيق إصلاحات نظام "أل أم دي"), *Echorouk Online*, 20 August. Available at: <https://www.echoroukonline.com/التجديد-الطلابي-يدعو-إلى-تطبيق-إصلاحا> (Accessed: 20 January 2023)
- Echorouk Online (2014a) 'Algeria: renewed strikes beset sectors of education, finance and higher education', *Echorouk Online*. Available at: <https://www.echoroukonline.com/algeria-renewed-strikes-beset-sectors-of-education-finance-and-higher-education> (Accessed: 22 January 2021)

Echourouk Online (2014b) 'More than 80% of LMD system students boycott university classes' (*Echorouk Online*, 1 December. Available at: <https://www.echoroukonline.com/>-أكثر من-80-بالمائة-من-طلبة-نظام-أل-أم-(Accessed: 16 August 2025)

Echourouk Online (2019) 'After the establishment of a new organization, this is a list of active unions in the higher education sector' (*Echorouk Online*. Available at: <https://www.echoroukonline.com/>-هذه قائمة النقابات الناشطة في قطاع التعليم (العلي) هذه قائمة النقابات-(Accessed: 25 June 2021)

Edge, J. and Richards, K. (1998) 'May I see your warrant, please?: Justifying outcomes in qualitative research', *Applied Linguistics*, 19(3), pp. 334–356. Available at: <https://doi.org/10.1093/applin/19.3.334>

Edinburgh Global (2023) 'The role of university autonomy in higher education'. *Edinburgh Global*. Available at: <https://global.ed.ac.uk/stories/the-role-of-university-autonomy-in-higher-educatio> (Accessed: 13 February 2024)

Edinburgh Global (2023) 'The role of university autonomy in higher education', *Edinburgh Global*. Available at: <https://global.ed.ac.uk/stories/the-role-of-university-autonomy-in-higher-educatio> (Accessed: 27 June 2024)

Educational Institute of Scotland (2011) *EIS submission to the review of higher education governance*. EIS-ULA, September 2011. Edinburgh: Scottish Government. Available at: <https://www.eis.org.uk/HEGovernance/Submission> (Accessed: 30 May 2022).

Educational Institute of Scotland (2021) *Educational Institute of Scotland*. Available at: <https://www.eis.org.uk> (Accessed: 16 August 2021).

Eichbaum, C. and Shaw, R. (2007a) 'Minding the minister? Ministerial advisers in New Zealand government', *Kōtuitui: New Zealand Journal of Social Sciences Online*, 2(2), pp. 95–113. Available at: <https://doi.org/10.1080/1177083x.2007.9522426>

Eichbaum, C. and Shaw, R. (2007b) 'Ministerial advisers and the politics of policy-making: Bureaucratic permanence and popular control', *Australian Journal of Public Administration*, 66(4), pp. 453–467. Available at: <https://doi.org/10.1111/j.1467-8500.2007.00556.x>

Eichbaum, C. and Shaw, R. (2008) 'Revisiting politicization: Political advisers and public servants in Westminster systems', *Governance*, 21(3), pp. 337–363. Available at: <https://doi.org/10.1111/j.1468-0491.2008.00403.x>

Eichbaum, C. and Shaw, R. (2010) *Partisan appointees and public servants: An international analysis of the role of the political adviser*. Cheltenham: Edward Elgar Publishing.

Eichbaum, C. and Shaw, R. (2011) 'Political staff in executive government: Conceptualising and mapping roles within the core executive', *Australian Journal of Political Science*, 46(4), pp. 583–600. Available at: <https://doi.org/10.1080/10361146.2011.623668>

- Eisenhardt, K.M. (1989) 'Building theories from case study research', *The Academy of Management Review*, 14(4), pp. 532–550. Available at: <https://doi.org/10.2307/258557>.
- El Watan (2013) 'Ben Ali Benzaghoul: "Je regrette que le rapport de la commission de réforme n'ait pas été rendu public"', *Djazairiess*. Available at: <https://www.djazairiess.com/fr/elwatan/ben-ali-benzaghoul> (Accessed: 12 March 2021).
- El Watan (2014) 'Commission Benzaghoul: La réforme qui n'a jamais abouti', *Djazairiess*, 20 July. Available at: <https://www.djazairiess.com/fr/elwatan/commission-benzaghoul> (Accessed: 25 October 2021).
- Eleazer, T. and Kingdom, O. (2021) 'Globalization and the North–South divide', *Icheke Journal of the Faculty of Humanities*, 19(1), pp. 157–170. Available at: <https://ichekejournal.com/wp-content/uploads/2022/06/13.-Globalization-and-the-North-South-Divide.pdf> (Accessed: 30 August 2025).
- Elken, M. and Vukasovic, M. (2014) *Dynamics of voluntary policy coordination: the case of Bologna Process*. Available at: <http://researchgate.net/> (Accessed: 14 November 2021).
- El-Ouahi, J. (2024) 'Research funding in the Middle East and North Africa: analyses of acknowledgments in scientific publications indexed in the Web of Science (2008–2021)', *Scientometrics*, 129, pp. 1–36. doi: 10.1007/s11192-024-04983-8.
- Emerson, R.M. (1962) 'Power-dependence relations', *American Sociological Review*, 27(1), pp. 31–41. Available at: <https://doi.org/10.2307/2089716> (Accessed: 23 June 2025).
- Enders, J. and Westerheijden, D.F. (2011) 'The Bologna Process: From the national to the regional to the global, and back', *Edward Elgar Publishing eBooks* [Preprint]. Available at: <https://doi.org/10.4337/9780857936233.00038>.
- Espey, J. (2023) 'Scientific evidence in policy processes: concepts and histories', in *Science in negotiation*. Sustainable Development Goals Series. Cham: Springer. Doi: 10.1007/978-3-031-18126-9_2.
- Esser, F. and Vliegthart, R. (2017) 'Comparative Research Methods', in Matthes, J., Davis, C.S. and Potter, R.F. (eds) *The International Encyclopedia of Communication Research Methods*. Available at: <https://doi.org/10.1002/9781118901731.iecrm0035>
- Eta, E.A. and Mngo, Z.Y. (2020) 'Policy diffusion and transfer of the Bologna Process in Africa's national, sub-regional and regional contexts', *European Educational Research Journal*, 20(1), pp. 59–82. Doi: 10.1177/1474904120951061.
- European Commission (2017) *Higher Education Reform Experts: Activity report*. Directorate-General for Education, Youth, Sport and Culture. Available at: <https://op.europa.eu/en/publication-detail/-/publication/710f8fdd-167b-11e8-9253-01aa75ed71a1> (Accessed: 17 April 2021).
- European Commission (2022) *The Bologna Process and the European Higher Education Area*. Available at: <https://education.ec.europa.eu/education-levels/higher->

education/inclusive-and-connected-higher-education/bologna-process (Accessed: 16 August 2025).

European Commission. Education, Audiovisual and Culture Executive Agency (2012) *Overview of the higher education systems in the Tempus partner countries: Southern Mediterranean*. Issue 14. Brussels: EACEA. Available at: <https://unesdoc.unesco.org/ark:/48223/pf0000219879> (Accessed: 16 August 2025)

Evans, J. (2007) 'Qualitative data analysis', *SAGE Publications Ltd eBooks*, pp. 175–185. Available at: <https://doi.org/10.4135/9781446213667.n18>.

Eversole, R. (2010) 'Remaking participation: Challenges for community development practice', *Community Development Journal*, 47(1), pp. 29–41. Available at: <https://doi.org/10.1093/cdj/bsq033>.

Exley, S. and Ball, S.J. (2014) 'Neo-liberalism and English education', in Turner, D. and Yolcu, H. (eds.) *Neo-liberal educational reforms: a critical analysis*. London: Routledge. Available at: https://www.researchgate.net/publication/288254216_Neo-liberalism_and_English_education (Accessed: 29 August 2025).

Faguet, J.-P. (2011) 'Decentralization and governance', *SSRN Electronic Journal* [Preprint]. Available at: <https://doi.org/10.2139/ssrn.1892149>.

Farshid, S., Deardorff, D.K., Heyl, J.D. and Adams, T. (2012) 'The Bologna Process and its impact in the European Higher Education Area and beyond', in Deardorff, D.K. *et al.* (eds) *The SAGE handbook of international higher education*. Thousand Oaks, CA: SAGE Publications, pp. 81–100.

Fawcett, J., Sloan, D. and Gunson, R. (2021) *Strengthening the think tank sector in Scotland*. IPPR Scotland. Available at: https://ippr-org.files.svdcdn.com/production/Downloads/1614955525_scotland-think-tanks-mar21.pdf?dm=1702046490 (Accessed: 19 November 2022).

Ferhani, F.F. (2006) Algérie, l'enseignement du français à la lumière de la réforme. *Le français aujourd'hui*, [online] (154), pp.11–18. Available at: <https://doi.org/10.3917/lfa.154.0011>

Fischer, A.R.H., Wentholt, M.T.A., Rowe, G. and Frewer, L.J. (2014) 'Expert involvement in policy development: A systematic review of current practice', *Science and Public Policy*, 41(3), pp. 332–343. Available at: <https://academic.oup.com/spp/article/41/3/332/1632782> (Accessed: 16 August 2025).

Fischer, A.R.H., Wentholt, M.T.A., Rowe, G. and Frewer, L.J. (2013) 'Expert involvement in policy development: A systematic review of current practice', *Science and Public Policy*, 41(3), pp. 332–343. Available at: <https://doi.org/10.1093/scipol/sct062>

Fischer, F., Miller, G. and Sidney, M.S. (eds.) (2007) *Handbook of public policy analysis: Theory, politics, and methods*. Boca Raton: CRC Press/Taylor & Francis.

Fisher, A. (2009) *A story of engagement: the British Council 1934–2009*. London: British Council.

Fitz, J., Halpin, D. and Power, S. (1994) 'Implementation research and education policy: Practice and prospects', *British Journal of Educational Studies*, 42(1), pp. 53–69. Available at: <https://doi.org/10.1080/00071005.1994.9973983>.

Fleischer, J. (2009) 'Power resources of parliamentary executives: Policy advice in the UK and Germany', *West European Politics*, 32(1), pp. 196–214. Available at: <https://doi.org/10.1080/01402380802509941>.

Florini, A. (2007) *The right to know*. New York: Columbia University Press. Available at: <https://doi.org/10.7312/flor14158>.

Flyvbjerg, B. (2006) 'Five misunderstandings about case-study research', *Qualitative Inquiry*, 12(2), pp. 219–245.

Fotiadou, M. (2022) 'Higher education since the 1980s', in *The language of employability*. Cham: Palgrave Macmillan. Available at: https://doi.org/10.1007/978-3-031-10252-3_2

Fox, N. (2009) *Using interviews in a research project*. The NIHR RDS for the East Midlands/Yorkshire & the Humber, 26, pp. 113–134. Available at: [Using_20Interviews_202006-libre.pdf \(d1wqtxts1xzle7.cloudfront.net\)](https://doi.org/10.1007/978-3-031-10252-3_2) (Accessed: 22 October 2021).

Fraussen, B. and Halpin, D. (2017) 'Think tanks and strategic policy-making: The contribution of think tanks to policy advisory systems', *Policy Sciences*, 50(1), pp. 105–124. <https://doi.org/10.1007/s11077-016-9246-0>

Freeman, J.L. and Stevens, J.P. (1987) 'A theoretical and conceptual reexamination of subsystem politics', *Public Policy and Administration*, 2(1), pp. 9–24. Available at: <https://doi.org/10.1177/095207678700200102>

Frowe, I. (2001) 'Language and educational research', *Journal of Philosophy of Education*, 35(2), pp. 175–186. Available at: <https://doi.org/10.1111/1467-9752.00219>

Fumasoli, T. (2015) 'multi-level governance in higher education research', in Huisman, J., de Boer, H., Dill, D.D. and Souto-Otero, M. (eds.) *The Palgrave international handbook of higher education policy and governance*. London: Palgrave Macmillan, pp. 76–94. [https://doi: 10.1007/978-1-137-45617-5_5](https://doi.org/10.1007/978-1-137-45617-5_5)

Gains, F. and Stoker, G. (2011) 'Special advisers and the transmission of ideas from the policy primeval soup', *Policy & Politics*, 39(4), pp. 485–498. Available at: <https://doi.org/10.1332/030557310x550169>

Galal, A. (2008) *The road not traveled: Education reform in the Middle East and North Africa*. MENA Development Report. Washington, DC: World Bank.

- Gallacher, J. and Raffe, D. (2012) 'Higher education policy in post-devolution UK: More convergence than divergence?', *Journal of Education Policy*, 27, pp. 467–490. Available at: <https://doi.org/10.1080/02680939.2011.626080>.
- Gallacher, J. (2006) 'Widening access or differentiation and stratification in higher education in Scotland', *Higher Education Quarterly*, 60(4), pp. 349–369. Available at: <https://doi.org/10.1111/j.1468-2273.2006.00328.x>.
- Gamage, K.A.A., Ayres, J., Behrend, M.B. and Smith, C. (2020) 'Academic standards and quality assurance: The impact of COVID-19 on university degree programs', *Sustainability*, 12(23), p. 10032. Available at: <https://doi.org/10.3390/su122310032>.
- Garrett, J. and Islam, Y. (1998) *Policy research and the policy process: Do the twain ever meet?* London: International Institute for Environment and Development. Available at: <https://www.iied.org/6138iied> (Accessed: 16 April 2021).
- George, E. St. (2006) 'Positioning higher education for the knowledge-based economy', *Higher Education*, 52(4), pp. 589–610. Available at: <https://doi.org/10.1007/s10734-005-0955-0>.
- Gephart, R.P. (1999) 'Paradigms and Research Methods', Research Methods Forum, Vol. 4 (Summer), Research Methods Division, Academy of Management. Available at: Paradigms and Research Methods: Academy of Management, Research Division. Research Methods Forum, Vol.4 (Summer 1999) | PDF | Positivism | Social Constructionism (Accessed: 12 June 2021).
- Gerring, J. (2004) 'What is a case study and what is it good for?', *American Political Science Review*, 98(2), pp. 341–354. Available at <http://www.jstor.org/stable/4145316>. Accessed 12 Sept. 2025 (Accessed: 25 April 2022).
- Ghanem, D. (2022) *Understanding the persistence of competitive authoritarianism in Algeria*. Cham: Palgrave Macmillan.
- Ghiat, B. (2023) 'Constraints of applying Bologna Process reforms in Algerian universities', *Dirassat Insaniya wa Ijtimaiya*, University of Oran, 2(3) (January). Available at <https://search.shamaa.org/fullrecord?ID=263480> (Accessed 19 January 2024)
- Ghouati, A. (2014) 'Systems of higher education and research in the Maghreb region', in Joshi, K. and Paivandi, S. (eds.) *Higher education across nations*. New Delhi: B.R. Publishing Corporation. Available at: Systems of Higher Education and Research in the Maghreb region (hal.science) (Accessed 20 March 2022).
- Ghouati, A. (2015) 'Une décennie du processus de Bologne au Maghreb', *Esprit critique: Revue internationale de sociologie et de sciences sociales*, 23(1). Conservatoire National des Arts et Métiers (CNAM), Pays-de-la-Loire. Available at: [Une décennie du processus de Bologne au Maghreb \(hal.science\)](#) (Accessed 12 February 2023)
- Glaser, M. and te Brömmelstroet, M. (2020) 'Unpacking policy transfer as a situated practice: Blending social, spatial, and sensory learning at a conference', *Applied Mobilities*, 7(2), pp. 163–185. Available at: <https://doi.org/10.1080/23800127.2020.1827559>.

Gonzalez Vicente, R. (2019) 'Where is the South? Global, postcolonial and intersectional perspectives', in Mawdsley, E., Fourie, E. and Nauta, W. (eds.) *Researching South-South Development Cooperation: The Politics of Knowledge Production*. Abingdon: Routledge, pp. 27–31.

Goodrick, D. (2014) *Comparative case studies. Methodological Briefs: Impact Evaluation 9*. Florence: UNICEF Office of Research.

Government of Algeria. (1999a) *Law No. 99-05 of 18 Dhou El Hidja 1419 corresponding to 4 April 1999, establishing the framework law on higher education, amended and supplemented*. Available at: <https://planipolis.iiep.unesco.org/en/1999/loi-no-99-05-du-18-dhou-el-hidja-1419-correspondant-au-4-avril-1999-portant-loi-dorientation> (Accessed: 22 August 2025)

Government of Algeria. (1999b) *Law No. 99-05 of 4 April 1999 on the orientation of higher education, amended by Law No. 2000-04 of 6 December 2000*. Article 43 establishes the National Conference of Universities and regional bodies for consultation, coordination, and evaluation. Algiers: Official Journal of the Algerian Republic. Available at: <https://www.mesrs.dz/index.php/fr/textes-juridiques/recueil-textes-juridiques/> (Accessed: 22 August 2025)

Government of Algeria. (2008) *Law No. 08-05 of 23 February 2008 amending and supplementing Law No. 98-11 of 22 August 1998 on the orientation and five-year programming of scientific research and technological development (1998–2002)*. Algiers: Official Journal of the Algerian Republic (J.O.R.A.D.P No. 10). Available at: <https://www.mesrs.dz/index.php/fr/textes-juridiques/recueil-textes-juridiques/> (Accessed: 22 August 2025)

Government of Algeria. (2019) *The higher education system in Algeria: national report, September*. Available at: https://www.meric-net.eu/files/fileusers/National_Report_template_MERIC-NET_Algeria_English.pdf (Accessed: 12 March 2021)

Grant, C. and Osanloo, A. (2014) 'Understanding, selecting, and integrating a theoretical framework in dissertation research: Creating the blueprint for your "house"', *Administrative Issues Journal: Education, Practice, and Research*, 4(2), pp. 12–26. Available at: <https://doi.org/10.5929/2014.4.2.9>.

Greene, J.C., Benjamin, L. and Goodyear, L. (2001) 'The merits of mixing methods in evaluation', *Evaluation*, 7(1), pp. 25–44. Available at: <https://doi.org/10.1177/13563890122209504>.

Grek, S. and Ozga, J. (2010) 'Re-inventing public education: The new role of knowledge in education policy making', *Public Policy and Administration*, 25(3), pp. 271–288. Available at: <https://doi.org/10.1177/0952076709356870>.

Grek, S. (2009) 'Governing by numbers: The PISA "Effect" in Europe', *Journal of Education Policy*, 24(1), pp. 23–37. Available at: <https://doi.org/10.1080/02680930802412669>

- Grimm, H.M. (2019) 'Introduction: The added value of public policy research in the Global South', in Grimm, H.M. (ed.) *Public Policy Research in the Global South: A Cross-Country Perspective*. Cham: Springer, pp. 1–19. doi: 10.1007/978-3-030-06061-9_1.
- Grindle, M.S. (ed.) (1980) *Politics and policy implementation in the Third World*. Princeton, NJ: Princeton University Press. Available at: <http://www.jstor.org/stable/j.ctt1m323qj>.
- Grix, J. (2004) *The foundations of research*. London: Palgrave Macmillan.
- Grove, J. (2012) 'Universities failing to consult students on access – NUS', *Times Higher Education*. Available at: <https://www.timeshighereducation.com/news/universities-failing-to-consult-students-on-access-nus/419233.article> (Accessed: 31 July 2023).
- Guba, E.G. and Lincoln, Y.S. (1989) 'What is this constructivist paradigm anyway?', in *Fourth generation evaluation*. London: Sage Publications, pp. 79–90.
- Guba, E.G. and Lincoln, Y.S. (1994) 'Competing paradigms in qualitative research', in Denzin, N.K. and Lincoln, Y.S. (eds.) *Handbook of qualitative research*. 3rd edn. Thousand Oaks, CA: Sage, pp. 105–117.
- Guba, E.G. (ed.) (1990) *The paradigm dialogue*. Newbury Park, CA: Sage.
- Guessoum, A. (2019) 'Introducing quality assurance in Algerian higher education: The case of the University of Science and Technology Houari Boumediene', in Badran, A., Baydoun, E. and Hillman, J.R. (eds.) *Major challenges facing higher education in the Arab world: Quality assurance and relevance*. Cham: Springer, pp. 295–310. Available at: https://doi.org/10.1007/978-3-030-03774-1_17.
- Gunn, A.J. (2017) 'Policy entrepreneurs and policy formulation', in Howlett, M. and Mukherjee, I. (eds.) *Handbook of policy formulation*. Cheltenham: Edward Elgar, pp. 265–282. Available at: <https://doi.org/10.4337/9781784719326.00024>.
- Gupta, K. (2012) 'Comparative public policy: Using the comparative method to advance our understanding of the policy process', *Policy Studies Journal*, 40, pp. 11–26. Available at: <https://doi.org/10.1111/j.1541-0072.2012.00443.x>.
- Haas, P.M. (1992) 'Introduction: Epistemic communities and international policy coordination', *International Organization*, 46(1), pp. 1–35. Available at: <https://doi.org/10.1017/S0020818300001442>.
- Hahn, A. (1987) 'Policy making models and their role in policy education', *Research Papers in Economics*. Available at: <https://core.ac.uk/download/pdf/7044344.pdf> (Accessed 12 June 2025).
- Halfman, W. and Hoppe, R. (2005) 'Science/policy boundaries: A changing division of labour in Dutch expert policy advice', in Maasen, S. and Weingart, P. (eds.) *Democratization of expertise? Exploring novel forms of scientific advice in political decision-making*. Dordrecht: Springer, pp. 135–151. Available at: https://doi.org/10.1007/1-4020-3754-6_8.

- Halligan, J. (1995) 'Policy advice and the public sector', in Peters, B.G. and Savoie, D.J. (eds.) *Governance in a changing environment*. Montreal: McGill-Queen's University Press, pp. 138–172.
- Halligan, J. (1998) 'Policy advice', in Shafritz, J.M. (ed.) *International encyclopedia of public policy and administration*. Vol. 3. Boulder, CO: Westview Press, pp. 686–688.
- Hammarberg, K., Kirkman, M. and De Lacey, S. (2016) 'Qualitative research methods: When to use them and how to judge them', *Human Reproduction*, 31(3), pp. 498–501. Available at: <https://doi.org/10.1093/humrep/dev334>.
- Hanegraaff, M., Beyers, J. and De Bruycker, I. (2016) 'Balancing inside and outside lobbying: The political strategies of lobbyists at global diplomatic conferences', *European Journal of Political Research*, 55(3), pp. 568–588. Available at: <https://doi.org/10.1111/1475-6765.12145>.
- Hantrais, L. (2009) *International comparative research: Theory, methods and practice*. Basingstoke: Palgrave Macmillan.
- Haouas, A., Ochi, A. and Labidi, M.A. (2021) 'Sources of Algeria's economic growth, 1979–2019: Augmented growth accounting framework and growth regression method', *Regional Science Policy & Practice* [Preprint]. Available at: <https://doi.org/10.1111/rsp3.12448>.
- Harrison, K. and Boyd, T. (2018) 'The role of ideology in politics and society', in *Understanding political ideas and movements*. Manchester: Manchester University Press. doi: 10.7765/9781526137951.00011.
- Harrison, T.M. and Sayogo, D.S. (2014) 'Transparency, participation, and accountability practices in open government: A comparative study', *Government Information Quarterly*, 31, pp. 513–525.
- Harvey, W. (2011) 'Strategies for conducting elite interviews', *Qualitative Research*, 11(4), pp. 431–441. <https://doi.org/10.1177/1468794111404329> (Original work published 2011)
- Hayes, M. (2017) 'Incrementalism and public policy-making', *Oxford Research Encyclopedia of Politics* [Preprint]. Available at: <https://doi.org/10.1093/acrefore/9780190228637.013.133>.
- Head, B.W. and Crowley, K. (2015) *Policy analysis in Australia*. Bristol: Policy Press.
- Head, B.W. (2008) 'Three lenses of evidence-based policy', *Australian Journal of Public Administration*, 67(1), pp. 1–11. Available at: <https://doi.org/10.1111/j.1467-8500.2007.00564.x>.
- Head, B.W. (2010a) 'Evidence-based policy: principles and requirements', in Productivity Commission (ed.) *Strengthening evidence-based policy in the Australian federation, Volume 1: Proceedings*. Canberra: Productivity Commission, pp. 13–26. Available at: <https://www.researchgate.net/publication/242709855> (Accessed: 13 July 2025).

Head, B.W. (2010b) 'Reconsidering evidence-based policy: key issues and challenges', *Policy and Society*, 29(2), pp. 77–94. Available at: <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.polsoc.2010.03.001>.

Head, B.W. (2013) 'Evidence-based policymaking – speaking truth to power?', *Australian Journal of Public Administration*, 72(4), pp. 397–403. Available at: <https://doi.org/10.1111/1467-8500.12037>.

Heclo, H. (1978) 'Issue networks and the executive establishment', in King, A. (ed.) *The new American political system*. Washington, DC: American Enterprise Institute for Public Policy Research, pp. 87–124.

Helms, L. (2008) 'Studying parliamentary opposition in old and new democracies: Issues and perspectives', *The Journal of Legislative Studies*, 14(1–2), pp. 6–19. Available at: <https://doi.org/10.1080/13572330801920788>.

Hernando, M.G., Pautz, H. and Stone, D. (2018) 'Think tanks in “hard times” – the Global Financial Crisis and economic advice', *Policy and Society*, 37(2), pp. 125–139. Available at: <https://doi.org/10.1080/14494035.2018.1487181>.

Heron, J. and Reason, P. (1997) 'A participatory inquiry paradigm', *Qualitative Inquiry*, 3(3), pp. 274–294. Available at: <https://doi.org/10.1177/107780049700300302>.

Hesstvedt, S. and Christensen, J. (2021) 'Political and administrative control of expert groups—A mixed-methods study', *Governance* [Preprint]. Available at: <https://doi.org/10.1111/gove.12599>.

Hewlett Foundation (2018) *Evidence-Informed Policymaking Strategy*. Available at: <https://www.hewlett.org/wp-content/uploads/2018/04/EIP-Strategy-March-2018.pdf> (Accessed: 31 July 2022).

Hickey, R. (2022) *Tuition fees and the market in UK higher education*. Oxford: Oxford University Press.

Highman, L., Marginson, S. and Papatsiba, V. (2023) *Student mobility and Brexit: Comparative perspectives*. London: UCL Press.

Higley, J. (2010) 'Elite theory and elites', in Leicht, K.T. and Jenkins, J.C. (eds.) *Handbooks of sociology and social research*. New York: Springer, pp. 161–176. Available at: https://doi.org/10.1007/978-0-387-68930-2_9.

Hill, M. (1997) *The policy process in the modern state*. 3rd edn. Hemel Hempstead: Prentice Hall/Harvester Wheatsheaf.

Hillman, N. (2013) *From grants to loans and tuition fees: A brief history of student finance in the UK*. London: Higher Education Policy Institute (HEPI).

Hoefer, R. (2022) 'Institutionalism as a theory for understanding policy creation: An underused resource', *Journal of Policy Practice and Research*, 3(2), pp. 71–76. Available at: <https://doi.org/10.1007/s42972-022-00059-0>.

- Hojnacki, M. (1997) 'Interest groups' decisions to join alliances or work alone', *American Journal of Political Science*, 41(1), pp. 61–87. Available at: <https://doi.org/10.2307/2111709>.
- Holden, H. (2010) *The Commission on Scottish Devolution – the Calman Commission*. Available at: <https://researchbriefings.files.parliament.uk/documents/SN04744/SN04744.pdf> (Accessed: 10 September 2022).
- Holyoke, T.T. (2020) 'Pluralism (the interest group theory of politics)', *Springer eBooks*, pp. 1–6. Available at: https://doi.org/10.1007/978-3-030-13895-0_95-1.
- Hooghe, L. and Marks, G. (2001) *Multi-level governance and European integration*. Lanham, MD: Rowman & Littlefield.
- Hooghe, L. and Marks, G. (2003) 'Unraveling the central state, but how? Types of multilevel governance', *American Political Science Review*, 97(2), pp. 233–243. Available at: <https://doi.org/10.1017/S0003055403000649>.
- Howlett, M. and Lindquist, E. (2004) 'Policy analysis and governance: Analytical and policy styles in Canada', *Journal of Comparative Policy Analysis: Research and Practice*, 6(3), pp. 225–249. Available at: <https://doi.org/10.1080/1387698042000305194>.
- Howlett, M. and Migone, A. (2013) 'Policy advice through the market: The role of external consultants in contemporary policy advisory systems', *Policy and Society*, 32(3), pp. 241–254. Available at: <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.polsoc.2013.07.005>.
- Howlett, M. and Ramesh, M. (1995) *Policy cycles and policy subsystems*. Canada: Oxford University Press.
- Howlett, M. and Wellstead, A.M. (2011) 'Policy analysts in the bureaucracy revisited: The nature of professional policy work in contemporary government', *Politics & Policy*, 39(4), pp. 613–633. Available at: <https://doi.org/10.1111/j.1747-1346.2011.00306.x>.
- Howlett, M. (2009) 'Policy advice in multi-level governance systems: Sub-national policy analysts and analysis', *International Review of Public Administration*, 13(3), pp. 1–16. Available at: <https://doi.org/10.1080/12294659.2009.10805127>.
- Howlett, M. (2011) 'Public managers as the missing variable in policy studies: An empirical investigation using Canadian data', *Review of Policy Research*, 28(3), pp. 247–263. Available at: <https://doi.org/10.1111/j.1541-1338.2011.00494.x>.
- Howlett, M. (2015) 'Policy analytical capacity: The supply and demand for policy analysis in government', *Policy and Society*, 34(3–4), pp. 173–182. Available at: <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.polsoc.2015.09.002>.
- Howlett, M. (2019) 'Comparing policy advisory systems beyond the OECD: Models, dynamics and the second-generation research agenda', *Policy Studies*, 40(3–4), pp. 241–259. Available at: <https://doi.org/10.1080/01442872.2018.1557626>.
- Howlett, M., Migone, A. and Tan, S.L. (2014) 'Duplicative or complementary? The relationship between policy consulting and internal policy analysis in Canadian

government’, *Canadian Journal of Political Science*, 47(1), pp. 113–134. Available at: <https://doi.org/10.1017/S0008423914000213>.

Howlett, M., Mukherjee, I. and Koppenjan, J. (2017) ‘Policy learning and policy networks in theory and practice: The role of policy brokers in the Indonesian biodiesel policy network’, *Policy and Society*, 36(2), pp. 233–250. Available at: <https://doi.org/10.1080/14494035.2017.1321230>.

Hubble, S. (2010) *The Browne Review of higher education funding and student finance*. London: House of Commons Library.

Hubble, S. (2017) *The Teaching Excellence Framework: Policy background and developments*. London: House of Commons Library.

Hufen, J.A.M. and Koppenjan, J.F.M. (2014) ‘How evidence becomes authoritative in public policy implementation: Lessons from three Dutch white ravens’, *Policy Studies*, 35(3), pp. 264–281. Available at: <https://doi.org/10.1080/01442872.2013.875148>.

Huisman, J., Adelman, C., Hsieh, C.-C., Shams, F. and Wilkins, S. (2012) ‘Europe’s Bologna Process and its impact on global higher education’, in Deardorff, D.K., de Wit, H., Heyl, J.D. and Adams, T. (eds.) *The SAGE handbook of international higher education*. Thousand Oaks, CA: SAGE, pp. 81–100. Available at: <https://doi.org/10.4135/9781452218397.n5>.

Humes, W. and Bryce, T. (2018) ‘The distinctiveness of Scottish education’, in Bryce, T., Humes, W., Gillies, D. and Kennedy, A. (eds.) *Scottish education*. Edinburgh: Edinburgh University Press, pp. 118–128. Available at: <https://doi.org/10.1515/9781474437851-012>.

Hunter, A. and Boswell, C. (2015) ‘Comparing the political functions of independent commissions: The case of UK migrant integration policy’, *Journal of Comparative Policy Analysis: Research and Practice*, 17(1), pp. 10–25. Available at: <https://doi.org/10.1080/13876988.2014.896117>.

Hurwitz, L. (1973) ‘Contemporary approaches to political stability’, *Comparative Politics*, 5(3), pp. 449–463. Available at: <https://doi.org/10.2307/421273>.

Hussain, F., Tsang, D. and Rafique, Z. (2023) ‘Policy advisory systems and public policy making: Bibliometric analysis, knowledge mapping, operationalization, and future research agenda’, *Review of Policy Research*. Available at: <https://doi.org/10.1111/ropr.12564>.

Hustedt, T. and Veit, S. (2017) ‘Policy advisory systems: Change dynamics and sources of variation’, *Policy Sciences*, 50(1), pp. 1–21. Available at: <https://doi.org/10.1007/s11077-016-9272-y>.

Hustedt, T. (2018) ‘Policy design and policy advisory systems’, in Howlett, M. and Mukherjee, I. (eds.) *Routledge handbook of policy design*. Abingdon: Routledge, pp. 201–211. Available at: <https://doi.org/10.4324/9781351252928-13>.

- Hustedt, T. (2019) ‘Studying policy advisory systems: Beyond the Westminster-bias?’, *Policy Studies*, 40(3–4), pp. 260–269. Available at: <https://doi.org/10.1080/01442872.2018.1557627>.
- Hyett, N., Kenny, A. and Dickson-Swift, V. (2014) ‘Methodology or method? A critical review of qualitative case study reports’, *International Journal of Qualitative Studies on Health and Well-being*, 9(1), pp. 1–12. Available at: <https://doi.org/10.3402/qhw.v9.23606>.
- Iannelli, C. (2011) ‘Educational expansion and social mobility: The Scottish case’, *Social Policy and Society*, 10(2), pp. 251–264. Available at: <https://doi.org/10.1017/S147474641000059X>.
- Iannelli, C., Smyth, E. and Klein, M. (2016) ‘Curriculum differentiation and social inequality in higher education entry in Scotland and Ireland’, *British Educational Research Journal*, 42(4), pp. 561–581. Available at: <https://doi.org/10.1002/berj.3217>
- Idoughi, D. and Abdelhakim, D. (2013) ‘Towards an Algerian e-government strategy and achievements’, *DOAJ: Directory of Open Access Journals* [Preprint]. Available at: (PDF) TOWARDS AN ALGERIAN E-GOVERNMENT STRATEGY AND ACHIEVEMENTS (researchgate.net) (Accessed: 12 May 2021).
- Idri, N. (2005) ‘The LMD system experience as a struggle between the educational development and reform: An analytical study of the endeavour of the academic year 2004/2005 in Bejaia University with suggested solutions’, *Rencontres Internationales sur le Dispositif LMD – Problèmes et Perspectives*. Available at: <https://www.researchgate.net/publication/285594547> (Accessed: 6 June 2023).
- Independent panel report to the Review of Post-18 Education and Funding (2019) *Post-18 education review: Independent panel report*. London: DfE.
- International Budget Partnership (2012) *Open Budget Survey 2012: Algeria Country Summary*. Available at: <https://internationalbudget.org/wp-content/uploads/OBI2012-AlgeriaCS-English.pdf> (Accessed: 18 August 2025)
- Irani, E. (2019) ‘The use of videoconferencing for qualitative interviewing: Opportunities, challenges, and considerations’, *Clinical Nursing Research*, 28(1), pp. 3–8. Available at: <https://doi.org/10.1177/1054773818803170>.
- Jackson, R.L., Drummond, D.K. and Camara, S. (2007) ‘What is qualitative research?’, *Qualitative Research Reports in Communication*, 8(1), pp. 21–28. Available at: <https://doi.org/10.1080/17459430701617879>.
- James, N. and Busher, H. (2007) ‘Ethical issues in online educational research: Protecting privacy, establishing authenticity in email interviewing’, *International Journal of Research & Method in Education*, 30(1), pp. 101–113. Available at: <https://doi.org/10.1080/17437270701207868>.

James, T.E. and Jorgensen, P.D. (2009) 'Policy knowledge, policy formulation, and change: Revisiting a foundational question', *Policy Studies Journal*, 37(1), pp. 141–162. Available at: <https://doi.org/10.1111/j.1541-0072.2008.00300.x>.

Jones, C. (1970) *An Introduction to the Study of Public Policy*. Belmont, California: Wadsworth Publishing Company.

Jones, C. (1977) *An Introduction to the Study of Public Policy*. 2nd edn. North Scituate, Massachusetts: Duxbury Press.

Jordan, A.G. and Richardson, J.J. (1983) 'Policy communities: The British and European policy style', *Policy Studies Journal*, 11(4), pp. 603–615. Available at: <https://doi.org/10.1111/j.1541-0072.1983.tb00564.x>.

Jordan, A.G. and Richardson, J.J. (1983) 'Policy communities: The British and European policy style', *Policy Studies Journal*, 11(4), pp. 603–615. Available at: <https://doi.org/10.1111/j.1541-0072.1983.tb00564.x>

Jordan, G. and Richardson, J.J. (1982) 'The British policy style or the logic of negotiation?', in Richardson, J.J. (ed.) *Policy styles in Western Europe*. London: Allen & Unwin, pp. 80–110.

Jungblut, J. (2014) 'Partisan politics in higher education policy', in Goastellec, G. and Picard, F. (eds.) *Higher education in societies. Higher Education Research in the 21st Century Series*. Rotterdam: Sense Publishers, pp. 87–111. Available at: https://doi.org/10.1007/978-94-6209-746-9_7.

Kahanec, M. and Kralikova, R. (2011) 'Pulls of international student mobility', *IZA Discussion Paper*, No. 6233. Available at: Pulls of international student mobility (iza.org) (Accessed: 24 May 2023).

Katz, D. and Kahn, R.L. (1966) *The social psychology of organizations*. New York, NY: John Wiley & Sons, Inc.

Kawulich, B.B. and Chilisa, B. (2012) 'Selecting a research approach: Paradigm, methodology and methods', in Wagner, C., Kawulich, B. and Garner, M. (eds.) *Doing Social Research: A Global Context*. London: McGraw-Hill, pp. 51–61. Available at: https://www.researchgate.net/publication/257944787_Selecting_a_research_approach_Paradigm_methodology_and_methods (Accessed: 17 August 2025).

Keating, M. and Cairney, P. (2012) 'Introduction: Policy-making, learning and devolution', *Regional & Federal Studies*, 22(3), pp. 239–250. Available at: <https://doi.org/10.1080/13597566.2012.688269>.

Keating, M. (2005) 'Higher education in Scotland and England after devolution', *Regional & Federal Studies*, 15(4), pp. 423–435. Available at: <https://doi.org/10.1080/13597560500230524>.

- Keating, M. (2010) *The Government of Scotland: Public policy making after devolution*. Edinburgh: Edinburgh University Press. Available at: <https://www.jstor.org/stable/10.3366/j.ctt1g0b6p9> (Accessed: 5 June 2022).
- Keating, M., Cairney, P. and Hepburn, E. (2012) 'Policy convergence, transfer and learning in the UK under devolution', *Regional & Federal Studies*, 22(3), pp. 289–307. Available at: <https://doi.org/10.1080/13597566.2012.688272>.
- Keating, M., Stone, D. and Maxwell, S. (2001) *Bridging Research and Policy: An international workshop*. London: UK Department for International Development. Available at: <https://warwick.ac.uk/fac/soc/pais/research/csg/research/keytopic/other/bridging.pdf> (Accessed: 04 June 2023).
- Keeling, R. (2006) 'The Bologna Process and the Lisbon Research Agenda: the European Commission's expanding role in higher education discourse', *European Journal of Education*, 41(2), pp. 203–223. Available at: <https://doi.org/10.1111/j.1465-3435.2006.00256.x>.
- Keenan, J. (2003) 'Ethnicity, regionalism and political stability in Algeria's Grand Sud', *The Journal of North African Studies*, 8(3–4), pp. 67–96. Available at: <https://doi.org/10.1080/13629380308718517> (Accessed: 16 August 2025)
- Kelo, M. and Wächter, B. (2004) *Brain drain and brain gain: Migration in the European Union after enlargement*. Bonn: ACA Papers on International Cooperation in Education. Available at: [Migration.pdf \(aca-secretariat.be\)](https://www.aca-secretariat.be/Migration.pdf) (Accessed: 24 April 2025).
- Kelstrup, J.D. (2017) 'Quantitative differences in think tank dissemination activities in Germany, Denmark and the UK', *Policy Sciences*, 50(1), pp. 125–137. Available at: <https://doi.org/10.1007/s11077-016-9254-0>.
- Kickert, W.J.M., Klijn, E.-H. and Koppenjan, J.F.M. (1997) *Managing complex networks: Strategies for the public sector*. London: SAGE Publications.
- Kilavuz, M.T., Grewal, S. and Kubinec, R. (2023) 'Ghosts of the Black Decade: How legacies of violence shaped Algeria's Hirak protests', *Journal of Peace Research*, 60(1), pp. 9–25. Available at: <https://doi.org/10.1177/00223433221137613>.
- Kilemi, M. (2022) 'Governance in higher education'. *World Conference on Higher Education*, 3rd. Available at: <https://unesdoc.unesco.org/ark:/48223/pf0000389884> (Accessed: 14 May 2025).
- Kingdon, J. (1984) *Agendas, Alternatives and Public Policies*. Boston, MA: Little, Brown and Company.
- Kingdon, J. (2010) *Agendas, Alternatives and Public Policy*. 2nd edn. New York: Pearson.
- Kivunja, C. and Kuyini, A.B. (2017) 'Understanding and applying research paradigms in educational contexts', *International Journal of Higher Education*, 6(5), pp. 26–41. Available at: <https://doi.org/10.5430/ijhe.v6n5p26>.

Klemenčič, M. (2012) 'Student representation in Western Europe: Introduction to the special issue', *European Journal of Higher Education*, 2(1), pp. 2–19. Available at: <https://doi.org/10.1080/21568235.2012.695058>

Klemenčič, M. (2014) 'Student power in a global perspective and contemporary trends in student organising', *Studies in Higher Education*, 39(3), pp. 396–411. Available at: <https://doi.org/10.1080/03075079.2014.896177>

Kloß, S.T. (2017) 'The Global South as Subversive Practice: Challenges and Potentials of a Heuristic Concept', *The Global South*, 11(2), pp. 1-17. <https://doi.org/10.2979/globalsouth.11.2.01>.

Knoke, D. (1990) *Political Networks. The Structural Perspective*. Cambridge: Cambridge University Press.

Knoke, D. (1994) *Political networks: The structural perspective*. Cambridge: Cambridge University Press.

Knox, H. and Wyper, J. (2008) *Quality enhancement themes: The first year experience – Personalisation of the first year*. Gloucester: The Quality Assurance Agency for Higher Education. Available at: <https://dera.ioe.ac.uk/id/eprint/11594/1/personalisation-of-the-first-year-2.pdf> (Accessed: 4 August 2022).

König, T., Lin, N. and Silva, T.N. (2022) 'Government dominance and the role of opposition in parliamentary democracies', *European Journal of Political Research* [Preprint]. Available at: <https://doi.org/10.1111/1475-6765.12525>.

Kørnøv, L. and Thissen, W.A.H. (2000) 'Rationality in decision- and policy-making: implications for strategic environmental assessment', *Impact Assessment and Project Appraisal*, 18(3), pp. 191–200. Available at: <https://doi.org/10.3152/147154600781767402>.

Kouraiche, N. (2019) 'Assurance qualité dans l'enseignement supérieur en Algérie : tendances et pratiques', *Dirassat Économique*, 10(2), pp. 331-346. University Amar Telidji - Laghouat. DOI: 10.34118/djei.v10i2.216. Available at: <https://www.asjp.cerist.dz/en/article/94891> (Accessed: 12 September 2025).

Kowalski, A.M. (2020) Global South–Global North differences. In: W. Leal Filho, ed. *Encyclopedia of the UN Sustainable Development Goals: No Poverty*. Cham: Springer Nature Switzerland. Available at: https://www.researchgate.net/publication/342507407_Global_South-Global_North_Differences (Accessed 12 June 2025).

Kraft, M.E. and Furlong, S.R. (2004) *Public policy: politics, analysis, and alternatives*. Washington D.C.: CQ Press.

La Commission nationale de réforme du système éducatif (CNRSE) (2000) *Le rapport de la commission Benzaghoul*. Algiers: The Algerian Government.

Lahmar, F. (2024) 'Educational reform in Algeria: Dilemmas of globalization, equity, and decolonization', in Akgün, B. and Alpaydın, Y. (eds.) *Global Agendas and Education*

Reforms. Singapore: Palgrave Macmillan. Available at: https://doi.org/10.1007/978-981-97-3068-1_1.

Lahmer, M. (2021) 'An overview of 12 years of internationalization in the Algerian higher education', *Revue des Sciences Humaines de l'Université Oum El Bouaghi*, 8(2), pp. 1400–1407. Available at: <https://asjp.cerist.dz/en/article/161821> (Accessed: 13 May 2022).

Lai, C. and Lin, S.H. (2017) 'Systems theory', *The International Encyclopedia of Organizational Communication*, pp. 1–18. Available at: <https://doi.org/10.1002/9781118955567.wbieoc203>.

Lamont, T. (2021) 'WHO you want to reach – policymakers and managers', *Policy Press eBooks*, pp. 84–103. Available at: <https://doi.org/10.51952/9781447361176.ch006>.

Lasswell, H.D. (1956) *The decision process: seven categories of functional analysis*. College Park, MD: University of Maryland Press.

Lather, P. (1992) 'Critical frames in educational research: feminist and post-structural perspectives', *Theory into Practice*, 31(2), pp. 87–99. Available at: <http://www.jstor.org/stable/1476394> (Accessed: 13 May 2023).

Lavis, J.N., Robertson, D., Woodside, J.M., McLeod, C.B. and Abelson, J. (2003) 'How can research organisations more effectively transfer research knowledge to decision makers?', *The Milbank Quarterly*, 81(2), pp. 221–248. Available at: <https://doi.org/10.1111/1468-0009.t01-1-00052>

Le Roux, C.S. (2017) 'Language in education in Algeria: a historical vignette of a “most severe” sociolinguistic problem', *Language & History*, 60(2), pp. 112–128. Available at: <https://doi.org/10.1080/17597536.2017.1319103>.

Leifeld, P. and Schneider, V. (2012) 'Information exchange in policy networks', *American Journal of Political Science*, 56(3), pp. 731–744. Available at: <https://doi.org/10.1111/j.1540-5907.2011.00580.x>.

Levers, M.-J.D. (2013) 'Philosophical paradigms, grounded theory, and perspectives on emergence', *SAGE Open*, 3(4), pp. 1–6. Available at: <https://doi.org/10.1177/2158244013517243>.

Lewis, J. and Bolton, P. (2022) *Review of post-18 education and funding: Background*. London: House of Commons Library. Available at: <https://researchbriefings.files.parliament.uk/documents/CBP-9348/CBP-9348.pdf>. (Accessed: 18 March 2023).

Lewis, J., Bolton, P. and Wilson, L. (2023) *Post-18 education and funding: Policy update*. London: House of Commons Library. Available at: <https://researchbriefings.files.parliament.uk/documents/CBP-9839/CBP-9839.pdf> (Accessed: 13 July 2025).

Liftin, K. (1994) *Ozone discourse: science and politics in global environmental cooperation*. New York: Columbia University Press.

- Lincoln, Y. and Guba, E.G. (1985) *Naturalistic inquiry*. Newbury Park, CA: Sage.
- Lindblom, C.E. (1979) 'Still muddling, not yet through', *Public Administration Review*, 39(6), p. 517. Available at: <https://doi.org/10.2307/976178>.
- Lindvall, J. (2009) 'The real but limited influence of expert ideas', *World Politics*, 61(4), pp. 703–730. Available at: <http://www.jstor.org/stable/40263537>. (Accessed 22 Oct. 2021).
- Lipsett, A. (2008) 'NUS report reveals Scottish student hardship', *The Guardian*, 23 April. Available at: <https://www.theguardian.com/education/2008/apr/23/students.studentfinance> (Accessed: 12 May 2021).
- Liu, X. (2018) 'Interviewing elites', *International Journal of Qualitative Methods*, 17(1), p. 160940691877032. Available at: <https://doi.org/10.1177/1609406918770323>.
- Lumb, M. (2023) 'Discourses on Global North and Global South partnerships in internationalization strategies', *Comparative and International Education*, 51(2), pp.110–126. Available at: https://www.researchgate.net/publication/369526352_Discourses_on_Global_North_and_Global_South_Partnerships_in_Internationalization_Strategies (Accessed 12 June 2025).
- Mackenzie, J. (2015) *Establishing government think tanks: an overview of comparative models*. Working Paper 4. Jakarta: Knowledge Sector Initiative. Available at: <https://doi.org/10.13140/RG.2.1.1025.4889>.
- MacLeod, M. (2010) 'Edinburgh students' snowball protest over tuition fees', *The Guardian*, 30 November. Available at: <https://www.theguardian.com/edinburgh/2010/nov/30/edinburgh-students-snowball-protest-tuition-fees> (Accessed: 2 August 2022)
- Macrae, D. and Wilde, J. (1985) *Policy analysis for public decisions*. California: University Press of America.
- Mahendran, K. and Cook, D. (2007) *Participation and Engagement in Politics and Policy Making: Building a Bridge Between Europe and its Citizens – Evidence Review Paper One*. [Evidence Review Paper]. Public Dialogue Psychology Collaboratory – PDPC. Available at: https://www.researchgate.net/publication/369526352_Discourses_on_Global_North_and_Global_South_Partnerships_in_Internationalization_Strategies (Accessed: 21 November 2022).
- Maley, M. (2000) 'Conceptualising advisers' policy work: the distinctive policy roles of ministerial advisers in the Keating Government, 1991–96', *Australian Journal of Political Science*, 35(3), pp. 449–470. Available at: <https://doi.org/10.1080/713649346>
- Maley, M. (2011) 'Strategic links in a cut-throat world: rethinking the role and relationships of Australian ministerial staff', *Public Administration*, 89(4), pp. 1469–1488. Available at: <https://doi.org/10.1111/j.1467-9299.2011.01928.x>

- Malmqvist, J., Hellberg, K., Möllås, G., Rose, R. and Shevlin, M. (2019) ‘Conducting the pilot study: a neglected part of the research process? Methodological findings supporting the importance of piloting in qualitative research studies’, *International Journal of Qualitative Methods*, 18(1), pp. 1–11. Available at: <https://doi.org/10.1177/1609406919878341>
- Manwaring, R. (2019) ‘Political demand and policy advice: a framework for analysis’, *Policy Studies*, 40(3–4), pp. 270–286. Available at: <https://doi.org/10.1080/01442872.2018.1557622>
- Maqoura, M. and Bouriche, R. (2020) ‘The role of political parties in public policy-making in Algeria 1997–2017’, *Revue Algérienne des Sciences Politiques*, 6(1), pp. 146–165. Available at: <https://asjp.cerist.dz/en/article/109376> (Accessed: 20 August 2025).
- March, J.G. and Olsen, J.P. (2008) ‘Elaborating the “new institutionalism”’, in Rhodes, R.A.W., Binder, S.A. and Rockman, B.A. (eds) *The Oxford handbook of political institutions*. Oxford: Oxford University Press
- Mariotti, C. (2020) ‘Elite theory’, *The Palgrave Encyclopedia of Interest Groups, Lobbying and Public Affairs*, pp. 1–6. Available at: https://doi.org/10.1007/978-3-030-13895-0_67-1
- Marks, G. (1992) ‘Structural policy in the European Community’, in Sbragia, A. (ed.) *Euro-Politics: Institutions and policy-making in the “new” European Community*. Washington: Brookings Institution, pp. 191–224.
- Marks, G. (1993) ‘Structural policy and multi-level governance in the EC’, in Cafruny, A. and Rosenthal, G. (eds.) *The State of the European Community, Vol. 2: The Maastricht Debate and Beyond*. Boulder, CO: Lynne Rienner Publishers, pp. 391–410.
- Marks, G. (1996) ‘An actor-centred approach to multi-level governance’, *Regional & Federal Studies*, 6(2), pp. 20–38. Available at: <https://doi.org/10.1080/13597569608420966>
- Marsh, D. and Rhodes, R.A.W. (eds) (1992) *Policy networks in British government*. Oxford: Oxford University Press
- Marshall, N. (1995) ‘Policy communities, issue networks and the formulation of Australian higher education policy’, *Higher Education*, 30(3), pp. 273–293. Available at: <http://www.jstor.org/stable/3447851>
- Masetti, F. (2019) *Devolution in Scotland and the case study of the Scottish higher education system*. European Diversity and Autonomy Papers (EDAP) 01/2019. Bolzano: EURAC Research. Available at: <https://core.ac.uk/download/pdf/237467816.pdf> (Accessed: 23 May 2021).
- Matland, R. (1995) ‘Synthesizing the implementation literature: the ambiguity-conflict model of policy implementation’, *Journal of Public Administration Research and Theory*, 5(2), pp. 145–174. Available at: <https://www.jstor.org/stable/1181674> (Accessed: 15 May 2021).

Matthews, D. (2013) 'Final Scottish governance code is criticised', *Times Higher Education*, 19 July. Available at: <https://www.timeshighereducation.com/final-scottish-governance-code-is-criticised/2005848.article> (Accessed: 5 May 2022)

Mayer, I.S., van Daalen, C.E. and Bots, P.W.G. (2004) 'Perspectives on policy analyses: a framework for understanding and design', *International Journal of Technology, Policy and Management*, 4(2), p. 169. Available at: <https://doi.org/10.1504/ijtpm.2004.004819>

Mayne, R., Green, D., Guijt, I., Walsh, M., English, R. and Cairney, P. (2018) 'Using evidence to influence policy: Oxfam's experience', *Palgrave Communications*, 4(1). Available at: <https://doi.org/10.1057/s41599-018-0176-7>

Mazawi, A (2005) Contrasting perspectives on higher education governance in the Arab states. In: J.C. Smart, ed. *Higher education: Handbook of theory and research*. Vol. 20. Dordrecht: Springer, pp.133–189. Available at: https://doi.org/10.1007/1-4020-3279-X_3

McAteer, M. and Bennett, M. (2005) 'Devolution and local government: Evidence from Scotland', *Local Government Studies*, 31(3), pp. 285–306. Available at: <https://doi.org/10.1080/03003930500095095>.

McCann, E. (2011) 'Urban policy mobilities and global circuits of knowledge: toward a research agenda', *Annals of the Association of American Geographers*, 101(1), pp. 107–130. Available at: <https://doi.org/10.1080/00045608.2010.520219>

McClory, J. (2023) *Gauging international perceptions: Scotland and soft power*. British Council. Available at: https://scotland.britishcouncil.org/sites/default/files/t0026_scottish_soft_power_doc_s1_v20.pdf (Accessed: 22 August 2025).

McConnell, A. (2006) 'Central-local government relations in Scotland', *International Review of Administrative Sciences*, 72(1), pp. 73–84. Available at: <https://doi.org/10.1177/0020852306061622>.

McConnell, A. (2010) *Understanding policy success: rethinking public policy*. Basingstoke: Palgrave Macmillan.

McCool, D. (1998) 'The subsystem family of concepts: a critique and a proposal', *Political Research Quarterly*, 51(2), pp. 551–570. Available at: <https://doi.org/10.1177/106591299805100213>

McCready, E. and Winterstein, G. (2017) 'Negotiating epistemic authority', *Lecture Notes in Computer Science*, vol. 10247, pp. 74–89. Available at: https://doi.org/10.1007/978-3-319-61572-1_6

McFarland, A.S. (2004) *Neopluralism: the evolution of political process theory*. Lawrence, KS: University Press of Kansas

McDermott, M. (2018) 'Layering, conversion and drifting: A comparative analysis of path dependent change in consumer insolvency systems', *Chicago-Kent Law Review*, 93(3), pp. 765–802. Available at: <https://ssrn.com/abstract=3204771> (Accessed: 13 April 2025).

McGann, J.G. and Johnson, E.C. (2005) *Comparative think tanks, politics and public policy*. Cheltenham: Edward Elgar

McGann, J.G. (2020) '2020 global go to think tank index report', *TTCSP Global Go To Think Tank Index Reports*, 18. Philadelphia: University of Pennsylvania, Think Tanks and Civil Societies Program. Available at: https://repository.upenn.edu/think_tanks/18 (Accessed: 24 April 2022).

McGrath, C. (2024) *UK tuition fee policy: Recent developments and challenges*. London: Sutton Education Press.

McGuinness, D., Greenhalgh, P. and Pugalis, L. (2015) 'Is the grass always greener?', *The Geographical Journal*, 181, pp. 26–37. Available at: <https://doi.org/10.1111/geoj.12090>

McPherson, A. and Raab, C.D. (1988) *Governing education: a sociology of policy since 1945*. Edinburgh: Edinburgh University Press.

McPherson, A. (1990) *How good is Scottish education and how good is the case for change? Scottish Government Yearbook*. Available at: <https://www.academia.edu/94732941/> (Accessed: 15 May 2025).

Medaglia, R. (2012) 'eParticipation research: moving characterization forward (2006–2011)', *Government Information Quarterly*, 29, pp. 346–360. Available at: <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.giq.2012.02.010>

Meho, L.I. (2006) 'E-mail interviewing in qualitative research: a methodological discussion', *Journal of the American Society for Information Science and Technology*, 57(10), pp. 1284–1295. Available at: <https://doi.org/10.1002/asi.20416>

Mekdad, Y., Dahmani, A. and Louaj, M. (2014) 'Public spending on education and economic growth in Algeria: causality test', *International Journal of Business and Management*, 2(3), pp. 55–70. Available at: https://www.iises.net/download/Soubory/soubory-puvodni/pp55-70_ijobmV2N3.pdf (Accessed: 24 June 2021).

Mellouk, M. (2013) 'The LMD system: a major issue in higher education reform', *Dialogue Méditerranéen*, 4(1), pp. 85–91. Available at: <https://asjp.cerist.dz/en/article/17127> (Accessed: 14 May 2021).

Meltsner, A.J. (1976) *Policy analysts in the bureaucracy*. Berkeley: University of California Press

Meltsner, A.J. (1990) *Rules for rulers: the politics of advice*. Philadelphia: Temple University Press. Available at: <https://archive.org/details/rulesforrulerspo00melt> (Accessed: 23 December 2022).

- Merriam, S.B. (1998) *Qualitative research and case study applications in education: revised and expanded from "Case Study Research in Education"*. San Francisco, CA: Jossey-Bass.
- Metatla, O. (2016) 'Higher education reform in Algeria: reading between the lines', *Open Democracy*. Available at: <https://www.opendemocracy.net/en/north-africa-west-asia/higher-education-reform-in-algeria-reading-between-lines/> (Accessed: 15 November 2021)
- Metz, F. and Brandenberger, L. (2022) 'Policy networks across political systems', *American Journal of Political Science* [Preprint]. Available at: <https://doi.org/10.1111/ajps.12699>
- Meyer, M. and Molyneux-Hodgson, S. (2010) 'Introduction: the dynamics of epistemic communities', *Sociological Research Online*, 15. Available at: <https://doi.org/10.5153/sro.2154>
- Mezache-Bensaidane, N. (2017) *Aperçu sur le système d'enseignement supérieur et de recherche algérien*. 6th MENA Tertiary Education Conference, Marseille, 15–16 June. Ministry of Higher Education and Scientific Research, Algeria.
- Meziane, M. and Mahi, B. (2010) 'The LMD higher education system in the Maghreb countries: the example of Algeria'. *Shamaa Organization*. Available at: <https://search.shamaa.org/PDF/41452/MohammedEn41485.pdf> (Accessed: 19 December 2021)
- Miles, M.B. and Huberman, A.M. (1994) *Qualitative data analysis*. 2nd edn. Thousand Oaks, CA: SAGE Publications
- Miller, N.R. (1983) 'Pluralism and social choice', *The American Political Science Review*, 77(3), pp. 734–747. Available at: <https://www.umbc.edu> (Accessed: 22 September 2022).
- Mills, A.J., Durepos, G. and Wiebe, E. (eds) (2009) *Encyclopedia of case study research*. Thousand Oaks, CA: Sage Publications
- Minty, S. (2015) 'Young people's attitudes towards tuition fees and debt in Scotland and England', paper presented as part of symposium *Higher education in Scotland and the UK: Diverging or converging systems?* at the *British Educational Research Association Conference*, Queen's University Belfast, 16 September.
- Moffitt, S. (2010) 'Promoting agency reputation through public advice: advisory committee use in the FDA', *The Journal of Politics*, 72, pp. 880–893. Available at: <https://doi.org/10.1017/S002238161000023X>
- Mooney, G. and Poole, L. (2004) 'A land of milk and honey? Social policy in Scotland after devolution', *Critical Social Policy*, 24(4), pp. 458–483. Available at: <https://doi.org/10.1177/0261018304046672> (Original work published 2004)
- Morgan, D.L. (1998) *The focus group guidebook*. London: Sage
- Morgan, H. (2022) 'Conducting a qualitative document analysis', *The Qualitative Report*, 27(1), pp. 64–77. Available at: <https://hanimorgan.com/wp-content/uploads/2022/01/Hani-Morgan-Conducting-a-Qualitative-Document-Analysis-1.pdf> (Accessed: 15 December 2022).

Morgan, J. (2011) 'Liam Burns elected as next NUS president', *Times Higher Education*, 13 April. Available at: <https://www.timeshighereducation.com/news/liam-burns-elected-as-next-nus-president/415846.article> (Accessed: 9 December 2021)

Mountfield, R. (2002) 'If the Civil Service is to survive, it needs the security of legislation', *The Independent*. Available at: <http://www.independent.co.uk/opinion/commentators/robin-mountfield-if-the-civil-service-is-to-survive-it-needs-the-security-of-legislation-658883.html> (Accessed 10 November 2022)

Mulgan, G. (2005) 'Government, knowledge and the business of policy making: the potential and limits of evidence-based policy', *Evidence & Policy: A Journal of Research, Debate and Practice*, 1(2), pp. 215–226. Available at: <https://doi.org/10.1332/1744264053730789>

Murphy, M. and Morgan-Klein, B. (2001) 'Widening participation in Scottish higher education'. In: *The FE-HE Interface*, Stirling, UK, 20 September 2001. Available at Widening participation in Scottish higher education | Semantic Scholar (Accessed 12 July 2021).

Musette, Y. (2019) Quality assurance in the higher education institutions in Algeria: Constraints and levers for the implementation of the change. *Revue d'études sur les institutions et le développement*, (5), pp.86–107. Available at: https://www.academia.edu/40730104/Yasmine_Musette_2019_Quality_Assurance_the_Higher_education_institutions_in_Algeria_Constraints_and_levers_for_the_implementation_of_the_change (Accessed 12 June 2025).

Nachiappan, K. (2013) 'Think tanks and the knowledge–policy nexus in China', *Policy and Society*, 32(3), pp. 255–265. Available at: <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.polsoc.2013.07.006> (Accessed 26 April 2021)

Nag, N.S. (2018) 'Government, governance and good governance', *Indian Journal of Public Administration*, 64(1), pp. 122–130. Available at: <https://doi.org/10.1177/0019556117735448> (Accessed 26 April 2021)

National Institute for Health and Care Research (2019) *How researchers can influence policy and practice*. Available at: <https://www.nihr.ac.uk/documents/how-researchers-can-influence-policy-and-practice> (Accessed: 17 August 2025).

National Union of Students Scotland (2007) *Submission for the Scottish Government: Graduate Endowment Abolition (Scotland) Bill*. Available at: <http://archive.scottish.parliament.uk/s3/committees/ellc/documents/NationalUnionofStudentsScotland.pdf> (Accessed: 31 August 2021).

National Union of Students Scotland (2013) *Developing a Scottish code of good HE governance: NUS Scotland consultation response*. Edinburgh: Scottish Government. Available at: <https://www.scottishuniversitygovernance.ac.uk> (Accessed: 30 April 2021).

National Union of Students Scotland (2010) *Still in the red: Student finance, education funding and the cost of living*. Available at: <https://www.nusconnect.org.uk/resources/still-in-the-red-report> (Accessed: 22 August 2025)

National Union of Students Scotland (2022) *NUS Scotland homepage*. Available at: <https://www.nus-scotland.org.uk/about> (Accessed: 18 August 2025)

Necir, A. and Nadhir, G. (2019) 'Evaluation of the performance and trends of public expenditure in the Algerian economy for the period 1990–2016', *Journal of Economic, Management and Commercial Sciences*, 12(2), pp. 203–216. Available at: https://www.researchgate.net/publication/341549934_An_analytical_evaluation_study_of_the_performance_and_trends_of_public_spending_in_the_Algerian_economy_for_the_period_1990-2016 (Accessed: 7 January 2023)

Neill, P. (2000) 'Reinforcing standards', *Sixth report of the Committee on Standards in Public Life*. Available at: http://www.public-standards.gov.uk/publications/6th_report.aspx (Accessed 28 March 2021)

Neuman, W.L. (2005) *Social research methods: Qualitative and quantitative approaches*. Boston: Allyn & Bacon

Nohrstedt, D. (2011) 'Shifting resources and venues producing policy change in contested subsystems: A case study of Swedish signals intelligence policy', *Policy Studies Journal*, 39(3), pp. 461–484. Available at: <https://doi.org/10.1111/j.1541-0072.2011.00417.x>

Nokkala, T. and Bacevic, J. (2014) 'University Autonomy, Agenda Setting and the Construction of Agency: The Case of the European University Association in the European Higher Education Area', *European Educational Research Journal*, 13(6), 699–714. <https://doi.org/10.2304/eeerj.2014.13.6.699>

Norbert, G. and Marklund, C. (eds) (2014) *The paradox of openness*. Leiden: Brill

Noui, R. (2020) 'Higher education between massification and quality', *Higher Education Evaluation and Development*, ahead-of-print(ahead-of-print). Available at: <https://doi.org/10.1108/heed-04-2020-0008>

Nour, S. (2011) 'National, regional and global perspectives of higher education and science policies in the Arab region', *Minerva*, 49, pp. 387–423. Available at: <https://doi.org/10.1007/s11024-011-9183-1>

Nóvoa, A. and Yariv-Mashal, T. (2003) 'Comparative research in education: A mode of governance or a historical journey?', *Comparative Education*, 39(4), pp. 423–438. Available at: <http://www.jstor.org/stable/3593413> (Accessed: 10 July 2025)

Nowell, L.S., Norris, J.M., White, D.E. and Moules, N.J. (2017) 'Thematic analysis: striving to meet the trustworthiness criteria', *International Journal of Qualitative Methods*, 16, pp. 1–13. Available at: <https://doi.org/10.1177/1609406917733847>

Nutley, S.M., Davies, H.T.O. and Walter, I. (2002) *Evidence-based policy and practice: cross sector lessons from the UK*. London: ESRC UK Centre for Evidence Based Policy and

Practice. Available at: (PDF) Evidence Based Policy and Practice: Cross Sector Lessons From the UK (researchgate.net) (Accessed: 13 June 2021).

Nutley, S.M., Walter, I. and Davies, H.T.O. (2007) *Using evidence: How research can inform public services*. Bristol: Policy Press. Online edn, Policy Press Scholarship Online, 22 March. Available at: <https://doi.org/10.1332/policypress/9781861346650.001.0001>

O’Leary, Z. (2017) *The essential guide to doing your research project*. 3rd edn. London: SAGE Publications.

OECD (2022) *Country policy support*. Available at: <https://www.oecd.org/en/topics/sub-issues/structural-reform/country-tailored-policy-advice-work.html> (Accessed: 18 August 2025)

Olaniyi, J.O. (1998) *Foundations of public policy analysis*. Ibadan: Sunad Publishers

Onwuegbuzie, A.J. and Collins, K.M. (2007) ‘A typology of mixed methods sampling designs in social science research’, *The Qualitative Report*, 12(2), pp. 281–316. Available at: <https://doi.org/10.46743/2160-3715/2007.1638>

Osborne, D. and Gaebler, T. (1992) *Reinventing government: How the entrepreneurial spirit is transforming the public sector*. New York: Plume Books

Osborne, M. (2003) ‘Increasing or widening participation in higher education? — A European overview’, *European Journal of Education*, 38(1), pp. 5–24. Available at: <https://doi.org/10.1111/1467-3435.00277>

Osman, F. (2002) ‘Public policy making theories and their implications in developing countries’. Available at: https://www.researchgate.net/publication/253836498_PUBLIC_POLICY_MAKING_THEORIES_AND_THEIR_IMPLICATIONS_IN_DEVELOPING_COUNTRIES (Accessed: 23 April 2022)

Ourahmoune, N. (2021) ‘Algérie: la “Révolution du sourire pacifique” persiste et signe’, *The Conversation*, 28 March. Available at: <https://theconversation.com/algerie-la-revolution-du-sourire-pacifique-persiste-et-signe-157615> (Accessed: 20 November 2022)

Ozden, Ç.M. (2006) ‘Brain drain in Middle East & North Africa – The patterns under the surface’, *United Nations Expert Group Meeting on International Migration and Development in the Arab Region*, Beirut, 15–17 May. Available at: https://www.un.org/development/desa/pd/sites/www.un.org.development.desa.pd/files/200605_egm_p10_ozden.pdf (Accessed: 22 August 2022)

Ozga, J. and Jones, R. (2006) ‘Travelling and embedded policy: the case of knowledge transfer’, *Journal of Education Policy*, 21, pp. 1–17. Available

at: <https://doi.org/10.1080/02680930500391462>

Ozga, J. (2004) *From research to policy and practice: some issues in knowledge transfer*. CES Briefing No. 31. Edinburgh: Centre for Educational Sociology. Available at: <http://www.ces.ed.ac.uk/PDF%20Files/Brief031.pdf> (Accessed: 16 July 2025)

Ozga, J. (2020) 'Elites and expertise: the changing material production of knowledge for policy', in *Elites and knowledge production in education*. Cham: Springer, pp. 53–69. Available at: https://doi.org/10.1007/978-981-13-8347-2_3

Ozga, J., Grek, S. and Lawn, M. (2009) 'The new production of governing knowledge', *Soziale Welt*, 60(4), pp. 353–369. Available at: <https://doi.org/10.5771/0038-6073-2009-4-353>

Ozgur, H. and Kulaç, O. (2017) 'An overview of the stages (heuristics) model as a public policy analysis framework', *European Scientific Journal*, Special Edition, May. Available at: https://www.researchgate.net/publication/329377096_An_Overview_of_the_Stages_Heuristics_Model_as_a_Public_Policy_Analysis_Framework (Accessed: 23 November 2021)

Page, E.C. (1992) *Political authority and bureaucratic power: A comparative analysis*. London: Harvester Wheatsheaf.

Pahlman, K. (2014) 'A critical examination of the idea of evidence-based policymaking', *ANU Undergraduate Research Journal*, 6. Available at: <https://doi.org/10.22459/AURJ.06.2014.09>

Palumbo, A. (2017) *From government to governance*. 1st edn. Taylor and Francis. Available at: <https://www.perlego.com/book/1486718/from-government-to-governance-pdf> (Accessed: 7 July 2025)

Parashar, S. and Schulz, M. (2021) 'Colonial legacies, postcolonial "selfhood" and the (un)doing of Africa', *Third World Quarterly*, 42(5), pp. 867–881. Available at: <https://doi.org/10.1080/01436597.2021.1903313>

Paré, G. and Elam, J.J. (1997) 'Using case study research to build theories of IT implementation', in Lee, A.S., Liebenau, J. and DeGross, J.I. (eds) *Information systems and qualitative research*. London: Chapman & Hall, pp. 542–568

Park, E.L. (2009) 'Analysis of Korean students' international mobility by 2-D model: Driving force factor and directional factor', *Higher Education*, 57(6), pp. 741–755. Available at:

<https://doi.org/10.1007/s10734-008-9173-x>

Parsons, W. (2002) 'From muddling through to muddling up – evidence-based policy making and the modernisation of British government', *Public Policy and Administration*, 17(3), pp. 43–60. Available at: <https://doi.org/10.1177/095207670201700304> (Accessed 12 April 2023).

Paterson, L. (2001) 'Higher education and European regionalism', *Pedagogy, Culture and Society*, 9(1), pp. 133–160. Available at: <https://doi.org/10.1080/14681360100200117>

Paterson, L. (2003) *Scottish education in the twentieth century*. Edinburgh: Edinburgh University Press

Paterson, L. (2014) 'Education and opportunity: Is the UK departing from a common tradition?', *Journal of the British Academy*, 2, pp. 101–123. Available at: <https://doi.org/10.5871/jba/002.101>

Paterson, L. (2021a) 'Higher education and school history in Scotland in the second half of the twentieth century', *British Journal of Sociology of Education*, 42(7), pp. 989–1007. Available at: <https://doi.org/10.1080/01425692.2021.1962245>

Paterson, L. (2021b) 'Higher education expansion and the secondary school curriculum in Scotland in the second half of the twentieth century', *Oxford Review of Education*, 48(5), pp. 622–641. Available at: <https://doi.org/10.1080/03054985.2021.2002291>

Patton, M. (1990) *Qualitative evaluation and research methods*. 2nd edn. Newbury Park, CA: Sage

Paul, M. (2021) *The Turing Scheme: The UK's global student exchange programme*. London: Department for Education

Pautz, H. (2007) 'Scottish think-tanks and policy networks', *Scottish Affairs*, 58, pp. 57–77. Available at: <https://doi.org/10.3366/scot.2007.0004>

Pautz, H. (2010) 'Think tanks in the United Kingdom and Germany: Actors in the modernisation of social democracy', *The British Journal of Politics and International Relations*, 12(2), pp. 274–294. Available at: <https://doi.org/10.1111/j.1467-856x.2010.00402.x>

Pautz, H. (2013) 'The think tanks behind "Cameronism"', *The British Journal of Politics and International Relations*, 15(3), pp. 362–377. Available at: <https://doi.org/10.1111/j.1467->

Pautz, H. (2020) 'Think tanks and policy-making', in Peters, G. (ed.) *The Oxford Encyclopedia of Public Administration*. Oxford: Oxford University Press. Available at: https://doi.org/10.1093/acrefore/9780190228637.013.ORE_POL01420.R1

Pautz, H. (2020) 'Think tanks and policy-making', in Peters, G. (ed.) *The Oxford Encyclopedia of Public Administration*. Oxford: Oxford University Press. Available at: https://doi.org/10.1093/acrefore/9780190228637.013.ORE_POL01420.R1

Pennell, H. and West, A. (2005) 'The impact of increased tuition fees on higher education participation', *Higher Education Quarterly*, 59(2), pp. 127–137. Available at: <https://doi.org/10.1111/j.1468-2273.2005.00286.x>

Peters, B.G. and Barker, A. (1993) *Advising West European governments: inquiries, expertise and public policy*. Edinburgh: Edinburgh University Press.

Peters, B.G. and Barker, A. (1993) *Advising West European governments: inquiries, expertise and public policy*. Edinburgh: Edinburgh University Press

Peters, B.G. and Pierre, J. (2004) *Politicization of the public service in comparative perspective*. London: Routledge

Peters, B.G. and Pierre, J. (2004) *Politicization of the public service in comparative perspective*. London: Routledge

Peters, B.G. and Pierre, J. (2016) *Comparative governance: Rediscovering the functional dimension of governing*. Cambridge: Cambridge University Press. Available at: <https://www.cambridge.org/core/books/comparative-governance/E1206A8493AAAAA3683BDF05299DCD1F> (Accessed: 18 August 2025)

Peters, B.G. and Pierre, J. (2016) *Comparative governance: Rediscovering the functional dimension of governing*. Cambridge: Cambridge University Press. Available at: <https://www.cambridge.org/core/books/comparative-governance/E1206A8493AAAAA3683BDF05299DCD1F> (Accessed: 18 August 2025)

Peters, B.G. and Savoie, D.J. (eds) (2000) *Governance in the twenty-first century: revitalizing the public service*. Montreal/Kingston: Canadian Centre for Management Development/McGill-Queen's University Press

Peters, B.G. and Savoie, D.J. (eds) (2000) *Governance in the twenty-first century: revitalizing the public service*. Montreal/Kingston: Canadian Centre for Management Development/McGill-Queen's University Press.

Peters, B.G. (1996) *The policy capacity of government*. Ottawa: Canadian Centre for Management Development.

Peters, B.G. (2000) *Institutional theory: problems and prospects*. Political Science Series, No. 69. Vienna: Institute for Advanced Studies.

Peters, B.G. (2016) 'Institutionalism and public policy', in Zittoun, P. and Peters, B.G. (eds) *Contemporary approaches to public policy*. London: Palgrave Macmillan, pp. 57–72. Available at: https://doi.org/10.1057/978-1-137-50494-4_4

Peterson, J. (2003) 'Policy networks', *Political Science Series*, No. 90. Vienna: Institute for Advanced Studies. Available at: https://irihs.ihs.ac.at/id/eprint/1506/1/pw_90.pdf (Accessed: 20 December 2021)

Philippi, J. and Lauderdale, J. (2017) 'A guide to field notes for qualitative research: context and conversation', *Qualitative Health Research*, 28, p. 104973231769710. Available at: <https://doi.org/10.1177/1049732317697102>

Piattoni, S. (2009) 'Multi-level governance: A historical and conceptual analysis', *Journal of European Integration*, 31(2), pp. 163–180. Available at: <https://doi.org/10.1080/07036330802642755>

Piattoni, S. (2010) *The theory of multi-level governance: conceptual, empirical, and normative challenges*. Oxford: Oxford University Press

Pierre, J. and Peters, B.G. (2020) *Governance, politics and the state*. London: Red Globe Press.

Plowden, W. (ed.) (1987) *Advising the rulers*. Oxford: Basil Blackwell.

Polsby, N.W. (1960) 'How to Study Community Power: The Pluralist Alternative', *The Journal of Politics*, 22(3), pp. 474–484. Available at: <https://doi.org/10.2307/2126892>

Porter, C. (2010) 'What shapes the influence evidence has on policy? The role of politics in research utilisation'. Working Paper No. 62. University of Oxford. Available at: <https://ora.ox.ac.uk/objects/uuid:107d951e-aba9-4810-8370-0aeb640cc00c/files/m03a6864cf65114b1d8906a6d1f4aa32e> (Accessed: 14 February 2021)

Prakash, A. and Potoski, M. (2012) 'Research frontiers in comparative policy analysis: An introduction', *Journal of Policy Analysis and Management*, 31(1), p. 93. Available at: <http://www.jstor.org/stable/41429259> (Accessed: 6 July 2025)

Prasser, S. (2006a) *Royal commissions and public inquiries in Australia*. Sydney: Lexis Nexis.

Prasser, S. (2006b) 'Providing advice to government', *Papers on Parliament*, 46. Canberra: Senate of Australia. Available at: http://www.aph.gov.au/senate/pubs/pops/pop46/providing_advice.htm (Accessed: 23 October 2021).

Pring, R. (2000) 'The 'false dualism' of educational research', *Journal of Philosophy of Education*, 34(2), pp. 247–260. Available at: <http://dx.doi.org/10.1111/1467-9752.00171>

Priya, A. (2021) 'Case study methodology of qualitative research: Key attributes and navigating the conundrums in its application', *Sociological Bulletin*, 70(1), pp. 94–110. Available at: <https://doi.org/10.1177/0038022920970318>

Przeworski, A. and Teune, H. (1970) *The logic of comparative social inquiry*. New York: John Wiley.

Pulkkinen, U. and Simola, K. (2000) 'An expert panel approach to support risk informed decision making'. *STUK-YTO-TR 170*. Helsinki: Radiation and Nuclear Safety Authority. Available at: https://inis.iaea.org/collection/NCLCollectionStore/_Public/32/001/32001787.pdf?r=1 (Accessed: 11 March 2021)

QAA (2017) *The Quality Code toolkit: a guide to using the UK Quality Code for Higher Education*. Gloucester: Quality Assurance Agency for Higher Education. Available at: https://www.qaa.ac.uk/docs/qaa/quality-code/quality-code-toolkit-17.pdf?sfvrsn=4754ff81_4 (Accessed: 10 September 2025).

QAA Scotland (2007) *The Bologna process in higher education: Compatibility of the framework for qualifications of higher education institutions in Scotland with the European Higher Education Area*. Available at: https://eha.info/media.eha.info/file/Qualifications_frameworks/81/5/The-Bologna-Process-in-HE-2007_596815.pdf

Rabah, N.A. and Raouti, R. (2023) 'The impact of globalisation on higher education in Algeria', *Almi 'yār*, 25(6), pp. 994–1001. Available at: https://www.researchgate.net/publication/369309647_The_Impact_Of_Globalisation_On_

Higher_Education_In_Algeria (Accessed: 18 August 2025)

Radaelli, C.M. (1995) 'The role of knowledge in the policy process', *Journal of European Public Policy*, 2(2), pp. 159–183. Available at: <https://doi.org/10.1080/13501769508406981>

Radin, A. (2000) *Beyond Machiavelli: Policy analysis comes of age*. Washington, DC: Georgetown University Press

Raffe, D. (2011) *Policy borrowing or policy learning? How (not) to improve education systems*. Edinburgh: Centre for Educational Sociology, University of Edinburgh. Available at: <https://www.ces.ed.ac.uk/PDF%20Files/Brief057.pdf> (Accessed: 6 April 2021)

Raffe, D. (2015) 'Higher education governance and institutional autonomy in the post-devolution UK', in Riddell, S., Weedon, E. and Minty, S. (eds.) *Higher Education in Scotland and the UK: Diverging or Converging Systems?* Edinburgh: Edinburgh University Press, pp. 19–32

Ragin, C.C. (2014) *The comparative method: Moving beyond qualitative and quantitative strategies*. 2nd edn. Oakland: University of California Press.

Raina, P. (2023) *Devolution of power to Scotland, Wales and Northern Ireland: the inner history. Tony Blair's cabinet papers, 1997. Volume one, Devolution in Scotland and Wales*.

Rasmussen, A. (2014) 'Participation in written government consultations in Denmark and the UK: System and actor-level effects', *Government and Opposition*, 50(2), pp. 271–299. Available at: <https://doi.org/10.1017/gov.2014.16>

Raudla, R., Sarapuu, K., Vallistu, J., Onno, K. and Harbuzova, N. (2025) 'The politics of experimental policymaking: the influence of blame avoidance and credit claiming', *Policy Sciences*. Available at: <https://link.springer.com/content/pdf/10.1007/s11077-025-09568-7.pdf> (Accessed: 16 August 2025).

Reimers, F. and McGinn, N. (1997) *Informed dialogue: Using research to shape education policy around the world*. Paris: UNESCO International Institute for Educational Planning. Available at: [http://lst-iiiep.iiiep-unesco.org/cgi-bin/wwwi32.exe/\[in=epidoc1.in\]/?t2000=009155/\(100\)](http://lst-iiiep.iiiep-unesco.org/cgi-bin/wwwi32.exe/[in=epidoc1.in]/?t2000=009155/(100)) (Accessed: 17 February 2021)

Rey, S. and Hazem, S. (2019) 'Labor productivity and economic growth in a hydrocarbon-dependent economy: the Algerian case, 1984–2015', *The European Journal of Development Research*, 32(3), pp. 587–611. Available at: <https://doi.org/10.1057/s41287-019-00229-z>

Rezig, N. (2011) 'Teaching English in Algeria and educational reforms: An overview on the factors entailing students' failure in learning foreign languages at university', *Procedia - Social and Behavioral Sciences*, 29, pp. 1327–1333. Available at: <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.sbspro.2011.11.370>

Rhodes, R.A.W. and Marsh, D. (1992) 'New directions in the study of policy networks', *European Journal of Political Research*, 21(1–2), pp. 181–205. Available at: <https://doi.org/10.1111/j.1475-6765.1992.tb00294.x>

Rhodes, R.A.W. (1986) "'Power Dependence": Theories of Central-Local Relations – A Critical Reassessment', in Goldsmith, M.J. (ed.) *New Research in Central-Local Relations*. Aldershot: Gower

Rhodes, R.A.W. (1995) 'From prime ministerial power to core executive', in Rhodes, R.A.W. and Dunleavy, P. (eds.) *Prime Minister, Cabinet and Core Executive*. London: Macmillan, pp. 11–37

Rhodes, R.A.W. (1996) 'The new governance: Governing without government', *Political Studies*, 44(4), pp. 652–667. Available at: <https://doi.org/10.1111/j.1467-9248.1996.tb01747.x>

Rhodes, R.A.W. (1997) *Understanding governance: policy networks, governance, reflexivity and accountability*. Buckingham: Open University Press. Available at: https://www.researchgate.net/publication/233870082_Understanding_Governance_Policy_Networks_Governance_Reflexivity_and_Accountability#fullTextFileContent (Accessed: 15 June 2025)

Rhodes, R.A.W. (2006) 'Policy network analysis', in Moran, M., Rein, M. and Goodin, R.E. (eds.) *The Oxford Handbook of Public Policy*. Oxford: Oxford University Press, pp. 423–445. Available at: <https://doi.org/10.1093/oxfordhb/9780199548453.003.0020>

Rich, A. (2004) *Think tanks, public policy, and the politics of expertise*. Cambridge: Cambridge University Press. ISBN: 0-521-83029-X. Available at: <https://assets.cambridge.org/isbn13/97805218/30294/sample/9780521830294ws.pdf> (Accessed: 31 July 2022)

Rich, A., McGann, J., Weaver, R.K., Garnett, M., Thunert, M., Speth, R., and Traub-Merz, R. (2011) *Think tanks in policy making – Do they matter?* Shanghai: Friedrich-Ebert-Stiftung. Available at: <https://library.fes.de/pdf-files/bueros/china/08564.pdf> (Accessed: 18 August 2025).

Richards, H.M. and Schwartz, L.J. (2002) 'Ethics of qualitative research: Are there special issues for health services research?', *Family Practice*, 19(2), pp. 135–139. Available

at: <https://doi.org/10.1093/fampra/19.2.135>

Richardson, J. (1994) 'EU water policy: Uncertain agendas, shifting networks and complex coalitions', *Environmental Politics*, 3(4), pp. 139–167. Available at: <https://doi.org/10.1080/09644019408414170>

Richardson, J.J. and Jordan, A.G. (1979) *Governing under pressure: The policy process in a post-parliamentary democracy*. Oxford; New York: B. Blackwell

Riddell, S. (2016) 'Scottish higher education and social justice: tensions between data and discourse', *Scottish Educational Review*, 48(1), pp. 13–29. Available at: <https://doi.org/10.1163/27730840-04801003>

Riddell, S., Blackburn, L. and Minty, S. (2016) 'Widening access to higher education: Scotland in UK comparative perspective', paper prepared for the Scottish Government Widening Access Commission. Edinburgh: CREID, University of Edinburgh.

Riddell, S., Edward, S., Boeren, E. and Weedon, E. (2013) *Widening access to higher education: does anyone know what works?* Report to Universities Scotland. Edinburgh: Moray House School of Education and Sport, CREID, University of Edinburgh. Available at: <http://www.universities-scotland.ac.uk/uploads/WideningAccessToHE-CREID.pdf>

Riddell, S., Hunter Blackburn, L. and Minty, S. (2016) *Widening access to higher education: Scotland in UK comparative perspective*. Paper prepared for the Scottish Government's Commission on Widening Access. Edinburgh: CREID, University of Edinburgh. Available at: https://www.docs.hss.ed.ac.uk/education/creid/NewsEvents/52_v_CoWA_Paper.pdf (Accessed: 18 August 2025)

Riddell, S., Raffe, D., Croxford, L., Weedon, E., Minty, S. and Whittaker, S. (2013) *Higher education, the devolution settlement and the referendum on independence*. CREID Briefing No. 32. Edinburgh: Centre for Research in Education Inclusion and Diversity (CREID), University of Edinburgh. Available at: <http://www.docs.hss.ed.ac.uk/education/creid/Briefings/Briefing32.pdf> [Accessed 12 Sep. 2025].

Riedl, A. and Staubmann, H. (2021) 'Internationalisation, Brexit, and the EU academic system: a case study in Austria', *European Journal of English Studies*, 25(1), pp. 65–79. Available at: <https://doi.org/10.1080/13825577.2021.1918860>

Ripley, R.B. and Franklin, G.A. (1984) *Congress, the bureaucracy, and public policy*. Pacific Grove, CA: Brooks/Cole

Ritchie, J. and Lewis, J. (2003) *Qualitative research practice: A guide for social science students and researchers*. London: Sage

Rodon, J. and Sesé, F. (2008) 'Towards a framework for the transferability of results in IS qualitative research', *Sprouts: Working Papers on Information Systems*, 8(17). Available at: https://aisel.aisnet.org/sprouts_all/223/ (Accessed: 10 August 2022)

Rose, M. (2015) *Education in North Africa since independence: Country profile – Algeria*. London: British Council. Available at: <https://www.britishcouncil.org/sites/default/files/education-in-north-africa-since-independence-algeria.pdf> (Accessed: 23 March 2021)

Rowe, M. and McAllister, L. (2006) 'The roles of commissions of inquiry in the policy process', *Public Policy and Administration*, 21(4), pp. 99–115. Available at: <https://doi.org/10.1177/095207670602100408>

Rutledge, P.B. and Hogg, J.L.C. (2020) 'In-depth interviews', *The International Encyclopedia of Media Psychology*, pp. 1–7. Available at: <https://doi.org/10.1002/9781119011071.iemp0019>

Rutter, J. (2012) *Evidence and evaluation in policy making: a problem of supply or demand?* [Online]. London: Institute for Government. Available at: https://www.instituteforgovernment.org.uk/sites/default/files/publications/evidence%20and%20evaluation%20in%20template_final_0.pdf (Accessed: 10 June 2022)

Rycroft-Smith, L. (2022) 'Knowledge brokering to bridge the research-practice gap in education: Where are we now?', *Review of Education*, 10(1). Available at: <https://doi.org/10.1002/rev3.3341>

Saad, M., Guermat, C. and Boutifour, Z. (2020) 'The interaction between academia and industry and its impact on national innovation capacity: The case of Algeria', *Industry and Higher Education*, 35(5), pp. 570–580. Available at: <https://doi.org/10.1177/0950422220931418> (Original work published 2021) (Accessed: 24 August 2025).

Sabatier, P.A. (1988) 'An advocacy coalition framework of policy change and the role of policy-oriented learning therein', *Policy Sciences*, 21(2–3), pp. 129–168. Available at: <https://doi.org/10.1007/BF00136406>

Sabatier, P.A. (1998) 'The advocacy coalition framework: Revisions and relevance for Europe', *Journal of European Public Policy*, 5(1), pp. 98–130. Available

at: <https://doi.org/10.1080/13501768880000051>.

Sabatier, P.A. (1999) *The theories of the policy process*. Boulder, CO: Westview Press.

Sabatier, P.A. (2007) *The theories of the policy process*. 2nd edn. Boulder, CO: Westview Press.

Sabatier, P.A. and Jenkins-Smith, H.C. (1993a) *Policy change and learning: An advocacy coalition approach*. Boulder, CO: Westview Press.

Sabatier, P.A. and Jenkins-Smith, H.C. (1993b) 'The advocacy coalition framework: Assessment, revisions and implications for scholars and practitioners', in Sabatier, P.A. and Jenkins-Smith, H.C. (eds) *Policy change and learning: An advocacy coalition approach*. Boulder, CO: Westview Press, pp. 211–236.

Sabatier, P.A. and Weible, C.M. (2007) 'The advocacy coalition framework: Innovations and clarifications', in Sabatier, P.A. (ed.) *Theories of the policy process*. 2nd edn. Boulder, CO: Westview Press, pp. 189–220.

Sabatier, P.A. (1988) 'An advocacy coalition framework of policy change and the role of policy-oriented learning therein', *Policy Sciences*, 21(2–3), pp. 129–168. Available at: <https://doi.org/10.1007/BF00136406>

Sager, F. and Gofen, A. (2022) 'The polity of implementation: Organizational and institutional arrangements in policy implementation', *Governance*, 35(2), pp. 347–364. Available at: <https://doi.org/10.1111/gove.12677>

Saguin, K. (2018) 'Policy consulting in developing countries: Evidence from the Philippines', *Journal of Asian Public Policy*, 11(2), pp. 188–205. Available at: <https://doi.org/10.1080/17516234.2018.1462559>

Sahki, S. (2023) 'The Role of Algerian Think Tanks in warning the danger of the Abraham Accords between Morocco and Israel on National Security', *Algerian Journal of Legal and Political Sciences*, 60(03), pp. 249–262. Available at: <https://asjp.cerist.dz/en/article/225044> (Accessed: 6 January 2024).

Saint-Martin, D. and Allison, C.R. (2011) 'Rationalism and public policy: Mode of analysis or symbolic politics?', *Policy and Society*, 30(1), pp. 19–27. Available at: <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.polsoc.2010.12.003>

Salawu, I.A. (2023) 'Elite Theory in the Context of Public Policy Making', *International Journal of Emerging Multidisciplinaries Social Science*, 2(2). Available at: <https://doi.org/10.54938/ijemdss.2023.02.2.209>

Salawu, I.A. (2023) 'The Elite Theory in the Context of Public Policy Making', *International Journal of Emerging Multidisciplinaries: Social Science*, 2(2), pp. 1–6. Available at: <https://doi.org/10.54938/ijemdss.2023.02.2.209> (Accessed: 17 August 2025).

Sallee, M.W. and Flood, J.T. (2012) 'Using qualitative research to bridge research, policy, and practice', *Theory Into Practice*, 51(2), pp. 137–144. Available at: <https://doi.org/10.1080/00405841.2012.662873>.

Salmi, J. and Altbach, P.G. (2020) 'World-Class Universities', in Teixeira, P.N. and Shin, J.C. (eds) *The International Encyclopedia of Higher Education Systems and Institutions*. Dordrecht: Springer. Available at: https://doi.org/10.1007/978-94-017-8905-9_37 (Accessed: 6 January 2024).

Samadi, A.H., Alipourian, M., Afroozeh, S., Raanaei, A. and Panahi, M. (2024) 'An Introduction to Institutional Inertia: Concepts, Types and Causes', in Faghieh, N. and Samadi, A.H. (eds) *Institutional Inertia*. Dordrecht: Springer, pp. 47–86. Available at: https://link.springer.com/chapter/10.1007/978-3-031-51175-2_3 (Accessed: 6 January 2024).

Sandelowski, M. (1995) 'Sample size in qualitative research', *Research in Nursing & Health*, 18(2), pp. 179–183. Available at: <https://doi.org/10.1002/nur.4770180211>.

Sapeha, H., Wellstead, A. and Evans, B. (2020) 'Peering into the black box of government policy work: The challenge of governance and policy capacity', *Canadian Political Science Review*, 13(1), pp. 1–33. Available at: <https://doi.org/10.24124/c677/20191612>.

Sarfo, J.O., Debrah, T.P., Gbordzoe, N.I., Afful, W.T. and Obeng, P. (2021) 'Qualitative Research Designs, Sample Size and Saturation: Is Enough Always Enough?', *Journal of Advocacy, Research and Education*, 8(3), pp. 60–65. Available at: https://www.researchgate.net/publication/359046583_Qualitative_Research_Designs_Sample_Size_and_Saturation_Is_Enough_Always_Enough (Accessed: 6 January 2024).

Sarnou, H., Koç, S., Houcine, S. and Bouhadiba, F. (2012) 'LMD: New system in the Algerian university', *Arab World English Journal*, 3(4), pp. 179–194. Available at: https://www.academia.edu/9311110/Sarnou_H_Ko%C3%A7_S_Houcine_S_Bouhadiba_F_2012_LMD_New_system_in_the_Algerian_university_Arab_World_English_Journal_Vol_3_Issue_4_December_2012_179_194 (Accessed: 6 January 2024).

Sartori, G. (1991) 'Comparing and miscomparing', *Journal of Theoretical Politics*, 3(3), pp. 243–257. Available at: <https://doi.org/10.1177/0951692891003003001>

Sawahel, W. (2009) 'Algeria: Study abroad cuts to tackle brain drain', *University World News*, 30 April. Available at: <https://www.universityworldnews.com/post.php?story=20090430201022419> (Accessed: 10 March 2022).

Sawli, M., Abderahmani, F. and Elharouchi, K. (2019) 'Evaluation of public spending policies on higher education in Algeria: An analytical study (تقييم سياسات الإنفاق العام على التعليم – دراسة تحليلية (العالى فى الجزائر – دراسة تحليلية)', *Journal of Studies in Economics and Management* (مجلة دراسات فى الاقتصاد وإدارة الأعمال), 2 (1), pp. 185–212. Available at: <http://asjp.cerist.dz/en/article/124787> (Accessed: 6 January 2024).

Scharpf, F.W. (1997) *Games real actors play: Actor-centered institutionalism in policy research*. Boulder, CO: Westview Press. Available at: https://www.researchgate.net/publication/233870090_Games_Real_Actors_Play_Actor-Centered_Institutionalism_in_Policy_Research (Accessed 4 Sep. 2025).

Scharpf, F.W. (2000) Institutions in comparative policy research. *Comparative Political Studies*, 33(6–7), pp.762–790. Available at: <https://doi.org/10.1177/001041400003300604>

Scharpf, F.W. (2000) 'Institutions in comparative policy research', *Comparative Political Studies*, 33(6–7), pp. 762–790. Available at: <https://doi.org/10.1177/001041400003300604>

Schattschneider, E.E. (1953) *The semi-sovereign people: A realist's view of democracy in America*. New York: Holt, Rinehart and Winston.

Schlager, E. (1995) 'Policy making and collective action: Defining coalitions within the advocacy coalition framework', *Policy Sciences*, 28(3), pp. 243–270. Available at: <https://doi.org/10.1007/bf01000289>

Schneider, C.J., 2015. *Mind the Gap? Links between Policy and Academic Research on Foreign Aid*. [Unpublished working paper] University of California, San Diego. Available at: https://pages.ucsd.edu/~cjschneider/working_papers/pdf/mindthegap-W08B.pdf (Accessed 25 Aug. 2023).

Schoelen, L. (2024) *Algeria: Challenges and Chances in Global Higher Education*. Johannesburg: UJ Press. Available at: <https://library.oapen.org/bitstream/handle/20.500.12657/99156/9781776489947.pdf> (Accessed: 19 August 2025).

Schoelen, L., 2024. *Algeria: Challenges and Chances in the Global Higher Education Arena*. [ebook] University of Johannesburg Press. Available at: <https://library.oapen.org/bitstream/handle/20.500.12657/99156/9781776489947.pdf?sequence=1> (Accessed 25 Aug. 2025).

Schulhofer-Wohl, J. (2007) 'Civil war in Algeria, 1992–present', in Blanchard, E.M. (ed.) *Civil wars of the world: Major conflicts since World War II*. Santa Barbara, CA: ABC-CLIO. Available at: https://www.researchgate.net/publication/335756680_Civil_War_in_Algeria_1992-Present (Accessed: 10 July 2022).

Scotland, J. (2012) 'Exploring the philosophical underpinnings of research: Relating ontology and epistemology to the methodology and methods of the scientific, interpretive, and critical research paradigms', *English Language Teaching*, 5(9), pp. 9–16. Available at: <https://www.ccsenet.org/journal/index.php/elt/article/view/19183>.

Scott, C. (2005) 'Value-adding policy analysis and advice: New roles and skills for the public sector', *Policy Quarterly*, 1(3). Available at: <https://doi.org/10.26686/pq.v1i3.4244>.

Scott, P. (2021) *Scottish universities: stranded between union and devolution*. HEPI. Available at: <https://www.hepi.ac.uk/2021/07/21/scottish-universities-are-a-casualty-of-the-independence-debate/> (Accessed: 18 August 2025).

Scottish Constitutional Convention (1995) *Scotland's Parliament, Scotland's Right*. Edinburgh: Scottish Constitutional Convention. Available at: Scotland's Parliament, Scotland's right : Scotland. Scottish Constitutional Convention (1989) : Free Download, Borrow, and Streaming : Internet Archive (Accessed: 17 January 2020).

Scottish Government (2001) *Education (Graduate Endowment and Student Support) (Scotland) Bill*. Available at: <https://www.parliament.scot/bills-and-laws/bills/education-graduate-endowment-and-student-support-scotland-bill> (Accessed: 28 August 2021).

Scottish Government (2006) *More choices, more chances: A strategy to reduce the number of young people not in education, employment or training*. Available at: <http://www.scotland.gov.uk/Topics/Education/Life-Long-Learning/16581> (Accessed: 23 June 2022).

Scottish Government (2006) *The Student Fees (Specification) (Scotland) Order 2006 (SSI 2006/401)*. Available at: <https://www.legislation.gov.uk/ssi/2006/401/contents/made> (Accessed: 16 April 2021).

Scottish Government (2007a) *Skills for Scotland: A lifelong skills strategy for Scotland*. Available at: <http://www.scotland.gov.uk/Publications/2007/09/06091114/0> (Accessed: 15 April 2021).

Scottish Government (2010a) *Building a smarter future: Towards a sustainable Scottish solution for the future of higher education*. Edinburgh: Scottish Government. Available

at: <https://dera.ioe.ac.uk/id/eprint/2180> (Accessed: 30 May 2022).

Scottish Government (2010b) *Building a Smarter Future: Towards a Sustainable Scottish Solution for the Future of Higher Education – Consultation Report*. Edinburgh: Scottish Government. Available at: <https://dera.ioe.ac.uk/id/eprint/2995/1/0115660.pdf> (Accessed: 19 August 2025).

Scottish Government (2011a) *Putting learners at the centre: Delivering our ambitions for post-16 education*. Edinburgh: Scottish Government. Available at: <http://www.scotland.gov.uk/Publications/2011/09/15103949/0> (Accessed: 11 February 2023).

Scottish Government (2012) *Report of the review of higher education governance in Scotland*. Edinburgh: Scottish Government. Available at: <https://dera.ioe.ac.uk/id/eprint/13901/1/00386780.pdf> (Accessed: 12 November 2020).

Scottish Government (2012a) *Report of the Review of Higher Education Governance in Scotland*. Edinburgh: Scottish Government. (See Annex C: Consultation respondents).

Scottish Government (2013a) *Scotland's Future: Your guide to an independent Scotland*. Edinburgh: Scottish Government. Available at: <https://www.gov.scot/publications/scotlands-future/> (Accessed: 19 August 2025).

Scottish Government (2013b) *Governance code and supporting guidelines for members of the governing bodies of higher education institutions in Scotland*. Edinburgh: Scottish Government. Available at: <https://www.scottishuniversitygovernance.ac.uk> (Accessed: 30 May 2021).

Scottish Government (2014a) *One Scotland: The government's programme for Scotland 2014–2015*. Edinburgh: Scottish Government. Available at: basedrones.wordpress.com/wp-content/uploads/2014/11/programme-for-government.pdf (Accessed: 30 May 2022).

Scottish Government (2014b) *Consultation on a Higher Education Governance Bill*. Edinburgh: Scottish Government. Available at: <https://www.gov.scot/publications/foi-201900005478/> (Accessed: 23 January 2021).

Scottish Government (2015) *Consultation on a higher education governance bill: Analysis of written responses*. By Linda Nicholson. Edinburgh: Scottish Government Social Research. Available at: Consultation on a Higher Education Governance Bill: Analysis of written responses (ioe.ac.uk) (Accessed: 30 May 2022).

Scottish Government (2016a) *Higher Education Governance (Scotland) Act 2016*. Available at: <https://www.legislation.gov.uk/asp/2016/15/contents> (Accessed: 23 January 2021).

Scottish Government (2016b) *A blueprint for fairness: The final report of the Commission on Widening Access*. Edinburgh: Scottish Government. Available at: <https://www.gov.scot/publications/final-report-commission-widening-access/> (Accessed: 30 May 2022).

Scottish Government (2017a) *16+ learning choices*. Edinburgh: Scottish Government. Available at: <http://www.scotland.gov.uk/Topics/Education/Life-Long-Learning/16581/newpage4> (Accessed: 30 May 2022).

Scottish Government (2017b) *Laying the foundations for fair access: Annual report 2017, Commissioner for Fair Access*. Edinburgh: Scottish Government. Available at: <https://www.gov.scot/publications/laying-foundations-fair-access-annual-report-2017-commissioner-fair-access/> (Accessed: 30 May 2022).

Scottish Government (2019a) *Review of the governance of higher education in Scotland: FOI release (FOI/201900005478)*. Edinburgh: Scottish Government. Available at: <https://www.gov.scot/publications/foi-201900005478/> (Accessed: 23 January 2021).

Scottish Government (2019b) *Protecting Scotland's future: The Government's programme for Scotland 2019–2020*. Edinburgh: Scottish Government. Available at: <https://www.gov.scot/publications/protecting-scotlands-future-governments-programme-scotland-2019-20/> (Accessed: 19 August 2025).

Scottish Government (2022) *Scotland's national strategy for economic transformation: Evidence paper*. By Chief Economist Directorate. Edinburgh: Scottish Government. ISBN 9781804351475. Available at: <https://www.gov.scot/publications/scotland-national-strategy-economic-transformation-evidence-paper/> (Accessed: 30 May 2022).

Scottish Government (2025) *University internationalisation*. Available at: <https://www.gov.scot/policies/universities/university-internationalisation/> (Accessed: 31 August 2025).

Scottish Government (2008) *New horizons: Responding to the needs of the 21st century*. Edinburgh: Scottish Government. Available at: <http://www.scotland.gov.uk/Topics/Education/UniversitiesColleges/16640/hetaskforce/JFTnewhorizons> [Accessed 21 Jul. 2022].

Scottish National Party (SNP) (2007) *SNP manifesto programme: It's Time*. Edinburgh. Available at: <https://image.guardian.co.uk/sys->

files/Politics/documents/2007/04/12/SNPManifestoprogramme.pdf (Accessed: 15 June 2021).

Scottish Parliament (2015) *Stage 1 report on the Higher Education Governance (Scotland) Bill*. Edinburgh: Scottish Parliament. Available at: https://www.parliament.scot/S4_EducationandCultureCommittee/Reports/ECS042015R12.pdf (Accessed: 1 November 2022).

Scottish Parliament (2016a) *Higher Education Governance (Scotland) Bill: Stage 2 proceedings*. Edinburgh: Scottish Parliament. Available at: <https://www.parliament.scot/bills-and-laws/bills/s4/higher-education-governance-scotland-bill> (Accessed: 19 August 2025).

Scottish Parliament (2016b) *Higher Education Governance (Scotland) Bill: Stage 3 debate and final amendments*. Edinburgh: Scottish Parliament. Available at: <https://www.parliament.scot/bills-and-laws/bills/s4/higher-education-governance-scotland-bill> (Accessed: 19 August 2025).

Scottish Parliament (2022) *Devolved and reserved powers*. Available at: <https://www.parliament.scot/about/how-parliament-works/devolved-and-reserved-powers> (Accessed: 29 August 2023).

Scottish Parliament (2001) *Education (Graduate Endowment and Student Support) (Scotland) Act 2001*, asp 6. Available at: <https://www.legislation.gov.uk/asp/2001/6/contents> (Accessed: 17 August 2021).

Scottish Parliament (2005) *Further and Higher Education (Scotland) Act 2005*, asp 6. Available at: <https://www.legislation.gov.uk/asp/2005/6/contents> (Accessed: 17 August 2021).

Scottish Parliament (2013) *Post-16 Education (Scotland) Act 2013*, asp 12. Available at: <https://www.legislation.gov.uk/asp/2013/12/section/3/enacted> (Accessed: 17 August 2021).

Scottish Parliament (2016) *Higher Education Governance (Scotland) Act 2016*, asp 15. Available at: <https://www.legislation.gov.uk/asp/2016/15/contents> (Accessed: 17 August 2021).

Scottish Parliament (2022) 'Research prepared for the Parliament', *Scottish Parliament Website*. Available at: <https://www.parliament.scot/chamber-and-committees/research-prepared-for-parliament/about-research> (Accessed: 19 August 2025).

Scottish University Governance (2013) *Meetings: Scottish code for good higher education governance*. Edinburgh: Scottish University Governance. Available at: <https://www.scottishuniversitygovernance.ac.uk> (Accessed: 30 May 2022).

Seenan, G. and Carvel, J. (1999) 'Scots prepared to scrap tuition fees', *The Guardian*, 22 December. Available

Smith, K. (2013) *Beyond evidence based policy in public health: The interplay of ideas*. London: Palgrave Macmillan UK.

Soule, D.P.J., Leith, M.S. and Steven, M. (2012) 'Scottish devolution and national identity', *National Identities*, 14(1), pp. 1–10. Available at: <https://doi.org/10.1080/14608944.2012.657085>.

Souleh, S., 2016. *High Education and Scientific Research sector in Algeria: Challenges and changes are required for a better system*. Presented at: International conference on *Enjeux et défis des systèmes éducatifs dans le contexte de la mondialisation*, Ecole supérieure de statistique et économie appliquée, Alger (Algérie). [online] ResearchGate. Available at: https://www.researchgate.net/publication/286622763_High_Education_and_Scientific_Research_sector_in_Algeria_Challenges_and_changes_are_required_for_a_better_system (Accessed: 07 May 2025).

SPICe (2010) *Higher Education: Qualifications, Quality Assurance and Assessment*. Prepared by Fiona Mullen. *SPICe Briefing*, 27 September 2010. Edinburgh: Scottish Parliament. Available at: Higher Education: Qualifications, Quality Assurance and Assessment (ioe.ac.uk) (Accessed: 19 August 2025).

SPICe (2010b) *Barriers to widening access to higher education*. Prepared by Fiona Mullen. *SPICe Briefing SB 10-07*. Edinburgh: Scottish Parliament. Available at: <https://dera.ioe.ac.uk/id/eprint/1269/1/SB10-07.pdf> (Accessed: 30 May 2022).

SPICe (2015) *Higher Education Governance (Scotland) Bill*. Briefing by Macpherson, S. Edinburgh: Scottish Parliament. Available at: <https://dera.ioe.ac.uk/id/eprint/23243/3/b74s4-introd-pm.pdf> (Accessed: 30 May 2022).

SPICe (2019a) *The price of free tuition in Scotland*. *SPICe Spotlight*. Available at: <https://spice-spotlight.scot/2019/12/18/the-price-of-free-tuition-in-scotland/?noamp=mobile> (Accessed: 15 June 2021).

SPICe (2019b) *Evolution and dilution in devolution: Economic policy in Scotland*. *SPICe Spotlight*. Available at: <https://spice-spotlight.scot/2019/07/03/evolution-and-dilution-in-devolution-economic-policy-in-scotland/> (Accessed: 15 June 2021).

SPICe (2021) *Further and Higher Education in Scotland: Subject Profile*. Prepared by Lynne Currie. *SPICe Briefing SB 21-42*. Edinburgh: Scottish Parliament. Available at: <https://digitalpublications.parliament.scot/ResearchBriefings/Report/2021/7/27/748aa666-cc88-4f53-8b0c-36b6dfbc54e0> (Accessed: 19 August 2025).

SPICe, 2011. *Higher Education: Tuition fees and the 'Funding gap*. Briefing by Berry, K. and Georghiou, N. SB 11-49. Edinburgh: Scottish Parliament. Available at: <https://digitalpublications.parliament.scot/ResearchBriefings> [Accessed 16 Apr. 2021].

Spitz, R., (2023) The Algerian Hirak: civil society and the role of artists in a civic space under pressure. In: K. Weigand, ed. *Civil Society Responses to Changing Civic Spaces*. Cham: Springer, pp.165–190. Available at: https://link.springer.com/chapter/10.1007/978-3-031-23305-0_8 [Accessed 25 Aug. 2025].

Stake, R.E. (1995) *The art of case study research*. London: Sage Publications.

Standring, A. (2016) *Evidence-based policymaking as depoliticised governance strategy: the case of European drug policy*. In: O’Gorman, A., Potter, G. and Fountain, J. (eds.) *Evidence in European social drug research and drug policy*. Lengerich: Pabst Science Publishers, pp.35–52.

Starman, A.B. (2013) ‘The case study as a type of qualitative research’, *Journal of Contemporary Educational Studies*, 1, pp. 28–43. Available at: https://www.researchgate.net/profile/A-Biba-Rebolj-2/publication/265682891_The_case_study_as_a_type_of_qualitative_research/links/54183f560cf25ebee988104c/The-case-study-as-a-type-of-qualitative-research.pdf (Accessed: 24 August 2025).

Steve, J. (1999) ‘Student loans report aimed at holding together Scottish coalition government’, *World Socialist Web Site*, 29 December. Available at: <https://www.wsws.org/en/articles/1999/12/scot-d29.html> (Accessed: 31 July 2024).

Stewart, J. and Ayres, R. (2001) ‘Systems theory and policy practice: an exploration’, *Policy Sciences*, 34(1), pp. 79–94. Available at: <https://doi.org/10.1023/A:1010334804878>.

Stone, D. (1996) *Capturing the political imagination: Think tanks and the policy process*. 1st edn. London: Routledge. Available at: <https://doi.org/10.4324/9780203044292>.

Stone, D. (2010) *Knowledge and policy networks in global governance*. In: B. Young and C. Scherrer (eds.) *Gender knowledge and knowledge networks in international political economy*. Baden-Baden: Nomos, pp.36–54.

Stone, D. (2012) ‘Transfer and translation of policy’, *Policy Studies*, 33(6), pp. 483–499. Available at: <https://doi.org/10.1080/01442872.2012.695933>.

Strehlenert, H., Richter-Sundberg, L., Nyström, M.E. and Hasson, H. (2015) *Evidence-informed policy formulation and implementation: a comparative case study of two national policies for improving health and social care in Sweden*. *Implementation Science*, 10(1), Article 169. Available at: <https://implementationscience.biomedcentral.com/articles/10.1186/s13012-015-0359->

1 (Accessed 25 Aug. 2025).

Sutherland, W.J. and Burgman, M. (2015) 'Policy advice: Use experts wisely', *Nature*, 526(7573), pp. 317–318. Available at: <https://doi.org/10.1038/526317a>.

Sutton, R. (1999) *The policy process: An overview*. London: Overseas Development Institute. Available at: <https://odi.cdn.ngo/media/documents/2535.pdf> (Accessed: 13 June 2021).

Szmolka, I. (2022) 'Do political parties matter in bringing about a democratic transition? An analysis of their role after Bouteflika's resignation in Algeria', *Revista Española de Ciencia Política*, (58), pp. 205–236. Available at: <https://doi.org/10.21308/recp.58.07>.

Talbi, S. (2015) *Higher education in Algeria: Where are we now?* International Journal of Engineering Research and Management (IJERM), 2(11), pp.47–51. Available at: https://www.researchgate.net/publication/340818511_Higher_Education_In_Algeria_Where_Are_We_Now_International_Journal_of_Engineering_Research_And_Management_IJERM_ISSN_2349-2058_Volume-02_Issue-11_November_2015 (Accessed 25 Aug. 2025).

Teh, W.L., Abdin, E., Asharani, P.V., Siva Kumar, F.D., Roystonn, K., Wang, P., Shafie, S., Chang, S., Jeyagurunathan, A., Vaingankar, J.A., Sum, C.F., Lee, E.S., van Dam, R.M. and Subramaniam, M. (2023) 'Measuring social desirability bias in a multi-ethnic cohort sample: its relationship with self-reported physical activity, dietary habits, and factor structure', *BMC Public Health*, 23(415). Available at: <https://doi.org/10.1186/s12889-023-15309-3>

Teichler, U. (2014) 'Opportunities and problems of comparative higher education research: The daily life of research', *Higher Education*, 67(4), pp. 393–408. Available at: <http://www.jstor.org/stable/43648663> (Accessed: 08 July 2025).

Tellis, W. (1997) 'Application of a case study methodology', *The Qualitative Report*, 3(3). Available at: <https://doi.org/10.46743/2160-3715/1997.2015>.

Temenos, C. (2016) 'Mobilizing drug policy activism: Conferences, convergence spaces and ephemeral fixtures in social movement mobilization', *Space and Polity*, 20(1), pp. 124–141. Available at: <https://doi.org/10.1080/13562576.2015.1072913>.

The Algerian Ministry of Education (2000) *Système éducatif algérien: réforme du système éducatif*. Algiers: Ministère de l'Éducation Nationale.

The Algerian Ministry of Higher Education and Scientific Research. (2018) *Twinning project fiche: Support to the Ministry of Higher Education and Scientific Research for the*

reinforcement of pedagogical skills of teachers & researchers and the managerial capacities of managers. Algiers: Ministry of Higher Education and Scientific Research. Available at: <https://www.p3a-algerie.org> (Accessed: 12 March 2022)

The Algerian Ministry of Higher Education and Scientific Research. (2022a) *Central structures – وزارة التعليم العالي والبحث العلمي*. Algiers: Ministry of Higher Education and Scientific Research. Available at: <https://www.mesrs.dz/index.php/fr/structures-centrales/> (Accessed: 12 April 2022)

The Algerian Ministry of Higher Education and Scientific Research. (2022b) *Etablissements de recherche – Agence Thématique de Recherche en Sciences et Technologie*. Available at: <https://www.atrst.dz> (Accessed: 03 October 2022)

The Bologna Declaration (1999) *The European Higher Education Area. Joint declaration of the European ministers of education convened in Bologna at the 19th of June 1999*. Bologna. Available at: https://eha.info/Upload/document/ministerial_declarations/1999_Bologna_Declaration_English_553028.pdf (Accessed: 7 August 2025).

The Embassy of Algeria (2020) *Algerian/UK relations: Historical background*. London: Embassy of Algeria. Available at: <https://embassyofalgeria.uk/uncategorized/historic-background/> (Accessed: 5 September 2022).

The Glasgow Guardian (2013) ‘New governance code ignores SRC suggestions’, *The Glasgow Guardian*, 18 September. Available at: <https://glasgowguardian.co.uk/2013/09/18/new-governance-code-ignores-src-suggestions/> (Accessed: 16 August 2022).

The Government of Algeria (2019) *The higher education system in Algeria: National report*. Available at: https://www.meric-net.eu/files/fileusers/National_Report_template_MERIC-NET_Algeria_English.pdf (Accessed: 25 November 2021).

The Government of Algria (2022) *Rapport national de l’Algérie: Sommet sur la transformation de l’éducation, New York, 19 septembre 2022*. Available at: https://transformingeducationsummit.sdg4education2030.org/system/files/2022-09/ALGERIE_NC%20report.pdf (Accessed: 5 August 2025).

The Herald (2014) ‘Pledge to scrap tuition fees is now “writ in stane”’, *The Herald*, 19 November. Available at: <https://www.heraldscotland.com/news/13190168.pledge-scrap-tuition-fees-now-writ-stane/> (Accessed: 13 May 2021).

The Scotsman (2011) ‘New universities review mired in controversy from Day One’. Available at: <https://www.scotsman.com/news/new-universities-review-mired-in-controversy-from-day-one-1672135> (Accessed: 23 January 2021).

Thérien, J.-P. (1999) 'Beyond the North-South divide: The two tales of world poverty', *Third World Quarterly*, 20(4), pp. 723–742. Available at: <https://doi.org/10.1080/01436599913523>

Thompson, G. and Pforr, C. (2005) *Policy networks and good governance – A discussion*. Working Paper Series 2005:1. Perth: Curtin University of Technology, School of Management. Available at: https://espace.curtin.edu.au/bitstream/handle/20.500.11937/41480/19693_downloaded_stream_211.pdf?sequence=2 (Accessed 25 Aug. 2025).

Thorpe, K. (2020) *How to engage with policy makers: A guide for academics in the arts and humanities: The landscape of policy making in the UK and how academics can engage with it*. London: Institute for Government. Available at: <https://www.instituteforgovernment.org.uk/publication/report/how-engage-policy-makers> (Accessed: 12 March 2022).

Tiernan, A. (2007) *Power without responsibility: Ministerial staffers in Australian governments from Whitlam to Howard*. Sydney: UNSW Press.

Tiernan, A. (2011) 'Advising Australian Federal Governments: Assessing the evolving capacity and role of the Australian Public Service', *Australian Journal of Public Administration*, 70(4), pp. 335–346. Available at: <https://doi.org/10.1111/j.1467-8500.2011.00742.x>.

Tight, M. (2012) *Researching higher education*. 2nd edn. Maidenhead: McGraw-Hill/Open University Press.

Times Higher Education (1999a) 'Scottish universities face shock of the new'. Available at: <https://www.timeshighereducation.com/news/scottish-universities-face-shock-of-the-new/145969.article> (Accessed: 13 June 2021)

Times Higher Education (1999b) 'The Cubie report'. Available at: <https://www.timeshighereducation.com/features/the-cubie-report/149439.article> (Accessed: 7 August 2021).

Tinklin, T. and Hall, J. (1999) 'Getting round obstacles: Disabled students' experiences in higher education in Scotland', *Studies in Higher Education*, 24(2), pp. 183–194. Available at: <https://doi.org/10.1080/03075079912331379878>.

Tobin, G.A. and Begley, C.M. (2004) 'Methodological rigour within a qualitative framework', *Journal of Advanced Nursing*, 48(4), pp. 388–396. Available at: <https://pubmed.ncbi.nlm.nih.gov/15500533/> (Accessed: 23 May 2022).

Torrance, D. (2024) *Introduction to devolution in the United Kingdom*. London: UK Parliament. Available at: <https://researchbriefings.files.parliament.uk/documents/CBP-8599/CBP-8599.pdf> (Accessed: 23 June 2024).

Turnpenny, J., Jordan, A., Benson, D., Bradshaw, G. and Rayner, T. (2015) *The tools of policy formulation: An introduction*. In: A. Jordan and J. Turnpenny (eds.) *The tools of policy formulation: Actors, capacities, venues and effects*. Cheltenham: Edward Elgar, pp.3–30. DOI: 10.4337/9781783477043.00011.

UK Cabinet Office (1999) *Modernising government*. London: Cabinet Office.

UK Government (1998) *Scotland Act 1998*. Available at: <https://www.legislation.gov.uk/ukpga/1998/46/contents> (Accessed: November 2020).

UK Government (2008) *Graduate Endowment Abolition (Scotland) Act 2008*. Available at: <https://www.legislation.gov.uk/asp/2008/3/contents> (Accessed: 08 August 2021).

UK Government (2012) *Scotland Act 2012*. Available at: <https://www.legislation.gov.uk/ukpga/2012/11/contents/enacted> (Accessed: 11 May 2021).

UK Government (2013) *Devolution of powers to Scotland, Wales and Northern Ireland*. Available at: <https://www.gov.uk/guidance/devolution-of-powers-to-scotland-wales-and-northern-ireland> (Accessed: 23 March 2021)

UK Government (2014a) ‘The future of higher education in Scotland and the UK’, Speech at the ESRC event, University of Edinburgh, 29 June. Available at: <https://www.gov.uk/government/speeches/the-future-of-higher-education-in-scotland-and-the-uk> (Accessed: 28 April 2021).

UK Government (2014b) *Minister Hugh Robertson visit to Algeria*. Available at: <https://www.gov.uk/government/news/minister-hugh-robertson-visit-to-algeria> (Accessed: 31 July 2024).

UK Government (2016) *Scotland Act 2016*. Available at: <https://www.legislation.gov.uk/ukpga/2016/11/contents> (Accessed: 20 August 2025).

UK Government (2019) *Guidance: Devolution settlement: Scotland*. Available at: <https://www.gov.uk/guidance/devolution-settlement-scotland> (Accessed: 9 July 2022).

UK Government Office for Science (2013) *Engaging with academics: How to further strengthen open policy making – A guide for policy makers*. Available at: <https://assets.publishing.service.gov.uk/media/5a74e3fee5274a59fa715c49/13-581-engaging-with-academics-open-policy-making.pdf> (Accessed: 25 March 2021)

UK Government (2018) *Getting informed consent for user research*. Available at: <https://www.gov.uk/service-manual/user-research/getting-users-consent-for-research> (Accessed: 17 August 2025)

UK Parliament (2000) *Select Committee on Education and Employment Fourth Report. House of Commons - Education and Employment - Fourth Report*. Available at: <https://publications.parliament.uk/pa/cm199900/cmselect/cmduemp/297/29702.htm> (Accessed: 10 May 2021).

UK Parliament (2001) ‘Special advisers: boon or bane?’, *Fourth Report, House of Commons Public Administration Committee*, 13 March. Available at: House of Commons - Public Administration - Fourth Report (parliament.uk) (Accessed: 28 June 2021).

UK Parliament (2022) *Algeria: 60th anniversary of diplomatic relations. Volume 722: Debated on Wednesday 16 November 2022. Hansard*. Available at: <https://hansard.parliament.uk/commons/2022-11-16/debates/0ACDE26E-5054-48EC-B4EC-30E122EF50B6/Algeria60ThAnniversaryOfDiplomaticRelations> (Accessed: 25 April 2023).

UK Parliament. (2014) *Scottish independence referendum 2014*. By McInnes, R., Ayres, S. and Hawkins, O. Research Briefing RP14-50. Available at: <https://commonslibrary.parliament.uk/research-briefings/rp14-50/> (Accessed: 8 June 2021)

Unger, J.W. (2013) ‘Rebranding the Scottish Executive: A discourse-historical analysis’, *Journal of Language and Politics*, 12(1), pp. 59–79. Available at: <https://www.jbe-platform.com/docserver/fulltext/jlp.12.1.03ung.pdf>

UNISON Scotland (2015) *Higher Education Governance Bill: UNISON Scotland evidence to the Scottish Parliament Education and Culture Committee*. Edinburgh: UNISON Scotland. Available at: https://unison-scotland.org/wp-content/uploads/HigherEducationGovernanceBill_UNISONScotlandEvidencetoScotGovt_Aug2015.pdf (Accessed: 30 May 2022).

UNISON Scotland (2015) *Higher Education Governance Bill: UNISON Scotland evidence to the Scottish Government*. Available at: https://unison-scotland.org/wp-content/uploads/HigherEducationGovernanceBill_UNISONScotlandEvidencetoScotGovt_Aug2015.pdf (Accessed: 20 August 2025).

UNISON Scotland (2016) *Response to the Scottish Code of Good Higher Education Governance*. Available at: <https://unison-scotland.org/wp-content/uploads/Response-to-Scottish-Code-of-good-higher-education-governance-sept-2016.pdf> (Accessed: 20 August 2025).

Universities Scotland (2011) *Universities Scotland responds to announcement on university governance in today's Scottish Parliament education debate*. Available at: <https://www.universities-scotland.ac.uk/news/universities-scotland-responds-to-announcement-on-university-governance-in-todays-scottish-parliament-education-debate> (Accessed: 23 December 2021).

Universities Scotland (2014) *Action on access: Recommendations to achieve further progress on widening access to higher education in Scotland*. Available at: <https://web.archive.org/web/20140311143931/http://www.universities-scotland.ac.uk/uploads/Widening%20Access%20recommendations.pdf> (Accessed: 27 September 2021).

Universities Scotland (2015a) *Universities Scotland response to Scottish Government consultation on a Higher Education Governance Bill*. Available at: <https://www.universities-scotland.ac.uk/wp-content/uploads/2015/10/HE-Governance-Bill-consultation-US-response.pdf> (Accessed: 28 November 2022).

Universities Scotland (2015b) *Higher Education Governance (Scotland) Bill: Evidence from Universities Scotland to the Education and Culture Committee*. Available at: <https://www.universities-scotland.ac.uk/wp-content/uploads/2015/11/US-ECC-evidence-FINAL-web-version.pdf> (Accessed: 10 February 2022).

Universities Scotland (2016) *Written submission to the Education and Skills Committee for the session focused on Further Education and Higher Education on 7 September 2016*. Available at: <https://www.universities-scotland.ac.uk/wp-content/uploads/2016/08/US-7-Sept-Ed-Committee-written-evidence-opportunities-and-challenges-310816.pdf> (Accessed: 22 May 2022).

Universities Scotland (2017) *Brief for ministerial statement on widening access: Universities Scotland action May 2017*. Available at: <https://www.universities-scotland.ac.uk/wp-content/uploads/2017/05/Universities-Scotland-Brief-Ministerial-Statement-on-Widening-Access-FINAL.pdf> (Accessed: 23 March 2021).

Universities Scotland (2018) *Written submission from Universities Scotland: Education and Skills Committee 16 May*. Available at: <https://www.universities-scotland.ac.uk/wp-content/uploads/2018/05/WA-submission.pdf> (Accessed: 19 June 2021).

Universities Scotland (2022) *Universities Scotland homepage / Who we represent*. Available at: <https://www.universities-scotland.ac.uk/> (Accessed: 16 November 2021).

Universities UK (2017) *Devolution and higher education: Impact and future trends*. London: Universities UK. Available at: <https://www.universitiesuk.ac.uk/publications/devolution-and-higher-education-impact-and-future-trends> (Accessed: 18 December 2021).

University and College Union Scotland (2008) *Generation debt's financial problems only just beginning, warns UCU*. Available at: <https://www.ucu.org.uk/article/3459/Generation-debts-financial-problems-only-just-beginning-warns-UCU> (Accessed: 31 July 2022).

University and College Union Scotland (2010) *UCU and NUS set out week's protests in campaign against fees and education cuts*, 3 December. Available at: <https://www.ucu.org.uk/5146> (Accessed: 24 February 2021).

University and College Union Scotland (2011a) *Union says choice of chair for governance review is extraordinary and cause for serious concern*. Available at: <https://www.ucu.org.uk/article/5599/Union-says-choice-of-chair-for-governance-review-is-extraordinary-and-cause-for-serious-concern> (Accessed: 31 July 2022).

University and College Union Scotland (2011b) *Future of higher education conference*. Available at: <https://www.ucu.org.uk/SHEfuture> (Accessed: 31 July 2023).

University and College Union Scotland (2013) *Response to consultation on the development of a new Scottish Code of Good Higher Education Governance: Issues paper*. Edinburgh: UCU. Available at: <https://www.scottishuniversitygovernance.ac.uk/> (Accessed: 12 June 2022).

University and College Union Scotland (2015) *UCU Scotland response to Scottish Government consultation on a higher education governance bill*. Available at: https://www.ucu.org.uk/media/6981/Consultation-paper-on-a-higher-education-governance-bill-UCU-Scotland-response-Jan-15/pdf/ucuscotland_hegovernancebillconsultation_v2_jan15.pdf (Accessed: 31 July 2022).

University and College Union Scotland (2015) *UCU Scotland response to the Scottish Government consultation on a higher education governance bill*. Available at: https://www.ucu.org.uk/media/7379/UCU-Scotland-response-to-Scottish-Government-consultation-on-HE-governance-bill-Feb-15/pdf/ucu_scotgovhegovresponse_feb15.pdf (Accessed: 20 August 2025).

University of Boumerdes (2023) *Conférence Régionale des Universités du Centre*. Available at: <https://www.univ-boumerdes.dz/universit%C3%A9/cruc.html> (Accessed: 11 August 2023)

University of St Andrews (2019) *Student equality, diversity and inclusion report 2019: Population by gender*. Available at: <https://www.st-andrews.ac.uk/about/edi-progress-reports/student-equality-diversity-and-inclusion-report-2019/population-by-gender> (Accessed: 10 January 2021).

Valentine, J. (2019) 'Governance, marketization and Scotland's universities', *Scottish Left Review*, Issue 112 (July–August). Available at: <https://scottishleftreview.scot/governance-marketization-and-scotlands-universities/> (Accessed: 12 March 2021).

van den Berg, C.F. (2017) 'Dynamics in the Dutch policy advisory system: Externalization, politicization and the legacy of pillarization', *Policy Sciences*, 50(1), pp. 63–84.

Van der Heijden, J. and ten Heuvelhof, E. (2012) 'The mechanics of virtue: Lessons on public participation from implementing the Water Framework Directive in the Netherlands', *Environmental Policy and Governance*, 22(3), pp. 177–188. Available at: <https://doi.org/10.1002/eet.1583> (Accessed: 17 August 2025).

van der Heijden, J.J. and ten Heuvelhof, E.F. (2012) 'The mechanics of virtue: Lessons on public participation from implementing the Water Framework Directive in the Netherlands', *Environmental Policy and Governance*, 22, pp. 177–188.

Van Kammen, J., de Savigny, D. and Sewankambo, N. (2006) 'Using knowledge brokering to promote evidence-based policy-making: The need for support structures', *Bulletin of the World Health Organization*, 84(8), pp. 608–612. doi: 10.2471/blt.05.028308. PMID: 16917647; PMCID: PMC2627440.

Van Teijlingen, E.R. and Hundley, V. (2002) 'The importance of pilot studies', *Nursing Standard*, 16(40), pp. 33–36. Available at: <https://doi.org/10.7748/ns2002.06.16.40.33.c3214>

Van Teijlingen, E.R., Rennie, A.M., Hundley, V. and Graham, W. (2001) 'The importance of conducting and reporting pilot studies: The example of the Scottish Births Survey', *Journal of Advanced Nursing*, 34(3), pp. 289–295. Available at: <https://doi.org/10.1046/j.1365-2648.2001.01757.x>

Vasileiou, K., Barnett, J., Thorpe, S. and Young, T. (2018) 'Characterising and justifying sample size sufficiency in interview-based studies: Systematic analysis of qualitative health research over a 15-year period', *BMC Medical Research Methodology*, 18(1), p. 148. doi: 10.1186/s12874-018-0594-7.

Veit, S., Hustedt, T. and Bach, T. (2017) 'Dynamics of change in internal policy advisory systems: The hybridization of advisory capacities in Germany', *Policy Sciences*, 50(1), pp. 85–103. Doi: 10.1007/s11077-016-9273-x.

Veselý, A. (2013) 'Externalization of policy advice: Theory, methodology and evidence', *Policy and Society*, 32(3), pp. 199–209. Available at: <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.polsoc.2013.07.002>.

Veselý, A. (2016) 'Policy analysis in the Czech Republic: The state of the art', in A. Veselý, M. Nekola and E.M. Hejzlarová (eds.) *Policy analysis in the Czech Republic*. Bristol: Policy Press Scholarship Online. Available at: <https://doi.org/10.1332/policypress/9781447318149.003.0001> (Accessed: 8 November 2022).

Veselý, A. (2017) 'Policy advice as policy work: A conceptual framework for multi-level analysis', *Policy Sciences*, 50(1), pp. 139–154. Available at: <https://doi.org/10.1007/s11077-016-9255-z>.

Viebrock, E. (2009) 'Review article: Social policy in Scotland since devolution', *Social Policy and Society*, 8(3), pp. 419–430. Doi:10.1017/S1474746409004953

Vogel, B. and Henstra, D. (2015) 'Studying local climate adaptation: A heuristic research framework for comparative policy analysis', *Global Environmental Change*, 31, pp. 110–120. Available at: <https://meopar.ca/uploads/Vogel-and-Henstra-2015.pdf> (Accessed: 20 August 2025).

Vogel, J.P., Oxman, A.D., Glenton, C., Rosenbaum, S., Lewin, S., Gülmezoglu, A.M. and Souza, J.P. (2013) 'Policymakers' and other stakeholders' perceptions of key considerations for health system decisions and the presentation of evidence to inform those considerations: An international survey', *Health Research Policy and Systems*, 11, p. 19. doi: 10.1186/1478-4505-11-19. PMID: 23705832; PMCID: PMC3672010.

Vukasovic, M. (2017) 'Stakeholder organizations in the European higher education area: Exploring transnational policy dynamics', *Policy and Society*, 36(1), pp. 109–126. Available at: <https://doi.org/10.1080/14494035.2017.1286741>.

Vukasovic, M., Jungblut, J., Chou, M.H., Elken, M. and Ravinet, P. (2018) 'Multi-level, multi-actor and multi-issue dimensions of governance of the European Higher Education Area, and beyond', in Curaj, A., Deca, L. and Pricopie, R. (eds.) *European Higher Education Area: The impact of past and future policies*. Cham: Springer. Available at: https://doi.org/10.1007/978-3-319-77407-7_20.

Waterbury, J. (2019) 'Reform of higher education in the Arab world'. In: Badran, A., Baydoun, E. and Hillman, J.R. (eds.) *Major challenges facing higher education in the Arab world: Quality assurance and relevance*. Cham: Springer. Available at: https://doi.org/10.1007/978-3-030-03774-1_7

Weaver, R. and Stares, P. (2001) *Guidance for governance: An overview*, in: R.K. Weaver & P.B. Stares, (eds). *Guidance for governance: comparing alternative sources of public policy advice*. Tokyo: Japan Center for International Exchange, pp. 71–88. Available at: <https://jcie.org/researchpdfs/Guidance/weaver-stares.pdf> (Accessed: 31 July 2023).

Webber, D.J. (1991) 'The distribution and use of policy knowledge in the policy process', *Knowledge and Policy*, 4(4), pp. 6–35. Available at: <https://doi.org/10.1007/bf02692779>.

Weible, C.M. and Sabatier, P.A. (2007) 'A guide to the advocacy coalition framework', in Sabatier, P.A. (ed.) *Theories of the policy process*. 2nd edn. Boulder, CO: Westview Press, pp. 189–220.

Weiler, F. and Brändli, M. (2015) 'Inside versus outside lobbying: How the institutional framework shapes the lobbying behaviour of interest groups', *European Journal of Political Research*, 54(4), pp. 745–766. Available at: <https://doi.org/10.1111/1475-6765.12106>.

Weiss, C.H. (1977a) 'Research for policy's sake: The enlightenment function of social research', *Policy Analysis*, 3(4), pp. 531–545. Available at: <https://www.jstor.org/stable/42783234> (Accessed: 12 November 2021).

Weiss, C.H. (1977b) *Using social research in public policy making*. Lexington, MA: Lexington Books.

Weiss, C.H. (1979) 'The many meanings of research utilization', *Public Administration Review*, 39(5), pp. 426–431. Available at: <https://doi.org/10.2307/3109916>.

Weiss, C.H. (1995) 'The haphazard connection: Social science and public policy', *International Journal of Educational Research*, 23(2), pp. 137–150. Available at: <https://www.sciencedirect.com/science/article/abs/pii/0883035595914986> (Accessed: 13 December 2021).

Weiss, C.H. (1999) 'The interface between evaluation and public policy', *Evaluation*, 5(4), pp. 468–486. Available at: <https://doi.org/10.1177/135638909900500408>.

Welch, R. (2009) *Higher education in crisis: Marketisation, privatisation and globalisation*. London: Routledge.

Weller, P. (2002) *Don't tell the Prime Minister*. Brunswick, VIC: Scribe Publications Pty Limited.

Wellstead, A. and Stedman, R. (2010) 'Policy capacity and incapacity in Canada's federal government', *Public Management Review*, 12(6), pp. 893–910. Available at: <https://doi.org/10.1080/14719037.2010.488863>.

West, A. (2001) 'Comparing higher education in Europe and the UK', *Oxford Review of Education*, 27(2), pp. 267–281.

Whiteman, D. (1985) 'Reaffirming the importance of strategic use', *Knowledge*, 6(3), pp. 203–224. Available at: <https://doi.org/10.1177/107554708500600301>.

Wicks, N. (2002) *Transcript of press launch of Issues and Questions consultation paper on defining the boundaries within the Executive: Ministers, special advisers and permanent civil servants. Committee on Standards in Public Life*. Available at: http://www.public-standards.gov.uk/publications/speeches_and_summaries/2002/executive_iq_transcript.aspx (Accessed: 3 June 2022).

Wigglesworth, S. (2013) 'New governance code ignores SRC suggestions', *The Glasgow Guardian*, 18 September. Available at: <https://archive.glasgowguardian.co.uk/2013/09/18/new-governance-code-ignored-src-suggestions/> (Accessed: 19 August 2025).

Wigglesworth, S. (2013) 'New governance code ignores SRC suggestions', *The Glasgow Guardian*, 18 September. Available at: <https://glasgowguardian.co.uk/2013/09/18/new-governance-code-ignores-src-suggestions> (Accessed: 5 May 2022).

Wildavsky, A.B. (1984) *The politics of the budgetary process*. 4th edn. Boston: Little, Brown.

Wiles, R., Crow, G., Heath, S. and Charles, V. (2008) 'The management of confidentiality and anonymity in social research', *International Journal of Social Research Methodology*, 11(5), pp. 417–428. Available at: <https://doi.org/10.1080/13645570701622231> (Accessed: 20 August 2025).

Willig, C. (2013) *Introducing qualitative research in psychology*. 3rd edn. Maidenhead: Open University Press.

Willis, J. (2007) *Foundations of qualitative research: Interpretive and critical approaches*. Thousand Oaks, CA: SAGE Publications, Inc. Available at: <https://doi.org/10.4135/9781452230108>.

Willis, J.W. (2012) 'World views, paradigms, and the practice of social science research', in *Foundations of qualitative research: Interpretive and critical approaches*. Thousand Oaks, CA: SAGE Publications, Inc., pp. 1–26. Available at: <https://doi.org/10.4135/9781452230108>.

Willis, M.J. (2023) *Algeria: Politics and society from the Dark Decade to the Hirak*. Oxford: Oxford University Press. Available at: <https://doi.org/10.1093/oso/9780197657577.001.0001>.

Wilson, D. (2003) 'Unravelling control freakery: Redefining central-local relations', *British Journal of Politics and International Relations*, 5(3), pp. 317–346. Available at: <https://doi.org/10.1111/1467-856X.00109>

Wilson, R. (1997) *Student finance and the welfare state*. Buckingham: SRHE/Open University Press.

Witte, J. (2006) *Change of degrees and degrees of change: Comparing adaptations of European higher education systems in the context of the Bologna Process*. Enschede: CHEPS.

Wollmann, H. (2007) 'Policy evaluation and evaluation research', in *F. Fischer, G.J. Miller & M.S. Sidney, eds. Handbook of public policy analysis: theory, politics, and methods. 1st ed. London: Routledge. [online] Available at: https://www.taylorfrancis.com/chapters/edit/10.4324/9781315093192-39/policy-evaluation-evaluation-research-hellmut-wollmann (Accessed 25 Aug. 2025).*

World Bank (2012) *Rapport sur la gouvernance des universités en Algérie*. Available at: <http://documents.worldbank.org/curated/en/693921496903671931/Report-on-the-governance-of-universities-in-Algeria> (Accessed: 11 February 2020).

World Bank (2020) *Algeria: Key conditions and challenges*. Available at: <https://thedocs.worldbank.org/en/doc/34c241003a168d068d25567246ac30e6-0280012021/original/1-mpo-am21-algeria-dza-1006-kcm.pdf> (Accessed: 10 May 2023).

World Bank (2023) *Algeria: Overview*. Available at: <https://www.worldbank.org/en/country/algeria/overview> (Accessed: 9 January 2024).

World Education News and Reviews (2006) 'Education in the Maghreb – Algeria, Morocco & Tunisia'. Available at: <https://wenr.wes.org/2006/04/wenr-apr-2006-education-in-the-maghreb-algeria-morocco> [1]tunisia (Accessed: 30 May 2025).

Wyness, G. (2010) *Policy changes in UK higher education funding, 1963 to 2009*. London: Centre for Economic Performance.

Yahiyaoui, S. and Addad, A. (2025) 'The impact of student unionism on the educational system in Algerian universities', *ZAOULI*, 1(10), pp. 570–602. Available at: https://www.revue-zaouli.com/wp-content/uploads/2025/06/21-Smail-YAHIYAOUI-Abderrahmane-ADDAD_Zaouli-n%C2%B010-Vol.-1-Juin-2025.pdf (Accessed: 1 July 2025).

Yılmaz, M. and Kulaç, O. (2016) 'An analysis of smoking policy attitudes of low-income group and cigarette consumption patterns upon increased wage', *European Scientific Journal (ESJ)*, 12(10), pp. 82-90.

Yin, R. (2003) *Case study research: Design and methods*. 3rd edn. Thousand Oaks, CA: Sage.

Yin, R. (2009) *Case study research: Design and methods*. 4th edn. Thousand Oaks, CA: Sage Publications.

Yin, R.K. (1994) *Case study research: Design and methods*. Beverly Hills, CA: Sage.

Yin, R.K. (2018) *Case study research and applications: Design and methods*. 6th edn. Thousand Oaks, CA: Sage Publications.

Yin, R.K. and Campbell, D.T. (1989) *Case study research: Design and methods*. Sage Publications.

Young, E. and Quinn, L. (2012) *Making research evidence matter: A guide to policy advocacy in transition countries*. Available at: https://advocacyguide.icpolicyadvocacy.org/sites/icpa-book.local/files/Policy_Advocacy_Guidebook_2012.pdf (Accessed: 14 July 2022).

Zabalawi, I. and Floden, I.T. (2019) 'The diploma supplement as a tool for quality assurance and relevance', in *Major challenges facing higher education in the Arab world: Quality assurance and relevance*. Cham: Springer, pp. 237–255. Available at: https://doi.org/10.1007/978-3-030-03774-1_12.

Zaghlami, L. (2016) 'Ministry promises improvements to LMD system', *University World News*, 28 October. Available at: <https://www.universityworldnews.com/post.php?story=20161026090205421> (Accessed: 7 September 2022).

Zaghlami, L. (2016) 'Ministry promises improvements to LMD system', *University World News*, 28 October. Available at: <https://www.universityworldnews.com/post.php?story=20161026090205421> (Accessed: 7 September 2022).

Zeb-un-Nisa, G., Mustafa, G., Yaseen, Z., Arslan, M. and Imran, M. (2021) 'Theoretical approaches to study the public policy: An analysis of the cyclic/stages heuristic model', *PalArch's Journal of Archaeology of Egypt/Egyptology*, 18(10), pp. 1307–1321. Available at: <https://www.archives.palarch.nl/index.php/jae/article/view/10010> (Accessed: 16 August 2024).

Zeraoulia, F. (2022) *National reconciliation and peacebuilding in Algeria: Lessons for Libya?* Florence: European University Institute. Available at: https://www.researchgate.net/publication/360259279_National_reconciliation_and_peace_building_in_Algeria_lessons_for_Libya (Accessed: 11 March 2021).

Zerig, N. (2021) 'Public policy-making in Algeria between the continued dominance of the executive power and margin for legislative power intervention', صنع السياسة العامة في الجزائر بين استمرار هيمنة السلطة التنفيذية وهامش تدخل السلطة التشريعي, *Algerian Journal of Law and Political Science*, 6(2), pp. 795–814. Available at: <https://asjp.cerist.dz/en/downArticle/526/6/2/180164> (Accessed 25 Aug. 2022).

Zgaga, P. (2006) *Looking out: The Bologna Process in a global setting. On the "external dimension" of the Bologna Process*. Edited by T. Johansson. Oslo: Ministry of Education and Research (Norway). ISBN: 978-82-583-0910-6. Available at: https://www.researchgate.net/publication/259560976_Looking_out_The_Bologna_Process_in_a_Global_Setting_On_the_External_Dimension_of_the_Bologna_Process (Accessed: 1 September 2025).

Zidane, Y. (2025) *Rethinking higher education governance in Algeria: Toward a post-bureaucratic governance model*. In: *Governance in Algerian Higher Education Institutions: Between Theory and Practice*. [conference paper] Available at: <https://doi.org/10.13140/RG.2.2.16816.47364/1> (Accessed 25 Aug. 2025).

Zitouni, M. and Djaileb, F. (2014) 'International mobility and recognition of diplomas: The case of the LMD system in Algeria', *International Conference on Education and Social Sciences*. Available at: https://www.ocrints.org/intcess14_epublication/papers/7.pdf (Accessed 25 Aug. 2022).

Zorgan, L. (2012) 'ومشكلات الجامعة الجزائرية: دراسة ميدانية LMD إصلاح التعليم العالي الراهن', *مجلة العلوم الإجتماعية والأداب و العلوم الإجتماعية* 19(2), pp. 187–207. Available at: [ومشكلات LMD إصلاح التعليم العالي الراهن | ASJP \(cerist.dz\)](https://www.cerist.dz/ASJP) (Accessed: 15 March 2021).

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Appendix 1 The Interview Schedule

Introductory section

My name is Zenati Nor Elhouda, and I am doing my PhD at the University of the West of Scotland. The research is a comparative study of Algeria and Scotland with the aim of studying the policy making process of higher education policymaking between 1999-2020. I look at XYZ policy areas in both countries and am interested in understanding how policy was made, which actors were the most important in these processes and why they were important or influential.

IF THEY HAVE AGREED TO BEING RECORDED:

You have agreed to the interview being digitally recorded. In any research output, you will not be identifiable. Before we start, I need to get your verbal approval for taking part in this study on tape.

IF THEY HAVE NOT AGREED TO BEING RECORDED:

I will only take notes during the interview. In any research output, you will not be identifiable.

Before I start, do you have any questions on the research or on the interview?

The interview questions.

Introduction

I have contacted you [your organization] because you [it] were involved in the processes in question – for example, I know that you were [member of a commission; advisor to minister...]. Could you say, to start the interview, a little about yourself [and your organization] with regards to your career, expertise and roles in this policy area?

Interviewee's involvement in policy processes

1. In what ways were you or your organization involved in in higher education policy making in Algeria/Scotland? [Prompts: commissions; public debate; research...]

2. What was your role in the process? [Prompt: innovator; expected to legitimate already made decisions;...]
3. Were your views solicited? Who approached you? why you specifically?
4. Why do you think you or your organization were consulted? (Expertise, nominated by others, volunteered)
5. How did this involvement come about?
6. What were your or your organization's most important contributions? What were the key ideas? Which ones were most 'popular' from your audience's view and why?
7. Which contributions do you think were most influential on the eventual policy outcome?

The bigger picture – other actors

1. In your view, who were the most influential people in the making of higher education policy?
2. Why were certain actors influential and others not? [Prompt: actor list plus those mentioned in response to 1.)
3. Would you say there is something of a 'network' of higher education policymaking, a network composed of experts, civil servants, members of the business community, academics and so on?
4. 3a) If so, how would you describe it? [Prompt: exclusive, open, ideologically narrow/broad]
5. Did you collaborate with other actors to strengthen your claims or for any other reason?

Strategies and tactics of policy process influencing

1. At what stage was your input most influential? [Prompt: Agenda setting, policy formulation, policy adoption, policy implementation]
2. What strategies did you use to influence the policy you were involved in? [Prompts:..]

3. What strategies did others use and were they successful? [Prompts: go through relevant stakeholders and strategies]
4. What are the criteria you deem crucial for someone to be influential?

Concluding questions

Is there anything that I should have asked or anything that you'd like to add?

Regarding further interviews, do you think there are certain people or organisations that I should contact for an interview? [Maybe list a few here to indicate that you do know who to contact generally]

Appendix 2 Consent Form

INFORMED CONSENT FORM

Title of Project: An Examination of the Role of Expertise in Higher Education Policy Making: A Comparative Study of Algeria and Scotland (1999-2020).

Ethics Approval Number:16441

Researcher: Zenati Nor Elhouda

Researcher's email: [REDACTED]

Please read the following statements and, if you agree, initial the corresponding box to confirm agreement. Then please return the form, signed (just type your name), to the researchers in an email.

I confirm that I have read and understood the Participant Information Sheet for the study entitled “An Examination of the Role of Expertise in Higher Education Policy Making: A Comparative Study of Algeria and Scotland (1999-2020)”.

I have had the opportunity to consider the information, ask questions and have had these answered.

I understand that my participation is voluntary and that I am free to withdraw at any time without giving any reason.

I consent to the processing of my personal information (this will include contact details needed to organise the research interviews and demographic data regarding age, gender, employment, geographical locality) for the purposes explained to me. I understand that such information will be handled in accordance with all applicable data protection legislation.

I understand that my data will be treated confidentially and any publication resulting from this study will report only data that *does not identify* me or my organisation. I will remain anonymous.

I agree to having my voice digitally recorded and in case the interview is conducted via zoom or other similar platforms, then the meeting will be also recorded so that the interview with me can be transcribed.

I freely agree to participate in this study.

Signatures:

Name of participant (block capitals):

Name of researcher (block capitals):
ZENATI NOR ELHOUDA

Date :

Date :

Signature :

Signature :

Appendix 3 Plain Language Statement

UWS UNIVERSITY OF THE
WEST of SCOTLAND
School of Education and Social Science

Participant Information Sheet: An Examination of the Role of Expertise in Higher Education Policy Making: A Comparative Study of Algeria and Scotland (1999-2020).

To Whom It May Concern

Described below is a plain language statement regarding a research I am undertaking for a postgraduate degree at the University of the West of Scotland, UK.

Study title and Researcher Details

a. Title of Project: An Examination of the Role of Expertise in Higher Education Policy Making: A Comparative Study of Algeria and Scotland (1999-2020).

b. Name and Details of Researcher

Nor Elhouda Zenati, University of the West of Scotland, School of Education and Social sciences.

Email: [REDACTED]

c. Research Supervisors

Dr. Yonah Matemba, School of Education and Social Sciences, University of the West of Scotland. Email: [REDACTED]

Dr. Hartwig Pautz, School of Education and Social Sciences, University of the West of Scotland. Email: [REDACTED]

d. Degree Being Sought

I am undertaking this research as a requirement for the degree of Doctor of Philosophy.

Invitation to participate in the research

I would like to invite you to take part in this study entitled “An Examination of the Role of Expertise in Higher Education Policy Making: A Comparative Study of Algeria and Scotland (1999-2020).” In addition to document analysis, semi-structured interviews represent the primary research tool in this study. Therefore, before you decide whether to take part or not, it is important for you to understand why the research is being undertaken and what it will entail. Please take time to read the document carefully to decide whether you wish to take part or not. If you want more information about the study and how your future input will be used, please do not hesitate to contact me. My contact details are provided at the bottom of this document.

What is the purpose of this study?

The study will explore how different policy actors contributed in the shaping of higher education policy in Algeria and Scotland respectively in order to forge an understanding of their sphere of influence that directs or affects the process of policymaking. The study will analyse the role of the policy actors involved in higher education policy-making in Algeria and Scotland focusing on the period 1999-2020. The study will trace back the making of key policies underpinning higher education in Algeria and Scotland. The rationale for the period selected for the study is that in 1999 one of the major policies in Scottish higher education was introduced related to widening access. The end period for the study (i.e. 2020) is related to the most recent policy in Algerian higher education when the government enacted a policy supporting postgraduate Masters degree study without grade requirements for their bachelor’s degree courses. The new policy also cancelled the requirement of high grades for Masters degree as entry into doctoral study, preferring instead the use of a competitive entrance examination to screen eligible applicants for doctoral study.

Why have I been chosen?

I contacted you because you are a key stakeholder who has a direct experience and expertise in and of the higher education policy-making arena. You can therefore offer valuable insights to this study.

Do I have to take part?

Your participation remains, of course, voluntary. If you decide to take part, you will be asked to sign a consent form. If you decide to take part, you are still free to withdraw at any time and without giving a reason.

What will happen to me if I take part?

I will ask you to take part in a one-to-one interview. The interview will be conducted either personally or via the phone or via online platforms such as Zoom, Skype, or Google Meets. This depends on the current pandemic situation. However, if you find yourself more comfortable to the idea of online interviewing, this can be easily arranged. The interview – lasting around 60 minutes will be audio-recorded.

What are the possible disadvantages and risks of taking part?

I expect no disadvantages for you from participating in this study. In any form of publication from the study (article or an article for an academic journal) I will assure that you and your organisation cannot be identified. Again, your participation along with the information you share with the interviewer will remain confidential and no one can identify you or your input.

Data Protection Privacy Notice

The data controller for this study will be University of the West of Scotland (UWS). The UWS Data Protection Office provides oversight of UWS activities involving the processing of personal data, and can be contacted at dataprotection@uws.ac.uk. UWS's Data Protection Officer is Emma Cockrow and she can also be contacted at dataprotection@uws.ac.uk.

Your personal data will be processed for the purposes outlined in this notice. The legal basis that would be used to process your personal data will be the provision of your signed informed consent form.

Your personal data will be held by the University, and only by the University, as long as it is required for the study. I will anonymise the personal data you provide us with and will endeavour to minimise the processing of your personal data wherever possible. The data, recordings and transcriptions will be stored on password-protected computers to which only the supervisory team and I have access to.

If you are concerned about how your personal data is being processed, please contact UWS at dataprotection@uws.ac.uk. If you remain unsatisfied, you may wish to contact the Information Commissioner's Office (ICO). Contact details, and details of data subject rights, are available on the ICO website at: <https://ico.org.uk/for-organisations/data-protection-reform/overview-of-the-gdpr/individuals-rights/>

What will happen to the results of the research?

The results of the study will be used for the purposes of an examination for the award of a doctoral degree. In the future, parts of the completed research might be presented at a conference or submitted for publication in academic journals. In the case of the results being published, I will notify you with details on how to obtain a copy. Please note that in all future presentations or publications you will not be identified in any possible way.

Who is organising and funding the research?

The research is part of a general fulfilment for the award of a postgraduate degree at the University of the West of Scotland. The study is funded by the Algerian government.

Who has reviewed the study?

The project has been reviewed and approved by the Faculty of Education Ethics Committee. ESS Ethics Committee-Approval Number: 16441

Contact for further information

If you require any further information, please contact:

Nor Elhouda Zenati

University of the West of Scotland

School of Education & Social Sciences

Paisley PA1 2BE

Email:

Thank you for considering taking part in this study.

Appendix 4 University of the West of Scotland's Ethical Approval Letter

22/07/2021

Dear Nor Elhouda Zenati,

Your application 16441: Expertise in higher education policymaking: A comparative study between Algeria and Scotland 1999-2020, submission 13937, has been approved by the Education and Social Sciences SEC. You may now proceed with your study. If you wish to make any significant changes to the study you must seek the committee's approval before actioning them.

Good luck with your research.

Dr Iain McPhee

Appendix 5 Thematic map Algeria

Higher education policy in Algeria 1999-2020

Appendix 6 Thematic map Scotland

